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***Institutionalising Deliberative Democracy to Promote
Environmental Policy-Making: The Role of
Public Hearings***

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for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy in the
School of Media, Culture and Society**

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DECLARATION OF ORIGINALITY

This is to certify that I am responsible for the work submitted in this thesis, that the original work is my own except as specified in acknowledgements or in footnotes, and that neither the thesis nor the original work contained therein has been submitted to this or any other institution for a degree.

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Abstract

Liberal democracy has been accused of failing to deliver an environmentally sustainable future. In response, deliberative democracy has been heralded as the most promising and realistic form of democracy to promote green issues. Yet, used independently, deliberative processes can be inefficient and ineffective when it comes to policy and decision-making. Combining deliberative processes within liberal institutions is the most realistic way of combining the uses of each democratic model and furthering the environmental agenda. The assertion is that public hearings embody the correct hybrid characteristics to enable this coupling. Despite the plethora of research carried out on the potential of deliberative processes to work in conjunction with existing methods of decision-making, the potential of public hearings has been largely overlooked.

This research adopts a mixed method approach to help identify where public hearings could be most effectively utilised in the decision-making process. The thesis explores seven case studies which are, the Alpac hearing on the development of a pulp mill held in Alberta, Canada; the Formartine hearing on the development of a golf course, in Aberdeen, Scotland; the British Columbia Citizens' Assembly hearings on electoral reform, in British Columbia, Canada; the Glenmorrie hearing on a windfarm proposal in the Highlands in Scotland; the Helensburgh hearing on wind-power, in the west coast of Scotland; the United Nations (UN) hearing on the citizens versus the United Kingdom, in Geneva, and finally; a hearing held by the European Commission on manufacturing industries in Belgium.

The research is operationalised through a newly conceptualised normative framework – the Democratic Standard Enactment Index (DSEI) – whereby a fuzzy set Qualitative Comparative Analysis (fsQCA) is undertaken to highlight the thus far overlooked benefits of public hearings. Through the application of the DSEI and the fsQCA, the research finds that public hearings have the potential to enact some, if not all, of Smith's (2009a) democratic standards (inclusion, popular control, transparency and considered judgement), as well as the ability to fulfil the institutional goods of transferability and efficiency. The research finds that public hearings can facilitate an exchange of ideas and information, within a hitherto overlooked sphere of deliberation - the 'meso' level - which narrows the field of discussion while making it more accessible for wider groups of people, enabling the connection of micro and macro level deliberation. Consequently, public hearings can be considered to provide a unique function in institutionalising deliberative democracy and promoting environmental policy-making.

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Contents page

Contents page.....	5
Figures	8
Chapter 1: Introduction.....	9
1.1 Background.....	9
1.2 Research.....	11
1.3 Thesis outline.....	13
Chapter 2: Deliberative democratic theory and the absence of public hearings	15
2.1 Introduction.....	15
2.2 Deliberative Democracy	16
2.3 Evaluating deliberative processes	18
2.4 Institutionalising deliberative democracy	21
2.5 Public Hearings.....	25
2.5.1 Types of Public Hearings.....	26
2.5.2 Issues with Public Hearings	27
2.5.3 Public Hearings Varied Hybrid Credentials.....	33
2.6 Conclusion	34
Chapter 3: The hybrid possibilities of public hearings in environmental policy-making.....	35
3.1 Introduction.....	35
3.2 The Environmental Democratic Paradox.....	36
3.2.1 The Complex Role of Experts in Environmental Decision-making	38
3.2.2 Democratising Environmental Decision-making through Deliberation.....	41
3.3 How to Reconcile Experts and Citizens.....	47
3.3.1 How Could Hearings Accommodate this Coupling?.....	50
3.4 Conclusion	53
Chapter 4: Methodology	55
4.1 Introduction.....	55
4.2 Research.....	55
4.3 Conceptual Design	56
4.4 Research design	59
4.5 Stage 1: The DePER framework.....	61
4.6 Stage 2: The Democratic Standard Enactment Index (DSEI).....	66
4.6.1 Stage 2A: Designing the DSEI.....	66
4.6.2 Stage 2A/B: Designing and Implementing the DSEI.....	67
4.6.3 Stage 2C: DQI and the justification measurement.....	71
4.7 Stage 3: Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA).....	76

4.8 Conclusion	82
Chapter 5: Public hearings in practice	84
5.1 Introduction.....	84
5.2 Case study selection.....	84
5.3 Case studies.....	86
5.3.1 Case study 1: Alpac Public Hearing Alberta, Canada 1988-1990	89
5.3.2 Case study 2: Formartine Public Hearing Aberdeen, Scotland 2007.....	94
5.3.3 Case study 3: British Columbian Public Hearings British Columbia, Canada 2004	99
5.3.4 Case study 4: Glenmorrie public hearing, Caithness, Scotland 2014.....	103
5.3.5 Case study 5: Helensburgh’s Public Hearing, Argyll and Bute, Scotland 2013	106
5.3.6 Case study 6: Aarhus Convention Compliance Committee (ACCC), United Nations, Geneva (2011).....	109
5.3.7 Case study 7:	111
European Commission Task Force for Advanced Manufacturing for Clean Production Public Hearing, Belgium 2013	111
5.4 Conclusion	115
Chapter 6: Applying the Democratic Standard Enactment Index	117
6. 1 Introduction.....	117
6.2 Applying the Democratic Standard Enactment Index.....	117
6.2.1 Inclusion.....	118
6.2.2 Popular control.....	129
6.2.3 Transparency	136
6.2.4 Considered judgement.....	143
6.3 Findings and discussions.....	155
Chapter 7: Evaluating the democratic possibilities of public hearings	162
7.1 Introduction.....	162
7.2 Truth Table Analysis.....	163
7.2.1 Analysis of Inclusion	164
7.2.2 Analysis on Popular Control.....	169
7.2.3 Analysis on Transparency	173
7.2.4 Analysis on Considered Judgement	177
7.3 Key Findings and Recommendations	181
Chapter 8: Public hearings: filling the democratic gaps	187
8.1 Introduction.....	187
8.2 Effectiveness: The hybrid credentials of public hearings	188
8.2.1 Aligning deliberative processes and liberal institutions.....	188
8.2.2 Micro and macro deliberation	189
8.2.3 Strong and weak publics	191

8.2.4 The interaction between all stakeholders within deliberative discussions	192
8.3 The transferability of hearings: institutionalising public hearing	196
8.3.1 Green decision-making: transcending tokenistic participation	196
8.3.2 Initiating the discussion at all levels of governance.....	199
8.4 Conclusion	203
Chapter 9: Conclusion.....	205
9.1 Introduction.....	205
9.2 Key findings from the DSEI	205
9.2.1 Effecting change through agenda setting	206
9.2.2 Who’s taking part in the debate?.....	206
9.2.3 Effectual decision-making	209
9.2.4 Implementing change	210
9.2.5 Reviewing the decision	211
9.3 Key findings from the fsQCA.....	211
9.3.1 Creating an inclusive public hearing.....	211
9.3.2 Creating a public hearing which embodies popular control.....	212
9.3.3 Creating a transparent public hearing	213
9.3.4 Public hearings and considered judgement	214
9.4 Recommendations for UK public hearings.....	214
9.5 Next steps.....	217
Bibliography	219
Appendices.....	234
Appendix 1: Coding Categories for the Discourse Quality Index (DQI).....	234
Appendix 2: List of Attendees at EU Public Hearing.....	237
Appendix 3: Analysis Output for fuzzy set QCA	238

Figures

Figure 4.1 Research Design Framework.....	60
Figure 4.2 The DePER framework	62
Figure 4.3 Cube of Optimum Enactment.....	64
Figure 4.4 Democratic Standard Enactment Index	68

Tables

Table 4.1 Exemplary Truth Table.....	80
Table 5.1 Denoting the differing and similar aspects of each public hearing.....	88
Table 6.1 Inclusion.....	125
Table 6.2 Popular control.....	132
Table 6.3 Transparency.....	138
Table 6.4 Considered judgement	146
Table 7.1 Indicative truth table showing fuzzy set membership for inclusion	164
Table 7.2 Completed truth table for inclusion	165
Table 7.3 Sufficiency analysis solutions for outcome ‘inclusion’	166
Table 7.4 Indicative truth table showing fuzzy set membership for popular control.....	170
Table 7.5 Completed truth table for popular control.....	170
Table 7.6 Sufficiency analysis solutions for outcome ‘popular control’	171
Table 7.7 Indicative truth table showing fuzzy set membership for transparency.....	173
Table 7.8 Completed truth table for transparency.....	174
Table 7.9 Sufficiency analysis solutions for outcome ‘transparency’	175
Table 7.10 Indicative truth table showing fuzzy set membership for considered judgement.....	177
Table 7.11 Completed truth table for considered judgement.....	178
Table 7.12 Sufficiency analysis solutions for outcome ‘considered judgement’	180

Chapter 1: Introduction

Deliberative democrats believe that collective decisions should emerge from a process whereby individuals discuss public problems and solutions under conditions which encourage reasoned reflection and refined public judgement (Habermas 1996, Dryzek and Dunleavy 2009). The contemporary liberal democratic model is criticised for creating a chasm between the electorate and those that have the power to make decisions, resulting in a democratic deficit (Nabatchi 2007; Della Porta 2013). Bloomfield *et al.* (2001: 501) argue that the purpose of deliberative processes is to ‘enhance the functioning of representative democracy, not to replace it’. Yet, each democratic system, both liberal and deliberative, poses very real problems for environmental decision-making. While within liberal democracy the environment is rarely prioritised and the capitalist practices exacerbate the environmental crisis by relentless over-production and the pursuits of self-interested actions (O’Conner 1994; Foster 2002; Dobson 2007), deliberative democracy – although purported to align itself with the green movement due to the promotion of the common good and the moralising effects it affords (Dryzek 1987: 34) - is largely ineffective at enacting decisions and thus policies (Mansbridge *et al.* 2010, Elstub 2009). Therefore institutionalising deliberative processes within liberal institutions is the most realistic way of combining the uses of each democratic model and furthering the environmental agenda. The assertion is that public hearings embody the correct hybrid characteristics to enable this coupling. Despite the fact that deliberative processes have the potential to work in conjunction with other, already existing methods of decision-making, the potential of public hearings as an institutional mechanism has been largely overlooked in the deliberative democratic literature. This research seeks to rectify this and fill the gap in the deliberative research.

1.1 Background

Deliberative democrats have pursued a move towards empirical research in order to ascertain how deliberation can reasonably be instilled within existing democratic systems. This had led to a rise in the development and employment of democratic mechanisms which involve citizens in deliberative processes (Goodin 2008; Davidson *et al.* 2012; Stevenson and Dryzek 2014) as well as the design of innovative methods that claim to measure the potential of deliberation (Fishkin and Luskin 2005; Niemeyer and Dryzek 2007; Davidson and Stark 2011; Steiner

2012; Cinalli and O’Flynn 2014a; Elstub 2014b). Recent research in deliberative democratic theory has taken a ‘comparative turn’ which is vital for understanding which mechanism could realistically achieve deliberation in order to decipher how deliberative democratic governance can best be achieved, and what role each mechanism can serve (Ryan and Smith 2012: 90). Much research has surrounded the institutionalisation of deliberative democracy. Institutional design is necessary to capture the potential of deliberation. Due to the complexity that surrounds deliberative institutions, each face various and diverse problems and for this reason, Elstub (2014b) believes that no one mechanism will work effectively at all levels of governance and each stage of the decision-making process. Therefore it is important to ascertain what role each deliberative institution is able to fill most effectively by considering each institution’s use in an ‘integrated deliberative system’ (Hendriks 2006: 500). While wide discussion on deliberative methods have been witnessed, such as citizens’ juries, deliberative polls and citizens’ assemblies (Fishkin 2009; Fournier *et al.* 2011), as well as parliaments and associations (Steiner *et al.* 2004, Elstub 2007), the potential of public hearings has, as yet, remained unstudied.

Despite this lack of research into public hearings in relation to deliberative democracy, their deliberative potential has been acknowledged by a number of prominent theorists (Fung 2006; Hendriks 2011; Mansbridge *et al.* 2010). Moreover, their usefulness in the decision-making process has been particularly noted within a number of key studies (Karpowitz and Mansbridge 2005; Schylter and Stjernquist 2010; Fournier *et al.* 2011). Theorists (Kemp 1985; Salter 1989; Innes and Booher 2004) highlight the lack of serious research that surrounds hearings. Salter (1989) believes this may be due to the diversity of the practice. Public hearings can be flexible processes that adopt various procedures depending on their purpose or which level of governance they are held at. Yet, for hearings to be initiated into the deliberative democratic field, it is vital to determine the level of legitimacy, justice and effective governance that is drawn from the process (Fung 2006: 66).

As public hearings already exist within liberal democracies and are embedded within the liberal infrastructure, it will be argued within this thesis that they are well placed to play a part in forwarding environmental practices. The argument is that ‘hybrid’ forms of institutions, like public hearings, which bring representatives, experts, and lay citizens together into deliberation can help to overcome the failings of liberal and deliberative democracy in pursuing a green

agenda and instead, contribute to the promotion of green issues. Hybrid institutions are designed to couple different rationalities and forms to achieve their combined strength; ideally accommodating deliberative ideals and effective policies which increase legitimacy and effectiveness in democracy (Backstrand *et al.* 2010: 223). In order to decipher the role public hearings could fill, the initial inquiry must focus on the potential, if any, they yield in accommodating deliberation within their process. Hearings can do this by creating a new sphere of communication by providing a hybrid quality or a 'coupling' effect (Hendriks 2016) to the democratic process. This can be done by embedding deliberative processes within liberal institutions which will accommodate the combination of grassroots level knowledge with national level innovation and expertise. In addition, hearings have the ability to create a new level of deliberation, at a meso level which exists between the micro and macro level. Furthermore, hearings embody a hybrid capacity in that they are positioned between 'weak' and 'strong publics'. At present public hearings present a fundamentally flawed addition to the democratic process; however, throughout this discussion, recommendations for their improvement will be offered.

1.2 Research

The purpose of this research is to contribute to deliberative democratic theory by assisting with future comparisons between public hearings and other democratic processes, including mini-publics. Further to this, the study will provide evidence of their potential, and guidance for their improvement, which could accommodate the institutionalisation of deliberative democracy. The aim of the research is to forward public hearings as a process which can play a role in the integrated deliberative system, making use of their hybrid characteristics to forward the green agenda by connecting representative democratic processes with wide-scale public participation. Hearings can be used as a way of engaging citizens with the decision-making process, enabling 'lay' or 'non-partisan' citizens to participate alongside experts and stakeholders in problem solving environmental issues. Furthermore, public hearings can create an arena where non-experts can set the political agenda and influence the direction of key debates. This is vital for deepening the democratic process in order to achieve a considered and multifaceted outcome. The decisions or recommendations that result from the hearing will be used to advise and guide policy-making. The process of people coming together to 'learn, think and deliberate' is what makes the deliberative process so valid. From listening to expert

opinions; hearing evidence and discussing and comparing ideas, individuals will formulate widely valuable views. The research aims and objectives of this project are as follows:

Research Aims

- 1) Formulate an innovative methodology for assessing the institutionalisation of deliberative democracy.
- 2) Critically assess the value of public hearings in institutionalising deliberative democracy.

Research Objectives

- 1) Capture the potential of deliberative democracy by investigating institutional design.
- 2) Explore the role of public hearings as a deliberative institution at a micro and meso level.
- 3) Investigate the impact of public hearings within a variety of contexts.
- 4) Highlight the strengths and weaknesses of public hearings at each level of governance by evaluating their capacity to enact the democratic standards as defined by Smith (2009a) and adapted by Elstub (2014b).
- 5) Make suggestions regarding improvements that can be adopted which may strengthen the deliberative quality of hearings

Due to the complexity of evaluating not *if* public hearing are deliberative but instead, *can* they be, a mixed method approach is required. This includes the Deliberative Pragmatic Equilibrium Review (DePER) framework (Elstub 2014b); Democratic Standard Enactment Index (DSEI) which incorporates the justification measurement from the Discourse Quality Index (Steiner *et al.* 2004) and finally, a fuzzy set Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) (Ragin 1987). Elstub's (2014b) DePER framework works as the normative theoretical framework which shapes the case study selection through the assessment of micro institutions at varying levels of governance (local, regional, national, transnational, and global) and at different decision-making stages (agenda-setting, deliberation, decision-making, implementation and review). The framework sets the parameters for the research through Smith's (2009a) democratic goods, which are inclusion, popular control, transparency and considered judgement. Each hearing has been picked for its own unique insight into the hearing process; and although they vary to a certain extent in purpose and process, they are intended to highlight the potential of hearings to achieve the elements of deliberative democracy. There are seven case studies altogether which are, the Alpac hearing on the development of a pulp mill which was held in Alberta, Canada; the Formartine hearing on the development of a golf course, held in Aberdeen,

Scotland; the British Columbia Citizens' Assembly hearings on electoral reform, which took place in British Columbia, Canada; the Glenmorie hearing on a windfarm proposal held in the Highlands in Scotland; the Helensburgh hearing on wind-power, in the west coast of Scotland; the United Nations (UN) hearing on the citizens versus the United Kingdom, held in Geneva, and finally; a hearing held by the European Commission (EC) on manufacturing industries in Belgium.

The next research method is the newly designed DSEI. The purpose of this new model is to ground the normative indicators - inclusion, popular control, transparency and considered judgement - into measureable components. It does this by setting a series of 12 questions which shapes the data extraction from the case studies to establish the capacity of public hearings to host the democratic standards, and assigns a measurement for the degree to which the outcome exists. For this, the DSEI makes use of the justification measurement of the Discourse Quality Index (DQI). Through the assigning of numeric values to each case study, the researcher is able to analyse the data through the fuzzy set Qualitative Comparative Analysis (fsQCA) software. These methods have all been chosen for their ability to discern the capabilities of hearings and in doing so, can ascertain the strengths and weaknesses of each hearing at the different levels of governance and through the various procedures which are adopted in the public hearing process.

1.3 Thesis outline

Including this chapter, the research is separated into nine chapters. The second chapter introduces deliberative democratic theory, mapping its evolution from early theorists Habermas (1975) and Rawls (1971) to the modern day where practical applications of it have emerged for the past few decades. Much of the research has focused on deliberative democracy's 'institutionalisation' envisioning how it can be adopted within the liberal democratic paradigm in order to legitimise democratic decision-making. This chapter also introduces public hearings and offers insights into the literature which has focused on them and how they are presently perceived.

The third chapter continues the discussion on deliberative democracy but seeks to set this out in the context of the ecological literature. Highlighting the democratic gaps which exist within both the deliberative and liberal model, the chapter seeks to illustrate why a wider and more robust exploration of existing democratic processes must be undertaken, including public

hearings. From here, Fischer's (2003, 2009) investigation into the role of experts in environmental decision-making is used to provide justifications for public hearings in a deliberative context.

The fourth chapter looks at the conceptual design of this research, highlighting why and how the methods selected offer the best chance of achieving the aims. The chapter systematically sets out and discusses the research methods; which include Elstub's (2014b) DePER, the DSEI which includes the justification measurement of the DQI and finally, a fsQCA. Within this section the benefits and weaknesses of each are discussed and the appropriate application required for this research. The discussion includes an understanding of how each research aim will be met and why the four methods work together to plug the gaps which would be left by using them in solitary.

Chapter 5 introduces the case studies which provide the focus of this research. Each case study includes a brief background; details about the hearing itself; and then the outcome or impact which occurred as a result of the hearing.

The sixth chapter discusses the DSEI which has been devised in order to determine the democratic standard of a particular process, in this case the public hearing process. The first section looks at each of the democratic norms in order; and the second section offers a discussion on what has been revealed by this analysis, including some findings.

Using fsQCA, the seventh chapter analyses the usefulness of the public hearing in a deliberative setting by focusing on the seven case studies. The key findings from the analysis as a whole are discussed and some further considerations on the case studies.

The eighth chapter provides normative analysis on where public hearings could play a role in a democratic system, while considering how they can be improved and where the democratic gaps are at present. The chapter is split into two sections, which are shaped by Smith's (2009a) institutional goods (efficiency and transferability).

In the conclusion, chapter 9, recommendations are made for the improvement of public hearings and for future research in this area. It would seem evident from this research that public hearings harbour the ability to make a measurable impact on environmental policy-making and the institutionalisation of deliberative democracy. The overriding argument in this thesis is that the hybrid capabilities of hearings make them an effective process for forwarding a green agenda, and are currently being underused.

Chapter 2: Deliberative democratic theory and the absence of public hearings

2.1 Introduction

There is something of a crisis in terms of democratic legitimacy in the UK as a result of decreasing political engagement (Dalton 2004; Stoker 2006), the transference of political power to institutions, such as the European Union and the devolved assemblies (Weale 2007: 3), and the rise in socio-economic inequalities which impact on individual's political efficacy (Pateman 1970: 104; Pattie *et al.* 2003: 632-3). Research has shown that people are becoming disillusioned with the current form of representative democracy (Carman 2006), resulting in apathy, alienation and anger from a critically aware populace who feel sidelined, patronised and driven to the periphery of the political playing field (Dryzek and Dunleavy 2009: 253). Warren (2001: 226) states that, 'democracy, once again in favour, is in need of a conceptual renewal'. It is understood by political experts that there are limits to democracy while it remains in its traditional form. Dalton *et al.* (2004: 125) believe that democracy requires modernising in order to keep up with 'twenty-first century realities' and they report that, 'Citizens are increasingly demanding more transparency and accountability from their governments, and want greater public participation' (Dalton *et al.* 2003: 3). Further issues arise with the implementation of institutional amendments within contemporary democratic states, which requires further exploration.

If indeed democracy should involve widespread participation, what types of participation should be included or are preferable? Are citizens sufficiently knowledgeable about public issues to effectively contribute to decision-making? Are citizens and representatives more likely to pursue their own self-interest in decision-making? How can coherent social choices be made which not only benefit the wider populace but includes them in political discussions? Deliberative democracy is an attempt to resolve all these issues. The first section of this chapter will introduce deliberative democratic theory. The second section will look at how theorists have envisioned its institutionalisation. By institutionalisation it is meant that deliberation or deliberative activity are incorporated in the political system and wider decision-making process. Despite the plethora of information which surrounds the capacity of democratic and alternative institutions to institutionalise deliberative democracy, the role of public hearings has been widely neglected. Therefore the discussion on institutionalisation will lead to section three which introduces public hearings.

2.2 Deliberative Democracy

Issues surrounding the existing liberal democratic model highlight a lack of participation and representation. Widespread feelings of disillusionment throughout the population have indicated that democracy, in its present state, is failing (Dryzek and Dunleavy 2009). Philosopher John Dewey stated that 'the cure for the ailments of democracy is more democracy' (cited Dryzek and Dunleavy 2009: 209). By this he means that the authenticity of democracy could be validated by large scale participation which is substantive instead of merely symbolic. Deliberative democratic theory offers a critique of existing democracy and can be used as an ideal model for other methods to be compared (Elstub 2006: 301). Citizens would be engaged in political control by means of being actively critical, reflexive and competent. Deliberative democracy offers an inclusive and reasoned political dialogue which promotes a moderate adjustment to current political institutions (Smith 2003: 53).

The central normative claim of deliberative democracy is that political decision-making should be 'talk-centric' rather than 'vote-centric' (Chambers 2003: 308), although this does not necessarily rule out voting (Weale 2007: 80). Instead, communication and the process of arguing, bargaining, challenging, and informal discussion should all be as instrumental to democratic outcomes as aggregative methods (Warren 2002: 173) leading to decisions that are more consensual and which better approximate the common good (Smith 2001: 74; Elstub 2009: 5). Citizens will thus be challenged by conflicting perspectives and alternative opinions. Mill (1998: 352) stated, 'If they saw more, they probably would not see so keenly, nor so eagerly pursue one course of enquiry'. Meaning people's understanding will be enlarged by the interaction of various cultures as well as increasing exposure to diversity. Therefore, deliberation encompasses an exchange between cross cultural groups, which achieves a 'fusion of horizons' (Gadamer 1997, cited Passerin d'Entreves 2002: 44).

Deliberative democracy is considered to have four core themes – the participation of all relevant actors, the consideration and exchange of reasons, the transformation of preferences and finally, deliberation must be linked to collective decision-making (Elstub 2006: 303). First, the participation of all relevant actors includes the equal access and means to the deliberative process for all those affected. The reflexivity that effective deliberation initiates is said to improve the epistemic value of democracy because it draws from a broad information base (Connelly and Smith 2003: 73). This deliberative turn has arguably witnessed a move away

from independent and internal reflections for individuals toward 'interpersonal engagement' (Goodin and Niemeyer 2008: 38). Second, the consideration and exchange of reasons means that actors should offer justifications with their perspectives and in turn, listen to the perspectives of others (Meadowcroft 2004: 184). Deliberation encourages mutual understanding which resolves conflicts through discussion and argument. It allows citizens to acknowledge their own shortcomings and the fallibility of their own perspectives and judgments (Smith 2003: 59). The strength of this reflection is that it creates an enlarged mentality which increases respect between fellow citizens and encourages a greater openness to others points of view – '...a community of problem-solving inquirers communicating with each other' (Dryzek and Dunleavy 2009: 216). Such a process, according to deliberative democrats, is more likely to generate decisions which are better reasoned and informed. Additionally, they will be more public-orientated and consensual; and are therefore more legitimate and effective (Passerin d'Entreves 2002; Davidson and Stark 2011).

Third, it is aimed at the transformation of preferences (Elstub 2006: 302-3). This does not mean that all participants should be ready to change their minds, but instead be open to the possibility of having their opinion changed (Dryzek 1987: 665). In order for deliberation to occur, reflexive consideration of preferences must be explored within a non-coercive environment. Habermas (1975: 108) believes the power of a well-constructed point should be enough to invoke changes in mindsets, through the 'forceless force of the better argument'. Providing motivation and encouragement for individuals to articulate preferences and justifications which are 'public spirited in nature' should moralise individual's opinions (Johnson 1998: 171). The fourth element is that deliberative democracy must endeavour to link collective deliberation with decision-making (Dryzek 2006: 23; Elstub 2006: 303). As Bloomfield *et al.* (2001: 502) concede, 'For progress to be made, participation has to focus on the development of policy and practice and not just on their legitimation and delivery'. This creates a decision-making process where citizens can communicate their own opinions, consider other peoples' points of view and arrive upon collective judgments (Warren 2002: 173). Therefore the real strength of deliberation is the legitimacy that it lends to the decision made, be that through aggregation or consensus, which results from the emphasis placed on the deliberation itself and not just the outcome (Cohen 1989; Weale 2007; Dryzek 2009). As Warren (2007: 274) explains – it is 'virtually impossible' not to support deliberative democracy due to its proposal of an alternative way of doing politics. Promoting good practice around speaking and listening, respecting other

actors and individual opinions, connecting decision-making with reflective deliberation and including those that are affected by a decision offers few areas for criticisms.

In order for deliberative processes to be implemented on a wider level, certain democratic goods must be combined (Smith 2009a: 192). With that in mind, Smith has identified democratic principles which he believes are ‘fundamental to any theoretical account of the democratic legitimacy of institutions’ (2009a: 12) enabling comparisons to be made of the various institutions. Democratic goods that Smith deems necessary include inclusiveness, in terms of presence and voice; popular control, the level of influence the participants have over the process and its outcome; the transparency of the process, both to those participating and the wider public; and considered judgement, the ability of participants to understand technical aspects of the issue and the various perspectives of their fellow participants (Smith 2009a: 12). These will be discussed at length in section 4.6.2. Institutional goods are also necessary to complement the democratic goods, and to demonstrate the practicalities of the institutions under study, which are efficiency and transferability (Smith 2009a: 26-27). Preceding the discussion on the institutionalisation of deliberative democracy, an understanding of what makes any particular forum a realistic addition to the democratic process is necessary.

2.3 Evaluating deliberative processes

Deliberative practices require individuals to participate in time consuming and costly political practices. The benefits of the lengthy deliberation would have to significantly outweigh the costs in order for democratic innovations to succeed (Smith 2009a: 13). However, the process and the outcome of deliberative processes can often be conflicting. Elstub (2008: 170) refers to the ‘Weberian dilemma’ (1978) to explain; ‘Either decision-making institutions gain effectiveness at the cost of democratic deliberation or they retain democracy at the cost of effective decision-making’. Elstub (2008) believes politics requires decisions while deliberation can often hinder this, Chambers (1995: 241) considers these the ‘tensions between the goods of mutual understanding and efficiency’. As a result of this ‘...citizenship, deliberation, and decision-making fail to be linked together’ (Bohman 1996: 178). Elstub (2008: 170) points out that if collective discussion is not linked with decision-making, no matter how educated the population, democracy will not be strengthened and the decision-making process will be no fairer. Smith (2009a: 26) responds to these concerns by offering a reminder that for efficiency to be achieved, the costs of *not* participating in these innovative

political processes would need to be known. Johnson (1998: 175) believes that in order to work, deliberative processes must interact with 'non-deliberative decision-making procedures', such as voting. This would be a necessary part of encouraging efficiency within the deliberative process. A conclusive decision must be the result of deliberative methods.

If citizens are to participate in strategic level decision-making, it is crucial to understand the transferability of the designs used. What causes further complexities to proposals, is that if radical decentralisation occurs within a nation and all citizens become active in the political process – how would this transcend on a wider scale, be that globally or transnationally (Smith 2009a: 27). This is because only certain institutional mechanisms will be compatible with democratic goods and be able to adapt according to the complexities that arise at particular stages of the decision-making process. For this, the effectiveness of each specific democratic innovation (Smith 2009a: 12) has to be investigated to understand which mechanism works at each level. The institutional goods are closely tied as the transferability of a process must include its effectiveness and efficiency at any given level. If deliberative democratic procedures are unable to adapt to scale or are more efficient as participatory process at a lower level, then the effectiveness of the design is flawed. The importance of democratic innovations must be explored in order to ascertain the most effective process at each level. Designs can be properly adapted to work at various scales; within different political systems and to deal with particular issues (Smith 2009a: 26). This is why the effectiveness of public hearings must be analysed as an integral part of the democratic procedure. Both alongside other deliberative procedures but also in the hopes that existing hearings can be improved upon. Elstub (2014b) believes that these concepts must be considered from a particular deliberative democratic perspective when exploring the institutionalisation of deliberation. The importance of these principles is that they may not be realised in any one institution thus the conjoining of institutions is necessary in order to utilise their strongest aspects and realise the democratic and institutional principles.

Academic research has largely focused on practical applications of deliberation through specific processes, such as mini publics (Dahl 1989; Goodin 2008) and representative institutions (Steiner *et al.* 2004; Davidson and Stark 2011). Mini-publics, which can take the form of deliberative polls (Fishkin 1991, 2009) and citizens' juries (Crosby 1995; *see also* Goodin 2008), among other mechanisms have been critical to better understand the benefits that small group deliberation can bring to citizens. Mini-publics chiefly surround the

combination of a randomly selected group of citizens taken from a larger populous who are brought into discuss issues of public concern. Mini-publics bring together citizens who are given the chance to ‘learn, think and deliberate’ together (Goodin 2008: 21) providing the public with the opportunity to contribute to the political discussion in a way which diverges from the traditional platforms of citizen participation (Smith 2009a: 1). This creates an alternative sphere for participating in politics, legitimising the existing democratic institutions (Smith 2009a: 3-4). The coming together of a plurality of actors is designed to lead to decisions which better reflect public opinion and lead to a more competent policy output (Papadopoulos 2012: 127). Hendriks (2016: 49) highlights the democratic challenges mini-publics face due to their limited connections with decision-making arenas, decision-makers and the mass media. While the focus has very much surrounded citizen deliberation, the connection between these processes and representative institutions has remained largely ineffectual. Setälä (2010: 15) highlights that very often mini-publics are often held on an ‘ad hoc basis’ indicating that the motivation for holding them is unassured. Similarly, the impact of a mini-public is often deemed to be low, thus demonstrating the need for them to be coupled with representative institutions which hold the mandate for decision-making (Hendriks 2016).

For this reason, attempts have been made to couple mini-publics and representative institutions; the results are cautiously encouraging. The devolved parliament in Scotland, for instance, took careful measures to break with tradition in its divergence from Westminster, moving away from the combative form of politics to embrace a new consensual type of politics (Davidson *et al.* 2011: 379). Difficulties arise when attempting to implement mini-publics within a parliamentary level. Politicians can be reluctant to ‘power-share’ with citizens and ensuring that the outcome of the deliberative process is taken seriously can be problematic (Davidson and Elstub 2014: 374; Hendriks 2016: 47). This example is not unique, there are existing sites of citizen empowerment where citizens have a share in decision-making, like Participatory Budgeting (PB) in Porto Alegre, Town Meetings in New England and the *Landsgemeinde* in Switzerland. There has also been an increase in alternative methods for combining participatory processes with representative institutions, such as the Citizens’ Assemblies in Canada and the Netherlands (Fournier *et al.* 2011) and PB has been rolled out in other areas such as Rome, Sevilla (Ryan and Smith 2012) and Scotland¹. Smith (2009a) refers to these as ‘democratic innovations’ and considers that these procedures are highly complex as it is difficult to decide

¹ See PB Scotland website for more details, available at: <http://pbscotland.scot/>.

who should contribute on specialised decisions or discussions. More research is required to consider how participatory processes could take a greater or more effectual role in coupling deliberation and representative institutions. However, the complexity of institutionalising deliberative processes extends beyond coupling clearly definable institutions, as the next section discusses.

2.4 Institutionalising deliberative democracy

While the 'empirical turn' in deliberative democracy has focused on the impact individual institutions have on institutions and governance by measuring their capacity for deliberation, complications have arisen in attempting to institutionalise deliberative democracy as there are two broad approaches. Hendriks (2006) refers to these approaches as micro and macro level deliberation. Micro deliberative theory considers the ideal conditions necessary to produce deliberative outcome as small structured, deliberative procedures that exist within the state - this includes impartial participants coming to a decision in the same place and at the same time (Hendriks 2006; Elstub 2010b). Macro theories of deliberative democracy differ from micro theories in that macro processes encompass informal and unstructured public discussion, which takes place in the public sphere (Habermas 1996). These are less concerned with decisions and instead look at discursive communication which exists outside the confines of the state. This allows discourses to persist and expand over time (Chappell 2010: 487). Macro deliberation is not as concerned with decision-making but instead opinion formation and as Elstub (2010c: 299) states, occurs over 'space and time' (i.e. transnationally and generationally).

Elstub (2008) and Hendriks (2006) believe that these micro and macro deliberative strategies must be combined in order to institutionalise deliberative democracy. If micro and macro deliberative processes are implemented separately, micro deliberation tends to be 'too elitist'. It is claimed that only certain actors will be suited to taking part in such a process. This includes those that are able, or willing, to uphold the norms necessary for democratic activity – reasoning, open-mindedness, the ability to reflect on the common good (Hendriks 2006: 493). Young (2001) warns that this may exclude interest groups, social movements and activists. Similarly, those who struggle to articulate themselves or have reason to forward self-interested claims rather than pertain to the common good may struggle to participate (Hendriks 2006: 493). Further to this, micro institutional processes, such as citizen orientated mini-publics, will

only result in policy proposals and collective public engagement rather than informed decision-making (Hendriks 2011: 299).

While macro deliberative democracy tends to be more inclusive, by existing in more accessible mediums (*for example* news media, social movements or associations), they can be viewed as being insufficient at empowering individuals and integrating them effectively into political processes. If citizens are unable ‘to stimulate counter-knowledge and ask critical questions’, and political actors effectively evade the groups which are prevalent in the macro sphere, communication can become confrontational or ineffective, moving away from the deliberative focus (Hendriks 2006: 494). A further risk is that of communicative distortion. This can be seen through inequalities between certain groups through resources (time, knowledge, power) or in terms of group interests pursuing an agenda (Hendriks 2006: 494-5). The media, for instance, is dominated by private interests which drives its political and social commentary, resulting in bias or inaccurate reports (Bächtiger and Wegmann 2014: 120). Hjarvard (2008: 113) refers to this as ‘mediatisation of politics’ where the media provides polarising information whose purpose is to simplify news and attention grab, in an attempt to retain readership. Different institutions of deliberation will yield different results - for instance, parliaments may accommodate rational justification and even higher speech acts but may not enact preference transformation (Goodin 2005). Furthermore, the media on a macro level forum has the capacity to cite the various discourses and inform the political climate through an accessible forum, but cannot offer the same benefits as a micro institution (Curato 2012: 425). Unless macro processes are appropriately linked to deliberative communication through decision-making and micro initiatives (Bächtiger *et al.* 2009: 8) little citizen control will be realised.

This has led to an extensive proliferation of institutions for a variety of contexts, in conjunction with the widely accepted understanding that no one institution can do all things at all levels. Although the scale of deliberation is often thought to threaten its legitimacy, Habermas (1996) offers a way round this. Despite advocating the need for face-to-face deliberation and decision-making, Habermas (1996: 170) acknowledges that ‘at the level of direct and simple interactions, not all citizens can join in the shared exercise of such a practice’. Habermas therefore supports a two-track deliberation which encourages a ‘discursively structured public sphere’ that feeds into ‘representative bodies for deliberation and decision-making’ (1996:

182). As a result, a parliamentary body would be predominantly structured around the means of justifying decisions and be formally regulated, while citizens associated with different networks would be on a 'context of discovery' in informal and unregulated institutions. Further consideration has been given to how this might be achieved including, the linking of various institutions in order to create a deliberative sequence (Goodin 2005) or a deliberative system (Parkinson and Mansbridge 2012).

First, Goodin's (2005) deliberative model assigns various agents differing roles in the deliberative context. This, he believes, is a plausible alternative to the 'unitary actor' model of existing deliberation. Sequencing various institutions would result in a more effective deliberative system as long as the 'right combination and the right order' can be identified (Goodin 2005: 193). Sequencing deliberative processes incorporates the linking of micro and macro deliberation through collaboration between the electorate and the elected. The political parties work out their positions in a reasoned debate; they explain these positions within parliament – the format of which is guided by deliberative virtues; these stances are then put to a 'maximally expansive' deliberative body (the public), according to Goodin (2005: 193). During an election, the political actors focus on issues that surround the common good and all discussion serves to forward a deliberative agenda. Goodin (2005: 194) refers to this as 'deliberative Schumpeterianism' as the political parties are framing the political and public debate by deliberatively coming up with clear policy stances which are yet to be developed and shaped, but are nonetheless acceptable to the public. Parliament is not the only place where policy development can be decided upon – Goodin (2005: 194) considers that voluntary organisations, interest groups, the media, as well as mini-publics could also serve this purpose. Yet, Hendriks (2016: 43) argues that the sequential model Goodin envisions focuses solely on elites deliberating in representative institutions, leaving citizens scarcely more empowered than they are now.

Deliberative democracy has shifted focus more toward a systemic approach, which Elstub and McLaverty (2014: 189-90) describe as the beginning of the fourth generation of deliberation. Parkinson and Mansbridge (2012) explain that the systematic approach enables researchers to look at deliberation more widely and overcomes issues of scale. It can do this in a number of ways; first, it enables researchers to look beyond individual deliberative institutions and focus

on the process of deliberation between institutions. Second, it recognises that individual institutions have differing strengths and weaknesses, which each have a different deliberative quality. The complimentary nature of democratic innovations can overcome the deliberative deficiencies of one. And third, by identifying what could feasibly be achieved by a deliberative system researchers can start to envision where the gaps exist and thus, how they might be overcome (Mansbridge *et al.* 2012: 2-4). And yet, as Hendriks (2006: 498) highlights, there is no assurance that all the different aspects of the deliberative system will support one another or that the informal macro discussions will effectively engage with the formal micro deliberation. Additionally, Steiner (2012: 36) observes, 'Thinking of deliberation in systemic terms is a useful exercise, but it makes it more difficult to identify what is deliberative and what not'. How the deliberative system works cohesively and how the various spheres of deliberation feed into one another is unclear. As various deliberate theorists acknowledge, there is still little understanding of how various institutions can combine to overcome the weaknesses of each (Warren 2007; Smith 2009a; Elstub 2014b). Neblo (2005) argues that further research is necessary before systemic deliberation can be fully explored. Given that much is still to be understood about individual institutions, including public hearings, and how they inform the deliberative movement, the institutionalisation of individual institutions is still relevant.

Hendriks (2006) instead offers a more integrated model for connecting the two spheres of deliberation. She devises an 'integrated deliberative system' designed to consider how the deliberative arenas will interface. Actors participate in different democratic processes – or 'discursive spheres'. Due to the variety of discursive spheres which exist in society, actors may choose to participate in any or none, and some will exist in the state and others outside. She (2006: 501) explains 'activists and interest groups are more likely to engage in more informal discursive spheres, as there are fewer rules and constraints...In the more formal spheres, experts and parliamentarians will engage in specialised and structured fora'. Hendriks' model includes a 'mixed discursive sphere' which is designed to combine the informal and formal types of deliberation and the micro and macro institutions. This, she (2006: 501) argues, would encourage those that would not normally inhabit the opposite sphere, bringing together representatives and experts with citizens and interest groups. Hendriks (2016) has more recently concentrated on the concept of 'designed coupling' which focuses on mechanisms that assist in the connection of deliberative processes and the representative arenas. By linking macro discursive communication in micro institutions, the wider public discourse can inform

the agenda of micro deliberative practices thus feeding in issues which concern citizens. Yet if this is to be established, the uses of public hearings must also be considered.

With this understanding of what could reasonably be achieved by any single deliberative institution, or which role could be best served within the deliberative sequence or integrated deliberative system, the role of the public hearings is notable only by its absence. Where a hearing is explored it is largely to highlight its ineffectual nature within the democratic process. Although there is evidence to suggest that they have been a fundamental component of a deliberative system (Parkinson 2012: 75) or as part of a deliberative sequence (Fournier *et al.* 2011), hearings are often considered a featureless or anonymous part of the process. They are not viewed as a tool in themselves, which may be capable of exciting a level of empowerment, mobilisation and perhaps deliberation. Despite this, public hearings are a recognised part of liberal democratic institutions that have the capacity to engage different people with varying skills, which is a vital component of deliberative discussions. Moreover the hybrid capacity of public hearings to fulfil different roles is considerable as there are various versions of them. It is contended here that they are a hybrid institution and therefore well-placed to facilitate a 'designed coupling' of opposing spheres (Hendriks 2016).

2.5 Public Hearings

Public hearings are a self-selecting participatory process which welcomes a variety of actors to identify and focus on issues that require discussion (Barclay 2012: 3). A hearing is used to discuss issues of public concern and designed to incorporate public participation into local level decision-making. At a higher level they incorporate public opinion into decision-making (Wraith and Lamb 1971: 160). This offers an opportunity for members of the public, as well as other group interests, to be heard and can also be used to demand the right to inquiry into issues which may have caused concern (Klinke 2009; Bherer *et al.* 2014). In the majority of cases they take the form of a question and answer session between a selected panel and an audience. This includes a chance for the audience to respond to the panel once a question has been forwarded and this exchange is mediated by a chairperson. They can also be run in an organisational format which encourages individuals or groups to submit evidence which may or may not be presented in public. In its simplest form, a hearing is an ideal setting to bring a demographic together where they can 'explore, develop and transform ideas and preferences together' (Fung 2006: 68). This is created by a broad range of people from the 'common sense'

views of lay citizens, and 'formal views' of experts, representatives and government officials (Rodger 1985a: 210). Abels (2007: 108) describes them as having five normative functions: to inform affected citizens; to inform the administrator; to represent stakes; to legally protect the applicants and those who feel affected; and to increase the legitimacy of the final administrative design. Public hearings are particularly useful because they can be initiated by public pressure (Selman 1981: 150) and they embody the necessary criteria to position themselves in Hendriks' (2006) mixed discursive sphere.

2.5.1 Types of Public Hearings

The procedure or process of a public hearing can take diverse and varying forms which is why they are complicated to examine (Howe 1999: 295). Wraith and Lamb (1971: 159) observe;

It would be pointless to try and apply any coherent system to the use of the terms inquiry, public inquiry, public local inquiry, and 'opportunity to be heard' (hearing): it is safe to say that none exists..., and to state that much of the time, irrespective of the term used, one is talking about the same thing.

Hearings can vary dependent on what organisers are attempting to achieve; who is involved and are specific to the geographical region. They are mandated by law in North America and are viewed as vital for community building (Lando 2003: 73 Baker *et al.* 2005: 491). In the UK a growing interest has surrounded more innovative participatory methods but traditional methods such as hearings and public meetings are still the most prevalent (Baker *et al.* 2005: 491). Meinig (1998) separates a public hearing from a meeting by depicting the former as an 'open record hearing' while the latter, a 'closed record appeal'. There are two types of public hearings; legislative and quasi-judicial. There is some degree of overlap between the two and any hearing may possess elements of each (Hutton 1986: 3).

Legislative public hearings seek to gain public input on legislative matters and policy-making. They can also be known as 'discretionary inquiries' and cover a wide range of subject topics (AHP 2012). These can be depicted as less formal than quasi-judicial. The purpose is to invite public reaction to a proposal, and they are designed to include anyone who will be affected by a proposal in future. Legislative hearings can include a wider range of people and through this, a diversified participation can create effective compromise and discussion, much of the evidence and level of discussion can be thought-provoking (Meinig 1998). Meinig (1998) believes that this type of public hearing can be a useful tool for seeking accountability for future

plans. The impact of such processes range from country to country. Hearings vary in outcome, while many focus on arriving at some form of resolution throughout proceedings (AHP 2012), others offer an opportunity to air views and reassure the public that they are not being 'ignored or suppressed' (Wraith and Lamb 1971: 165). In the US, decisions made within a legislative hearing are usually accepted by the courts and are rarely challenged. If challenged, it is usually based on procedural violations of state law rather than the outcome or the content of the hearing (Meinig 1998).

Quasi-judicial public hearings, also known as 'mandatory inquiries', are designed to surround the legal rights of specific parties. The inquiry becomes mandatory when 'the rights or property of an individual are involved' (Wraith and Lamb 1971: 157). This type of hearing is common in the UK and is often used to deal specifically with land use matters. They are therefore subject to stricter procedural requirements than legislative hearings (Wraith and Lamb 1971: 23). This procedure is more formal than legislative but not as formal as a court – again, the courts or the government can overturn a decision if proper procedure is not followed. Written procedures must be established in advance of the process, copies of which should be available for the officials holding the hearing and the attending public. Two week's public notice has to be given prior to the meetings (Meinig 1998). These usually take the form of an 'administrative hearing'. The administrative hearing is a similar process to that of a court trial and within the hearing the participants will seek to establish the facts in any case, with a chance of those who are being challenged to dispute the claims. Limitations are set on these hearings in that the final decision can only be based on the evidence gathered at the hearing.

2.5.2 Issues with Public Hearings

Presently hearings are somewhat overlooked in deliberative literature. However, there are a number of reasons for this. Hearings are often criticised for enacting an ineffective influence over government decisions, despite being perfectly positioned to make a credible impact. Innes and Booher (2004: 419), among others (King *et al.* 1998; Baker *et al.* 2005), believe that methods of participation - specifically existing methods of public hearings - are ineffective; unsatisfactory and not legitimate ways of formulating decision-making. Rodger (1985b: 413) believes that the public have lost faith in public hearings or the inquiry process because it's, '...not fair and offends their sense of natural justice'.

There is a complexity that surrounds the formal communication of public opinion. The outlet is not necessarily a facilitator of the means, this means that citizens are frequently left disappointed or disillusioned after dedicating their time and effort toward an inconclusive and undetermined outcome. By taking part in a hearing, the public have a place in the decision-making process, but there is still a level of mistrust surrounding the process where, in the past, the process itself has been viewed as a façade designed to seek legality for a pre-determined decision (Rodger 1978: 105; Adams 2004: 44; Baker *et al.* 2005: 495). The manipulation of the democratic process is a difficult issue (Rodger 1978: 106). Etzioni (1968) suggests that the democratic deficit is an inevitable feature of complex modern society, which leads to alienation for many who feel excluded from controlling the quality and direction of their lives. The democratic institutions designed to address this problem succeed only in delivering an 'inauthentic' experience, including public hearings. Etzioni argues that 'inauthentic structures devote a higher ratio of their efforts than alienating ones to concealing their contours and to generating the appearance of responsiveness' (Etzioni 1968: 619-20).

According to Rodger (1978), the inauthenticity within the public inquiry system is determined by three issues. First, the political role of the public inquiry in mediating the relationship between expert and political practice. This can highlight the influence and impact of political will and public opinion on political processes. Second, the 'classification' and 'framing of knowledge and information' which is deemed relevant in order to evaluate the public issues. This issue speaks to the broad problem of agenda setting and determination of what counts as relevance in the evidence process and the extent to which non-interest groups possess sufficient power to control the direction of the inquiry process. And the third issue concerns the extent to which a public inquiry allows discussion to move to a more detailed level (Rodger 1978: 105). This is similar to Habermas' (1984) concept of the 'ideal speech situation': does the process follow the logic of a systems rationality which narrows down what can, and cannot, be discussed in line with a delimited inquiry remit or a 'discursive rationality'. Does it pursue the 'truth' and justificatory evidence to support arguments and assertions in public hearings? Criticisms can be too easily deflected by well versed officials. Officials do not listen and poor levels of deliberation are achieved because in many instances, especially in the US, 'dialogue is forbidden' (Adams 2004: 44). This means that the degree of popular control that exists within hearings is currently limited.

A further issue arises as hearings are generally held too late in the decision-making process (Adams 2004: 44). Kemp (1985: 177) states that public hearings are a tool for manipulation by legitimising the actions and interests of dominant groups in capitalist societies. This 'back door brokering' means that powerful individuals have already set the agenda and decisions are made in private before being aired to the public (Young 2000: 4). As Lando (2003: 76) proclaims, upon reaching a decision officials often read from a 'prepared statement' which highlights the lack of impact the hearing has had. Kemp (1985: 177) accuses public hearings of offering a sphere that systematically distorts the communication process and Baker *et al.* (2005: 491) argues that officials do not want to share decision-making power. Very often the process of hearings does little to facilitate engagement between officials and citizens, and provides an unsatisfactory level of debate. Instead, public inquiries can become a central focus for opposing parties which can lead to strong rooted resentment and embody protests, petitions and bad public feelings (Young 2000: 104). Furthermore, doubts regarding the ability of lay citizens to comprehend the complexities of certain issues may arise. The public's comments may not be treated with the same degree of respect that experts are. Other individuals may be more experienced and the majority resistant to the minority claim (Young 2000: 55). Kemp (1985: 177) concurs and suggests that public hearings tend to be a one way communication from people to government used to gauge reactions to proposed plans or decisions. Conversely though, it can also be considered a one-way communication where the public come to vent their anger and discontent. Adams (2004: 44) believes hearings can transcend into false claims and thinly veiled attacks on officials. This can mean input is decidedly lessened as the public can become a 'reactive and judgemental' in an effort to 'sabotage administrators' (King *et al.* 1998: 320). In addition, it has been said that the attendees do not represent a true microcosm of wider society (Klinke 2009).

Public hearings, more often than not, have an open, self-selective method on who can attend. The danger in this is that the same sort of people can attend;

People who show up...are more likely to be extremists on the issue being discussed because they have greater personal incentives to participate. Hearings may be dominated by those with very strong views on the subject being discussed, crowding out moderate voices that may represent large segments of the community (Adams 2004: 44).

This can be intimidating for those who are not familiar with the process or as outspoken. Participants of hearings seldom include younger or less educated people (Baker *et al.* 2005:

492). Research conducted by Midden (1995: 316) found that women were less likely to take part than men and that people who identified as 'left wing' were more likely to attend. Mini-publics in contrast usually adopt random or stratified sampling to ensure that everyone has an equal chance of participating (Elstub 2014: 174). Fishkin (2009: 98), among others (Few *et al.* 2007: 49-50), highlights his concern of self-selection in public processes, fearing that the process is exposed to domination by organised interests. Social pressure will increase the chances of individuals bowing to the collective will. The chance of a representative sample being obtained through self-selection is significantly lessened meaning that predictions or generalisations about wider society cannot be made (Fishkin 2009: 132-3). Instead, Fishkin believes that random sampling is preferable as it offers a more representative sample of wider society. He uses random sampling for recruiting in deliberative polls and considers this method able to overcome issues of scale meaning that a small randomly sample can still be representative regardless of whether the sample is representing a town city or nation state or even a supranational state such as the EU. Yet he acknowledges that there is no assurance that this microcosm will represent any or all views of the wider public (Fishkin 2009: 97-99) and that it is still reliant on an element of self-selection as individuals still have to choose to take part once they have been selected (Elstub 2014: 174).

James (2008) on the other hand argues that stratified sampling is more effective in gathering an inclusive sample and adds that quotas may be necessary. While it is not necessary to provide a proportional representation of the population – as very often the issue that is being spoken about does not call for an exact microcosm - instead a group that represents the diversity in that particular society is acceptable. For example, James (2008: 122) explains that while a representative sample may include one individual from a minority group, 'an isolated individual is less likely to express a minority position that contradicts the dominant perspective'. Having less a 'representative sample' and more of a 'descriptive sample', which invites those from minority groups, would be more likely to highlight diversity and the varied opinions of that specific demographic (James 2008: 123). An important aspect of getting people involved in participatory and deliberative processes is to invite them. As Verba *et al.* (1995) found when they asked 'Why don't people participate in politics?' There are three answers: 1) 'They can't; 2) 'They don't want to' and; 3) 'Nobody asked'. Davies *et al.* (2006: 80-1) report that people invited to take part in a deliberative or participatory process typically accept.

Undeniably random and stratified sampling are necessary for producing more representative groups of people. Moreover it is vital for motivating people to get involved in democratic processes. However, in defence of self-selection, it affords a certain degree of inclusiveness in that if people wish to attend – they can attend. Public hearings are open to all that wish to take part, thus often the number of attendees and the capacity for information exchange can be one of a hearings greatest functions (Karjalainen 2014: 10). Although self-selection, such as that used in hearings, is guilty of many disadvantages it could, in this instance, provide an alternative by including citizens themselves who are seeking knowledge, answers to questions and to be involved. As it has been said; ‘Are the views of a random sample more useful than those of active participants in a lengthy consultation? The public must judge’ (Spicer Commission 1991, cited Catt and Murphy 2003: 409). And as Smith (2009a: 80-1) concedes those who choose to participate in open processes often tend to be more educated and have a higher level of political interest. Self-selection may be in opposition to the ‘ideal’ deliberative vision but by adopting an ‘opt-in’ process more akin to liberal representative democracy, a *different* demographic from that selected to participate in mini-publics, is able to participate and become democratically active.

It is therefore necessary to acknowledge that public hearings in many countries are presently flawed. The emphasis for their redemption must be focussed on which point of the decision-making process hearings are held. In the US they are part of the legal system – utilised as a ‘legitimising’ tool for a purely administrative process. In the UK they are regularly approached with suspicion, in essence because of the prominence of government official’s influence on the outcome. Often they are held once planning is underway and the consultation period is over, understandably members of the public feel that their input is appealed for belatedly. That being said, public hearings have all the rudiments of an effective process thus should be considered a useful addition as a deliberative democratic institution. The use of self-selection affords hearings a unique aspect as a deliberative process. The deliberative capacity, as yet unknown, could prove an asset to the democratic process. Crucially, they are an existing part of the contemporary democratic process, insomuch as they are frequently used within liberal democracies in matters of policy and planning (Lando 2003, Wraith and Lamb 1971). Further to this, hearings have an intrinsic role in initiating participation in administrative governance in the European Union and North America (*see* Checkoway 1981; Beierle and Cayford 2002; Baker *et al.* 2005; Abels 2007,) which are often held by law (in the US); or at least have legal

provisions (in the EU); or recommended procedural requirements (in the UK) (Baker *et al.* 2005). Davidson and Stark (2012: 158) highlight that very often attention has been given to ‘discursive mechanism’, such as citizens’ juries, as opposed to existing representative institutions. This is, as they explain, due to the aversion to adversarial politics in deliberative research as it fails to fulfil the ideal conditions for deliberation. Such an explanation could then be attributed to the lack of public hearings in the democratic literature given the process’s combative and antagonistic reputation (King *et al.* 1998; Adams 2004).

A less jaundiced view is that hearings legitimise decisions made by dominant political and economic players by encouraging transparency and accountability (Kemp 1985: 177). Innes and Booher (2004: 422) contend that;

This framework is not based on the mechanistic imagery of citizens pushing on government, but on the complex systems imagery of a fluid network of interacting agents, gathering information from each other and the environment and acting autonomously based on their needs, understanding and, shared heuristics.

It gives experts a platform to respond to concerns raised by lay opinion regarding specific decisions; but also gives the public the chance to gain information, be involved and communicate their own worries. According to Hutton (1986: 12) an inquiry should, ‘consider all feasible alternatives and seek to ensure that all the assumptions, material facts, issues and arguments are brought out, tested and fully and fairly discussed’. It has been noted that when hearings are not made available to citizens during a controversial planning or development project, they (citizens) can become reactionary and resentful (MacIntosh 2012: 3). Klinke (2009: 353) tells us; ‘affected and interested people perceive the public hearings as one of the cornerstones in the public participation’. Hearings are looked to as a recognised institution by citizens, and citizens can ‘seek justice’ if this is not made available to them, even if other consultation processes are in action². Furthermore while the literature suggests that they have a bad reputation in the UK and the US (King *et al.* 1998; Bloomfield *et al.* 2001; Innes and Booher 2004), in Canada, Finland and Sweden (Bherer *et al.* 2014; Schylter and Stjernquist 2010; Karjalainen 2014) public hearings have been an intrinsic part in achieving an inclusive

² A case in point is the local people of Edinburgh taking their grievance with Edinburgh Council over the environmental implication of the development of the Tram system to the UN when a public hearing was not held. Karpowitz and Mansbridge (2005) in their chapter on Disagreement and Consensus have reported a similar outcome in their case study.

and participatory decision-making process, especially in environmental decision-making (Dryzek 2005; Karpowitz and Mansbridge 2005; Schylter and Stjernquist 2010; Fournior *et al.* 2011). The next section will argue that this is because public hearings are a 'hybrid' form of institution.

2.5.3 Public Hearings Varied Hybrid Credentials

A hybrid institution refers to the capacity of a single institution to combine differing practices, such as the development of government policies alongside and within local and community participatory processes. This would be, in essence, better suited to dealing with the complexities of modern society – specifically when attempting to reach a level of deliberation within a participatory process, designed to result in a decision. According to Backstrand *et al.* (2010: 223); 'Hybrid institutions are designed to couple different rationalities and forms to achieve their combined strength; ideally accommodating deliberative ideals and effective policies which increase legitimacy and effectiveness in democracy'. And to paraphrase Fung (2004: 69-70), it is better to combine decentralised and centralised institutions as the differences of each institution can inform the other and lead to better decision-making. He says: '...a hybrid design, in which local autonomy requires centralised support and accountability and in which accomplishing broader aims requires street-level innovation and civic engagement, is more promising than either simple centralisation or decentralisation'. An institution or process could therefore be considered hybrid when it is capable of bringing seemingly opposing spheres together or connecting areas which require connection. Warren (2009: 5) believes public hearings to be centred, non-elected institutions, he explains: 'Centred institutions receive input, process it, issue authoritative decisions, and then organise collective actions'. In attempting to realise Warren's call for democratisation to happen at an electoral level, this ability to combine all stakeholders to work at the mixed discursive level indicates that hearings could well accommodate democratisation at this level (Warren 2009: 8) thus promoting public input and community representation with electoral legitimacy.

Therefore, it could reasonably be assumed that the public hearing could embody a position within Hendriks' (2006) integrated deliberative system in the mixed discursive sphere. Hearings could bring together the informal actors into a process which enables them to connect with the formal actors in the middle ground thus coupling the two spheres of deliberation (Hendriks 2006, 2016). Similarly, by existing within this mixed sphere, there is potential to

engage in the type of civic engagement through interest groups as discussed by Davidson *et al.* (2011) within the public hearing process. In essence a hybrid institution, like a public hearing, could help to connect micro and macro level deliberation by creating a third level of deliberative democracy, the 'meso' level (this will be explored later in the thesis section 8.2.2). Subsequently hearings could enact the key democratic principles by which democratic deliberation is measured, whilst aligning them with effective and efficient decision-making processes under a liberal democracy. This will be explored in the next chapter.

2.6 Conclusion

Deliberative democracy has evolved throughout the past three decades from a theory to a practically applicable framework in which to adopt and amend existing liberal institutions. The theory has the ability to transcend national and geographical political institutions, and become an ecumenical model of democracy, able to widen inclusion; increase transparency and empower citizens. It is now in, what some would consider, its fourth generation and as such, it is time to reflect on where the theory has come from and what metaphorical procedural stones may have been left unturned. Deliberative democratic theories have failed to come up with a convincing answer to global deliberation. Moreover the merging of micro and macro deliberation has left questions unanswered. Where each institution can play a role in the institutionalisation is unclear and incomplete. Before starting to consider the deliberative systems which Parkinson and Mansfield (2012) are calling for, it is necessary to be aware of what existing institutions are capable of. In order to decide what is missing from the deliberative system, what is needed must first be examined. If each democratic innovation is capable of reversing representative democracy's demise, where then is the public hearing to play a role? It is inevitable that hearings would be unable to realise all six of these democratic and institutional norms, and yet it would seem that they could partially realise them all and, as Smith (2009a: 20) says, 'institutions may realise these goods in different ways and in different combinations'. The next chapter will further the exploration of hearings by examining what public hearing's hybrid characteristics could bring to the deliberative democratic model and where hearings can be of use within environmental policy-making. This will include a discussion on the role of experts in the political sphere and how their input to the environmental narrative can more effectively guide the deliberative process.

Chapter 3: The hybrid possibilities of public hearings in environmental policy-making

3.1 Introduction

Liberal democracy has been accused of failing to tackle the innate challenges which face the environment (Dryzek 2000; Eckersley 2000). The use of Administrative Rationalism and the prominence of the cost-benefit analysis in guiding decision-making has not only intensified the environmental crisis but corroded the relationship between the public and its representatives (Dryzek 2005: 85). It has been argued that centralised governments; technocrats and bureaucrats are under-qualified to make decisions regarding environmental policies (Hajer 1998: 247). More recently cynicism has surrounded scientists and politicians as experts (Worcester 2002: 16). Attention has therefore been paid to the role of traditional liberal representative democratic institutions and deliberative democratic innovations in environmental decision-making. A process which accommodates the public discussion of problems and solutions under conditions that support external and internal reflection and public judgement is said to facilitate environmentally driven policy-making (Parkins and Mitchell 2005: 531). However, both liberal democracy and deliberative democracy have been criticised for failing to promote green issues (Dryzek 2000: 141-42). The complexities that surround environmental decision-making mean that it is understandably problematic to decipher what action to take. This is further aggravated by convoluted ideas about *who* should be tackling these issues and *how* they should be tackled. Competing ideologies have resulted in a crossover between who is considered an expert on any given issue. At a time when environmentalists were postulating the end of the world (Meadows *et al.* 1972, Carson 1962) and others were refuting these claims (Simon and Kahn 1984; Lomborg 2001) or fostering a more pragmatic outlook through the adoption of ecological modernisation (Dryzek 1992; Christoff 2000); ecological socialism (Biehl 1997) or ecological anarchism (Bookchin 1971), a minefield of varying depictions on the best way to manage the environment emerged.

The effects of the environment are multifaceted as they affect everyone. Therefore, when it comes to the environment everyone is a stakeholder (Grimble and Chan 1995: 114) – so how to manage decision-making? The contemporary political system and the environment would appear to be at loggerheads in terms of policy-making. It could be argued that one of the key failings of deliberative democracy to pursue a green agenda is its failure to properly utilise

experts and citizens in the process. It could be further argued that the inability of deliberation to result in decisions is due to the exclusion of policy-makers from the discussion. The chapter will first look at how experts could inform the debate by reimagining the position they hold in a democratic society. Primarily looking at Fischer's (2009) vision of a participatory inquiry, this will explore the role of experts as teachers or guides to citizens through the deliberative process and thus, in the field of 'policy inquiry'. This chapter will consider how public hearings can encompass a deliberative agenda and, in harnessing the expertise of all actors, could forward the green agenda.

3.2 The Environmental Democratic Paradox

Green thinkers note that environmental goods are public goods, whose protection is not best served by a liberal aggregative model of democracy (*see* Jacobs 1997; Barry 1999). Baber and Bartlett (2005: 120) believe that liberal democracy has failed in achieving environmental sustainability as surely as it has lost its democratic character, and deliberative democracy has emerged as a response to this. Liberalism's failure to deal with climate change and the increasing consumption and production sector is largely due to the promotion of self-interest and is exacerbated by the way politics is practised; the distribution of power and the exclusion of certain groups in the political arena (Smith 2003: 54). Baber and Bartlett (2005: 2) state that liberalism has been rendered obsolete by the 'scope and the seriousness' of the environmental issues facing humankind. Despite the apparent optimism regarding individuals, and their ability to take decisive action when faced with high levels of risk, the present democratic state does little to facilitate this (Beck 1992; Dryzek and Dunleavy 2009). In contemporary society the environment is rarely given precedence due to the preservation of egocentricity (Fischer 2000: 111) and the lack of incentives to become a 'morally responsible agent' (Eckersley 1999: 42).

Dryzek (2000: 9) notes that under liberalism, citizens are often pulled between the contrary forces of individual freedom and the common good. Liberal politics are moulded by predetermined interests; therefore individuals are encouraged to behave in an individualistic fashion rather than considering society as a whole. This is arguably a result of an uneducated and disillusioned population that has neither the means nor knowledge to challenge government decisions. Offe and Preuss (1991, cited in Smith 2003: 55) claimed that;

Contemporary liberal institutions are not designed to encourage engagement and the testing of preferences and value orientation – citizenship is typically a passive affair which leads to a moral and political ‘deskilling’ of the electorate and the spread of cynical attitudes about public affairs and the notion of a public good.

Smith (2003: 53) concurs and emphasizes that human behaviour encompasses a lack of consideration of the non-human world. Rather than the public blindly accepting the views of established authorities, collective choices should be made through ‘reasoned discussion’ (Meadowcroft 2004: 184).

Beck (1992: 61) highlights the risks that individuals face due to the prominent concentration of globalised modernisation. Industrialisation and an increasing demand for the ‘good life’ exacerbates political and social inequalities. This is further aggravated by ‘outdated’ political and administrative responses to the risk society (Fischer 2000; Beck 1992). The growing threat has led to a response which Beck (1992) believes has compelled the green movement to push society in a more reflexive direction. Dryzek and Dunleavy explain (2009: 253); ‘risk society is peopled by critically aware citizens who no longer accept the inevitability and desirability of economic growth and technological change’. Beck (1992: 61) believes that a degree of responsibility is accepted thus new forms of democratic ‘subpolitics’ emerge (1992: 196) which he refers to as ecological democracy (Beck 1995). By this Beck means innovative, discursive and multi-faceted politics which would, in turn, achieve greater levels of ‘preserving’ politics (1992: 235). From here, Smith (2003: 65) elaborates;

When faced with high levels of uncertainty and risk, deliberative institutions promise an ingenious mechanism through which the application of scientific and technological knowledge and expertise might be democratically regulated – an institutional setting within which the barriers between ‘expert’ and ‘lay’ knowledge can be challenged and reformulated.

Environmental protection largely relies on levels of public interest and pressure. Green solutions need to include long term plans, which inevitably clash with short term individual interests (Eckersley 1996: 171). Preventative methods or green policies are often unpopular with the right and left ideological spheres. Subsequently, the correct antidote is rarely achieved by short term governments working to gain wide-spread support (Wissenburg 2006: 21). Dryzek (2005: 75) considers that, in most developed countries, environmental issues have been tackled by a ‘problem solving’ discourse which he refers to as Administrative Rationalism.

Administrative Rationalism was developed in response to the growing concerns surrounding sustainability. Governments in the past have adopted a strategy similar to that of defence planning, security and the health service, which comprises of representatives relinquishing policy development to the appropriate department (Dryzek 2005: 85). In dealing with issues like environmentalism, developed countries have been seen to implement an almost assimilated type of policy initiative action, favouring expert driven policies (Howes 2005: 32). This endorses a system that 'rationally' manages environmental issues from a top-down, expert based, advisory capacity which is demonstrably exclusive (Dryzek 2005: 86). Private decision-making processes are often susceptible to maximizing private interests, and these interests are often decided by cost-benefit analysis (CBA) (Beierle and Cayford 2002: 3). CBA is used to guide crucial environmental decisions. This involves a comparison of the economic costs and the benefits of proposed policies (Smith 2003: 29) which is ultimately detrimental to future generations and non-human life as the economic benefits are often perceived to outweigh the ecological costs (Smith 2003: 54, Eckersley 1996: 214). Moreover, the decisions guided by rational choice predict that all actors – consumers and businesses - will be acting under the pursuit of self-interest, therefore the assumption is that market driven policies will provide admissible solutions (Howes 2005: 76). This removes the power from those that could contribute to a better ecological understanding and here, Habermas offers a reminder; 'specialised and competent fulfilment of tasks by experts is no protection against a *paternalistic* self-empowerment' by administrative agencies (1996: 188). By allocating the role of environmental policy-making to bureaucrats and agencies, it has removed power from the actual people that are impacted by environmental issues, thus deepening the existing democratic deficit (Weale 1992: 155).

3.2.1 The Complex Role of Experts in Environmental Decision-making

The role of experts in a democratic society has long been debated (Dewey 1927; Dahl 1989; Fischer 2000). An expert is a fairly flexible term but generally includes those that are widely accepted to be a reputable source of knowledge and skilled in a particular field. The status of expert is accepted by wider society whether through the position they hold or the authority their knowledge earns (Fischer 2009: 17). With an increasing move towards an eco-managerialism (Luke 1999) and technocratic governance (Fischer 1999) a shift toward professional led policy-making has been witnessed, which has seen professional experts taking a more prominent position in guiding policy-making and working closely in conjunction with governments. The

need for bureaucrats, civil servants, advisory boards has greatly increased due to the information revolution and what Fischer (2000: 14) refers to as the emergence of a 'expertocracy'. Experts enjoy a level of autonomy that no other groups in contemporary society do (Fischer 2009: 23). They do not need to rely on electoral support, like politicians, or adhere to a set of principles, like the media. Pressure groups and trade unions too cannot boast the freedom that professional experts have due to the assumed power which is associated with knowledge and skill. The narrative surrounding the expert has become progressively critical (Fischer 2009: 20).

This perceived expertocracy places citizens in a disadvantaged position as an 'unequal communicative relationship' (Fischer 2000: 18) is created, whereby citizens struggle to comprehend the technical language and administrative goals set by the experts leading to what Almassi (2012: 33) describes as a '*social-epistemic problem*'. Due to the lack of understanding on such complex issues, and faced with conflicting evidence, non-experts cannot hope to dispute or challenge the expert opinion. This is further exacerbated by the 'dialectical superiority' of these experts which, while not being an indicator of the truth of their claims, enables them to discuss issues with ease. In turn, making them more persuasive and believable, putting the non-expert at a disadvantage (Goldman 2001; Almassi 2012). The problem arises when lay citizens are ill-equipped to become more informed on such a complex issue as climate change; Hardwig (1985, 1994) refers to this as 'epistemic dependence'. People can collect evidence which may validate and support their beliefs but there are limitations on how much evidence can be gathered. The enormity of the subject and the world; the restrictions on individual abilities to observe and collect vast quantities of empirical evidence over time and space mean that this is not possible (Almassi 2012: 31). The lay citizen is therefore reliant on experts for information. Instead of professionals and citizens coming together to overcome these limitations, there has been a parting of ways as the wider public have become increasingly disillusioned with the technocratic expert.

Habermas (1971) observes that a significant problem in contemporary society is a tendency for apparently open and democratic decision-making processes to be characterised by what he calls 'technocratic decisionism' and 'scientism' in which the knowledge and experience of scientific, technocratic and academic elites crowd out the voice of ordinary citizens. The illegitimate influence of the professional experts in both the private and public lives of citizens

has contributed to a distrust, a cynicism, a drop in public confidence, and at times public protests (Fischer 1999: 295). In a unequal and troubled world, 'Professional experts...have been portrayed as perpetuating, if not creating, many of the social injustices plaguing modern Western societies' (Fischer 2009: 21). Controversy has arisen over particular events where experts have failed to consider the wider implications of their decisions on lay citizens and communities. Examples include risk assessments carried on new developments which neglect to inform the surrounding communities about the danger of the hazardous waste (Richardson *et al.* 1993; Wiebe 2014); the announcement of new medicines and treatments, which are withheld from those who need it; regulation on who can legally get abortions and who cannot (Fischer 1999: 295); the widely controversial debates on genetically modified foods and cloning; the development of nuclear power plants, windfarms and solar fields, Carbon Capture and Storage, and fracking, which all claim to improve the global foot print, while impacting heavily on the communities in which they are situated, resulting in what Fischer (1999, 2000) describes as a 'techno-pessimism'.

Evidence that declining relations - not just between experts and citizens - but between experts themselves have been witnessed, where professionals have accused their peers of having 'vested interests' or perceived 'agendas' (Roberts and Escobar 2014: 31-2). Experts are accused of furthering their own agenda in order to maintain contracts, funding and notoriety as well as using their position to persuade political officials and talk down to lay citizens (Fischer 1999: 296). Therefore, it can be argued that participatory democracy had lost its edge to political-administrative power (Rodger 1985a: 203). As Fischer states, 'In this view, technical risk assessments serve, wittingly or unwittingly, to render less visible the fundamental social questions embedded in the very design of technological research (Fischer 1995: 185-7; Fischer 1999: 297). In this way, by undermining the social implications of developments, the entire idea of risk assessment is flawed. There has therefore been a call to promote more democratic means of policy planning. Deliberative democrats believe that deliberation offers a resolution here. This however, has resulted in an unnecessary obstacle to citizen participation where the suggested conflicting inputs of citizens and experts would appear to be counterproductive. Indeed deliberative democrats have suggested that the use of public opinion should be in direct opposition to technical expertise (Manin 1987: 355; Fung 2003: 343). This would more likely include replacing the technocratic response to the environmental crisis with a participatory and pluralistic approach.

3.2.2 Democratising Environmental Decision-making through Deliberation

Deliberative democracy has quickly established itself as a new orthodoxy within contemporary democratic theory (Smith 2001: 72) which many have forwarded as the most realistic form of democracy to forward the best interests of green issues (Dobson 1996, Goodin 1996; Dryzek 2000; Smith 2003; Arias-Maldonado 2007). For this reason and due to the varied and complex discourses which surround environmental policy-making, calls for decision-making to more closely include citizens have been made. Without the wider populace's input the legitimacy of the democratic society is lacking. Burby (2003: 35) believes that participation produces better decisions through four key areas: the principle of fairness and equity; the right to information and to express opinions and decisions; the need for wider representation, especially of marginalised groups, and the importance of capturing insights of citizens. Undoubtedly, citizens are willing to become engaged in salient political issues; capable of effectively mobilising and organising to set the agenda and demand to be heard (Richardson *et al.* 1993). However, providing the right tools (knowledge, information and a voice) and facilitating the right arena for such a conversation is more challenging (Baker *et al.* 2005: 491).

Deliberative democrats believe that effective problem solving in decentralised areas will achieve greater levels of ecological policy-making, as Dryzek and Dunleavy (2009: 263) explain; 'from the viewpoint of many environmental agendas this democratisation is mere incremental tinkering, yet it is perhaps indicative of the possibilities for more extensive political-ecological reform'. Furthermore Dryzek, in particular, emphasises that green matters are compatible with deliberative democracy: 'extensive competent participation means that a variety of voices can be raised on behalf of a wide variety of concerns' (Dryzek 1992: 39). It is assumed that deliberation's ability to drive participants in the direction of the common good will lead to decisions which are more likely to protect the environment-as-public-good (Elstub 2009: 4). Eckersley (2000: 120) says,

Public spirited deliberation is the process by which we learn of our dependence on others (and the environment) and the process by which we learn to recognize and respect differently situated others (including non-human others and future generations).

This has been acknowledged as a means of internalising the interests of non-human nature (Eckersley 2004) and future generations (Hayward 1998) by encouraging people to think beyond their own arbitrary understanding of nature; thereby developing an ecological citizenship among the populace.

Deliberation's epistemic value is also viewed as relevant to ecological problems, which are complex, interconnected and non-reducible. It is thought to improve understanding across individuals representing different facets of the problem (Dryzek 1987, 1992). Consequently, and more specifically for environmental decision-making, citizens are expected to make collective decisions on the basis of discussion and reason; this is designed to promote the common good (Fabre 2003: 107; Carpini *et al.* 2004: 321; Coenen 2008: 2). As acknowledged in section 2.2, this provides individuals with the incentive to forward ideas and beliefs which are publically justifiable and less likely to promote opinions which are morally reprehensible (Dryzek 1987: 665; Johnson 1998: 171). Again, this results in a moralising impact on public discussion (Dryzek 1987: 34) from the emphasis which is placed on the deliberation itself, and not just the outcome. Parkins and Mitchell (2005: 532) argue that deliberative democratic theory encourages public debate, political and personal reflection and informed public opinion, which is particularly relevant in terms of accommodating environmental practice, due to the educative element it can offer. Deliberative methods have the capacity to 'forge an honest and creative deliberative approach that can be more democratic and can yield genuine benefits for the process of societal adaptation' (Few *et al.* 2007: 55).

Issues of an ecological nature can often be highly complex, and often surrounded by contestable discourses that need to be tackled in a sensitive manner. Therefore, there is evidence to support that deliberative democracy can offer some substantial advantages to the environmental movement. It is important, however, to remember that although limited, ground has been made toward encapsulating sustainability under liberal democracies. Various forms of participatory methods are becoming familiar in environmental policy-making within liberal societies including traditional methods, such as public hearings and meetings, and more recently citizen juries, stakeholder advisory committees and facilitated mediations (Beierle and Cayford 2002: 1). This, as Beierle and Cayford (2002: 1) believe, has been instrumental in determining how the environment is managed and protected. Adversely though, while environmental sustainability encounters limitations under the current ideological framework of which most developed countries adhere to, environmental protection largely relies on levels of public interest and pressure. Aforementioned, green solutions need to include long term plans which clashes with short term individual interests (Eckersley 1996; Wissenburg 2006). This will continue to be problematic as long as liberal democratic societies, and in turn capitalism, perpetuates a society governed by consumerism. However, deliberative democracy is not

without its critics. Accusations of utopianism and tokenism have been directed by a number of prominent theorists (Bloomfield *et al.* 2001; Shapiro 2003; Mutz 2006).

There are four key issues which arise that challenge the assumption that deliberative democracy and ecological rational behaviour can naturally be reconciled. First, environmental issues may not be prioritised; second, deliberation is an ineffective decision-making process; third, liberal values will prevail within deliberative processes and fourth, the focus on citizen deliberation. The first, there is little to indicate that deliberative structures will prioritise green issues (Dobson 1993; Dryzek 2000; Baber and Bartlett 2005). As Goodin (1992: 198) said, 'To advocate democracy is to advocate procedures, to advocate environmentalism is to advocate substantive outcomes; what guarantee can we have that the former procedures will yield the latter sorts of outcomes'. Within any form of democracy there will always be a leading anthropocentric perspective, which means that human need may always be dominant and it cannot be guaranteed that through deliberation people will place the earth's needs ahead of their own (Arias-Maldonado 2007: 237). What may be good for the people is often not good for the environment, specifically in terms of employment, economic growth, material wealth and so forth. Elstub (2009: 30) rightly points out that there are varying notions of the common good and what constitutes the common good can differ in any situation. Increased pluralism means that the common good can no longer be so easily identified. Pluralism and participation are often in conflict with one another, as Innes and Booher (2004: 422) consider, 'the first lacks legitimacy with citizens, but is often effective, and the second is seldom effective, but has considerable more legitimacy'. The probability of reaching consensus and discussing all relevant views will be severely diminished by increased pluralism (Elstub 2014b: 399).

This can be linked with the second key issue, which is that deliberation is an ineffective decision-making process (Elstub 2009; Mansbridge *et al.* 2010). The time constraints, sheer number of participants and issues of distance render it impractical (Warren 2002: 177; Goodin 2005: 170). The pluralistic nature of deliberative methods and the diversity of opinions that would be forwarded could be endless. Increasingly diverse cultures, both nationally and globally, make enacting deliberative democracy a more challenging endeavour (Beierle and Cayford 2002: 4). Some have questioned what lay citizens can reasonably be expected to contribute to the democratic process, other than voting (Hibbing and Theiss-Moore 2002). As Elstub (2009: 44) rightly notes much of the evidence that claim a positive link between

deliberative democracy and sustainability exists have focussed on non-partisan deliberation which has had little or no impact on decision-making, consequently the outcome can often result in 'policy learning' rather than policy-making (*see* Flynn 2009: 61-64 for examples). Often deliberative institutions, such as citizens' juries, only hold an advisory role (Abels 2007: 108). And as Flynn (2009: 59) observes, institutions, such as citizens' juries, cannot be assumed capable of tackling the complex issues that surround climate change alone. Nor can any one institution for that matter.

Elstub (2009: 6) points out, when citizens are asked to make environmentally sustainable decisions, rather than recommendations, the conviction of their own argument is often not assured. Again, participants will not necessarily choose the environment over their own happiness of life style. However, as many deliberative democrat theorists argue, in order to realise deliberative democracy it is vital that public debate leads to a decision (Bohman 1996; Dryzek 2000; Squires 2002; Elstub 2009). It is assumed that the strength of varying perspectives and the ability to articulate them is enough to arrive at knowledgeable decisions, as Brown (2014: 50) explains, 'Deliberative democrats thus often reference Aristotle's notion that because different people know different things, when they put their knowledge together, they collectively know more than the experts'. However, Fung (2006: 69) states that very often, even though citizens are engaged in the deliberative process, the decisions themselves are made 'through the *technical expertise* of officials whose training and professional specialization suits them to solving particular problems'. Representatives can be in touch with deep rooted community issues but individuals very often do not know about technical issues (Rodger 1978: 105).

While green theorists have been drawn to deliberative democracy as a means of rectifying liberal democracy's articulation of self-interested preferences (Barry and Hardin 1982; Dryzek 2000), attempting to accommodate the relationship between the formal and informal sectors is problematic and theorists have failed to reach a consensus on how best to institutionalise these effectively and legitimately. One, as previously mentioned, encompasses communication and mutually arrived upon consensus in the informal sector; the other, instrumental action and politics in the formal sector. Contrary to popular belief that deliberation 'assists' the decision-making process, Judith Squires (2002: 141) asserts that it instead 'interrupts' it. Despite the participation of all affected members of the public, the final decision will undoubtedly be cast

by elected representative and judges (Squires 2002). Decisions may be influenced by deliberation but will ultimately be decided on aggregate. Furthermore, Squires (2002: 142) emphasises that if deliberation has influenced the outcome of a decision, it is unlikely that citizens will fully understand the extent of its influence due to the conflicting structural relations between deliberation and aggregation. Having said that, there are tools which Squires concedes could be effective in bridging the gap between the formal and informal, such as Ackerman and Fishkin's (2004) deliberation days.

The third issue with deliberative democracy is there is no way of reconciling it with the real world and all the challenges that come with it – the globalised market, capitalist individualism and the administrative state (Baber and Bartlett 2005: 12). How deliberation can transcend local politics and whether ordinary citizens can effectively challenge the 'expert-driven style of environmental management' that dominates policy-making today is unknown (Few *et al.* 2007: 53). Decentralising the distribution of power to local level is often assumed to lead to bottom-up decisions, gaining legitimacy for policies made further up. However, as Baber and Bartlett state (2005: 130), decentralisation alone is not adequate to enact green decisions. It is easy to imagine that decentralised communities or local level governing bodies may respond appropriately to environmental problems in their area but as the research shows, this may not always be the case (*see* Richardson *et al.* 1993; Ford 2008). There is a risk that top-down power can persist despite the use of participatory and deliberative methods. Aforementioned, it is difficult to decide who is qualified to advise on environmental matters and it is vital that grassroots level and affected parties are part of the deliberative process (Few *et al.* 2007: 48). Yet, even with the adoption of participatory and deliberative processes as add-ons some participants may have more influence over proceedings than others (Sanders 1997; Young 2000). Therefore, challenges which exist within liberal democracies are unlikely to be overcome through deliberative democratic practices. The existing barriers to participation - lack of resources (money, the amount of people invested in a specific interest) and discrimination (Chappell 2010: 296) - would subsist within a deliberative process.

Which leads to the fourth issue. While a fundamental aspect of deliberative participation is the combination of all affected voices (Young 2001: 672), a number of deliberative democratic theorists (Beierle and Cayford 2002: 75-76; Baber and Bartlett 2005: 199-200; Fischer 2009; Brown 2014) believe that the decision process should include experts in the field, as well as those who are affected by the decisions. Through this, the conflicting perspectives will be

addressed and the surrounding discourses known to all. This would prevent problem-solving in one area causing greater problems elsewhere. Within mini-publics, there is often an emphasis placed on citizen deliberation, rather than an interaction between the various levels of stakeholders and decision-makers. Experts and government officials currently participate in an advisory or informant capacity rather than join the deliberation itself (Brown 2006) and as discussed above, expert's role in democratic decision-making has come under fire (Fischer 2009). As Grimble and Chan (1995: 114) rightly state stakeholders are, 'all those who affect, and/or are affected by, the policies, decisions and actions of the system; they can be individuals, communities, social groups, or institutions of any size, aggregation or level in society'. This is particularly relevant for environmentalism as it could be argued that in accordance with Grimble and Chan's definition, when it comes to ecological sustainability everyone must be a stakeholder as all are affected. The participation of one group does not have to be to the exclusion of the other. The use of experts and policy-makers enables participants to work within the capacity of what is reasonable and realistic.

Citizen deliberation, as it has been shown, has many benefits and is essential to the improvement of democratic processes, yet one issue that Flynn deems problematic is the formal, transformative powers of deliberative institutions. As he (2009: 60) reflects,

Because 'ordinary' citizens are transformed from passive into active participants in the policy process, they are no longer in fact a faithful representative set of sometimes 'rationally ignorant/indifferent' voters and consumers. All one can learn is how one might respond.

By this he means that if lay citizens are better able to make decisions and adopt a wider more pluralistic way of thinking through the deliberative experience, then surely this is enabling 'ordinary' citizens to think more in line with experts than other, non-participating citizens (Flynn 2009: 59). This mirrors, in some respects, Bohman's (1996: 64) reflection that 'the layperson can take on the perspective of the expert by becoming a well-informed citizen'. It cannot then follow that this is automatically a good thing. Contention between the large majority of citizens that did not participate and those that were selected may emerge. Although self-selection, such as that used in hearings, is guilty of many disadvantages (*see* section 2.5.2) it could, in this instance, provide an alternative in that citizens themselves are seeking knowledge, answers to questions and to be involved. Therefore they are already in some ways

separate from those that shy away from being part of such a process. Resentment from those that were not 'selected' during random sampling is thus somewhat avoided. Further concerns which emerge from mini-publics is the unease some feel about making decisions on behalf of other citizens (Elstub 2009: 48). Lang (2007: 62) comments that it is; 'a mistake to expect ordinary citizens to act as representatives of *all* viewpoints or interests'. Decisions regarding policy changes as well as the best action to deter pollutants and degradation must be considered not just by economists, but by politicians, environmentalists, moralists, agriculturalists and theologians (Goodin 2005: 249). Brown (2014) states that although public knowledge is of vital importance, it is not infallible in terms of knowing the best route to take on innovative policies. While it is important not to undervalue the public by assuming they cannot cope with the complexities of ecological issues, the importance of their participation lies in the scrutiny and transparency of the political process, actors and decisions. To do this effectively, it is necessary to resolve the conflict between expert and citizens.

3.3 How to Reconcile Experts and Citizens

Despite the rejection of expert analysis as a legitimate and reliable source, most of what citizens know about environmental issues has been highlighted by experts. Scientists and academics are necessary for setting parameters for action plans and to forward realistic policy innovation or adaption as they are arguably more qualified and knowledgeable (Fischer 1999: 294; Brown 2014: 50). According to Moore (2011: 3), it is more often than not scientific, environmental or technological research which casts light on specific issues. Although experts do not have any legitimised right to make decisions on behalf of the public, their research is imperative to agenda setting and decision-making. Especially for environmental decisions, technical and scientific evidence is vital for pursuing suitable outcomes. It is important to remember though that while these people are experts in their field, the rest of the time they are members of the public as they are unlikely to have expertise in more than one area (Fischer 2009: 57). Certainly, the capacity for engaged citizens to become knowledgeable on issues like these has increased with the technological turn. Yet, it is evident that individuals are more likely to consult evidence which supports their ideological preferences thus enforcing their own opinions (*see* Nickerson 1998 on confirmation bias). As Fischer (1999: 297) says, 'Given the subjective sides of risk...there can no longer be genuine experts in such decisions'. Creating a reflexive and critical mode of discussion which can be accommodated through a democratic process is therefore vital. It is necessary then to consider how experts could be most effective in their role

as information provider and agenda setters. How then can the reconciling of experts and citizens be envisioned? Furthermore, how to combine policy-makers into this process without alienating lay citizens?

O'Flynn (2015) discusses the importance of 'pulling together' and 'togetherness', specifically in divided societies. His thoughts are well applied here. O'Flynn (2015: 4) postulates that togetherness can be interpreted as a shared intention and a desire to pursue a course of action. In order to work together, experts and citizens would need to adopt a 'joint co-operative endeavour' where the responsibilities of each party are known (2015: 2). This would entail the division of labour in order to achieve a shared goal. With the understanding that not all values are shared amongst parties; the belief that all parties are working for the greater good would lead to greater levels of reciprocity; as O'Flynn (2015: 2) explains, 'developing and promoting shared intentions can serve as an antidote to conflict and be an important driver'. Again, O'Flynn (2015) considers this in reference to achieving peace and democracy, yet the sentiment can be applied to the benefits of combining expert guidance and citizen knowledge.

To this end, Fischer (1999) suggests a rethinking of the role of experts and lay citizens in participatory processes. Once a development or issue has arisen, rather than it being the responsibility of the scientists or experts to collate the evidence, the citizens can undertake a 'participatory inquiry'. This would entail gathering information in the area affected by the problem which would include; 'Working together to solve a problem or plan a course of action, such "client centred" learning is grounded in the "ordinary knowledge" and social experiences relevant to the specific real-life goals and purposes of the participants themselves' (Fischer 1999: 299). This, according to Fischer (1999), opens up the decision-making process beyond an implementation strategy, which only takes external interests and advice into account, to a process which encompasses wider concerns, interest and insights. The participatory inquiry would be a rigorous research process where experts assist local people in gathering the appropriate evidence specific to their area. Such a scheme would provide case appropriate evidence – evidence which reflects the geographical area or the social issues of a community, which is often lacking from empirical evidence utilised by experts (Fischer 2009). All too often the data provided for participatory processes will be utilised from existing evidence which underestimates the importance of the social context. Fischer (2000: 149-50) stresses the ability

of citizens to fully comprehend the complexities of technical problems once it has been explained to them in a language they understand.

Participatory inquiry, Fischer (2000: 151) suggests, sees citizens taking on different forms of information gathering. This can encompass 'popular epidemiology', which is where the lay citizens themselves gather statistics and information, helping to guide and build their understanding of the risks and hazards associated with developments or technology (Brown 1997: 137). Vital links can be made between the environmental implications in various areas enabling citizens to formulate a formidable oppositional force in which to campaign or protest their viewpoint. Popular epidemiology depicts a process in which people choose to educate and inform themselves about their community and the larger society in which their community resides. It is 'explicitly political and activist in nature' (Fischer 2000: 151) and 'a form of risk communication by lay persons to professional audiences' (Brown 1990: 84). From this, non-experts can address the issues associated with risk and offer solutions, taking into account the vast and conflicting discourses that surround the problem. Citizens will seek out experts to help them fathom the convoluted research and empirical evidence, and decipher the correct action to take. To enable citizens to carry out this expansive information gathering session, information regarding the project is made available. However, it is problematic to envision in what sort of forum this exchange of communication may take.

Fischer (2000: 238-9) recommends consensus conferences as the most likely setting to accommodate the deliberation between all these actors despite, he acknowledges, the unrealistic time pressures. Consensus conferences, much like many democratic innovations, have faced criticisms. The issue of self-selection arises as citizens have to apply to take part, meaning that a representative demographic is unlikely to be obtained; the dominance of particular, more confident outspoken members is probable; the inequity between the participants in terms of education and socio-economic background has been witnessed and, what is considered to be most problematic within this study – closing the gap between public deliberation and policy-making is unlikely (Fishkin 1996; Fishkin and Luskin 2000). The desire to reach consensus within deliberative democracy can be highly problematic resulting instead, in a divergence of opinion, or an expectation that participants will adjust their perspectives in an effort to reach common ground (Bohman 1996; Young 1996; Elstub 2010c). Instead, within this research it is believed that a decision reached, where all parties do not agree but they

acknowledge the fairness of the process that led them there, would be more acceptable to all – a fair compromise (Singer 1973). That is not to say that consensus conferences do not serve a purpose, but instead, it is suggested here that public hearings can accommodate this role in some form too.

3.3.1 How Could Hearings Accommodate this Coupling?

The argument forwarded throughout this chapter has been that deliberative democracy offers a promising addition to the contemporary democratic decision-making model. Yet, in terms of environmental governance, deliberative democracy falls short. The folly of mini-publics is that they rarely result in tangible outputs; they are unassured to deliver environmental outcomes; they are unlikely to effectively challenge the existing democratic model and finally, they exclude important actors from the table. The uses of democratic processes cannot be underestimated, citizen input is vital for setting an agenda which reflect popular opinion. Citizens, as discussed in the section above, can become counter experts in their own right and are a crucial part of understanding how environmental impacts affect communities, and to determine solutions to these issues. Yet, they cannot be expected to be the solution in themselves. There must be a process which facilitates the coming together of all groups in society. As Fischer (2000) rightly contends, consensus conferences are a creditable option for bringing together experts and citizens and properly instilling the participatory inquiry system. Having said that, hearings certainly have a role to play here.

When comparing consensus conferences and public hearings there are specific differences which indicate that they undertake very different roles. An admittedly small point is that the notice for a public hearing is often longer than a consensus conferences meaning that if citizens are to organise and gather evidence, they have more time. Importantly though, within a hearing there is no call for consensus, instead using an aggregative method, a decision will likely result at the end of the hearing. Aforementioned – aggregative decision-making must play a role in deliberative processes if an end point is to be reached. Furthermore, the public can set the agenda for a public hearing rather than having the agenda set for them by organisers, which offers a level of popular control that some other mini-publics cannot. Additionally, the level of deliberation is not expected to be as high – admittedly a flaw – but in terms of lay citizens having their say the process it is not so intensive in terms of time and energy. The hearing may indeed ignite a different type of conversation from the currently studied micro institutions, but

as Davidson and Stark (2012: 175) rightly suggest, ‘diluted forms of deliberation, which fit more easily with the norms of representative democracy, have more chance of being institutionalised’. The almost agonistic style of talking, which is at times conflictual, can offer some benefits.

Unlike deliberative theorists, agonistic democracy does not assume that within political speech and action there will always be rational dialogue, neutral justification, or political consensus. It does not minimize citizens’ ethical differences either; instead, it takes disagreement as the natural starting-point for much political debate (Mouffe 2013). As Chantal Mouffe (2005: 3) critically observes, ‘there is much talk today of “dialogue” and “deliberation” but what is the meaning of such words in the political field, if no real choice is at hand and if the participants in the discussion are not able to decide between clearly differentiated alternatives?’ (Mouffe 2005: 3). Warren (2007: 278) agrees and continues this thought by highlighting that the communicative outcome is more important than the communicative intent, he says; ‘If angry demonstration is necessary to persuade others that they should notice unpleasant facts, that is a contribution to deliberation – although the initial intentions may not be ‘deliberative’’. Therefore, it is vital to have a forum which can accommodate conflict and contention. That being said, within this research, hearings are viewed as a place to sound out these differences and grievances as a cathartic outlet not as a means of continuing an ongoing conflict. Again though, it should be emphasised that these are marked differences between the two processes, not an argument that a hearing is better or more effectual. In addition to the points made above, hearings offer significant benefits specific to environmental decision-making.

First, one aspect that hearings share with consensus conferences - the process involves the participation of a number of key players, including those who *do* hold the legitimate power to implement decisions. The citizens are therefore there to inform policy-making. It is important to remember that even within deliberative democracy, national government officials are a necessary and unavoidable part of the policy-making process. This is because officials still hold decision-making powers, even when responding to public demand. In addition, the danger of wide scale deliberation is its inability to respond to pressing issues or abide by an efficient decision-making process. This is a problem, as environmentalists will agree; time is short in terms of environmental issues. Therefore it is beneficial to have a representative government that is willing to set the agenda; make tough decisions and implement the policies needed to

tackle environmental instability (Lightbody 2012: 66). It is invaluable for citizens to be able to interact directly with governments and be involved with the policy formation process, but the efficiency of such a system is unfeasible. Ultimately, governments are essential for steering ecological and economic decisions, and must be responsible for taking action and making decisions. In this way they can be held accountable and they can respond to a wide variety of opinions. Nations and governments are expected to utilise existing technology, encourage and pay for the formulation of new science while limiting the amount of damage which is seen to be done by them (Baber and Bartlett 2005: 9-10). But not only this, studies have shown that policy-making is more innovative if it's done with national governance (*see* Howes 2005) as they are a form of experts in themselves and have access to the correct resources.

In addition, other - important groups - are also able to gain access to the hearing, such as the media, interest groups and counter experts, who have not been selected to take part. All these groups are important to discussions on environmental issues. The media play a big part in setting the agenda and engaging deliberation at a macro-level (Curato 2012: 425). They also have the capacity to reach a wider audience than the small participatory processes so that the process and outcome can reach more people. This can accommodate a much wider debate. Interest groups are often negatively perceived in the deliberative literature due to their entrenched causes and vested interests (Hendriks 2016: 48). Nonetheless, these groups are often representing sections of the wider populace who maybe do not wish to speak for themselves or alone, have no say. In reference to Hendriks' (2006) mixed discursive sphere, these actors are more likely to occupy a 'mixed' venue, which is located between the micro and macro spheres of deliberation. Greater participation from more groups, and an arena which facilitates this meeting – like a hearing, can help to highlight the intricacies of environmental policy-making where there are no easy answers. Therefore, the convoluted nature of projects which threaten environmental stability in local and national areas can be problem solved by a wide variety of actors, in an arena that escapes the 'elitist and populist downfalls' (Hendriks 2006: 501). With the chance that the end result is an actual decision.

Second, problem solving in the community and mobilising against a perceived danger is something that is intrinsic to the public hearing process. As will be seen from the case studies discussed in the following chapter, very often local communities can organise an effective opposition to development plans by utilising their own expertise and local knowledge. This is effectual in countering professionals and developers who may have neglected to fully consider

the societal impacts of projects, development and decisions effecting communities. Therefore not only could hearings offer a unique deliberative opportunity to the policy process but provide assistance in offering a practical way to discuss green issues by including a variety of actors who are all vital to the decision-making process. In this way it can 'bridge the gaps between populist and elitist forms of democracy' (Brown 2014: 50). Experts of science, academia, business, ecology, farming, as well as representatives of interest groups (to name a few) are all able to provide information; perspectives which many may not have encountered. National government officials too have unique insights into multi-level and cross sector problem solving. Furthermore there is a distinct risk in having a citizen led participation or deliberation only. Therefore the opportunity for all considered parties to speak in one process lends a distinctive attribute to the hearing (Abels 2007: 109). As the following chapters will highlight, experts and governmental representatives enrich the deliberative process as well as lay citizens. Limiting deliberation to citizens may well be diminishing the deliberative process and the collaboration of all would strengthen the process significantly.

3.4 Conclusion

If deliberative democracy is failing to result in decisions and liberal democracy fails to prioritise a green agenda, it is left to associations and the public to force these issues into the public and political sphere with the help of experts of science and technology. While there are obvious flaws which limit liberal democracies compatibility with the green movement, it cannot be assumed that deliberative democracy can cure all ecological ailments. Reasonably deliberation cannot be expected to put to rights all inequalities that exist in society just by promoting dialogue and offering an inclusive process. What it can offer is a reasonable adjustment to a flawed system which may lead to better formulated decisions that are more likely to result in decisions that prioritise the environment. Consequently deliberative mechanisms enacted within liberal institutions, which public hearings can reasonably claim to be, are a realistic alternative for practical application. Hearings are a recognised part of liberal institutions which have the capacity to engage different people with varying skills, each as important to environmentally sustainable discussions. Hearings may offer the chance to not only formulate discussions, consider discourses, come to some form of mutual understanding, but also have the power to impact on decisions.

Through the collaboration of the key political actors (citizens, experts and policy-makers) the input of a cross section of society through interest groups and associations and the awareness and scrutiny delivered by the media, hearings can offer a suitable arena for debate to take place. Environmental issues should be open to public discussion and deliberation. This will ensure that the heavy burden of climate change will not fall to any one group within society. The interaction of perspectives, knowledge and experiences is a positive approach to problem solving and planning. If there is to be a taskforce of sorts for environmental decision-making, experts must be willing to serve as advisers to more than just political elites. They must serve a greater purpose than collating the evidence and setting the agenda. Infact experts must be prepared to offer council to the wider communities, as Fischer (1999: 301) rights points out;

If we are to take democracy seriously...we must confront directly the question of the relation of science and technology to participation. Democracy without citizen participation and discussion is ultimately a meaningless concept.

This is not to say that experts will be free from scrutiny, indeed the opposite; a deliberative arena promotes the perfect opportunity to scrutinise expert evidence and have scientists justify and explain their findings (Brown 2014: 54). Although citizens offer an expertise of their own in terms of local knowledge, which is undoubtedly useful to pursuing a localised green agenda, in terms of a national or supranational decision-making, it is less likely what role citizens could fill. Through the use of case study analysis this is something that will be addressed. This research is designed to expose in what capacity a public hearing demonstrates the ability to enact the democratic standards and in doing so – what type of hearing; what stage of the decision-making process and at what level of governance does the hearing take place? The results of which will identify where hearings would most suitably play a role in a deliberative context and how it can forward an environmental agenda, which will ultimately result in ecologically positive policies. The next chapter sets out the research methods which provide a methodological matrix designed to offer a theoretical and empirical insight into the democratic worth of public hearings.

Chapter 4: Methodology

4.1 Introduction

This research aims to provide evidence, and guidance, of where public hearings could accommodate the institutionalisation of deliberative democracy. Further to this, the study will contribute to deliberative democratic theory by assisting with future comparisons between public hearings and other democratic processes, including mini-publics. This chapter will first discuss the conceptual design of the research, highlighting why the methods that have been selected offer the best chance of achieving the aims of the research. Second, the chapter will systematically set out the research methods – the methods have been applied in three stages; first, the Deliberative Pragmatic Equilibrium Review (DePER) framework; second, the Democratic Standard Enactment Index (DSEI), incorporating the justification criteria of the Discourse Quality Index (DQI); and third, the Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA). These have all been chosen for their ability to discern the capabilities of hearings. The methods will be applied to seven distinct case studies. Within this section the benefits and weaknesses of each method will be deliberated and the appropriate application of each explained. This will include an understanding of how each aim will be met and why the methods work collectively to plug the gaps left by using them individually.

4.2 Research

It is paramount at this point to recall the aims and objectives of the research to justify the selection of the research methods. The aim of the research is to envision public hearings as a process which can accommodate the institutionalisation of deliberative democracy. In order to do this it is necessary for the research to 1) Capture the potential of deliberative democracy by first investigating institutional design and 2) Explore the role of public hearings as a deliberative institution at a micro and meso level. As such, in order to effectively consider institutional design within a deliberative context, it is necessary to consider what each separate institution can bring to deliberation's institutionalisation. This includes where they would be best placed within the policy process. Therefore the next aim is to 3) Investigate the impact of public hearings within a variety of contexts to ascertain its uses and 4) Highlight the strengths and weaknesses of public hearings at each level of the decision-making process by measuring their capacity to enact the democratic standards as defined by Smith (2009a) and adapted by Elstub (2014b) which are inclusion, popular control, transparency and considered judgement.

Specifically due to their hybrid characteristics, hearings can be used as a way of bringing together various actors to problem solve on environmental issues. Creating an arena where non-experts can set the political agenda and influence the direction of key debates, but still welcome experts and policy makers into the arena could plausibly enact a positive juxtaposition of all the necessary players for forwarding the green agenda. For this reason the final aim is, 5) Make suggestions regarding improvements that can be adopted which may strengthen the deliberative quality of hearings. In the following section, the attention will turn to the conceptual design.

4.3 Conceptual Design

The growing interest that has surrounded deliberation has meant that there is now a considerable wealth of literature on the subject. However, normative theory has been criticised for becoming introverted and ‘narcissistic’ as a result of theorists critiquing the work of others, rather than engaging with pressing contemporary issues (Martineau and Squires 2012: 524). This is believed to have led to chasm between normative theory and empirical investigation which has been deepening since the 1970s (Martineau and Squires 2012: 524). In addition, according to Bächtiger and Steenbergen (2004: 2), there has been a considerable dearth of research on ‘real-world deliberation’ and therefore a number of gaps are also evident in the existing research. First, there is a shortage of empirical research; second, there is a lack of methods in which to measure and quantify the quality of deliberation and finally, there has been no systematic investigation of the institutions that may prove to be most effective in institutionalising deliberation into the political infrastructure. Therefore, a reconnection of the two methods has been called for (Bächtiger and Steenbergen 2004; Elstub 2010b; Krook 2010; Martineau and Squires 2012).

In particular, due to the ‘empirical turn’ (Bächtiger *et al.* 2009; Dryzek 2010), moves have been made to address the first gap in the existing research - the shortage of empirical evidence. Despite the impressive body of literature that had been generated over the deliberative theoretical evolution, these works remained highly abstract and failed to engage with questions of institutional design for some time (Smith 2001: 79). Gradually, practical applications of deliberative theory and examples of citizen deliberation started to emerge (*see* Dryzek 1987; Fishkin and Luskin 2005; Warren 2007; Niemeyer 2011; Cinalli and O’Flynn 2014a). This research will contribute to the existing research by making use of case studies on public hearings held in Scotland and Canada as well as at local, national and global levels of governance. This will add to the plethora of real world examples now in circulation which

focus on deliberative processes but in addition, give an insight about public hearings and their ability to host deliberative democratic standards, which have as yet still to be considered. The mode of this study will also contribute to our understanding of the mechanics and the ability of 'scaling up' institutions beyond a micro level.

In reference to the second gap detected by Bächtiger and Steenbergen (2004: 2) – the lack of methods in which to quantify and measure the quality of deliberation - there are various measurements of deliberation emerging including micro and macro, indirect and direct measures (see Black *et al.* 2009; Bächtiger *et al.* 2010b: 2). Micro analytical approaches study the quality of deliberation by analysing the discourse between individuals and the comments made in the deliberative process, through means such as the DQI. This may prove vital for creating a level of discourse which is necessary for a deliberative style of policy-making. The macro analytical differs as it uses methods, such as content analysis, to code the discussion and make judgements on the process in its entirety. Direct measures focus on the process of deliberation according to its theoretical definition and indirect measures explore deliberation by focusing on the variables that indicate the presence of deliberation (Black *et al.* 2009: 3). The indirect and macro measures are of most benefit in exploring the public hearings' process and is therefore adopted as the primary research method through the Qualitative Comparative Analysis to test for the potential of enacting democratic standards. While the macro cannot provide such detailed and specific information as the micro measurement it gives the researcher a, 'bird's eye view of the interaction, and may be able to capture important aspects of the interaction that are not evident by studying each individual comment separately' (Black *et al.* 2009: 15). The exploration will be guided by the DePER framework and the DSEI in order to offer some theoretical grounding. Yet, Bächtiger *et al.* (2010b: 2) highlight the drawbacks of indirect and macro methods. Indirect methods are challenging because it is overreaching to assume that deliberation will definitely take place even if all democratic conditions are met. This is problematic as whether or not the ideal conditions exist in which to initiate the process of deliberation, there is no guarantee that it will take place.

Specifically with hearings, where it is unknown as to whether deliberation does emerge from the process, it is vital that the research does not just focus on the ideal conditions required to instigate discussion, but also that a level of deliberation was likely to have occurred. More widely though, it is overreaching to assume that any indirect measures or methods used are

beyond fault or limitations. For instance, to gauge pre- and post-deliberation, such as surveys and interviews where the public are asked to measure the level of deliberation themselves, are unreliable as the risk of social desirability is high (Pedrini 2014: 269). In addition, macro-analytical approaches can be limited by their inability to ensure inter-coder reliability. The measurements that are available are widely acknowledged to be flawed – as it is understandably impossible to make any measurement infallible; using multiple methods, will undoubtedly limit the disadvantages of any singular method. Therefore, in order to avoid the pitfalls of focusing solely on whether the conditions necessary for democratic deliberation have occurred, the measurement used will incorporate a direct and micro-analytical approach as well – this will be in the form of the Steenbergen *et al.*'s (2003) and Steiner's (2012) justification measurement which will be adjusted to fit within this theoretical framework (this will be discussed in more detail later in the chapter).

The third gap that Bächtiger and Steenbergen (2004: 2) have highlighted has driven this research. The usefulness or appropriateness of each deliberative mechanism must be systematically analysed in order to discern the role it could play within the democratic process. However, it is vital to remember where the research is heading when deciding the ideal research methods to use. Therefore, various methods are required to fulfil the different areas of the proposed research and to appropriately tackle the aims of this investigation. Mixed methods will produce more specific results of what works and at what stage but more importantly, be able to yield some reasons and explanations for this. The various methods used for this research are particularly complementary. Principally, much of their compatibility stems from their comparative entities; all four (DePER framework, DSEI, QCA and the DQI) encompass the ability to combine normative theory with empirical evidence. Within the next section, efforts have been made to highlight the shortcomings of the individual method, while also exploring their core strengths, in order to explain the function each method can fulfil and its limitations. By combining the methods, a clearer and more comprehensive understanding of the potential of public hearings and their capacity to embody democratic norms will highlight their usefulness within an integrated deliberative system. The research will combine normative political theory and empirical investigation to ensure that the findings are reliable and can be applied to real-world cases facilitating future comparative research in this area. Each of these methods is outlined in detail below.

4.4 Research design

For the application of these methods it is vital that the research is guided by normative theory so that it is deciphering what is happening and what could happen. The research methods have been applied in three key stages, which is illustrated in figure 4.1. Stage one: selection of case studies guided by the DePER framework. Stage two: design and the application of the DSEI, which includes aspects of the DQI. And Stage three: analyse the data through the application of fsQCA. Each of these stages connects directly to each of the subsequent chapters which further explain the application and offers a discussion of the findings but this section seeks to explain the research approach and account for each stage of the research.

Figure 4.1 Research Design Framework

* For full model of Stage 2b see Figure 4.4

4.5 Stage 1: The DePER framework

To facilitate the comparison of democratic innovations and other institutional devices, Elstub (2014b) has developed the 'Deliberative Pragmatic Equilibrium Review' (DePER) comparative framework. Comparing institutions from a deliberative democratic perspective through the application of the DePER framework is an attempt, 'to understand better the extent to which the values posited by deliberative theory can be realised under not only current but also potential conditions' (Thompson 2008: 500), through the coupling of empirical and normative theory. In order to fully understand the institutions of deliberation and what function they can serve, it is important to investigate the limitations and the weaknesses of each. In the DePER framework this is achieved by comparing various micro institution's ability to enact deliberative interpretations of Smith's (2009a) democratic principles (inclusiveness, popular control, considered judgement, and transparency), despite the contrasting features of complexity (pluralism, scale, inequality, need for expertise, globalisation), that are present at varying levels of governance (local, regional, national, transnational, and global) and at different decision-making stages (agenda-setting, deliberation, decision-making, implementation and review) (Elstub 2014b: 388). These stages are a general guide and it is acknowledged that there is a degree of overlap and blurring between the stages but by focusing on these, it can be determined whether public hearings can bridge the gap between democracy and deliberation. The democratic norms have been set aside for case selection and will be drawn upon instead in the DSEI. The process is demonstrated in figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2 The DePER framework

The DePER framework combines normative and empirical analysis by building on Fung’s (2007) ‘pragmatic equilibrium’ and Saward’s (2003) ‘reflexive proceduralism’. In order to compare institutions it is necessary to systematically review the existing empirical evidence to gain an insight into the relationships between the relevant devices and the democratic principles. Saward (2003) argues that different institutional mechanisms will work effectively at different level of governance or at certain points in the decision-making process. Therefore the process must be reflexive as the institutions and processes are constantly changing and evolving (Elstub 2014b: 389). Saward (2003: 164) believes that the principles and institutions contain differing ‘bundles’ of interpretations but all are interpreted according to the mechanisms applied, which is why they should be judged on their performance. For Saward (2003: 164), the emphasis should be placed on empirical evidence for a real insight into the performance of institutions; this will highlight the conditions necessary for them to operate effectively and the tensions that arise between the democratic principles. Furthermore, Saward argues that the relationship between institutions and democratic principles should be understood ‘without reference to some philosophical ‘outside’ which can justify and define the

principles with finality' (Saward 2003: 163). However, Fung (2007) believes this emphasis on empirical evidence and the disregard for normative theory places serious limits on Saward's approach.

Unlike Saward, Fung's (2007) pragmatic equilibrium approach supports a narrow view on theory which is why its application is suitable for deliberative democracy. For this reason, Elstub (2014b) revises Saward's work in two ways for his DePER framework. He focuses specifically on deliberative democracy, narrowing the focus from Saward's rather more ecumenical approach. The second revision is that the comparison of the micro institutional devices' effectiveness at each level is considered from a normative review of the empirical evidence using Fung's approach (Elstub 2014b). Fung believes normative theory is vital for postulating on future practices and is fundamental for deciphering explanations and highlighting core problems from the outcomes of case studies. The development of empirical work alongside normative theory can offer a substantive insight into the actual outcomes of deliberative institutions. As Elstub (2010a: 255) explains;

In one sense democracy exists in practice and we must seek to explain how and why it operates as it does, and theorise accordingly about what is practically possible in a given context. On the other it is a normative ideal that can and should criticise and guide practice. However, if practical reality is ignored then the ability of theory to inform democratic practice in context is clearly compromised.

The importance of this empirical work will give 'a sense of what may work, how, when, and why – and what may be difficult' (Dryzek 2007: 240). In a sense empirical work highlights *what is* and normative *what could be*.

Fung (2007: 445) states that deliberative democracy will reach pragmatic equilibrium if 'the consequences of the institutions that it prescribes realise its values well and better than any other feasible institutional arrangements over a wide range of problems and contexts'. What the DePER framework should do is narrow down at which point the democratic principles will be enacted most effectively. What is significant is that different models of democracy will encompass different equilibrium points, but if the focus is narrowed by concentrating on one specific model of democracy, i.e. deliberative democracy, by combining normative judgment with empirical evidence the point of equilibrium should be located (*see* Elstub 2014b: 390-1).

This means researchers can feasibly predict where deliberative institutions can best approximate the democratic norms at each stage of the decision-making process and at each level of governance (Elstub 2014b: 404). The diagram illustrates how the DePER framework works out the optimum point of enactment assisting the achievement of equilibrium:

Figure 4.3 Cube of Optimum Enactment

The DePER framework helped identify the right case studies for this research⁴. Therefore, following the recommendation of Elstub’s framework, case studies which were believed to be institutionalised at global, transnational, national, regional and local level were sought. In order to offer empirical evidence of the uses of public hearings it was necessary to look at examples from a variety of levels lest some offer insights that the others could not. Further to this, focusing on hearings which had different purposes and followed alternative procedures was

³ Elstub (2014b) states that this is inspired by Heinelt (2010: 105) ‘Cube of democratic metropolitan governance’.

⁴ Explanations and justifications of case study selection are set out and discussed in detail in section 5.2.

required to offer suggestions for their application in deliberative theory. The DePER framework has therefore provided a systematic structure for how the research was approached. Yet, for a number of reasons it was necessary to make some fundamental adjustments to ensure that it could be applied to the research being undertaken here.

There are three key problems with the DePER framework as a model for this research. First, although Elstub's framework provides a cohesive yet simple analytical tool, the proposed mode of measurement is admittedly one of its weaker elements. Elstub (2014b: 405) suggests five categories for measuring: low, low-moderate, moderate, moderate-high and high. These have been chosen not just for the ease in which they allow comparison but five is also an adequate number for enabling a distinction to be made between the institutions reviewed. However, as Elstub (2014b: 404) concedes, it is difficult to decipher how each should be classified because there is 'no absolute standard to judge by'. Moreover, the range of quantitative and qualitative empirical data that will be drawn from and the normative judgement applied, means any comparisons made and in turn, the conclusions arrived upon, run the risk of descending into 'complete relativism' (Elstub 2014b: 404). Although the categorizations of normative judgements are justified, this is, as Elstub himself points out, one of the main weaknesses of the DePER framework. One which was tackled by conjoining the DSEI and QCA.

Another of the more problematic aspects of Elstub's framework is the decision-making process. Although this has been devised by Saward (2003) and adopted by Smith (2009a), and Elstub (2014b) himself adds the review stage, this simplistic vision of the decision-making process is rather short-sighted and challenging in terms of deliberative democracy. Although the theorists above acknowledge the risks of simplifying such a complex process, they have all nevertheless utilised it without really challenging the assumption that it is a useful practice. Many, if not all deliberative institutions (including hearings), will fall short of embodying any of these stages, and may instead be placed at none or many of these stages. For instance, it is optimistic to imagine that any one process will be directly accountable for the agenda-setting stage. Often institutions will have the agenda set prior to being held. As discussed, this can often be set by technical experts, the media or even the pressure of public demand. If a development is being proposed, that then sets the agenda for the public forum. That is not to say that the public forum is not useful to narrow the agenda and have some form of debate regarding the issue. The debate

too will include macro and micro level debate, with one informing the other and vice versa. The debate, regardless of whether a discussion is held within a process, will unlikely be the end point of the discussion. Conversation evolves over time and space therefore it cannot be attributed to one institution. By assuming, through the DePER framework, that this can in some way be captured and measured is highly problematic. For this reason it is awkward to envision where any one institution may serve a purpose and this was taken into account when consulting the DePER framework.

The third key problem is that measuring conceptual terms like the democratic standards set out by Smith (2009a) and Elstub (2014b) is problematic. How to ground these norms in quantifiable terms is difficult, and what could be viewed as a significant challenge when applying this framework to the research. The DePER framework can be redirected and reapplied to QCA but in terms of creating a quantifiable model it was necessary to devise a more sophisticated measurement. That is not to say Elstub's framework is inefficient, indeed it sets a standard for the researcher to start from and as such is a useful tool. Moreover it enables the researcher to use it as a check point to look for good practice. But for these reasons, the DSEI has been designed to instil a more specific index for measuring hearings, building on Elstub's DePER, which provides a clearer and more effective structure and 'check list'. This enables the researcher to apply the QCA to the normative theory which has been identified by the DePER framework.

4.6 Stage 2: The Democratic Standard Enactment Index (DSEI)

The DSEI is designed to support the DePER framework in the problem areas highlighted above. While Elstub's framework works as a guide, it is not entirely effective in offering a way to measure the micro institution which is the focus of design. In addition, there is a distinctive 'gap' between assessing and analysing whether the micro institution demonstrates the ability to host the democratic norms.

4.6.1 Stage 2A: Designing the DSEI

The first phase of stage 2, 2A, concentrated on designing the framework. Therefore, there were two key informants to the design of this framework – the cases themselves and the democratic norms. As illustrated in figure 4.1 the data collection followed a cyclical pattern with both of these aspects feeding into the research design. The case studies were therefore viewed in a

holistic fashion, both in terms of how they could host the democratic norms and what could be learned from them. This is vital when analysing something as complex as levels of governance and unique public hearing processes. The DSEI has been designed to narrow the focus and extract the data which is specifically connected to the distinct issues this research is exploring. This, of course, makes it much less likely that unexpected phenomenon will reveal itself to the researcher but in limiting the output the data becomes more manageable. Yet, having a thorough knowledge of the case studies, by analysing them closely, means that unpredictable outcomes are less likely to occur, or at least would have revealed themselves earlier. And as Gerring (2007: 1) tells us ‘We gain better understanding of the whole by focusing on a key part’. While a case study analysis is a method in its own right (Yin 2014) in this research it is an integral part of the wider methodological matrix from which this research is conducted (Elstub and Lightbody 2014).

Smith’s (2009b) investigative approach to the feasibility of democratic innovations provides an insight into the democratic legitimacy of deliberative methods. Smith’s (2009b) ‘goods based model’ provides a normative framework in order to ascertain if public hearing have the capacity to perform a deliberative democratic function. As Smith (2009b: 3) explains; ‘This allows us to better understand how variations in institutional design can affect the realisation of goods that are valued by deliberative democrats – and potentially how weaknesses in design might be ameliorated’. Therefore the realisation, or partial realisation, of these goods indicates that a democratic institution is of some worth. By considering whether hearings can enact any combination of the democratic norms allows insights on both theory and practice (Smith 2009b). Enacting all democratic goods at any one time, at each stage of the democratic process and each level of governance is understandably problematic for any one mechanism, be that a deliberative one or otherwise. By combining various mechanisms though, deliberative democrats believe that each will fulfil a different but equally vital role in the deliberative process (Goodin 2005; Elstub 2014b). These norms were therefore used to both design the framework and for data extraction. The next step was to decipher the framing of this model and how it could be implemented. This is explained below and illustrated in figure 4.4 below.

4.6.2 Stage 2A/B: Designing and Implementing the DSEI

To establish a measurable variable which can be justifiably considered to represent the democratic goods, it is necessary to minimise the subjectivity of such a method. In order to

measure inclusion, popular control, transparency and considered judgment (set out below), which are normative conceptual indicators of democratic standards but are also freely open to interpretation, the DSEI attempts to ground them by applying practical elements to them by providing an ‘enactment index’. First, by offering a scale which is compatible with fsQCA and second, by breaking down the conceptual indicators into separate measurable components the normative concepts can be analysed. The simplicity of this framework means it can be applied to other democratic institutions, such as mini-publics, and it is designed to be transparent. The diagram below (figure 4.4) provides a guide to data collection through the setting of 12 key questions. These work both independently, and in conjunction with one another, to gather information on how obtainable the dependent outcome is.

Figure 4.4 Democratic Standard Enactment Index

* This figure sets out a more detailed explanation of Stage 2b from figure 4.1.

Guided by Smith’s (2009a) and Elstub’s (2014b) explanation of what is necessary for achieving each of these democratic goods, the questions offer a yes or no (QCA 1 = present, 0 = absent) option for whether that level of membership has been achieved. Each question in the diagram has four boxes underneath. One or more of these boxes may be ticked and they are colour coded so that the democratic norm they are associated with is easily identified. A ‘tick’ indicates that

the question measures one or more of the norms; yellow for inclusion, pink for popular control, green for transparency and blue for considered judgement. There is a degree of overlap and to this end, any one question could apply to the assessment of more than one normative indicator, question 4 for example. There are exceptions though, and certain criteria are designed to assess the impact of just one democratic norm; question 2, for example. The first, which is inclusion, considers what would lead to a reliable measurement of this democratic good, which can be seen in the diagram to have six corresponding questions.

Smith (2009a: 20) considers 'inclusiveness' a vital aspect of democratic institutions. This, he believes, includes the equal rights of all to participate. The difficulty arises in selecting a democratic innovation which engages with all citizens and does not marginalize or exempt any social group from participating. This is challenging as it is complex to ensure all voices are heard equally and have equal impact on outcomes. Various institutions will encourage different responses due to the resources and support they offer. Moreover, the institutions themselves will have differing outcomes dependent on the level of power they have over the decision-making process (Smith 2009a: 21). Mansbridge *et al.* (2010: 65) too tells us: 'The deliberation should, ideally, be open to all those affected by the decision. The participants should have equal opportunity to influence the process, have equal resources, and be protected by basic rights.' Knight and Johnson (1997: 280) state that processes of deliberative democracy require 'equal opportunity of access to political influence' and Elstub (2014b: 395) considers that it is important to decide whether there has been 'political equality of voice and presence'.

Within deliberative institutions, it is necessary to provide individuals with the chance to get involved and make sure no one is excluded; this is ensured through participatory and representative mechanisms. Therefore in order to ascertain if people were able to access the process, the first three questions focus on whether the process was easily attended in terms of knowing it was taking place, notice given and if it was accessible. Individuals will be more supportive and invested in a system that they have a chance to participate in. In addition, if the public is allowed to deliberate on certain issues the outcome is more likely to reflect the 'general will' (Femia 1996: 373). Dryzek (1990: 202) believes inclusiveness is a fundamental condition for a more legitimate and trustworthy form of political authority. All citizens should have the right to be heard with an equal right to challenge decisions and put forward ideas. The

fourth and sixth question seeks to ascertain if a diverse group of people attended both in presence and contribution, while the fifth reviews the selection process.

Regardless of whether a process is inclusive or not, Smith believes that this may not necessarily infer that the outcome has any sort of political impact (Smith 2009a: 23). 'Popular control' is an incumbent part of the decision-making process. Definitions of democracy emphasise the right of all to participate in collective decisions. However, for Smith (2009a: 22) popular control may not necessarily include conclusive outcomes; as institutions may not ensure decisions. The control instead resides in the influence over the decision-making process and the ability of citizens to operate alongside government officials and public authorities (Smith 2009a: 24). This power will become apparent through the agenda setting power that the public wields. Smith (2009a: 23) believes that often participatory processes are designed around 'safe issues' ones that are not too controversial in order to avoid conflict. Yet, if agenda setting power is placed in the hands of the participants and they have the ability to shape the conversation, this would be placing prominent control in their hands; as such, conditions within that participatory process would have to be conducive to realising and protecting this popular control. It is necessary to assess the extent institutional designs will accommodate citizens participating in a deliberative process to reach a conclusion (Elstub 2014b: 394). If institutional design cannot hope to cover all elements of effectiveness - through citizen participation, outcome and equality - it is vital to investigate what each deliberative process will contribute to the decision-making process. Popular control is thus measured through the diversity of attendees (question 4), and the impact the public had on the agenda (7), the debate (6) and the outcome (8 and 11). The role of chair is also be paramount to ensure fairness and that no individual or group dominates (9).

'Transparency' is necessary within democratic institutions as it ensures that there is a degree of openness between participants throughout the decision-making process. Smith (2009a: 25) says transparency is vital for citizens for a number of reasons; so individuals understand how the issue being considered has been selected, who is organising the proceeding and finally, how the outcome of proceedings will effect political decisions. Individuals are being asked to participate in proceedings that are unfamiliar to them and that may have significant impact publically and politically. In this instance, transparency can reassure sceptics and critics who may question the validity of the democratic innovations. This creates a deeper understanding

of how conclusions are arrived upon and decisions made, which in turn assures individuals that their participation is crucial (Smith 2009a: 25). Smith (2009a: 26) considers publicity important to ensure transparency. Elstub (2014b: 398) points out that it encourages decisions that are for the common good as it ensures public deliberation is 'genuinely public'. Therefore, transparency is key to improving democratic processes and legitimising decision-making. Figure 4.4 shows that this is measured through the chairperson (9), the information available which would allow people to contribute appropriately (1, 10) and that the outcome had not yet been decided (11).

'Considered judgement' is often overlooked within the democratic process. While inclusiveness and popular control are often perceived as the vital goods of democracy, the legitimacy of decision-making is ensured by the ability of citizens to make reflective and considered judgements (Smith 2009a: 24). Thus considered judgement cannot be achieved merely through democratic institutions such as election, referendums and public meetings. The legitimacy, that is considered to result from deliberation, can only be determined through the understanding of technical details by the relevant participating citizens (Elstub 2014b: 398). Therefore, crucial for this is that the necessary information is accessible so that participant can contribute effectively (question 10). Through collective and public debate a variety of perspectives are highlighted and discussed, measured through the diversity of opinions offered (4 and 6). Deliberation creates an environment which ensures participants justify their policy preferences in ways which take into account the values, perspectives and interests of others (Meadowcroft 2004: 184). For this reason it was necessary to include aspects of the DQI to measure the capabilities of public hearings to host deliberation (12). In order to understand this, the DQI has to be explained in some detail.

4.6.3 Stage 2C: DQI and the justification measurement

The DQI uses a 'quantitative measure of discourse in deliberation' (Steenbergen *et al.* 2003: 22) and it finds its roots in Habermas' discourse ethics and represents the main foundations that deliberation is built upon (King 2005: 1). This has been formulated as a means of measuring the ideal speech act, set out by Habermas' theoretical approach - communicative rationality - by providing seven principles which enable researchers to assess the quality of deliberation in any speech act (Davidson *et al.* 2012). Habermas (1984) considers that there are

varying forms of rationality required for decision-making – instrumental and communicative. This enables negotiations and bargaining to become deliberation. It offers an empirical insight into a theoretical subject and political theory. The DQI is identified as having six key elements (Steiner *et al.* 2004: 19-24).

These six key elements are fundamental in measuring the level of deliberation, in which there are fundamental links to Smith's democratic goods, and in particular, considered judgement. Although this study is primarily interested in the justification measurement, the other areas are summarised for a comprehensive understanding of the DQI. First is open participation or equality, this should be an inclusive process open to all who wish to participate. This will combine a wide variety of perspectives where even the rules and procedures are open to discussion. In connection with deliberation, inclusion means all citizens should be able to participate as equals without restrictions and free from internal and external coercion (King 2005: 2). As Chambers (2003: 322) points out, all participants should be on 'equal footing', which includes an equal opportunity of influencing political processes, as well as being given the time and ability to forward persuasive and considered arguments. However, Bächtiger *et al.* (2010b: 4) take this further; they believe that the ability to measure this political influence and the impact of persuasive argument through the analysis of transcripts alone is problematic. They instead believe that counting the frequency of individuals input, as well as the volume of input each individual contributes (Bächtiger *et al.* 2010b: 5)

Second, any and all assertions, claims and statements should be logically justified. This element specifically embodies considered judgement which is one of the democratic norms required for deliberation to occur. This can be achieved through the give and take of rational discussion which helps avoid conflict by ensuring discussions are measured and considered. Discourse ethics seek to establish consensus or an established norm through considered dialogue (King 2005: 2). Thus the conclusion arrived upon throughout the process should have some bearing on the evidence which has been given to justify the argument. In this way the greater the link between the premise and the conclusion, the more coherent the justification can be considered (Steenbergen *et al.* 2003: 25).

Third, common good. The discourse should encourage a sense of community where the group as a whole is considered before that of the individual, unless they can reason that their opinion

is more compatible with the collective group. This can be connected to some degree with the principle of popular control. Where the control is in the hands of the people and decisions are made closer to the people that they affect; this allows people to be included in the process which creates a better likelihood the common good will be observed. However, when referring to the common good, definitions must be carefully set out as there are two, equally valuable interpretations. Steenbergen *et al.* (2003: 26) refer to the notion that the common good is when the 'least advantaged in a society are helped' as stated by Rawls (1971) in his difference principle. Yet, it is also important to consider the utilitarian terms, the will of the majority (Bächtiger *et al.* 2010b: 5). Decisions reached through discussion and debate guided by considered judgement are far more likely to approximate the common good (Elstub 2009, Smith 2001).

Fourth, respect. An acknowledgement of the right of all, regardless of which social group they belong, to be heard. Listening to one another is fundamental to the deliberative process, which ensures a level of respect is adhered to. Not only does this help to include people of varying social groups that are often marginalised in liberal political processes but it focuses debate on issues that can be sidelined. Demands are then brought to the forefront of discussion, and as long as they are justified, they will be respected and thus considered. Counterarguments too, are a critical part of the deliberative process in creating constructive level of discourse. Competing ideas and differing perspectives must be listened to and respected, including a chance to evaluate the response, not just disregard it off-hand (Steenbergen *et al.* 2003: 26). Again, here this can be easily linked with considered judgement. Having respect for other speakers is fundamental to the democratic process, and without it.

Fifth, either a general consensus should be arrived upon or on failing that – compromise that may result in solutions/decisions (Steenbergen *et al.* 2003: 26). Ideally participants would be open to persuasion and willing to compromise throughout discussion in order for the debate to progress (Davidson *et al.* 2012) and there should be a wish to reach a consensus (King 2005: 2). However, Steenbergen *et al.* (2003: 26) state that although consensus is desirable it is not absolutely necessary. What is required for deliberation to take place is that people are open to the chance of changing their opinion based on the persuasive argument of others. Nonetheless, when people consider the opinions of others and judge based on the arguments put forward, it is more likely that to lead to consensual decision-making (Smith 2001: 74).

And finally, authenticity, or ‘the absence of deception’ when relating opinions or persuading others. Although the truthfulness of individuals while exchanging dialogue is a desirable component of deliberation it is difficult to measure, and according to Davidson *et al.* (2012: 6), ‘almost impossible to verify and one which invites excessive speculation and measurement error’. For this reason Steenbergen *et al.* (2003: 26) omit the final point of discourse ethics from DQI. These points together represent the foundations of the deliberative theory.

Coding categories

Steiner (2012) operationalises each of these elements by reformulating them as dimensions upon which speech acts can be coded and subsequently measured. They use seven coding categories which reveals how well a discourse corresponds to the principles of discourse ethics in order to measure the quality of deliberation evident throughout the discussion. The only dimension that will be applied to this research will be the ‘justification’ measurement⁵.

Level of justification

This measures the justification given for demands. Regarding the level of justification employed, a speech act can be coded according to four categories: no justification; inferior justification; qualified justification and sophisticated justification. Steiner (2012: 183) explains why justifying ones claims is so important in a deliberative interchange: ‘If...actors justify their claims in a rational way, they also show respect toward the claims of others. If, on the other hand, the level of justification is low, the level of respect is also low’. The reasons given can be explicit or implicit as long as all participants understand the link between demand and justification(s). For hearings this is vital as it includes lay and official persons, it is probable that some participants will not always understand technical terminology; reasons and justification will help to illustrate the meaning. The existing evidence will be investigated to decipher the level of justification offered throughout the hearings process including ‘justifications’ for opinions and for the lay citizen, it is useful to include anecdotal storytelling as a means of illustrating their meaning. Young (2000: 73-4) highlights that it can facilitate a deeper understanding of people’s experiences by highlighting differences in background or situation. Cinalli and O’Flynn (2014b: 86) agree and note that the telling of stories is an accessible means of communication for those with lower levels of education or people who are

⁵ The full DQI measurement can be found in appendix 1.

not native speakers who lack the necessary vocabulary. There is strong evidence to suggest that storytelling is a powerful tool within deliberative arenas and for this reason it would be desirable to include this form of discourse within this study (Young 2000; Bächtiger *et al.* 2010a). Therefore when used in hearings and noted in the minutes, stories will be accepted as a justification of a comment if indeed it does offer some explanation. The level of justification measurement, which is adopted into the DSEI scale for considered judgement, is set out below:

Level of justification of arguments (Steiner 2012: 270).

1. The speaker does not present any arguments (asks, for example, merely for additional information).
2. The speaker only says that X should or should not be done, that it is a wonderful or terrible idea, etc. But no reason is given for why X should or should not be done.
3. The speaker justifies only with illustrations why X should or should be done.
4. The speaker gives a reason Y why X should or should not be done. But no linkage is made why Y will contribute to X.
5. The speaker gives a reason Y why X should or should not be done, and a linkage is made why Y will contribute to X.
6. The speaker gives at least two reasons why X should be done and for at least two reasons a linkage is made with X.

Originally it had been the intention of the mixed method approach to apply a full DQI to transcripts of the hearings. However, no transcripts were available and there were no recordings of the case studies which could have been manually transcribed. Interpreting the minutes into a series of justification is limited for a number of reasons; first whoever has written the transcriptions has interpreted the speech acts, they may well have missed some key points or interpreted the speaker incorrectly. Second, it is difficult to get a sense if someone was emotional – angry, resentful, upset – or if they were gesturing to those they spoke to, maybe encouragingly or emotively to get a response. There will also be a limited feeling as to whether that person was well received by the audience or the adjudicator. A further difficulty in using minutes, or transcripts for that matter, is that there is no knowledge of those that did not take part nor those that remained silent. However, if 30% of participants or more people gave meaningful presentations, it would be safe to assume that this is worth measuring. This measurement will therefore not be included unless a percent of members from a variety of groups made measurable speech acts (again this will be set out in chapter 6). The DQI is therefore a ‘theoretically grounded measurement instrument’ (Elstub and Lightbody 2014: 21)

which allow researchers to quantitatively measure the deliberative quality of any particular discourse. The quality of deliberation which results from the process is vital as it is crucial to ascertain whether or not hearings are utilising their potential.

The DSEI is applied to the case studies and the necessary information extracted. However, although there can be a definitive yes and no answer to each of the questions posed in figure 4, in order to determine the extent to which each of the democratic norms could exist in the hearing it was necessary to think more widely. For this reason, 6 options which ranged between yes and no depicting the extent to which the hearing had been found to answer the question were set out (*see* section 6.2). This was done through a holistic measurement which was both informed by the researcher's knowledge of the democratic norms, the case studies and a wider understanding of the public hearing process. While the DSEI cannot offer a measurement for the democratic standards, what it can do is enable the researcher to extract and enumerate the vital information. On deducing how the hearings perform on a numerical scale, this enables the DePER framework to be coupled with a method which is both qualitative and quantitative – the fsQCA – assisting the measurement of the hearing. This is a scant explanation of the DSEI but a more detailed description of its design, and how it is applied to each case study, is set out in chapter 5. On establishing the case studies and extracting the information, using the DSEI, the next step was to analyse the information with fsQCA.

4.7 Stage 3: Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA)

To explain the fsQCA it is necessary first to understand the original form csQCA. Charles Ragin's systematic comparative case study analysis, qualitative comparative analysis (QCA), was first developed in the late 1980s and early 1990s. QCA was initially applied in the political sciences and historical sociology (Berg-Schlosser *et al.* 2009: 3) and like the DePER framework, was designed to confront the widening gap between theory and data (Rihoux 2006: 681). The research design can be applied to research that has small and intermediate number of cases (N), this can range from anywhere from 5-50 cases (Rihoux 2006: 682). There are a number of variations of QCA but for the benefit of an initial overview, the label QCA will be used as an umbrella term to refer to the whole approach, specific techniques will be specified. QCA has a number of fundamental strengths which make the ideal analytical tool for comparing democratic institutions, especially in conjunction with the DePER framework.

Analytically QCA bases itself around two core ideas. First, 'causal combination'; the effect of any one condition may result from the presence or absence of any other existing conditions. Second, 'equifinality'; this is the understanding that multiple causal paths may exist which will lead to the outcome (Berg-Schlosser *et al.* 2009, Ragin 1987, 2000). The variable orientated element of QCA separates cases into a collection of scores which are placed in the context of co-variation within a population of comparable units, in order to analyse the causal homogeneity. It can highlight the degree in which the independent variable may affect the outcome (Krook 2010: 879). Within QCA, the independent variable is referred to as a 'condition' and the 'outcome' is the dependent variable. It yields results that do not focus on one single causal model but instead, researchers are encouraged to specify a number and character of different causal models which exist among comparable cases for a number of reasons. 1) to determine the combination of conditions (independent variable) which produces the outcome (dependent variable). 2) it may be that a variety of combinations that result in the same outcome. And 3) dependent on the outcome, it may be that a given condition may initiate a different impact on the outcome (Rihoux 2006: 682). Thus many causal paths may lead to the same outcome, and may depend on one another in order to achieve it. This is why it is vital to consider a case as a whole (Rihoux 2006: 682).

QCA is grounded in the analysis of set relations not correlations. According to Berg-Schlosser *et al.* (2009: 6), 'theoretical discourse is set-theoretic by nature and QCA techniques enable a rich dialogue with theory'. The choice of the variables that are analysed should be closely guided by theory so for this research it will be framed by Smith's democratic principles – inclusion, popular control, transparency and considered judgement. This is where the DSEI can work alongside QCA. QCA requires clear variables to be provided by theory and the DSEI can deliver these. It is important here to acknowledge that QCA will be unable to reveal the level of deliberation enacted by public hearings, or if indeed deliberation has taken place, as that is not its purpose. As the DSEI is flawed for exactly the same reason, this is where the use of specific DQI criteria will help. What it can tell us, however, is if the necessary conditions exist within a hearing for deliberation to occur and if these conditions are sufficient in doing so. Ryan and Smith (2012: 93) explain; 'for necessity to be established the set of cases containing the outcome must be a subset of the set of cases displaying the cause. Similarly, for sufficiency to be established the set of cases containing the causal conditions must be a subset of the cases displaying the outcome'. Embodying the correct democratic goods to enact deliberation would

mean that public hearings do have the potential to be deliberative, the answer to which is ultimately the aim of this research.

QCA demonstrates many of the core qualities of quantitative approaches. Through the reliance of Boolean algebra it reduces the analysis to a series of variables, by this it is meant, it can; 'identify, simplify and compare the combinations of conditions leading to a particular outcome' (Krook 2010: 890) - which means that the method can be easily replicated by others. This, as Berg-Schlosser *et al.* (2009: 3) argues, constitutes an important step in eradicating factors of no consequence and increasing understanding of 'real world' cases helping create some prominent empirical evidence. This will be particularly insightful for public hearings as it will consider the case studies that have already been analysed but consider them in terms of deliberation. It will highlight the potential that hearings could be harbouring, and the benefits to deliberative studies that they could bring, this can be drawn from the process over a variety of case studies. By this, it formalises qualitative methods by offering the insight of specific cases while affording the ability to see cross-case patterns and predict generalisations from the quantitative methods (Krook 2010: 890), which will assist in making suggestions for future public hearings. This renders the study, and result, more capable of making predictions and generalisations. As Berg-Schlosser *et al.* (2009: 11) argue, this is vital as the goal of the research should not be limited to description, instead it should be used as a predictive tool for future explanations and generalisations.

The simplified application of QCA involves identifying the outcome that the researcher is interested in, and the conditions necessary for it to occur. If one or more of these are evident then the chances are that the outcome will be achieved. In order to do this it is necessary to identify 'positive' cases where these outcomes were evident. 'Negative' cases must then be identified, which are ones that seem to demonstrate the correct conditions, but nevertheless fail to display it (Berg-Schlosser and De Meur 2009: 21). Together, these cases will set the frame for the relevant cases to be analysed. Necessity and sufficiency is the way in which the conditions are related to the outcomes relationship is expressed. Van der Heijden (2015: 582) explains:

Necessity refers to the situation that the outcome (here: compliance) cannot be produced without a condition (here: a compliance motivation) – thus, if the outcome is present the condition will be present, and vice versa. Sufficiency refers to the situation in which a

condition itself can produce the outcome without the help of other conditions. For example, humans need oxygen to sustain life (oxygen is a necessary condition for human life), but oxygen in itself is not sufficient to live (food and water, for instance, are other necessary conditions).

By streamlining the causal conditions it can be deciphered which is really required.

The coding is done through an understanding of the cases, which requires 'careful dialogue between theory and evidence' (Krook 2010: 891). Therefore coding is carefully considered by a knowledge of the case which Krook believes increases the usefulness of the results for yielding political phenomena. Equifinality very often gives a number of plausible combinations of conditions rather than an infinite variation of options. This study is trying to ascertain that deliberative democracy can be achieved however, as previously mentioned, there are four goods that have been identified as being required to enact deliberative democracy – inclusion, popular control, transparency and considered judgement. Therefore they must all be analysed separately which means each becomes an independent outcome. 0 would then stand for non-inclusion and 1 inclusion, and in the next analysis 0 would stand for non-popular control and 1 popular control, and so on. The conditions have to be set out for each which will all be continuous interval level variables. In order to be coded they must be dichotomised according to relevant thresholds. As previously mentioned these conditions are subjective and are therefore more problematic to code. However, Rihoux and De Meur (2009: 42) set a framework for good practice, this includes transparency when justifying one's thresholds using theoretical or substantive grounds. And try, where possible, to use technical criteria and ensure it is always dichotomised in the right direction so their presence (1) coincides with a positive outcome (1). Following these guidelines should ensure that the measurement is legitimate offering a reliable and valid outcome.

In order to do this it is necessary to construct a truth table based on the reasonable understanding of which conditions seem especially promising. The truth table will sort cases by the combination of causal combinations they exhibit. This will include all plausible combinations of conditions even ones without empirical evidence. It will be determined by whether the rows are displaying consistency scores that are either 1 or 0 which indicates perfect consistency. 0.50 indicates perfect inconsistency (Rihoux and De Meur 2009: 44). Some contradictions, which will be any row that is not equal to 1 or 0, can be resolved by specific circumstances. This can be explained through an understanding of the case study; case

knowledge allows the researcher to explain any unexpected outcomes. Cases will be compared within each contradictory row and where possible identify any decisive differences between positive and negative cases – this will enable the truth table to be revised accordingly. This may mean adding certain conditions or taking away ones that were considered important but have proved otherwise. Following these initial stages, where results will be concentrating on highlighting the presence or absence of key conditions, the search will then be refined (Olsen 2011).

Table 4.1 Exemplary Truth Table⁶

Case ID	PriorMob	SevereAus	GovCor	PriceRis	Protest
a	0	0	1	0	0
b	0	0	1	0	0
c	0	0	1	0	0
d	0	0	1	0	0
e	0	0	1	1	0
f	0	0	1	1	0
g	0	0	1	1	0
h	0	0	1	1	0
i	0	0	1	1	0
j	0	0	1	1	1
k	0	1	0	1	1
l	0	1	0	1	1
m	0	1	0	1	1

Each row of the truth table represents a logical combination of values. Each row is assigned an output value (a score of 1 or 0 on the dependent variable) based on the scores of the cases which share that combination of scores on the independent variables. Thus, both the different combinations of input values (independent variables) and their associated output values (the dependant variable) are summarised in a truth table. Each row is not a single case but a summary of all the cases with a certain combination of input values. In this respect, a truth table is like a cell from multi-way cross classification of several categorical independent variables (Ragin 1987: 87). This works as an effective visual aid and highlights patterns and similarities between cases that may not otherwise be apparent. Here, it can provide an excellent tool for data analysis (Berg-Schlosser *et al.* 2009: 15).

⁶ Taken and adapted from a powerpoint presentation on Crisp and Fuzzy Set Qualitative Comparative Analysis by Peer C. Fiss, University of Southern California.

A discernible limitation of the truth table is that it is designed to analyse conditions where the dichotomies are either absent or present. The dichotomous measurement of crisp set QCA is problematic as it infers a clear threshold of distinction between a score where a condition has been observed as either present or absent. In many instances in political science research such a 'cut and dry' answer may not exist. The *degree* to which the condition occurs may vary (Ryan and Smith 2012: 95). QCA has therefore been developed beyond the first type of QCA (crisp-set QCA) into two other variations 'multi-value' (mvQCA) and 'fuzzy-set' (fsQCA) (Berg-Schlosser *et al.* 2009: 15). Here, the column elements can extend beyond binary to ordinal or scaled index variates (Olsen 2011). The truth table is ideal for limited levels of diversity between cases but in order to analyse what the research hopes to, the level and degree of deliberation which public hearings can plausibly instigate, it is necessary to move away from standard truth table analysis (Ragin 2009: 88). While it could be assumed that some element of deliberation is occurring in a hearing, this may not be the case in every instance; there may be a degree to which the democratic standards are being enacted in any particular hearing.

fsQCA enables the researcher to standardise levels of set membership by using values in between 0 and 1 (Kent 2008: 3). Membership scores in fuzzy set relate to the extent a case belongs to a particular set. This can include full-, partial- and non-membership but there are varying degrees of these. The fsQCA will generate a table that only includes positive cases where membership is over 0.5 or greater. The researcher's analysis of the causal complexity can therefore be theoretically explained or relationships predicted, such as the subset relation while making the 'fine-grained distinctions' through the use of interval-scale variables (Ragin 2009: 89). fsQCA highlights the presence of causal conditions and the combinations of conditions which can indicate the most useful cases and consistency within the cases (Kent 2008: 4). This is vital for deciphering the conditions which are necessary for accommodating deliberation within any given process. As is necessary within the fuzzy set, the measurement ranges between 0-1.

The DSEI has a detailed index devised specifically to numerate the normative concepts which will be analysed through the fuzzy set. Assigning set membership to cases is done using the literature which discusses these democratic norms and on deliberative democratic theory more widely; besides additional information gathered on the cases. This has been collected from journal articles; newspapers articles; books; letters; emails; minutes; transcribed conversations;

websites and at times social media (twitter and Facebook). The point of maximum indifference is located at 0.5. For this reason the set membership will be assigned at the points which have been set out by Ryan and Smith (2012: 107):

'In our study, membership in sets takes one of eight values corresponding to the following logical verbal statements:

- 1.0 - 'Fully in' the set
- 0.83 - 'mostly but not fully in'
- 0.67 - 'more or less in'
- 0.52 - 'marginally more in'
- 0.48 - 'marginally more out'
- 0.33 - 'more or less out'
- 0.17 - 'mostly but not fully out'
- 0 - 'fully out'.

As seen from above, with the use of an 8 point scale, the problematic nature of suggesting that any case could have a membership score which is at the half way point of the set has been avoided. This, as Ryan and Smith (2012: 107) stipulate, presents the score in a 'logical limbo' which would then remove it from the analysis. The way the scale works here enables researchers to bypass this issue by ascribing measurements at either side of the crossover point (0.48 and 0.52). Ryan and Smith (2012: 107) explain; 'This is not simply a technical solution, but rather again corresponds to simple verbal description of the degree to which phenomena can be observed, namely 'marginally more in/out'. The DSEI is principally designed to assess the potential of institutions, specifically public hearings, and as such answers to the questions set in figure 4.4 have been given which correlate with Ryan and Smith's (2012) measurement, allowing the researcher to assess the presence of the democratic norms. The outcome of the fsQCA is discussed in detail in chapter 7.

4.8 Conclusion

Connecting empirical evidence and normative theory is necessary to draw from the rich back-catalogue of wide reaching evidence which covers a multitude of issues. This will narrow the

focus of the normative claims allowing them to be practical rather than, as they have been accused of becoming, increasingly abstract (Krook 2010; Elstub 2014b) meaning that conceptual principles can be applied to current issues that are culturally, politically and socially relevant. The methodology in this research is complex and multilayered. However, in terms of what the research is attempting to explore - not *are* hearings deliberative but *can* they demonstrate the capacity to harbour deliberative democratic norms – there is no straightforward research method which could have been applied. The methodology adopted here is not just a mixed method approach but also utilises comparative research tools and theoretical and normative analysis.

To answer the question of whether public hearings can institutionalise environmental policy-making it is imperative to examine if they have the potential to enact the democratic standards. The overarching framework is guided by the DePER framework and underpinned by the author's own DSEI. Yet, there is no robust way to apply DePER to an institution due to the presence of the normative indicators – popular control, inclusion, transparency and considered judgement – and the simplistic five stage decision-making process. The DSEI has been designed to narrow the focus and extract the data which is specifically connected to the distinct issues this research is exploring. The fsQCA entails a robust case study analysis and in order to explore and extrapolate the cases and quantify the conceptual democratic standards it was necessary to cast a wider methodological net. If the QCA can identify the necessary conditions for the democratic goods to exist, it can be used to shape the procedure hearings follow in the future. A particular compatible component that all these methods encompass is their comparative element. Each brings its own distinctive analytical benefits which will enable an engagement between the normative theory and existing empirical evidence. Utilising a mixed method approach should help to avoid the acknowledged weaknesses of each method. The next chapter will discuss the case studies which are included within this research and offer justifications for their selection.

Chapter 5: Public hearings in practice

5.1 Introduction

The previous chapters have introduced deliberative democratic theory, posed the question of how best to institutionalise public hearings in a democratic system and set out the research methods. Keeping in mind the conflicting literature on hearings and the various types of hearing, for this research it was important to gather case studies from a wide ranging set of examples. These needed to include quasi-judicial and legislative, stand alone and sequential hearings, and ones held at different levels of governance, as recommended by the DePER framework. This chapter sets out Stage 1, as denoted by the Research Design Framework figure 4.1 in section 4.6.2. The chapter introduces the case studies which will be analysed by the methods set out in chapter 4. For this to be done properly, the seven hearings have been chosen because they all have certain elements which make them particularly interesting or relevant to this study. Much of the detail has been removed due to time restrictions⁷ but adequate information is given to provide a reasonable sense of the political environment. The chapter begins with an explanation of the case study selection and will then move on to discuss the cases themselves. Each case study will be introduced with a brief background; details about the hearing itself and the outcome of the hearing.

5.2 Case study selection

The rationale behind this thesis lends itself to improving the public hearing process. Aforementioned, hearings are presently underused and much of this is due to how they are presently utilised. The recommendations that emerge from this research are designed to improve UK hearings specifically, but can be applied more generally to all hearings. As hearings differ in procedure, jurisdiction and even policy aspects, as well as being influenced by societal and cultural contextualisation, it is challenging to propose guidance that can be applied to all public hearings. Therefore, the selection of case studies had to be as broad as possible while enabling comparisons to be made between the cases. For this reason, random case study selection was not an option for this research. Indeed, the cases studies within this research have been cherry-picked for their usefulness but as Yin (2014) states, this is an

⁷ More detail on each case can be found in chapter 6.

acceptable way to choose case studies. He separates two approaches for multiple case study design. The first is the literal replication. This is where cases are expected to have seminal outcomes and would consist of three or four cases. The second is the theoretical replication. This is designed for cases which are predicted to have a different setting and thus expected to have contrasting results enabling the researcher to pursue a number of patterns from this theoretical replication (Yin 2014: 35-6).

There were a number of objectives which guided the case study selection in order to fulfil the aims of the research. The first was to do a cross-national comparison. With comparable decentralised systems of governance, Canada and Scotland offered an interesting contrast. Second, timescale; one of the hearings is from 1988 and the most recent in 2014 enabling insights into a pre-internet participatory process in comparison to today's. Third, that they represent the various levels of governance – local to supranational. And fourth, they represent the numerous formats of hearings which exist in order to gain insights to the available procedures. Further to these key objectives, barriers existed which shaped the case study selection which should be noted before embarking on a detailed description of the hearings. As discussed in section 4.6.3 it had been the original aim of this study to examine hearings through recordings or at the very least transcripts, but it was clear from early on that this was not going to be possible - there were no recordings or transcripts for any of the hearings that feature in this research. There were a very limited number of cases which could be found that included recordings or transcripts, while offering the background documentation necessary for carrying out the fsQCA. Although many public hearings, both in Canada and Scotland, are recorded problems would have arisen had they been selected. For the analysis to be completed the hearing process must have finished, and if possible the decision had to be ruled and publically known – which was not the case with many hearings. Although the hearing did not have to be a perfect example of democratic participation for research to be carried out, in certain hearings, the low levels of participation or inclusiveness meant that any analysis would be fairly fruitless. What is more, it must be understood how little information was available on hearings in general and it took a significant amount of time and energy to finalise the seven case studies. Consequently, this analysis may not be generalisable due to the small-n of the sample, but also due to the uniqueness of the cases, and yet it contributes to the research into public hearings in a significant and important way. Considering the current, and often contrasting, uses of hearings will help to isolate useful and weak areas. The cases discussed are in no way shining

examples of the public hearing process – in many instances they are extremely flawed – and yet this is how the research will garner how and where improvements can be made and what consistent and commendable attributes could be sought in public hearings.

5.3 Case studies

This section discusses the case studies in more depth. There is a broad variance in procedures and guidelines between the hearings that the case studies focus on. Yet, regardless of country or level of governance, the purpose of any hearing will be similar. Most public hearings seek to gather information and provide feedback on a particular topic or issue. It can be done through a series of hearings, or just one. The chair can be a panel of people appointed by the government, a representative body or somebody nominated to take on the role (OECD 2001: 48). For both Scotland and Canada, there must be an announcement period which includes a notification of the date, time and place of the public hearing (MEF 2002; A Guide to the Planning System in Scotland 2009). At a local level the outcome of the public hearing can impact on decisions, on planning, Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) and public disputes. The OECD countries seek to include public consultation in legislative decisions as a matter of implementing ‘best practice’ (Catt and Murphy 2003: 407). Having said that, the decision made by the chairing body can be overruled by parliament. Similarly, decisions made at the EU or UN are only recommendations and they do not have the power to make national governments adopt the changes (ESC 2014: 2). Although it exposes the government to greater scrutiny if they do not⁸.

⁸ For further information on the procedures and purpose of the public hearing see Annex B. Inquiry Sessions. <http://www.gov.scot/Publications/2011/11/01145123/14>. National Energy Board, Public Participation and Land Matters, <http://www.neb-one.gc.ca/clf-nsi/rthnb/pblcprtctn/nvlvngthpblc-eng.html>. Economic and Social Council (ESC) 2014, ‘Maastricht Recommendations on Promoting Effective Public Participation in Decision-making in Environmental Matters’ http://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/env/pp/mop5/Documents/Category_II_documents/ece.mp.pp.2014.8.eng_adv_edited_copy_01.pdf. Ministry of Environment and Forests (MEF), (2002) Environmental Impact Assessment Notification, [http://envfor.nic.in/legis/eia/so-60\(e\).html](http://envfor.nic.in/legis/eia/so-60(e).html). National Energy Board, Public Participation and Land Matters, <http://www.neb-one.gc.ca/clf-nsi/rthnb/pblcprtctn/nvlvngthpblc-eng.html>.

There are seven case studies in total. Three were held in Scotland, the first was a hearing held by the Formartine Committee in Aberdeen on the development of a golf course and hotel by Trump International Golf Links Scotland (TIGLS); the second hearing was held in Glenmorie by the Scottish government on a windfarm development and the third in a small town called Helensburgh on the west coast of Scotland also on a proposed windfarm. Two of the case studies were from Canada, the first was held in the Alberta Province on a pulp mill project which had been opposed by the public and the second was on electoral reform held as part of wider participatory event. The sixth case study was held by the Aarhus Commission, which is a group commissioned by the United Nations, designed to independently settle disputes in member states; and the final case study was a hearing held by the European Commission on Europe's future in green manufacturing and industry. All the hearings apart from one have an environmental focus. The hearings differ on their predicted outcome, i.e. two are designed to gather information from the public on their thoughts on a specific issue/development; one for information giving, one was part of a sequential approach to decision-making and the others were designed to lead to a final decision on a specific issue or project. There are examples of both quasi-judicial and legislative hearings; this will be highlighted as each case is introduced but can be seen more clearly in the table below. Finally, the case studies are set out in a particular order to assist discussion and to draw comparisons between certain hearings. Table 5.1 illustrates the key characteristics of each hearing.

Table 5.1 Denoting the differing and similar aspects of each public hearing

	ALPAC	FORMARTINE	BCCA	GLENMORIE	HELENSBURGH	UN	EU
COUNTRY	Canada	Scotland	Canada	Scotland	Scotland	-	-
LEVEL OF GOVERNANCE	Local/ provincial	Local/ devolved	Local/ federal	Local/ devolved	Local	Supranational	Regional
TYPE	Legislative	Legislative	Legislative	Quasi-judicial	Legislative	Quasi-judicial	Legislative
PURPOSE	Planning approval	Planning approval	Information gathering	Planning approval	Information sharing	Review	Information gathering
FORM	Inquiry	Inquiry	Sequential	Inquiry	Sequential	Inquiry	Sequential
NUMBER	11	1	50	1	1	1	3
FACILITATOR(S)	Panel (chair)	Panel (chair)	Several chairs	Reporter	Panel (chair)	Comitee (chair)	Several chairs
ORGANISERS	Government body	Council	Organised task force (CA staff)	Government body	Local interested party	Compliance Committee	Task force (EC Industrial Policy Communication)
CAUSE	Public pressure	Planning law	Consultation	Planning law	Consultation	Public pressure	Consultation
SUBJECT	Pulp mill	Golf course & facilities	Electoral reform	Wind farm	Wind power	Aarhus Convention	Advanced Manufacturing

Table 5.1 denotes the country the hearing was held in; the level of governance; the type of hearing; the purpose of it and the form it took; the number of hearings that were held; the chair – whether it was a single chair, a panel or a committee; who organised the hearing; the catalyst for the hearing and finally, the subject of the hearing. As highlighted by the table above, there are a number of key differences and similarities in many of the hearings which will be discussed throughout this chapter. Yet, it is interesting to highlight the most significant inconsistencies. The use of three Scottish case studies is deliberate as this enables the comparison of hearings that share a similar procedure, legal and political system, and focus. The two Canadian examples have been chosen to highlight any disparities between the countries, specifically comparing the devolved and provincial government's style of employing hearings in their legislative system. Five of the hearings are legislative while two are quasi-judicial. There is a divergence in purpose of some of the hearings ranging from planning approval to information sharing and gathering, and one reviews an existing policy decision. Some of the public hearings processes made use of more than one hearing, depending on the jurisdiction that it was covering. Another marked difference is the facilitator, which can be a single chair or a panel. Furthermore, the organisers of the event and the cause stemmed from a variety of sources. Organisers were government officials, organised committees and even interested non-political groups, while the catalyst for the hearings were planning laws, public pressure or required consultation. The subject discussed within the hearings predominantly surrounded an issue which had ecological ramifications, all except one. This hearing focused on electoral reform but for research purposes, it provides insights into a unique and modernised approach to the deliberative process. The following section will give a brief background, the hearing procedure and the decision to come out of the hearing.

5.3.1 Case study 1: Alpac Public Hearing Alberta, Canada 1988-1990

Background

The Alberta-Pacific Pulp Mill (Alpac) is a bleached pulp mill in Alberta, Canada. The Japanese-owned Alpac mill was to be sited on the Athabasca River in Northern Alberta. At the time, the development would lead to the world's largest pulp mill at a cost of \$1.3 billion which, when completed, would have the capacity to produce 1,500 tons per day of bleached hardwood pulp (Novek 1993: 338). Its development was proposed in December 1988, with no public

consultation, approval or public knowledge about the project. In June 1989 a petition signed by 300,000 Albertans, one eighth the provincial population, called for a moratorium on pulp mill developments until after a full public hearing (Novek 1993: 350).

The Alberta Government, in particular, was seen as approving the proposed mill without any credible public involvement, where the public could provide input upon which the decision would be based. The feeling was that only public pressure had forced the government to hold hearings (DeSorcy 1990: 74, cited Richardson et al. 1993: 3).

The proposal was not only considered objectionable due to the lack of public input but it brought the number of pulp mills on the Peace-Athabasca watershed to seven. The wood required to produce the pulp was to be harvested from a 73, 000 square kilometres of boreal mixed-wood forest native to the area (Novek 1993: 344) – a substantial sized area which was a big part of the community and home to various species. Further to this, the environmental implications for the river, which would be responsible for disposing of the large quantity of toxins produced as part of the pulping process, were significant. It has been estimated that the;

Pulp and Paper industry produces 50 per cent of all waste dumped into the nation's waters, and 80 per cent of all biological waste requiring oxygen for degradation – stripping oxygen from receiving waters, suffocating and killing aquatic life (Campbell 1991: 32, cited Richardson et al. 1993: 3).

The hearing itself was publically driven (Richardson et al. 1993: 3-4) due to the citizen's indignation that a decision had been made by the government with no public consultation. The public demanded an EIA on what was considered the high number of controversial matters which surrounded the project. Due to 'rising public pressure and the threat of litigation...the Province of Alberta was "dragged" into what was reputed to be the most comprehensive scrutiny of a pulp mill ever conducted in Canada' (Richardson et al. 1993: 4).

Public hearing

A public inquiry was held which included 11 hearings in total and testimonies from 750 individuals. The individuals who were heard by the Review Board during the course of the hearing either spoke at the hearings or through a third party (Review Board Report). This was a multi-faceted hearing whose impact was felt throughout many communities. Debate and discourse span beyond the micro level and much of the narrative was witnessed on a macro

level; debate was held through media articles and broadcasts, in editorials, letters to the editor and interviews were held by the review board with government officials, environmental organisations, and in the provincial legislature. These discussions, debates and discourses were reported within the hearings (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 28). The effects of which had ramifications for more than one level of governance. Given its reflexive and far reaching affects, it can be considered a thorough and effective procedure with a lengthy consultation period.

A richly diverse group took part in the processes. Native leaders and environmentalists, who had in the past been at odds, made alliances;

Expert versus non-experts; local people versus outsiders; new technologies versus old technologies, standards in Alberta versus those in the rest of Canada; community minded citizens versus complainers; nature as resource versus nature as having spiritual value (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 16)

This led to what Richardson *et al.* (1993: 16-17) describes as 'breaking through dichotomies' as well as ensuring that 'closed off, implied or left unsaid' arguments were unlikely. The attendees included board members, company representatives, public participants, government officials, public, media (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 28). The panel which was reviewing the process was made up of seven men and one women. It took the form of a formal hearing – non-judicial - but still structured. The chairman of the Board explained;

The Review Board does not wish to be overly formal in the procedures that we'll be using in these hearings. They will be conducted in a non-confrontational manner. We'll be questioning each other, not cross-examining each other. Participants are not required to have legal counsel present, although you are welcome to do so if you wish, and the rules will be the same for everyone (Gerry DeSorcy, cited Richardson *et al.* 1993: 28).

Presenters had to speak into microphones and directly address the Review Boards. The representatives from Alpac were often in situ in formal attire. Their attendees had a number of representatives on the stage as well as a solid contingent in the audience. The media was also in attendance. For this reason, it was commented from some of the members of public that contributed that they felt the process was intimidating, they were made to feel 'degraded' (cited

Richardson *et al.* 1993: 27). The principal issues of concern identified by the panel as arising from the public consultation process were:

- Effluent discharge to the Athabasca River including cumulative effects on the Peace-Athabasca River systems and resulting impacts on downstream water quality and on fisheries.
 - Effects of timber harvesting on Indian reserve lands including those on hunting, trapping and fishing as well as socio-economic concerns.
 - Effects of the mill on the area surrounding the proposed site including matters such as the site selection criteria, emissions to the atmosphere and socio-economic impacts.
 - Other matters, some within the terms of reference (such as possible effects on navigable waters) and others outside the terms of reference (such as recycling).
- (Review Board Report).

It was widely understood by the public and the developers that the government had already given the go-ahead to Alpac regardless of the outcome of the hearings. The local government officials had also agreed to issue debentures and financial support for the project. Richardson *et al.* (1993: 11) highlight the fact that the Alberta government managed to narrow the focus of what was investigated as part of the EIA, where the review excluded the effects on forestry operations, despite members of the public objecting to this. This meant that no real debate was had over this issue. Omitting this issue from the agenda is a strong example of the power the provincial government exercised over this hearing (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 130). Moreover, it was reported that during the inquiry process Alpac had continued with its plans. More land was purchased in the proposed site area; a local development permit was acquired; equipment was bought; the mill site was prepared and cleared and the utilities were laying their lines, pipes and readying themselves for the development to be put into action (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 32-3). This did not go unnoticed by the public;

I can see the level of confidence over there and I understand where it comes from...the bids are out on road construction three weeks ago for this mill, there are ads on the Athabasca local paper for workers for road building. I guess the government hasn't told them yet that this is not a sure thing (Hearing attendee, cited Richardson *et al.* 1993: 33).

Yet in response to the bold assumptions of the developers and the back door brokering of the government, it can be said that the presentations at these hearings embodied strong and unified groups both in favour and against the proposals. The indigenous communities in particular were insightful, opening the developers and governments minds to aspects of the development that had not been thought before. Despite the strength of opposition and the power to demand the public consultation, the final decision was not in the public's hands. It was particularly noted in the final report that all points and contributions had been taken into account however, there is no way to determine whether this is lip-service or not.

Outcome

The Alpac EIA Review Board released its report in March 1990. The project was 'not to be approved at this time' until such time as they could prove that there would be no detrimental effect to the river or the river's users which would be confirmed by 'further scientific studies' (Novek 1993: 350; Richardson *et al.* 1993: 152). Among the recommendations, they stipulated that EIAs should include cumulative assessments which had not been carried out prior to the hearings; this has since been initiated into policy on this sort of development (CEA⁹) and from the Alpac hearings substantial funding into further study of the area was granted (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 153). The decision was unanimous throughout the Review Board. Yet, the developers stated that the President of Alpac was still '100%' committed to seeing the development through and work toward the Board's recommendations. The government however announced that they believed the report was unbalanced and a biased approach had been taken in the production of the report. Alpac had claimed there were errors in the report. Another report was completed by an independent body, a scientist, whose findings correlated with the recommendations of the Review Board. Alpac agreed to modify their bleaching process so that the amount of absorbable organic halogen discharged into the Athabasca River would be reduced from 1.3 to 0.35 kilograms per tonnes of pulp (Novek 1993: 351). Despite unanimous commendations from two unconnected bodies, the provincial government agreed to abide by the recommendations of the Review Board but overturned the decision 9 months later (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 5). The tests were to be continued but the project was ultimately approved.

⁹ For more information see Cumulative Effects Assessment Practitioners' Guide.
<http://www.ceaa.gc.ca/default.asp?lang=En&n=43952694-1&toc=show&offset=13>.

Richardson *et al.* (1993: 171-76) highlight that a couple of things would have led to vast improvements. The hearings should have been held earlier in the process. And yet, the participation of so many affected people, the organisation of a community to speak out – whether in support or against the mill – they believe to be intrinsic to the adjustments that were made to the decision itself. The use of ‘counter-experts’ to disprove or even to simplify the oppositions claims in the form of scientists was fundamental for the strength of the resistance Alpac came up against. The number of hearings too was significant. It took into consideration communities that were downstream who would be negatively affected by the mill and would have no discernible benefits. The organisation of these hearings meant that the government could not just push through such an unpopular enterprise without reviewing some measurements and modify some estimations, resulting in an adjustment of Alpac’s bid, which ultimately made things better for those that had to live near the mill. It also meant that the government had to rethink the use of empty terms such as ‘sustainable development’, ‘environmental integrity’ and ‘ecologically sound’. These terms were challenged and as such, the government could no longer use them with any credibility.

5.3.2 Case study 2: Formartine Public Hearing Aberdeen, Scotland 2007

Background

The planning application for a golf course and housing was received on the 27th of November, 2006 by the Aberdeenshire Council. The proposed development was to include two eighteen-hole golf courses – one a ‘world class championship links golf course’ - a clubhouse and other golfing facilities, thirty-six golf villas, a five star hotel, 950 timeshare flats in four blocks, staff accommodation suitable for a sizeable workforce and 500 houses which were intended to be for sale on the open market (Ford 2011: 33-34). The Menie Estate, where the development was proposed, is 10km north of Aberdeen and covers an area of 452 ha of estate, agricultural land, heath and dune (McCulloch *et al.* 2008: 21¹⁰). To the north of the site is an area of Site of Special Scientific Interest (SSSI) which as stated in Policy 19 of Development plan policies on ecology and nature conservation:

the Local Biodiversity Action Plans, Sites of Interest to Natural Science, Areas of Landscape Significance, or other sites identified in local plans will only be permitted

¹⁰ Report since removed from the Scottish government website.

where it can be demonstrated that any damaging impact is considered acceptable overall or there is a public interest which outweighs the conservation interest (McCulloch et al. 2008: 28).

The land itself has been traditionally used for shooting, walkers and other recreational use. However, the SSSI includes vegetation specific to only this area in Scotland. The sand dunes too were of specific scientific interest as they are reported to being 'dynamic', building on them would require stabilising them, putting an end to centuries of evolution and changing the dune formation processes with a loss of dune habitat, flora and fauna. Yet, 'Far from acknowledging that natural movement of sand as a defining characteristic of the SSSI, essential and the basis of its scientific importance, Mr Trump argued that by preventing sand movement he would be 'preserving the dunes' ' (Ford 2011: 36). There were other environmental concerns – increased pollution in the local area due to the rise of traffic; landscape and visual impact of the hotel and holiday apartments in particular; drainage and water quality – especially with the increased demands on the water supply and waste disposal (Minutes from Special Meeting 2007: 3-4). Although measures were to be incorporated to protect and ensure the continuance of safe haven for badgers, breeding birds, bats, otters, fungi and lichen (Minutes from Special Meeting 2007: 3-4).

The process of the TIGLS (Trump International Golf Links Scotland) application took a long time as initially much of the supporting evidence was missing – including the EIA, transport impact assessment, drainage impact assessment and financial appraisal. These were received on the 30th March 2007 (Wightman 2011: 6). All objections had to be taken into consideration and there were many – the Scottish National Heritage (SNH), Royal Society for Protection of Birds (RSPB) and Scottish Wildlife Trust were among some 450 letters of representation (Ford 2011: 37). Following the Special Meeting however, the councillors were in receipt of 2999 - 1048 objections and 1951 supporters - as well as a 766 name petition objecting to the proposal (Ford, 2008: 37). Many of the opposition and supporters organised themselves into groups, such as 'Sustainable Aberdeenshire' which opposed TIGLS's planning application, and the 'Aberdeen and Grampian Chamber of Commerce' which championed the idea that the development would boost Aberdeen's economy, employment and lead to an increase in tourism. This group encouraged local businesses to send in letters of support for the enterprise.

Controversy surrounding the development was rife early on. In addition to the development being proposed on a SSSI, local people were unhappy about the proximity of the golf course to their property; the lack of assurance that they would still have access to the dunes, which had never before been prohibited; and the amount of power Donald Trump seemed to wield (Wightman 2011; Kelly 2013). Trump's influence included buying up the surrounding land, socialising with the Scottish government and local business 'big wigs' and allegedly making unreasonable demands (Ford 2011). Very early on Trump himself had threatened to pull out of the development if planning application was delayed or the off-shore windfarm proposed by the Aberdeen Renewable Energy Group was granted (Ford 2011: 38).

The estimation of the number of jobs created for local people and the benefits for the community, as well as the promises to limit the amount of environmental damages, were doubted by many and much discussed by the media (Press and Journal 2006; Scotland on Sunday 2006; The Scotsman 2006). Comparisons were made between the proposals made in Aberdeen with Trump's golf course in the US, and the flagrant disregard for planning regulations witnessed there. Due to the Freedom of Information Act the media and others had access to minutes of meetings, emails and other documents which clarified suspicions that Trump had long held support from officials before the announcement made in March 2006. Most notably Former First Minister Jack McConnell from as early as October 2005, leading to accusations of Mr McConnell breaching the Scottish Ministerial Code – something he denied (Ford 2011: 40; Wightman 2011: 5). Furthermore minutes from a meeting which were obtained by The Scotsman (2006) highlighted that Trump had such high expectations of purchasing houses privately that he included them in his planning application, breaking planning policies.

Many of the opposition, most notably SNH, said they would not oppose the development if steps were taken to preserve the SSSI (this could be achieved if only one golf course was built) but TIGLS responded that that was not an option. The rhetoric which surrounded this project was covered at length by local and national papers. However, many were timely articles on the advantages of the development in the months preceding the hearing. Much of the favourable coverage intensified before the Council Meetings in which the councillors were called upon to make a final decision. A demonstration attended by 200 protesters was held on Menie beach (Ford 2011: 41).

Public hearing

It was decided by the Formartine Area Committee¹¹, after receiving and reviewing the comprehensive report, that a decision would be deferred until the councillors visited the site and held a public hearing. The report stated that although the development impinged upon many of the Council's environmental policies, it did offer many economic advantages to the area. The report recommended that the development should be allowed to go ahead, subject to conditions. The hearing which was to take place on the 27th of September 2007 and was held in the evening, following the site visit (Ford 2011: 42). The hearing lasted 5 hours and was held in the local school – Balmedie School. There were 28 presentations (30 put forward but individuals had had to leave the hearing), both for and against the proposal (Minutes from Special Meeting 2007).

Individuals spoke for themselves and others spoke on behalf of groups. A wide variety of opinions were forwarded and represented. Many interest groups were represented including SNH, RSPB, businesses from the area, scientists, councillors and lay citizens. It was understood that individuals who wished to speak had to make themselves known prior to the hearing, as customary (Notification of Public Hearing 2007). However, the chair, who was head of the Council, asked during the hearing if anyone else wished to address the committee (Minutes from Special Meeting 2007). It was acknowledged that all points of view had been taken into consideration, and yet again, there is little to assure the public that this was indeed the case. Those that spoke had put time and effort into their presentations and spoke at great length with varied levels of references and evidence (Minutes from Special Meeting 2007). There was an extremely well planned objection and opposition to the development. The grassroots movement which led the charge against Trump were well prepared with facts and figures to illustrate their arguments.

The hearing was widely advertised and had caught the interest of not just the national but also the international media. More specific to the area, the fact that the hearing was taking place, the outcome and the decision were all discussed in great length in the Scotland on Sunday; Press and Journal; The Scotsman; the Telegraph; the Daily Record; the BBC; STV; The Ellon and Times and East Gordon Advertiser. Websites dedicated to the local area where support or

¹¹ The Formartine Area Committee is a committee set up to deal with planning applications in the Aberdeenshire area, for more information see: <http://committees.aberdeenshire.gov.uk/committees.aspx?commid=5>

opposition groups rallied. Scottish local radio stations and local news reported on the hearing and due to its controversial nature and high profile developer, the development itself garnered attention worldwide. Like the Alpac hearing, this was a development where controversy really led to the hearing being followed more widely. The site was deemed problematic by many as early as April 2006 due to the clashes between the SNH and at the developers over the SSSI (Ford 2011).

Outcome

The hearing itself was never designed to come to a conclusion. It was understood that the Council would listen to all participants who wished to speak. It is alleged that the Councillors took into account all that went on in the hearing and all those represented; it was apparent that varied and conflicting opinions were evident. Ford (2008: 43) reports that most councillors 'expressed either concern or outright opposition to development being allowed on the SSSI'. He also adds that the Council had no doubt that there would be many people unhappy with whichever decision was arrived upon. After much consideration and by a very small margin, the council decided to reject the planning application in lieu of the environmental disadvantages and the other planning policies which were not being met sufficiently (McCulloch *et al.* 2008: 10). It was widely agreed that many aspects of planning policies were being breached by the application; although it was considered by some that it was worth flaunting the rules for the economic benefits that were on offer. Councillor Ford (2008: 47-8) remarks that denying applications is standard procedure for planning applications to encourage the proposers to improve their proposal and bring it more in-line with Council and planning demands. He, and others, predicted that the planning application would be resubmitted and it was likely to be accepted with some amendments (Wightman 2011: 8). However, there was wide scale outrage in response to the decision (Wightman 2011: 8). It is apparent that Trump's 'all-or-nothing' attitude to planning was taken seriously (Ford 2011). The project was called in by the Scottish government and a report was completed in October 2008 which recommended the development be allowed to proceed (McCulloch *et al.* 2008). The Scottish government overturned the decision of the Aberdeen Special Committee and Cllr Ford was dismissed. The Secretary of State has the right to call in any applications and recall appeals where s/he feels there a national planning interest, as was seen to be the case in Trump's enterprise (Boyack 1999: 111).

5.3.3 Case study 3: British Columbian Public Hearings British Columbia, Canada 2004

Why this case study?

This case study is included specifically due to its uniqueness and for the insights it affords into the linking of institutions. First, and most importantly, the hearings held in British Columbia (BC) were part of a larger deliberative process. The innovative and unique way of utilising hearings within this process was particularly advantageous to this analysis due to their use within a deliberative sequence. Here the hearings are used to help set the agenda for the deliberation stage; the outcome of which is of great comparative worth for the other case studies. Rather than the hearing trying to encapsulate all aspects of the decision-making process here, they can be seen as only one part of a deliberative sequence. Second, the hearings in this case study do not focus on environmental issues; although the subject it does focus on – electoral reform – is also contentious and somewhat divisive. Electoral reform requires ‘problem-solving’ to ensure it serves the most people and there is no one right answer. Increasingly, governments are under pressure to be seen to be ‘greening’ their policies or actions, therefore looking at hearings which are being used for other purposes may well reveal interesting outcomes or useful comparisons. By including a hearing that does not look at environmental issues, it may become apparent that environmental public hearings differ in a fundamental way; whether this be in the procedure it undertakes or how emotive a subject it is. Third, the other hearings included thus far have all been directly or indirectly part of a legislative process which must be, by law, undertaken before developments are given the go-ahead. Therefore, by including a hearing which cannot be dismissed as ‘tokenism’ or accused of being held too early in the development process, improvements or necessary adjustments may or may not surface. Fourth, the power of decision-making through a referendum, was placed solely into the public’s control so assessing the impact and value of linking a public hearing with a citizens’ assembly and referendum is vital for what it might reveal. Did individuals feel more confident? Less confrontational? More included? For these reasons, this hearing will be included which may highlight what, if anything is missing in the other hearings or what is consistent throughout all hearings.

Background

Within the British Columbian Citizen’s Assembly (BCCA), held in 2004, public hearings were used a part of a wider deliberative experiment (Ratner 2005: 24). The purpose of the Citizen’s

Assembly was to engage ordinary citizens in the discussion and decision-making process on electoral reform (Ratner 2005: 24). The BCCA, which had been a campaign pledge by the Liberal Party, was designed to alleviate some of the disillusionment that the public were feeling during the time with the existing political parties and political system. With declining voter turnout and increasing disaffection among the electorate, the political system was ready for change (Fung and Warren 2010: 55). The Assembly itself included 160 randomly selected citizens – one male and one female from each province (Ratner 2005, p.24). Fung and Warren (2010: 57) explain the structure of the CA:

The enabling legislation specified that the BCCA would include 158 residents of British Columbia (two for each electoral district, or 'riding'), be staffed by a chair and secretarial staff, work throughout 2004 and be granted a budget of \$5.5 million to conduct its business.

The budget allowed for a fully staffed team including a chief research officer, a project coordinator and an associate director of communications. The electoral system which had been in use was the first-past-the-post (FPTP) system which was widely unpopular. The introduction of a mixed member proportionality (MMP) system was deemed the most likely alternative, which could have been down to the advocacy for this system waged by the Green Party (Ratner 2005: 26).

The Assembly began with a 'learning phase' which was designed to ensure that the citizens understood the inner workings of the electoral systems. The Assembly met for 6 weekends between January and March. The CA members heard from experts and discussed the information they had heard in small groups (Fung and Warren 2010: 59). This helped to consolidate which aspects of certain electoral systems were synonymous with the core values which the British Columbian people consider most important. The values which emerged from these discussions were – strong local representation; a reasonable degree of proportionality between seats and votes; and optimal voter choice (Ratner 2005: 25). The second phase was the 'consultation phase' which was conducted through a series of public hearing; the purpose of which was to hear from members of the general public. These were held from May to June. Individual CA members held the hearings, which included a diverse group of attendees (Fung and Warren, 2010: 59). And third the 'deliberative phase', where the members discussed the

benefits of various electoral systems and whether the existing system should be replaced (Fung and Warren 2010: 53). The whole process lasted 3 months (Fung and Warren 2010: 59).

Public hearing

There were 50 public hearings in total, which ran concurrently with the learning phase, over a period of two months. Citizens were encouraged to attend and 2850 members of the public did (Lang 2007: 45). If individuals were unable to attend the hearings they were able to submit their thoughts by email or post. At any time between four and sixteen members of the CA members would be in attendance at the hearings, which would include someone from a neighbouring province and another from a different region of the province (Fournier *et al.* 2011: 7). This was designed to ensure continuity throughout the hearings but also so that CA's could get to grips with the local issues and concerns that citizens had in all areas of the province (Ratner 2005: 25). Hearings were advertised by local newspapers, on the Assembly website and by posters (Ratner 2005: 25).

The hearings ranged from 150 members of the public in attendance in a more urban setting, to 20 people at a more rural setting. In all 387 presenters were heard; most had pre-requested to be heard. The hearing included a short informational video which set out the 5 'families' of the electoral systems. Speakers spoke from a lectern and the CA were arranged at a table at the front of the hearing room with the attendees arranged around them in a 'theatre style' (Ratner 2005: 25). The hearings were held in conference facilities in the local communities and were formally structured around the presentations (Lang 2007: 45). The hearings were recorded and minutes were taken. Many issues were raised during the hearing process – the advantages of a proportional system and of local representation. The quality of discussion and the deep understanding of the complexities of electoral systems by the public were specifically noted: 'In the public hearings I attended I was impressed by the familiarity of speakers with some of the intricacies of electoral systems' (Ratner 2005: 26). And yet, it was also noted that those that were members of the Assembly felt that they knew significantly more than the lay citizens, in some ways highlighting the divergence between the participants of the hearings and those that attended the assembly in its entirety.

The process was attended by more than the public. Interest groups, advocacy organisations, political parties, trade unions, academics, members of CA, general public (Fung and Warren 2010: 59) and elected government officials (Lang 2007: 40). Lang (2007: 40) explains;

'Some presenters got up and spoke for youth representation, women's representation, and the general principles that they should guide the Assembly members as they made their decision. They spoke on behalf of unions, political parties, think tanks, and other community organisations'.

The CA had a website which played host to 47,000 visitors from 148 countries. The CA member's also maintained contact with the media to ensure dialogue continued outwith the process. The sessions were broadcast too. Therefore information was readily available to those who wanted it for the public hearings (Fung and Warren 2010: 61). Over 1603 substantive submissions were received before the beginning of the Deliberative Phase which provided a great deal of information for the CA members. These were managed on a web-based system to ensure that they were accessible to the wider public as well as the members of the CA (Ratner 2005: 26). The findings of the hearings were brought together and reviewed over a weekend by Assembly members. A randomly selected group of assembly members were given the job of presenting the more informative hearings at the opening plenary meeting of the Deliberative Phase of the CA (Ratner 2005: 25).

Outcome

The findings of the hearings fed into the discussions in the subsequent stages of the CA. There was a vote which came later, in the deliberative phase, based on much of the information which had been gathered by the hearing process. Although, the recommendation from the CA members was the STV system, the majority of citizens in the hearings preferred MMP. This may have been because individuals had been privy to more information or expert tutoring, which led to their way of thinking becoming more in line with the experts (Ratner 2005: 29). It seems that the CA participants were concerned with how the assembly's outcome would be received by the wider public. There was concern that the outcome would be met with some mistrust or confusion, given that many of the public had been seen to support MMP. Indeed the pressure of public opinion and the press was obviously felt as one member was heard saying, 'Let's go out of here as a united voice... whatever the outcome. If we don't, the press will kill us' (Ratner 2005: 29), this Ratner believed to be the 'general sentiment'. It is arguable whether or not this is direct evidence of pressure for conformity or consensus within the assembly. Or it could be due to the responsibility of such a decision on members of the public. Following the deliberative and review sequence, the findings and recommendations were put

into a report which was sent to all 1.5 million households in BC in order to help the public make up their minds about the referendum. And yet on the lead up to the referendum most citizens claimed that they knew little or nothing about the Citizens' Assembly or the electoral system they were proposing (which was a form of STV) (Lang 2007: 36; Fung and Warren 2010: 54).

5.3.4 Case study 4: Glenmorie public hearing, Caithness, Scotland 2014

Background

A windfarm was proposed in Caithness which falls into the jurisdiction of the Highland Council. The development was proposed by Infinergy Limited and consent was sought by the Scottish Government Renewable Energy Division (Statements from Hearing and Inquiry document 2014:1¹²). When the application was first submitted in 2011, the farm included 43 turbines. However, following a consultation period with Scottish Natural Heritage (SNH) and the council, the application was modified to 34 wind turbines (Rice 2014: 13). Each turbine was proposed to be at maximum height (125 metres) which would enable the windfarm to generate at a capacity of 116 megawatts. The planning application included the necessary infrastructure too which would include the development of 31.9 km of access road and improvements made to the existing track (Rice 2014: 3). The site was to extend to around 1,214 hectares and was located approximately 10 kilometres south-west of Bonar Bridge. It was to be situated on the Limekiln Estate which is split between the Glencalvie and Kildermorie estates (Northern Times 2013). The main turbine envelope was on an upland area of managed moorland to the south-east of Carn Chuinneag (a Corbett). The construction period was expected to last 30 months (Rice 2014: 13).

The landscape and the visual amenity of the unspoilt land were highlighted as key concerns. This was deemed to pose 'significant effect(s)' for the wild land which surrounded the development site (Rice 2014: 4) and had been acknowledged by the applicant. Significant visual impacts would be felt by 3 of the 18 viewpoints of the proposed site. Yet, it was felt that it was unlikely that any persons would be impacted upon 'significantly' (Rice 2014: 5). The number of the turbines were perceived to be a problem and the fact that existing windfarms

¹² Since removed from the Scottish government website.

were already visible in the area meant that the cumulative effects were deemed an issue (Statements from Hearing and Inquiry document 2014: 1), although these were also seen to be minimal by the reporter (Rice 2014: 4). This was challenged by other parties who felt that the applicant had underestimated the wider visual impact of the farm (Northern Times 2013). No guarantee had been offered that all development impacts would be reversible when decommissioning the site, such as the tracks leading to the site (Rice 2014: 5).

The applicant argued that tourism was not a significant income for that part of the Highlands unless those visitors stayed to spend money in the area. Moreover the main visitors are those that are hunting who, they argued, were unlikely to be put off by the turbines (Rice 2014: 5). The developers argued that the importance of renewable energy and low carbon technologies are of increasing significance to the Scottish economy. The proposed development was predicted to contribute £56.4 million to the Scottish economy as well as to create 53 jobs during the construction period. This would include £20.1 million and 26 jobs for the Highlands and £6.1 million and 7 jobs in the immediate area. The argument being that this created much needed revenue and employment in an area that sorely needed it. The applicant also predicted that there would be further economic incentives for the local area such as the use of the track to enhance recreational access (Rice 2014: 5).

There was a general feeling among the local people that the Highlands have already significantly contributed to the Scottish Governments renewable energy target with existing or proposed windfarms (BBC 2013; Northern Times 2013). Furthermore, there is an acknowledgment that there are other methods to tackling and mitigating climate change which do not have such negative impacts (Rice 2014: 3-4). In addition, controversy arose when it emerged that the company behind the Glenmorie development, Wind Energy, was not a registered electricity licensee, which suggested that the Glenmorie application was unlawful. The John Muir's Trust and interest group 'Save Our Straths' (SOS) backed these assertions and demanded that the inquiry should not go ahead due to the unnecessary expense it would entail (Caledonian Mercury 2013). The reporter, leading the inquiry, decided that the inquiry should go ahead which was met by wide spread criticism (The Scotsman 2013).

Public hearing

The hearing was held over a few days 23rd-25th of October, 2013. It was decided by the Scottish government appointed reporter – Ms Rice - that the hearing sessions would take the form of a

structured discussion between the parties involved; no formal examination or cross examination were permitted. Parties were to be given the opportunity to explain their position, elaborate on areas of concern, put forward their point of view, and ask relevant questions informally through the reporter. The reporter sought contributions from parties and indicated when she felt that she had sufficient information on each topic (Rice 2014: 171). Within the hearing itself it was decided that the applicant would present first, then the council and then they would welcome other groups and individuals forward for comment. Yet, if individuals struggled to present during the hearing, the reporter said she would be happy to accommodate them at a more appropriate time for them. The hearings were held at the Ardross Community Hall in Rosshire, it was acknowledged by the reporter that the hearing had been scheduled for the evening to accommodate attendance, but the hearing on visual impact was held during the day. Council members; the applicant; the Highland Council; the Save Our Straths group; the John Muir Trust, the Mountaineering Council of Scotland, the Scottish Rights of Way and Access Society (Scotways) and lay citizens were in attendance (Statements from Hearing and Inquiry document 2014). Persons were expected to announce their interest in the inquiry process, and those individuals or parties would be notified about the hearing process (Rice 2014: 175). Attendees had to submit a request to attend in writing before the 30th of August 2013 (Rice 2014: 183) but hearing statements could be submitted as late as the 23rd of September, the date of the first hearing (Rice 2014: 183). They would also be circulated to those parties presenting closing statements and posted on the Scottish Government's Department of Planning and Environmental Appeals (DPEA) website (Rice 2014: 172).

Information regarding the process was readily available. All relevant papers associated with the case (including the Environmental Statement) was to be placed on deposit by the council, for inspection by members of the public, at the public library. The applicant and the council were to co-operate in supplying this information (Rice 2014: 174). When circulating papers for the inquiry, each party was to ensure that they placed a copy on deposit by sending an extra copy to the council. And in turn, the council should bring the deposit set of documents to the hearing and inquiry sessions before they begin. Each party taking part in an inquiry or hearing session were to exchange the papers that they were intending to lodge to the other parties who were taking part in the same session. Furthermore, all and any new material submitted was to be published on the DPEA website (Rice 2014: 174). Moreover the site was widely written on and discussed by the local and national media.

The level of discussion at the hearing seems to have been at a very articulate level. Most of those in attendance were part of an organised group, either one that they had been created for this issue or ones that had pre-existed. Consequently the quality of presentation were very high (detailed minutes were available on the Scottish Government website). This may have been why more residents who were not attached to a group did not come to the hearing. Many of the groups objecting highlighted one or two reasons for opposing the project: environmental impacts; visual impacts; impact on tourism; cumulative landscape impacts or that the benefits of the project were being overstated (Statements from Hearing and Inquiry document 2014). The link was made to the actual project with evidence on how these impacts would be felt by the population; both human and animal.

Outcome

The proposed windfarm was rejected due to the unacceptable impact it would have on the community (BBC 2013; Statements from Hearing and Inquiry document 2014). The development was deemed too large and would cause substantial environmental impacts while only making a modest contribution to the Scottish Government's renewable energy target. The Scottish government minister Fergus Ewing announced the report's findings and concluded that the windfarm had been rejected as it would cause 'unacceptable landscape and visual impacts' (BBC 2014). It was concluded that the benefits of such a development would not outweigh the disadvantages to national planning policy and the local development plan. The recommendations to reject the farm were accepted and upheld by the Scottish government (The Scotsman 2014).

5.3.5 Case study 5: Helensburgh's Public Hearing, Argyll and Bute, Scotland 2013

Background

In 2013, an application for five 800kW wind turbines, all standing at 86 metres was proposed. The development was to be erected 2km north of Helensburgh, on Tom Na H Airidh hill, and would be visible from a number of vantage points around the peninsula; including a limited view from Helensburgh itself (Lochside Press 2014). The windfarm application has been submitted by Helensburgh Renewables working in conjunction with Green Cat Renewables and the landowner Luss Estates (Community Energy Scotland). The project was estimated, by

the developers, to bring in £100, 000 a year and £4 million over the project's lifetime. The community was to own 33% of the development (Daily Record 2013; CES 2014; Helensburgh Advertiser 2015). Argyll and Bute council held a number of public consultations on the issue; both to inform the public and to get a sense of the general opinion. These included a question and answer session; an exhibition and presentation period and a postal survey. This led to the formation of the Turbines Evaluation Group – Helensburgh (TEG-H) which consists of 9 ostensibly non-partial residents' intent on investigating, gathering information and coming to a balanced assessment on the development. The group had highlighted what they believe to be the key issues facing the community in regards to the plans; these are the visual impacts to the landscape for the town and surrounding communities; the environmental implications for the wild life; and the long term economic disadvantage which Helensburgh may suffer. An overall cumulative impact report was also carried out.

The hearing, held on the 6th of June 2013, was designed to inform the public about wind-power and a development that had been proposed in the region. The hearing was set up as part of a series of 'Big Debates' in the town which sought to engage the public on issues that effected them and to educate the townspeople on the more technical details of proposed developments. Argyll and Bute Council, and particular the Helensburgh area, is notable for its efforts to include its population to get involved in local politics and local development. The hearing was organised by the editorial team of the local newspaper, the Helensburgh Advertiser. It was understood from the outset that the debate was designed only to inform. It was deemed necessary in an informative and advisory capacity to tackle the highly controversial discourses that surrounded the windfarms. Protests regarding the proposed site had been fairly well documented with support being sought from neighbouring protest groups (Loch Lomond protest group). There was also a well-organised group on the competing side which deemed the development necessary.

Public hearing

This debate was designed to feed into a more exclusive debate on the windfarms between councillors who would make the definitive decisions. Therefore the hearing was not strictly designed to discuss the minutia of the specific sites of Rosneath and Helensburgh but instead to inform the public of the realistic impacts on the town – both economic and environmental (Helensburgh Advertiser 2013). The panel was made up of a six panellists on the debate were: James Fraser, chairman of Friends of Loch Lomond and the Trossachs; Patrick Harvie, MSP,

co-convener of the Scottish Green Party; Stuart McMillan, MSP representing the Scottish Government; Gordon Cowan, a founder Fintry Development Trust; Stuart Young, Caithness Windfarm Information Forum and Dr Ken Brown founder member of the new Alliance Party of Scotland. Questions had to be lodged prior to the event through email or post. Yet, participants were still encouraged to comment and ask questions during the process. The audience were predominantly against the proposal of a windfarm in Helensburgh but there was a solid contingent in favour of them too. The chair was careful to include questions and comments from both sides (witness observation).

The discussions and information were supplemented by interest group and other websites and a couple of local papers (CES; Helensburgh Advertiser; Loch Lomond protest group; The Lochside Press). The venue was at most central point of town, however, for the surrounding area it could have been a considerable trip (30 mins). Presentations were given from many of the participants, although the quality of the speech acts was limited to anecdotal, the speakers justified their positions and spoke well (witness observation). Much was also based on basic arguments for and against wind-power in relation to Helensburgh but little was discussed about the actual merits of wind-power. The audience and panel obviously had marked opinions on wind-power and there was no real feeling of open mindedness or depth of knowledge. The panellists articulated themselves and their points coherently and certainly helped to inform the public on the issue of renewables (witness observation).

Outcome

In a public consultation the development was rejected by the 100 attendees (45 voted against, 21 in favour and 37 abstained). The council has also received 279 formal letters of objection and 8 in favour. In a survey, 89% of the public said they were against the development (Helensburgh Advertiser 2014). The community windfarm groups supporting the development claimed Helensburgh was a 'banana town' (Build Absolutely Nothing Anywhere Near Anyone) (The Lochside Press 2013). Further objections had been received from Shandon and Rhu council, the interest group Scotland Against Spin, Scottish Natural Heritage and Lomond and Trossachs National Park. The final decision has only just been made with a final rejection for the project coming in July 2015 despite Community Councillors voting 3-2 in favour of the project only months before (although it is worth mentioning there are 12 councillors but only 5 were in attendance). However, with the newest rejection coming from Glasgow Airport in March 2015, the development was deemed undoable (Helensburgh Advertiser 2015).

5.3.6 Case study 6: Aarhus Convention Compliance Committee (ACCC), United Nations, Geneva (2011)

Background

On the 26th November 2010, the Moray Feu Traffic Subcommittee, consisting of residents residing in Moray Feu who protested the Edinburgh Tram system and the rerouting of one of Edinburgh's busiest roads through their neighbourhood (correspondence from A. MacIntosh to ACCC 2012), submitted a complaint against the Edinburgh Council, and in turn the UK as a member of the UN. The committee stated that the UK government had failed to comply with the three pillars of the Convention. First by carrying out an inadequate environmental impact assessment and failing to share information with the public. Second, by preventing residents from having any meaningful input to the development of the Edinburgh Tram Network. Third a private Act of Parliament had been used to approve the project that was both unpopular and potentially harmful due to the environmental implications (correspondence from A. MacIntosh to ACCC 2012).

The case itself was a massive undertaking for the locals, who felt that they were not being listened to and could not access the information they required which would enable them to take further steps (Newsnight Scotland 2013). The hearing was held in Switzerland by a committee for the UN called the Aarhus Convention Compliance Committee (ACCC). Parihar (2013) says that the committee upholds environmental law and ensures 'access to justice' making the democratic process in representative democracies who are members of the UN easier and fairer for individuals, committees and non-governmental organisations. Ebbesson (2013) agrees and considers;

the work of the Compliance Committee keeps these [...] issues alive. If this Convention had not had a committee like this, the member state would have had much more scope for self-serving interpretations without anyone challenging that.

Findings of the Aarhus Compliance Committee are not binding but are highly influential (BBC 2011; Bruce 2012). The main governing body of the Convention is referred to as the 'Meetings

of the Parties' (UNECE¹³). This includes all 50 Parties to the Convention. The purpose of the Meeting of the Parties is to uphold the Convention. Parties are required to establish 'arrangements of a non-confrontational, non-judicial and consultative nature for reviewing compliance' (Aarhus Convention, article 15).

Public Hearing

The hearing was held on the 15th of December, 2011 in Geneva. The Compliance Committee is made up of eight individuals (plus a chairperson) from different countries and different backgrounds, who all specialise in varying disciplines with law – human rights, international law and environmental law. The Committee members were elected by the Meeting of the Parties and are expected to be neutral and represent the people of the UN, not their own country (ESC 2004). Significantly, the hearing was not open to the public (only the parties involved) – yet this gave people enough time to send comments of protest or support and lobby if they so chose (phone conversation with a UN representative). The announcement was made to the concerned parties on the 3rd of November, 2011. The Moray Feu Traffic Subcommittee was the driving force for this hearing based on its complaint against the Edinburgh Council stating that it had failed to comply with Convention of Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-Making and access to Justice in Environmental Matters (which is more commonly known as the Aarhus Convention) (correspondence from A. MacIntosh to ACCC 2012). The hearing was documented:

The Committee entered into discussion in open session on communication ACCC/C/2010/53 (United Kingdom), with the participation of representatives of the Party concerned and the communicant...The Committee confirmed that communication ACCC/C/2010/53 was admissible. The Committee then deliberated upon the communication in closed session. It requested the parties to submit some additional information relating to the subject of the communication (UNESC 2012: 4).

The Committee found that Edinburgh City Council did not follow recommended procedure in concern of the element of access to information concerning the timely supply of raw data. However, they found the complaints regarding access to justice and meaningful public

¹³ Access to all documents on this hearing:
<http://www.unece.org/env/pp/compliance/Compliancecommittee/53TableUK.html>

participation to be unfounded, this was disputed by the complainants (Correspondence from the Moray Feu to ACCC, 2012).

Outcome

The conclusion of the hearing was a small victory for the complainants in the form of a recommendation stipulating that the Freedom of Information should be upheld and information must be released as councils/parties receive it. As the Aarhus Convention ruled, without access to data (basic facts and figures) developments cannot be democratically challenged and thus questioning authority can often become impossible (ESC 2013). Furthermore, the Aarhus Convention reminded the UK government that the facts and figures are not the property of Edinburgh Council which meant they had no right to withhold them (Compliance Committee 2013). Again, similar to the Alpac hearing, this recommendation was taken seriously by the UK government as moves were made to challenge this ruling. However, at the current time it is expected that the right to information throughout this sort of process will be fulfilled. Yet, it is a concern that without the expertise and the bullish determination of the interest group that this matter may never have been taken in front of the Aarhus Convention.

5.3.7 Case study 7:

European Commission Task Force for Advanced Manufacturing for Clean Production Public Hearing, Belgium 2013

Background

A Task Force for the Advanced Manufacturing Technologies for Clean Production was set up by the European Commission in order to 'coordinate efforts to increase the competitiveness of the EU's manufacturing industry and ensuring clean and energy efficient industrial production in Europe' (Background Paper for Stakeholders' Contributions). The task force included a working group of representatives from various EC departments Research and Innovation, Education and Culture, Communication Networks and Technology, Energy, Environment, Competition, External Trade, Regional policy and others. The department for Enterprise and Industry was to act as coordinator. The aim of this was to reach the proposed target of new technologies and innovation while re-establishing the decreasing industry in Europe. Six areas were prioritised including micro-/nanoelectronics, nanotechnology, photonics, advanced materials, industrial biotechnology and advanced manufacturing technologies. These had been

identified as the EU's Key Enabling Technologies (KETs), Bio based products, Clean Vehicles, Smart Grids, Sustainable Construction and Production, and Advanced Manufacturing Technologies for Clean Production. The task force was set up to ensure that EU's manufacturing industry remained competitive while ensuring high levels of clean and energy efficient production were pursued (Background Paper for Stakeholders' Contributions).

The hearing was held following a sequence of information gathering techniques, one of which was a questionnaire which was sent out to industry, Member States and other stakeholders. The objective of this form of consultation was claimed to be to receive the views of stakeholders or people concerned by the topic of the consultation. The task force sought to gain insights into the three following areas:

- How can Europe accelerate the commercialisation of advanced manufacturing technologies?
 - How can the demand for manufacturing technologies be supported?
 - And can skills shortages and competence deficits be reduced?
- (Background Paper for Stakeholders' Contributions).

Public hearing

The hearing was attended by over 100 people. The Head of Unit Innovation Policy for Growth DG Enterprise and Industry explains that the purpose of the process was to problem-solve and gather information. It was designed to promote rhetoric and discussion between those that who could lead the taskforce in a positive direction. There was a diverse group of people in attendance from 16 different countries (Belgium, Germany, Denmark, UK, Turkey, Sweden, Norway, Spain, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Greece, Finland, Poland, the Netherlands and France), although the majority were from Belgium (EC Task Force 2013: 12-16). The participants were representing a wide range of stakeholders. This included individuals and companies that had a significant amount of interest in the outcome of the hearings and knowledge on the subject. Among them, members of the EC, SEA Europe, EFRA, Association of Swedish Engineering Industries, Italy's National Research Council alongside a number of University representatives, and Manufacturing experts¹⁴. Therefore, there were representatives from many different countries as well as national and supranational organisations (Minutes

¹⁴ A list of the various institutions is available in the appendices (appendix 2).

from Public Hearing). There were leading academics in attendance as well as members of interest groups. The purpose of this hearing was to amalgamate an educated taskforce who would take steps towards an appropriate course of action. The opening statement claims that this hearing was designed to encourage industry, Member States and 'other stakeholders' to contribute. It is unclear who is to assume the title of 'stakeholder' from this but there may be claim for arguing that the organisers were not adverse to all participants, including lay citizens attending (EC Task Force 2013, Report of the Task Force 2014¹⁵).

The task force used an innovative workshop which enabled people to listen to panels and they were encouraged to contribute (EC Task Force 2013). Feedback forms were also distributed. Specifically the task force encouraged the different sectors to bring their areas of expertise;

As for industry, the aim is to gather views from both the producers of advanced technologies (engineering industries and others) and the users/clients (manufacturing industries). As for Member States, the aim is to gather information about possible relevant national initiatives the EC should consider as best-practice...When proposing solutions, stakeholders are invited to focus on actions that can be implemented within a short timeframe and through which significant effects can be created (Background Paper for Stakeholders' Contributions).

Apart from this public hearing, there were a series of workshops in May 2013 where the ideas deciphered in the hearing would be consolidated; and another hearing was held to validate the findings. A final report was to be submitted from the Task Force to the Competitiveness Council late in 2013 (EC Task Force 2013). Since then a third public hearing has been held in order to continue with the work which was done by the initial consultations¹⁶.

Outcome

As this was an information gathering public hearing the outcome was steered by the participants. Innovation and problem solving was the leading agenda. Ultimately the hearings resulted in a report which was used to guide future practice and to facilitate the improvement of productivity, resource' efficiency and competitiveness in manufacturing. This was deemed

¹⁵ See <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/news/advancing-manufacturing-advancing-europe-report-task-force-advanced-manufacturing-clean> for more information.

¹⁶ See http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/policies/innovation/policy/amt/public-hearings-workshops/index_en.htm for more information.

to be a necessary part of ensuring European manufacturing and industry would remain competitive in a global market. Three main courses of action were identified; first, stimulating the commercialisation of advanced manufacturing technologies. This was thought to include increased expenditure in research and development, yet using research more effectively by commercialising it within the single market (Report of the Task Force 2014: 15). Further to this, there was a recommendation to promote public private partnerships (PPPs). This would enable the development of research, as well as its finding and implementation within the market. In addition, it would bring the Commission closer with the businesses and work toward a 'multi-stakeholder community to share 'best practice' and tackling common issues throughout Member States.

Second, eradicating the existing barriers of demand for these technologies including the negative impact of the economic recession, the lack of investment in equipment and decrease in demand. This could be tackled through closer links with European Investment Bank to improve the long-term financing of capital goods in the economy through credit lines and structural funds. Increased funding has seen contributions to research institutions, such as the University of Sheffield, leading to the creation of the Advanced Manufacturing Research Centre (Report of the Task Force 2014: 20). The Sustainable Industry Low Carbon scheme launched by the EC promotes innovation which will help reduce the greenhouse gas emissions and in turn supports the European manufactures by bringing about awareness about Advanced Manufacturing technologies. National policies in member states can help create demand and persuade manufactures to adopt this best practice (Report of the Task Force 2014: 22).

Finally, it was recommended that skill shortages and competence deficits needed to be overcome in advanced manufacturing. This was considered to include technically competent workers at craft and operative levels; leadership and management skills; senior managers capable of assessing markets and regulatory compliance; skills which focus on skill chain management and finally research and development skills, which would include design skills (Report of the Task Force 2014: 26). Conclusively it was determined that this could be achieved with clearer links between industry, education and training institutions through partnerships like the 'Knowledge and Innovation Community (KIC)', life-long learning programmes and the exchange of workplace practices and innovation (Report of the Task Force 2014: 26-27), resulting in future legislation and practice within this sector. Ultimately the hearings held on

this topic have managed to compile expertise and a strengthened community with the European Commission.

5.4 Conclusion

The above has set out a brief background of all of the hearings. The complexities of each hearing have not been explored in detail here, but deeper insights into the cases will be revealed in the next chapter (stage 2 of the research framework, figure 4.1). There are similarities within the hearings. Not only in terms of the issues discussed but the weaknesses which are evident in many of them. The self-selection or 'opting in' process is obviously problematic, specifically in ensuring diversity and inclusion within the attendees. The BCCA had a more representative sample of participants yet in some ways this highlighted the divergence between those that had a place in the CA and the hearing. What is understood by the term 'lay' citizen is made more complicated if some are educated or informed to a greater degree than others.

The notion of expert is naturally problematic; not only in terms of the distrust some members of the public felt for experts – specifically scientists who use complex language, statistics or terminologies to explain issues to the public – but also when considering the informed citizen. As demonstrated through the Alpac hearing, there were disputes and resentment surrounding who could be considered an expert on the subject. Local people argued that they had a firm understanding of the eco-system, more so than the developers and on occasion the scientists. On many occasions the local people highlighted holes in the development plans which had not been recognised by the 'experts', specifically in terms of the level of toxins in the water and the effects on the fish that the population consumed (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 80). In the Formartine hearing again, the developer underestimated the ability of the townspeople to organise and mobilise against the proposals. While claiming that the project would 'stabilise' the dunes, in fact the developer and his team failed to appreciate the dynamic uniqueness of the sand dunes. Definitions of expert have to be widened to include local people, not just those with qualifications, but local knowledge needs to be understood to enrich, and therefore be necessary, to this process – by randomly sampling, the insight of these people may be suspended.

A further similarity is that the first five hearings are all 'local' and yet all, except the Helensburgh hearing, are a matter which have national (or federal government in terms of the

BCCA and the Alpac hearing) impact. This could be why both the Formartine and Alpac decisions were overturned following the hearing. If the chairperson, task force or the public have the power to make the decision it should be known to all participants before the process takes place. Overturning decisions will only lead to more distrust and scepticism from the public. This is the most likely outcome to negatively affect the relations between state actors and citizens in terms of public consultation. The resultant impact will be the public's reluctance to take part in a process in the future. The powerlessness which stems from feeling 'stabbed in the back' or ignored, breeds resentment or arguably worse, apathy. Having set out the backgrounds and narratives which surrounded each of these unique and complex participatory processes, the next chapter will conduct a theoretical analysis into these case studies by applying the Democratic Standard Enactment Index to them. This will enable the researcher to compartmentalise these hearings into quantifiable and measurable concepts in order to ascertain where the value of each exists.

Chapter 6: Applying the Democratic Standard Enactment Index

6.1 Introduction

The methods chapter has detailed how fsQCA works and this chapter will explain how the DSEI has been applied to the case studies that are being investigated, which are the Alpac hearing on the pulp mill; the Formartine hearing on Trump's golf course; the BCCA hearings on electoral reform; the Glenmorie hearing on a windfarm; the hearing in Helensburgh on wind-power; the UN hearing on the citizens versus the United Kingdom and finally; the EU hearing on manufacturing in green industries. This chapter will first look at how the framework was formulated and offer a discussion of the key measurements, indicating how the evidence was collated. The second section will look at each of the democratic standards in order (inclusion, popular control, transparency and considered judgement); explanations of what each question is evaluating will be offered; how this has been applied to each case study and how the degree of membership has been decided on. Finally, the third section will offer a discussion on what has been revealed by this analysis, including some findings.

6.2 Applying the Democratic Standard Enactment Index

Due to the ambiguous nature of the outcomes that this research is hoping to determine, it is imperative that the following offers convincing theoretical explanations for the degree of membership in order for this model to provide a robust measurement. 1 and 0 will be used when there is irrefutable evidence which confirms full membership or full non-membership. All values in between will be used when a degree of subjectivity is evident or when the researcher has had to make a decision based purely on her interpretation of the evidence. This method is supported by Ragin (2008: 88 *footnote*) where scores over 0.95 can be considered full membership and below 0.05 full non-membership. The following will first set out why these questions were arrived upon – for instance, how did they determine whether inclusion or popular control, and so forth, were evident. Following this, a table illustrating the resulting values will be shown highlighting the membership awarded for each condition and outcome, and a discussion of how this decision was arrived at. The conclusion of this section will offer an explanation for the value given.

6.2.1 Inclusion

A key normative aspect of deliberative democratic participation is - who should be included, or excluded, in any or all decisions? Inclusion can be measured by who was in attendance, but also importantly, who had the ability to attend had they wished. Smith believes (2009a: 21) that the selection process design has a considerable impact on this; if indeed participants were randomly selected or if the process is self-selecting, and how accessible the process was. In order to measure inclusion, the most critical factors are publicity of the process and inclusion through presence and voice. These factors have therefore been converted into 'conditions' (independent variables). The following sets out the conditions which will be analysed in order to decipher whether inclusion is obtainable through a hearing, and which conditions are necessary for this to occur. From this, it can be seen that there are no infallible ways of measuring the inclusivity of any process, although the measurement set has tried to measure whether all those affected have had the opportunity to participate. If so, did they have an equal amount of time to speak their mind and information which may have helped them navigate such a process. In order to assess the extent of this influence the following DSEI value will be set to assess the case studies:

(1) Did they advertise the process extensively?

1.0	Yes (including contacting individuals on an individual level)
0.83	Yes, national newspaper/websites/ local newspaper/community/magazines/radio/leaflets/rallies /stalls/ information sessions/council websites
0.67	Yes, but not using all means above (minus two, i.e. information sessions and stalls)
0.52	Yes, but limited to specialist or council websites/ local newspaper or national newspapers/community magazine/leaflets/radio
0.48	They advertised but not extensively – gaps in community ¹⁷
0.33	Community papers
0.17	Specialist websites ¹⁸
0	No

¹⁷ Gaps could emerge in more rural areas for example, or generationally dependent on the type of advertising utilised.

¹⁸ Here, specialist websites are deemed as less inclusive as they do not accommodate the necessary level of publicity due to the narrow nature of their demographic. Moreover local papers are not considered significant advertising. There must be some effort to attract those that may not read papers or use the internet.

In order to ascertain a general level of inclusion it must first be established that different societal groups were *aware* of the proceedings. In Canada, it would seem that the notice can be anything up to 6 months and nothing below 6 weeks (MEF 2002), while procedural requirements in the UK dictate that notice should be given at least one week to ten days in advance of a hearing (A Guide to the Planning System in Scotland 2009). Yet, this is a limited measure of time if individuals have to take time off work, get child care or wish to come prepared. Hearings are often known to the groups of interest before this time, to allow for preparation. Notice can be given through various mediums: online, newspapers, public notices, posted newsletters/leaflets, internet, radio, information sessions or the television. It is good practice to ensure that those that may be affected by the proposed action are informed in enough time to prepare for and attend the meeting, although this is not a legal obligation. Multiple methods may be necessary to reach a diverse demographic (King *et al.* 1998: 322). Moreover, preparation time may not just be for groups of interest – i.e. developers, pressure groups, and governmental organisations but also individuals who wish to find out more or find support in people that are likeminded. Therefore 6 weeks is the time determined to be an acceptable notice period.

(2) Was enough notice given?

1.0	Yes
0.83	Six weeks
0.67	One month
0.52	Three weeks
0.48	Two weeks
0.33	One week
0.17	days (less than a week)
0	No

If properly publicised and held in an accessible place the process of a public hearing has potential. However, there are obvious limitations to the above measurements, as it is not apparent who was prevented from attending due to social barriers. If barriers exist that prevent individuals from attending or participating this will limit the quality and diversity of

deliberation. This is not specific to public hearings as this form of exclusion exists in the broader political system. Yet, *where* the actual hearing is held will play a strong role on who will be able to attend. It must be somewhere accessible, considering the needs of people that are likely to attend – single parents, young, elderly, disabled and so forth (Baker *et al.* 2005: 496). Also, proceedings can often be intimidating to members of the public as, to them, it is similar to a day in court (Hutton 1986: 9). Therefore, it may be less intimidating to hold the hearing in a non-official building. What is important is to ensure that the place is easy to find and accessible to all. In order to measure accessibility the variables will be:

(3) Was the accessibility to the hearing acceptable?

1.0	Yes
0.83	Time, date, venue, language all considered
0.67	Three of the above
0.52	Two of the above
0.48	One of the above
0.33	No but there were reasons for this ¹⁹
0.17	No it was not considered an important aspect
0	No

Elstub (2010b: 314) points out that the decisions made are often in relation to who has done the deliberating. Who has access into the deliberative process is vital to the outcome. As Young (2000: 23) highlights, the purpose of inclusion is that it; ‘allows for maximum expression of interests, opinions and perspectives relevant to the problems or issues for which a public seeks solutions’. Innes and Booher (2004: 422) suggest that the key to participation is ‘collaboration, dialogue and interaction’, which includes a wide and diverse demographic. The more ideas and perspectives that are heard, the greater the chance for inclusion to result in considered judgement and transparency. Dryzek and Dunleavy (2009: 220) consider that deliberation can be ensured by, ‘specifying that all interest groups active in lobbying make their case in public hearings, where they can be challenged by one another and by sceptical legislators’. The more

¹⁹ A reason, such as this venue/ time had been the lesser of two evils. There is an argument to say that no setting will suit everyone but if attempts have been made to make it as good as possible, this will be recognised and explained within the case study.

diverse the participants the more deliberative the process can become. Innes and Booher (2004: 422) believe that such a process should incorporate citizens, organised interests, academics, profit-making and non-profit making organisations, planners and public administrations. Therefore the fourth condition is:

(4) Was there a diverse range of groups in attendance?

1.0	Yes
0.83	Diverse range (interest groups/political officials/experts/lay citizens/community organisations/ NGOs/ business groups/media/social commentators)
0.67	Diverse range including 6 of the above
0.52	Diverse range including 5 of the above
0.48	Diverse range including 4 of the above
0.33	Groups included 3 of the above
0.17	Groups included 2 of the above
0	No

This measurement will be used with discretion and the diversity of the groups will be justified. Unfortunately what cannot be determined at this point in public hearings is what sort of demographic attended. From the minutes there is evidence to suggest a diversity of gender, for instance, by making assumptions based on the names of those presenting but what cannot be discussed here is whether various groups of society were represented. For example, it is not immediately obvious that there was an intergenerational population in attendance nor that those representing various socioeconomic or minority groups. By representing, it is not meant that they are speaking on behalf of minority groups but that voices are evident from a range of backgrounds; that those in attendance are representative of the wider populace. The nearest the researcher can get to determining diversity within a hearing is through the possible participants listed above within scale 4. In order to ensure that a diverse demographic were in attendance it would be necessary to control the selection process or at least take note of who was there by some sort of survey. This though, would be better served by different types of mini-publics which specialise in inclusivity of this sort. Yet, this is worthy of note as a particular failing of a public hearing.

To ensure that the attendees are representative of wider society, many mini-publics make use of random sampling or a stratified method. Most hearings at a local or national level will be recruited through self-selection. Many deliberative theorists (James 2008; Fishkin 2009) believe this does not ensure an inclusive process, yet as argued, there is a level of inclusion which is obtained through this process. One that should be considered, which is why the fifth condition tests for how those that attended were included and the following condition measures what sort of contribution they made (condition 6).

(5) Were attendees selected in an inclusive way?

1.0	Yes
0.83	Stratified recruitment
0.67	Random sample
0.52	Self-selection
0.48	Opt in
0.33	Application process
0.17	Invite only
0	No, closed access

Views vary on which is the most effective form of recruitment. Aforementioned, the most popular options for recruitment in deliberative processes are stratified or random sampling (Goodin and Dryzek 2008; Smith 2009a). Fishkin and Luskin believe that recruitment through random sampling is preferable, as they state, ‘Only random sampling assures everyone has an equal probability of being chosen to participate’ (2005: 288), which is true. Although for Fishkin (2009: 132-3) the ability to apply the results of such a process to a wider population would seem to be of more importance than ensuring that minority groups are not just represented but have a fair chance of expressing their own, often conflicting ideas (James 2008: 120-3). Assuming that one person can communicate all the views of their minority group not only places unfair pressure on that individual but is not conducive to entering conversations where mixed groups learn from one another. People of varied genders, ethnicity, age and socio-economic backgrounds need to be part of the bigger conversation for these processes to fulfil their own purpose. Quotas, or stratified sampling, will ensure these groups are represented

unlike random sampling which, to some degree, leaves it up to chance. This is why stratified sampling has been placed higher than random sampling on the scale.

More specific for public hearings is the aforementioned self-selection process, defended in section 2.5.2. Self-selection is worth measuring and should not be considered fully exclusive as it has its uses, including accommodating those who have an opinion and wish to be heard. Often those that are enthused or politically motivated lack a suitable outlet, this gives a platform for those that would otherwise be powerless to call for accountability on an issue which has affected them. For this reason, self-selection has been placed above the 0.5 membership scale. The next scale is the 'opt in' process 0.48. Opting in means that the participants have to make themselves known prior to the hearing, but are still free to attend. This is a little more exclusive than self-selection because announcing themselves prior to the hearing may put some individuals off. Furthermore, it restricts those that may have attended on the spur of the moment. An application process is when the participants have to seek permission to attend, usually from the chair or organiser. They have to be granted permission to attend, again a process which may put some off who wish to remain anonymous or flexible. And finally, 'invite only' is usually when it is a closed hearing – this can be due to it being a sensitive subject or organisers wishing to avoid outside interference.

On securing entry to the hearing, the level of inclusion may not be straightforward. There can often be limitations and exclusions even once someone has gained access to the deliberative process. Young (2000: 55) refers to this as 'internal exclusion'. Those who have access to the process may well be excluded from *within* the hearing. Opinions can be forwarded by officials as fact and the public are often bamboozled by the technical level of the information – again, this is the risk of 'dialectical superiority' (Almassi 2012: 34) discussed in section 3.2.1. Participants need to feel that the issue being discussed is resolved not just 'absorbed' by the existing political institutions, and the human goals set must be respected. The public can get frustrated when their opinion makes no impact. It has been said that the process often puts off enthusiastic members of the public (Innes and Booher 2004: 419). Therefore, not only should people have access to the process but a voice too. This is vital to ensure that all who attended had the opportunity to hear and be heard. The importance of participation is fundamental – on this, Thompson (2008: 527) says: 'Equal participation requires that no one person or advantaged group completely dominate the reason-giving process, even if the deliberators are

not strictly equal in power and prestige'. This, according to Steiner (2012: 37), should be done without fear of interruptions. Mutz (2006) reminds us, it is vital that opposing views are shared and there is greater exposure to 'cross cutting' conversations; 'Cross-cutting exposure is assumed to promote greater awareness of oppositional views because no individual person thinking in isolation can foresee the variety of perspectives through which political issues may be perceived' (Mutz 2006: 9). The role played by those who attended is considered within the sixth condition. Were they merely an audience or active participants?

(6) Was everyone allowed to contribute?

1.0	Yes
0.83	Points were taken from all attendees
0.67	Everyone actively encouraged to contribute
0.52	Prior permission needed but yes
0.48	Yes, but only called on as a witness
0.33	Yes, but people could interrupt ²⁰
0.17	No, there to bear witness
0	No

So to explain this more clearly: the set 'inclusion' (inc) is calculated from 6 explanatory factors, namely 'publicity' (pub), 'notice' (not), 'accessibility' (access), 'selection method' (select), 'groups in attendance' (groups) and 'all contributions welcome' (con) using fuzzy 'AND'. Therefore, the argument being postulated is that in order to realise the democratic norm 'inclusion' it must demonstrate the ability to realise some, if not all, combination of these conditions. Table 6.1 shows the values each of the seven hearings were awarded and the section below offers justifications for these decisions while offering more information about each case study. The outcome has been measured as an average of the conditions, where all conditions have been deemed to hold measurements which are of equal worth, as recommended by Jordan (2012: 94). However, knowledge of the cases has informed the outcome measurement too. If

²⁰ This is valued here as a negative aspect as it is possible that interruption can intimidate or derail the speaker. Individuals can, of course, counter the argument which has been made but this does not need to be done through interruption. The wish to counter the speaker can be noted through a hand signal to the chair for instance.

there was specific proof that the hearing had not been terribly inclusive, for instance, such was the case of the UN case study, this will have guided the choice of membership value.

Case study values

Table 6.1 Inclusion

Row	CASES (public hearing)	PUB	NOT	ACS	GRP	SLT	CON	Y (Outcome: Inclusion)	~Y (Outcome: Non-Inclusion)
1	ALPAC	0.52	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.52	0.67	0.83	0.17
2	FORMARTINE	0.83	0.48	0.67	0.83	0.52	0.67	0.83	0.17
3	BCCA	0.67	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.52	0.67	0.83	0.17
4	GLENMORIE	0.67	0.83	0.67	0.83	0.48	0.52	0.67	0.33
5	HELENSBURGH	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.52	0.67	0.67	0.33
6	UN	0.48	0.83	0.48	0.48	0.17	0.83	0.33	0.67
7	EU	0.48	0.83	0.67	0.67	0.48	0.67	0.67	0.33

Table 6.1 shows how this calibration using the intersection of sets (logical 'AND') of the following 'publicity' (PUB), 'notice' (NOT), 'accessibility' (ACS), 'groups in attendance' (GRP), 'selection method' (SLT) AND 'all contributions welcome' (CON).

PUB = 1.PUBLICITY ²¹

NOT = 2.NOTICE GIVEN

ACS = 3. ACCESSIBILITY OF EVENT

GRP = 4.GROUPS IN ATTENDANCE

SLT = 5.MODE OF SELECTING PARTICIPANTS

CON = 6.EVERYONE'S CONTRIBUTION WELCOME

Alpac

The Alpac hearing was awarded 0.52 for publicity. The development plans were known to the public as early as 1988, but only through rumours. The Town Council, Chamber of Commerce and County Council had all been privy to information that the townspeople had not been (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 2). The controversy of the hearing meant that it was well documented not just in the community but more widely. Given that the internet was still in its infancy at this point, social media, blogging and websites would not have been available as an information or advertising tool. Therefore it must be concluded that the advertising would have been limited on this point, in comparison to today. Understandably this is not a fault of this hearing per se

²¹ The numbers denote the question they represent in the model, see DSEI figure 4.4 (p. 68) for the complete list of questions.

but this may highlight interesting outcomes on the pervasive nature of the internet as an advertising tool. This hearing did better in terms of the notice they gave, which was over 6 weeks (0.83), and the hearings were viewed to be accessible in terms of language, venue, time and date (0.83) (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 4). The hearings were extended from five hearings to eleven in order to accommodate the high percentage of the public that wished to participate, but also to reflect the far reaching impact that the development would affect (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 5). ‘Those affected’ would be from a variety of communities due to the air and water pollution which would result from the pulp mill and the use of the forest for timber, which was to be transferred from common usage to private usage and control (Novek 1993: 341-344). Similarly it received a 0.83 for who was in attendance; as stated in section 5.3.1, there were many different groups in attendance forwarding a wealth of ideas and thoughts including community members, interest groups, government officials and environmental experts (Richardson *et al.* 1993). Like most of the other hearings, the Alpac hearing used a self-selection process (0.52) to recruit people, as is consistent with public hearings. Finally, it received 0.67 for contribution as there was a wide variety of people heard throughout the process.

Formartine

The hearing was advertised widely and also reported on nationwide (0.83). The fact that the hearing was taking place, the outcome and the decision were discussed in many local and national papers, local and national websites, Scottish local radio stations and local news reports (BBC; The Guardian; The Independent²²). Planning law in the UK dictates that the hearing was announced both on the local council’s and the Scottish government’s website. It did not do well in terms of giving people notice (0.48) giving only 2 weeks to 10 days’ notice (Extract from planning application 2007). Yet, it received higher levels of membership in terms of accessibility (0.67) for a reasonable venue, date and the language being appropriate for the population of that area, although it may have been held too late in the evening for some people as many had to leave before its conclusion (Minutes from Special Meeting 2007). A wide variety of opinions were forwarded, including experts and local people, as well as members of

²² BBC (2007) http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/scotland/north_east/7102856.stm. The Guardian (2007) <http://www.theguardian.com/uk/2007/nov/29/golf.communities>. The Independent (2013) <http://www.independent.co.uk/news/uk/home-news/donald-trump-fails-to-deliver-on-golf-resort-jobs-pledge-8693854.html>.

interest, community and business groups from a self-selected audience (0.83, 0.52). It was understood that individuals who wished to speak had to make themselves known prior to the hearing, as customary. However, the chair also asked if anyone else wished to address the committee, specifically on points that they may have raised in writing before the hearing (Minutes from Special Meeting 2007), resulting in a 0.67, which is the same measurement for the Alpac hearing. Only one wanted to be added to the list which meant there were 30 speakers from various representatives or speaking for themselves, from both sides of the debate (Minutes from Special Meeting 2007).

BCCA

The hearing for the BCCA was advertised by local papers, explained at length on the Assembly website and by leaflets and posters (Ratner 2005: 25). They could have contacted a wider audience by using other means but have managed to obtain a 0.67 for publicity. They gave the necessary 6 weeks' notice and the venue was chosen for its accessibility to most people (0.83). The hearings were usually 3 hours in length, either held on Saturday evenings or on weekday evenings. There were also over 50 hearings which took place so if people wished to attend there would arguably be one within distance for them to attend and language appropriate to the region was considered (0.83) (Ratner 2005: 25). A wide variety of people were represented by those in attendance including interest groups, advocacy organisations, political parties, trade unions, academics, members of CA, general public (Fung and Warren 2010: 59) and elected government officials (Lang 2007: 40) which earned them a high membership for the forth condition 'grp' (0.83). Again, it was a self-selecting process (0.52), which differed from the randomly sampled Assembly and everyone was encouraged to contribute to the discussion (0.67). A total of 363 presentations were heard throughout the 50 hearings (Fournier *et al.* 2011: 40).

Glenmorie

This hearing's publicity of the event was placed at 0.67 as it made use of local media, national media and specific websites designed to accommodate the wider rhetoric which surrounded this development (BBC 2013; Northern times 2013; The Highland Council website). It gave 6 weeks' notice (0.83) and the venue, language and date were suitable for the hearing, yet the visual impact hearing was held during a week day, limiting the people that could attend (0.67) (Rice 2014: 11). There was a good variety of groups and individuals in attendance (0.83), yet the process had an 'opt in' process where individuals had to announce their intention to attend

through a written request prior to the meeting (0.48). Hearing statements could be submitted as late as the 23rd of September, the date of the first hearing (Rice 2014: 183). If individuals struggled to present during the hearing the reporter said she would be happy to accommodate them at a time that they would find more appropriate. Yet, people could only speak if they had sought prior permission (0.52) (Rice 2014: 172).

Helensburgh

The Helensburgh hearing was advertised in local papers, local radio and community magazines receiving a value of 0.67 (CES; Helensburgh Advertiser; Your Radio). Although discussions had been had about the hearing for some time, it was officially only announced a month before it happened (0.67). The day of the hearing, the venue and language were appropriate but was held quite late (from 8-10pm). The people from the surrounding villages were expected to travel to the nearest town for the hearing, which was at least 30 minutes' drive away for some. Yet, public transport was taken into consideration when fixing the time and place for the hearing (0.67) (witness observation). An alternative would have been to hold more than one hearing on this matter. There was a diverse group of people in attendance the public, MPs, interest groups and community organisations (0.67) (Helensburgh Advertiser 2013). Everyone who attended were encouraged to contribute and it was a self-selecting process (0.67, 0.52) (witness observation).

UN

This hearing was advertised but there were gaps. It was announced on the UN website and the website of the Moray Feu Traffic Subcommittee. Advertising outside of that was in national and local medians; the BBC (including a Newsnight report on EU involvement²³), the regional variation of ITV for Scotland – STV. Yet, the ongoing nature of the process was not widely known. A population were therefore aware of it (0.48). The hearing was announced 6 weeks before the hearing was to take place (0.83) (UNECE 2011). Although significantly, the hearing was not open to the public, only the parties involved (those that had brought the breach of human rights to the Committee and the legal team representing the UK government, 0.17: invite only) – yet this gave people enough time to send comments of protest or support and lobby if they had chosen to (ESC 2014). The hearing was held in Geneva. The sort of hearing that it

²³ Video on UN involvement in Edinburgh Tram System http://www.2daymedia.com/ASPPProcessURL/partner-nonav-preview.aspx?search=15122011_1&folderid=5063&linkname=newsnightreportintol

was, access was unlikely to suit everyone (0.48) - if indeed a wider populace had chosen to bear witness they would have been disadvantaged. The date and time were awkward as it was held mid-week. The language was in English which may have suited a wider group of people but the technical level of the information discussed may have isolated some attendees (ESC 2004). As discussed in section 5.3.6, the group in attendance was not diverse in terms of the criteria set out although, the Compliance Committee is a commendable and diversely rich group (0.48). The work that it has done should be accredited here but it is important to stick to the scale set out; this Committee cannot be considered to represent the wider populace. While the process limited the people in attendance, points were taken from all attendees (0.83) (Conversation with UN representative).

EU

The hearing was publicised extensively on the European Commission website although, it was advertised to specific arenas, such as science circles, environmental organisations, member states and heads of industry (0.48). It was advertised early, probably due to where it was being held and to ensure people could book flights or travel arrangements (0.83) (Background Paper for Stakeholders' Contributions). Accessibility was difficult to measure as it was held in Belgium which was not convenient to any participants aside from those that lived in Belgium. However, as that is the EC centre – it is understandable and in turn justifiable for it to be held there (0.67). There are easier ways to ensure more people could get involved which include group conferencing and live-streaming, which was not available. There was a diverse group in attendance (0.67) (*see* appendix 2). Like the Glenmorie event this was an 'opt in' process where individuals had to announce that they would be attending (0.48). Attendees were all encouraged to contribute to the discussion throughout the process (0.67).

6.2.2 Popular control

The inclusiveness of the decision-making process is similar to the level of popular control, as discussed in section 4.6.2. It is very often who has access to the process that will dictate the agenda and the direction the discussion takes, as well as the outcome. Much of this will depend on whether individuals have instigated the hearing or whether officials are organising the process without public input. An important aspect of agenda-setting will be establishing the terms of reference or remit of a public hearing, which often excludes the public. A further complication of the hearings being driven by a political body is that it can be used as a formality

to gain legitimacy for a decision which has previously been made or for a development which has already been approved, rather than giving consideration or precedence of the actual democratic outcome. Finally, how the public influence the final decision is paramount to measuring popular control. Therefore the first measurement of popular control will be:

(7) Has the public hearing been driven by the public?

- | | |
|------|---|
| 1.0 | Yes |
| 0.83 | grassroots movement with some organisation |
| 0.67 | organisation/ public body |
| 0.52 | protests groups with public membership |
| 0.48 | political body |
| 0.33 | held as a part of the planning system ²⁴ |
| 0.17 | business/developer |
| 0 | No |

In order to evaluate the level of contribution from the public, the following conditions will be used again: (4) Was there a diverse range of groups in attendance? and (6) Was everyone allowed to contribute? This will impact on the control the public were able to wield. Vital for popular control is the impact the public had on the final decision (Smith 2009a). Therefore the next measurement for popular control, and the eighth condition is:

(8) Did participants vote at the end?

- | | |
|------|--|
| 1.0 | Yes, directly led to policy initiative |
| 0.83 | Yes, affected outcome/final decision |
| 0.67 | Yes but actual decision was taken at a later date with the knowledge of the public feeling demonstrated in the hearing |
| 0.52 | All opinions taken into consideration and guided final decision/there was no necessity for vote ²⁵ |

²⁴ By this it is meant that it is a legal necessity as part of the planning process.

²⁵ Although there is no requirement for voting in certain public hearing i.e. an information sharing hearing, there is something to be gained from voting to decipher how the participants feel about the issue even just through a show of hands. This would lead to greater level of transparency because decisions that are made which are contrary to the public opinion should be highlighted and explained in reviews.

0.48	Yes but unsure whether it guided final decision
0.33	Yes but did not lead to final outcome
0.17	No decision to be made from hearing/ all opinions taken on board (acknowledged in final report) but no vote held
0	No

Combining this with variable (6) will help determine the level of popular control during the process.

Organisers should consider using a trained facilitator who can effectively guide discussions on contentious issues. On this point Howe (1999: 304) believes that experience should not be underestimated; ‘and for lay chair(person) as well as for lawyers, earlier proven experience of inquiry work...is surely the best qualification. Best of all, perhaps, is such experience linked with a degree of humility as well as humanity’. Choosing a facilitator is of vital importance for popular control as they will be in charge of guiding the discussion. The chief spokesperson must be especially well versed on the topic and is also responsible for sharing any new information which may arise during proceedings (Hutton 1986: 5). A neutral chairperson can ensure that the process follows the desires of the citizens, and not that of the public bodies.

(9) Was there a reputable chairperson?²⁶

1.0	Yes
0.83	Neutral/uninvolved and qualified invigilator
0.67	Organised task force appointed by public
0.52	Expert in particular field, (academic, economist, lawyer)
0.48	Organised task force appointed by government
0.33	Organised task force appointed by developers
0.17	Member of council/political actor
0	No

Having a level of control over all the various stages of the decision-making is a part of popular control (Smith 2009a; Elstub 2014b). The previous scales give some indication of the impact

²⁶ The chairperson can also be referred to as the ‘moderator’ or ‘facilitator’.

that the participants could have over the agenda (7), throughout the process (4) and on the final decision (6,8). The following measurement will reflect on the impact the participants could have over the outcome by considering whether the outcome of the process was made prior to the hearing or if there is the potential of participants to impact on the outcome. The final question posed is therefore:

(10) Was the outcome²⁷ of the hearing still to be determined?

- 1.0 Yes
- 0.83 Yes, options of decisions to be discussed
- 0.67 Yes, there was a number of predetermined options up for discussion
- 0.52 Yes, a choice of two or three options were to be discussed
- 0.48 The outcome was (fairly) likely to go in a certain direction
- 0.33 Hearing was being held because of objection to an existing decision
- 0.17 The hearing was just a formality or a necessary part of legal system
- 0 Outcome obvious before concluded/predetermined decision

This condition is also used in the ‘transparency section’. Again, the outcome ‘popular control’ has been set as an average of the conditions – this has also been guided by the researcher’s knowledge of the cases. It is assumed that all conditions hold equal importance to the outcome.

Case study values

Table 6.2 Popular control

Row	CASES (public hearing)	GRP	CON	PUBDRI	VOTE	CHR	OTCM	Y (Outcome: Popular Control)	-Y (Outcome: Non-Popular Control)
1	ALPAC	0.83	0.67	0.83	0.17	0.48	0.33	0.48	0.52
2	FORMARTINE	0.83	0.67	0.33	0.17	0.17	0.83	0.33	0.67
3	BCCA	0.83	0.67	0.48	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.17
4	GLENMORIE	0.83	0.52	0.48	0.17	0.48	0.52	0.52	0.48
5	HELENSBURGH	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.52	0.52	0.83	0.48	0.52
6	UN	0.48	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.33	0.67	0.33
7	EU	0.67	0.67	0.48	0.17	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.17

²⁷ When referring to ‘outcome’ here, this is referring to the actual outcome of the public hearing - not the outcome of the set membership which, as the independent variable, is popular control.

Table 6.2 shows how this calibration using the intersection of sets (logical 'AND') of the following 'groups in attendance' (GRP), 'everyone's contribution welcome' (CON), 'publically driven hearing by public' (PUBDRI), 'vote' (VOTE) AND 'chairperson' (CHR).

GRP = 4.GROUPS IN ATTENDANCE

CON = 6.EVERYONE'S CONTRIBUTION WELCOME

PUBDRI = 7.PUBLIC HEARING DRIVEN BY PUBLIC

VOTE = 8.VOTE AFTERWARDS

CHR = 9.CHAIRPERSON

OTCM = 10.OUTCOME STILL TO BE DETERMINED

Alpac

As above, Alpac scored well for the variety of people in attendance (0.83). The greater the diversity in attendance, the more representative the process and the more varied the perspectives highlighted throughout the process. Individuals were encouraged to forward their opinions (0.67). Most interestingly for the hearings on the Alpac development, it was concluded by the Review Board Report that the hearing had indeed been publically driven (0.83) (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 3-4). The participants did not get to vote at the end of the process (0.17) and the process was chaired by an organised task force which had been appointed by the government (0.48), referred to as the Alpac EIA Review Board (*see* Richardson *et al.* 1993: 4-5). The final criterion for popular control is whether the outcome of the hearings was still to be determined. Although the hearing was publically driven this was because the government had already given the go-ahead to Alpac and the public were, by and large, hostile to the project (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 1-2). Clearly they were able to mobilise effectively yet this meant that the outcome was only likely to go one of two ways: to go ahead with the existing decision or for the government to withdraw its agreement on the project (0.33).

Formartine

In terms of the level of contribution from the public and the diversity of groups in attendance, the Aberdeen hearing had high levels of membership (0.67, 0.83). As the hearing was held as a necessary part of the planning system, it was not seen to have a high membership for being publically driven (0.33) (Ford 2011). Although all the views were seen to be taken into consideration, the participants did not vote at the end which means there is no guarantee that they influenced the outcome (0.17). Another notable low membership measurement was

received for the chair being Head of the council (Councillor Loveday) and therefore, not seen to be qualified or reassuringly unbiased (0.17). Yet, the outcome of the process was uncertain and many options were to be discussed on specific aspects of the site (0.83). Most notably how many golf courses would be accepted (one or two); the housing; the SSSI and how it could or would be protected (Kelly 2013: 2).

BCCA

Similar to the two hearings above, there was a high membership for the variety of those in attendance and the contribution of the participants (0.83, 0.67). The value of 0.83 has been awarded because everyone who attended the hearing, as well as the wider public, had their direct say over the outcome of the referendum over a period of time. The membership is moderate in terms of the process being publically driven (0.48). This experimental participatory process was brought about by Premier Gordon Campbell when his party, the Liberal Party, were the victors in the 2001 election (Ratner 2005: 24). While the hearings were organised by the CA staff and many of the CA members organised the hearings in their own communities (Fournier *et al.* 2011: 40), they had been given the go-ahead by the government. Yet, arguably it was the disaffection of the public which drove the Liberal Party to promise public input into constitutional change as part of their electoral campaign. The membership is high in terms of the chair. Here, a value of 0.83 has been given. The chair of the CA, who was assuredly qualified and neutral, nominated who would moderate at the hearings – who were CA members (Fournier *et al.* 2011: 29). In addition the sessions were designed to ensure citizen's concerns were heard. They were there to discuss the option of electoral reform. Therefore, no decisions had been made nor was any type of electoral system being heralded above the rest (Ratner 2005: 24) and the outcome was still to be determined (0.83).

Glenmorrie

The Glenmorrie hearing had a range of representatives and participants (0.83) but received a lower membership value for contributions (0.52). The hearing was held in relation to the recommended procedural requirements of the 1997 Town and Country Planning and the Planning (Scotland) Act 2006, as well as a necessary procedure in accordance with the Electricity Act of 1989 (Rice 2014: 3). It was agreed that a hearing should be held by a number of parties who felt that the cumulative and sequential impacts of the windfarm environmental,

aesthetic and the larger impacts on the residents of the area should be known (0.48) (Rice 2014: 10). Yet, it was widely reported that the broader inquiry had been brought on by pressure from the Highland Council and the 300 letters of complaint that the proposals were met with (BBC 2013; The Northern Times 2013; The Scotsman 2013). Again, the participants did not vote at the end. A pattern has emerged in this regard, hearings held at a low level of governance and usually focusing on planning developments do not use voting to decipher the public feeling at the end. This is perhaps a notable, yet unnecessary, absence from the public hearing process (0.17). An organised task force appointed by the government was expected to hold the inquisitorial process, the hearing and write the necessary recommendations (0.48) (Rice 2014). The result from this hearing would be a yes or no answer to a wind-farm. This value of 0.52 was given because there were no other options up for discussion for instance, community windfarm versus privately owned windfarm; or alternatives about where it should go. The discussion therefore, was limited to 'for' and 'against' for the proposed planning meaning the community had little control over the outcome of the discussion (The Scotsman 2013).

Helensburgh

The first three conditions of the Helensburgh hearing all received a consistent 0.67. A variety of groups (0.67) were invited to contribute throughout the process (0.67). The hearings itself was set up by a public body supported by the local paper (0.67) (Helensburgh Advertiser 2013). It was understood by all participants before taking part that this process was an information gathering and sharing event. For this reason, as nothing was being decided upon and it was just a chance to share ideas and thoughts, there was no vote at the end of the process (0.52) (witness observation). The chairperson was the editor of the local paper, so although he was unlikely to be biased, there was no guarantee that he was qualified (0.52). The discussion on wind-power was designed to gather people's thoughts and get a sense of the response to the upcoming windfarm which was being proposed, so the outcome of the hearing was still to be determined (0.83).

UN

As discussed in the inclusion section 6.2.1, the groups in attendance were not as diverse as they could have been in this hearing (0.48). However, the contribution was from all attendants (0.83). The hearing has been brought on by a grassroots movement which has organised themselves into an effective pressure group (0.83) (BBC 2011). In this instance there was a vote which affected the outcome previously noted in section 5.3.6 (0.83). The chair of the

ACCC is an expert in his field and was elected to this position by the Member of the Parties. He is Jonas Ebbesson, a Professor of Environmental Law, and Director of Stockholm Environmental Law and Policy Centre, at Stockholm University. He has acted as a consultant for various governmental, intergovernmental and non-governmental bodies as well as for law firms and environmental consultants²⁸. Being wholly unconnected to the project will be used as a recommendation for his neutrality (0.83). Like the Alpac hearing this hearing was held due to an objection to a development; therefore the panel was considering the three points of contention which had been brought before them and they were only likely to uphold or offer some amendments to these actions (0.33) (UNESC 2012).

EU

The first membership values are again consistent with a variety of people contributing to the process (0.67, 0.67). The hearing was driven by a Task Force which was set up by the EC. Due to the driving force behind this organisation, it is considered fair to count it as a political body, it was therefore given a 0.48. This was more of a ‘problem solving’ process rather than a policy shaping agenda. Therefore, no votes were taken at the end but the opinions were undoubtedly taken into consideration and acknowledged in the final report (0.17). The EU hearing differs from the hearing held in Helensburgh in that there was a specific outcome expected from the EU hearing – a recommendation – whereas in the Helensburgh hearing no outcome was expected meaning that there was nothing to be voted on. The chairs were neutral and qualified. The first chair was Andrea Gentili, Deputy Head of Unit New forms of production DG Research and Innovation. For the second panel, the chair was Bonifacio Garcia Porras, Head of Unit Innovation Policy for Growth DG Enterprise and Industry; and the final panel was chaired by Peter Baur, Deputy Head of Unit Higher education and innovation; entrepreneurship; EIT DG Education and Culture (0.83) (Agenda and minutes from hearing 2013). As this was an information gathering public hearing the outcome was very much in the hands of the participants (0.83). Innovation and problem solving was the leading agenda (Background Paper for Stakeholders’ Contributions).

6.2.3 Transparency

The openness of the process will dictate how transparent it is. There are various elements which need to be considered for this. First of all, is information readily available regarding the process

²⁸ ACCC members details can be found here: <http://www.unece.org/environmental-policy/treaties/public-participation/aarhus-convention/envpptfwg/envppcc/aarhuscc-members.html>

and the issue which will be discussed? The goals and the procedure must be understood by all who participate; therefore all stages of the hearing must be explained. The issues that will be discussed need to be clarified. This should be done through the means of publicising (Baker *et al.* 2005: 498). Again, this may include giving out information prior to the hearing by means, such as a meeting or a briefing appropriate to the issues that will be discussed (Fung 2006: 68). This can be measured to some extent by the information available to participants before, during and following the process. This is because participants will have to remain flexible throughout proceedings, assuming that change may occur through new evidence or changing circumstances. Further to this, who is actually in attendance will impact on how transparent the process is. Not only should people bear witness to the process, but all levels of governance and aspects of development should be open and transparent within the hearing process for it to be democratically legitimate and effectual as a process. Unless there is a particular reason for it to be a closed hearing if, for instance, the issue is particularly sensitive.

Therefore, the measurement will be built round the question:

(11) Was information made publicly available?²⁹

1.0	Yes
0.83	Throughout the whole process – before/during/after specific information on the issue easy to find
0.67	Yes, but just through the 2 stages of the process/ specific information on the issue easy to find
0.52	Yes, but just through one stage, specific information on the issue easy to find
0.48	Related but not specific information available, fairly easy to find (internet, websites etc)
0.33	Related but not specific information available, had to be specifically asked for
0.17	Independent study must be done to find any information on the subject matter
0	No, information kept from participants

To decipher the democratic norm the level of publicity which surrounded the event (1) Did they advertise the process extensively? will also be considered.

²⁹ 'Information' refers to the subject matter – information on the development or developers, but also information which will qualify the participants to participate properly, ie technical terminology, EIAs etc. This is not the same as information on the process itself; information on the procedure of the public hearing is expected to be given when the hearing is announced.

The ‘follow up’ or feedback, that is part of a public hearing’s procedure, means that a level of transparency can feasibly be achieved. In order to make the process more democratic and participants more confident in the outcome, restrictions must be imposed on back door access for specific legislators and, highlighting and taking action against monetary inducements in the decision-making process. To avoid this the purpose of the public hearing must be understood by all – is the purpose merely to provide information to the public; an invitation to verbalise opinions and comments; or a tool for decision-making and policy setting? It is also crucial to the proceedings to determine if the outcome of the hearing was already decided, which can often be the case in hearings. Therefore the next variable will be: (10) Was the outcome of the hearing still to be determined?, which has been discussed in the section on popular control.

The measurement of this democratic norm will also make use of the chairperson value here to determine how neutral, fair and objective the chair has been. Therefore, also included is: (9) Was there a reputable chairperson? A chairperson that is qualified and unbiased is paramount to the integrity of the process. It is more often than not the chair’s job to ensure the participants are kept informed of new developments; that time is shared equally and that the participants are taken seriously. The transparency that can be assured through a non-partisan facilitator cannot be underestimated. Table 6.3 shows the case values for the case studies which will be explained below. Again, the outcome (y) is based on an average of the set scores, supported by the researcher’s knowledge of the cases. All the set conditions are deemed to hold equal weight within the analysis.

Case study values

Table 6.3 Transparency

Row	CASES (public hearing)	PUB	INFO	OTCM	CHR	Y (Outcome: Transparency)	-Y (Outcome: Non-Transparency)
1	ALPAC	0.52	0.17	0.33	0.48	0.33	0.67
2	FORMARTINE	0.83	0.67	0.83	0.17	0.67	0.33
3	BCCA	0.67	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.17
4	GLENMORIE	0.67	0.83	0.52	0.48	0.67	0.33
5	HELENSBURGH	0.67	0.67	0.83	0.52	0.52	0.48
6	UN	0.48	0.67	0.33	0.83	0.52	0.48
7	EU	0.48	0.48	0.83	0.83	0.67	0.33

PUB = 1.PUBLICITY

INFO = 10.INFORMATION AVAILABLE TO ALL THROUGHOUT PROCESS

OTCM = 11.OUTCOME STILL TO BE DETERMINED

CHR = 9.CHAIRPERSON

Alpac

In terms of transparency, this was not the strongest aspect of the Alpac hearing. The process did not appear to be open or transparent. The publicity of the hearing had a reasonable level of membership (0.52). Much of the publicity was helped through word of mouth and through the local press. The controversy of the development flamed a lot of the discussion and ultimately led to a high turnout (Novel 1993: 351). It is worth reiterating that the internet was not available to accommodate the great amount of discussion and interest which surrounded this hearing, but moreover for this democratic good the values, themes and discourses could have been better served through a proper publicised process. Furthermore, it can be seen from table 6.3 that there is a low level of membership for available information which cannot be attributed to the lack of internet (0.17). It appeared that information was not given freely - for instance an EIA was not carried out by the time the hearings were heard - and at times, estimated claims made within the application were wildly optimistic (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 130). For instance, in 1988 it was announced that 3900 jobs would be created either directly or indirectly by the project. Six months later a similar number of jobs was reiterated but this time expressed in terms of man hours (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 130). These jobs, it was promised, would be far-reaching throughout the area which suffered from high unemployment and comparatively low income, as was the case in many areas in North America at this time (Novek 1993: 343). However, throughout the process it became increasingly obvious that the jobs on offer would be significantly fewer than first promised. Moreover, many of the jobs would be seasonal or for outside contractors; ultimately creating very few opportunities for native people (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 135-141).

There were other implications for the health of the workers, where concerns were raised regarding exposure to various chemical toxins due to the bleaching process. This, was on top of the health implications of the wider population by the polluted rivers and other by-products which was raised by representatives of the Canadian Paperworkers Union (Novek 1993: 342; Richardson *et al.* 1993: 135). This highlights that much of the information was not available to the participants or wider public. The outcome of the hearing, as previously stated, was limited due to the hearing's purpose being to challenge an existing development (0.33) which already had the support of the government. More worryingly was the land purchasing that was being carried out by Alpac while the hearing was going on (highlighted in section 5.3.1), suggesting

that Alpac were fairly confident that the outcome would be in their favour. Finally, the chair could not be seen to be neutral or non-bias as they were an organised task force by the government which could be considered as having a vested interest in the outcome (0.48) (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 4).

Formartine

Three of the conditions of this outcome were of high membership. Information was made readily available regarding the development (0.83). Although much of the TIGLS's application had been delayed in being submitted, the hearing was not held until all documentation was received (Wightman 2011: 4). As discussed in section 5.3.2 there appeared to be some dubious contact between members of the Scottish Government and Mr Trump, but due to the Freedom of Information Act the documents connected with the development were all made available. The media attention was paramount to informing the public discussion as well as online forums, while organised public opposition and support was instrumental to publicising the event (0.83) (Ford 2011: 38). With such a huge and complex development being proposed, the outcome was not set. Various aspects had to be discussed which meant that the outcome was not known, ensuring that the process was open and transparent (0.83) (McCulloch *et al.* 2008). The chair was a member of the council which is problematic in terms of the transparency of the decision (0.17).

BCCA

The BCCA public hearings were particularly transparent. The process was advertised early meaning that people were more likely, or more able, to go (0.67). There was much discussion surrounding the event with it being such a unique process with its connection to the CA (Fung and Warren 2010: 61). Electoral reform was a key issue which drove the Liberal party campaign, and by which the party was thus successful, indicating that it was a subject the public felt strongly about. The media, social networks and organisational group made efforts to keep the public informed (0.83) (Fung and Warren 2010: 61). Further to this, by having an independent chair, the hearings were chaired by members of the CA; this meant that there should not have been a vested interest, instead it was a process designed to allow the CA members to hear from the public (0.83) (Fournier *et al.* 2011: 41). The outcome was yet to be decided thus ensuring that the process was transparent (0.83). The public knew going in that they would get a chance to vote in a referendum on this issue. Their input into the hearing

would also help to guide the recommendations which emerged from the CA, although (Fournier *et al.* 2011: 107) concede that the hearings may have had little impact on the final outcome.

Glenmorie

The Glenmorie hearing was publicised early and widely (0.67). The controversy of building a windfarm in the Highlands was such that the opposition organised themselves extremely effectively and quickly, accommodated by the coverage from the local press. The organisers of the hearing ensured that all information and necessary documentation was in the library, as well as being available at the sessions (Rice 2014:174). Furthermore, all the documents were available on the Scottish Government's website for the necessary 12 week post-decision rule (0.83). The organised groups were giving evidence to the 'reporter' (chair) to some respect, in an attempt to persuade the decision in a certain direction. Therefore the public did understand going in, what the outcome was likely to be – either a rejection or an approval for the windfarm (0.52). The participants appreciated that they would not have a direct impact on the final impact. However, offering more alternatives may have opened this hearing up to wider discussion.

The reporter had been appointed by the SG – a Ms Rice – who took on the role of mediator at the hearing and wrote the concluding report which recommended the rejection of the project (0.48). A government official cannot be assured to be a neutral chair. In Scotland, and the UK, there are certain renewable targets which the governments are expected to meet, which is recommended by EU environmental policy. The Scottish Government's target for 100% of Scottish demand for electricity to be met from renewable sources is to be achieved by 2020. Whereas the UK's target is of 15% of all energy requirements to be met from renewable sources by 2020, which has been set out by the 2009 EU Renewables Energy Directive. The EU has a 2020 target of 20% of all energy requirements to be met from renewable sources which gives an indication of how pressing Scotland's targets are in comparison to the aims of the UK and the EU³⁰. This means that unnecessary pressure or temptation could hypothetically be placed on the individual. An individual completely unrelated should be responsible for making this decision.

³⁰ See renewables targets: UK Renewables Energy Roadmap Update 2013. https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/255182/; And the vision for how this can be achieved: UK Renewable Energy Roadmap, Technical Assessment of the 2 Renewable Energy Action Plans. http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/jrc/downloads/jrc_reference_report_2011_reap.pdf; Scotland's 3 Renewable Resource <http://www.scotland.gov.uk/Resource/Doc/47176/0014633.pdf>.

Helensburgh

In terms of transparency for the Helensburgh hearing, it was fairly well publicised using the necessary channels and information (0.67) (radio, newspaper, websites, information forums). The sort of information required for this sort of process is not very technical or detailed (0.67). As an information gathering process, this was more to hear people's concerns and their views, rather than determine a specific outcome. The public knew that their role was to listen and be listened to. The panel were suitably qualified and did well to inform the public of the various discourses which surround wind-power (witness observation). As such, the participants were able to access information for themselves prior to the hearing or learn from the experts while they were there (0.83). The chair, as discussed, was not a strong candidate but he had no vested interest in the outcome of the hearing making the process capable of overall transparency (0.52).

UN

The UN process was transparent in certain aspects but the lack of documentation, recordings or minutes on what was discussed is highly problematic. While understandably narrowing those that were in attendance to ensure a focused and fair process, this limits the larger impact the Committee has to offer as many more could know about the system and how it works to protect lay citizens. By referring contested decisions made by national government, to an otherwise neutral third party, enables the UN to make use of its role as a supranational adjudicator, making it an effective tool in legitimising decisions. Although it was covered on the national news and Newsnight, more could have been done to publicise this type of event (0.48). In regards to information being readily available, the Committee was given the necessary documentation which allowed them to make a decision. Furthermore, due to the confidentiality clause the identity of the Parties involved can be kept anonymous from public knowledge but 'no information held by the Committee shall be kept confidential' (ESC 2004: 6). Yet, information for the wider population, although available on the hearing and the outcome, the follow up information was not easy to find (0.67). The communicant (Moray Feu Traffic Subcommittee of Lord Moray's Feuars Committee) knew that that there were a few matters being considered by the Committee therefore the outcome was not assured for themselves nor the defendant (the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland) (0.33) (Compliance Committee,

2013³¹). These terms are appropriate in this case as this was much more like a judicial process than the other hearings; again explaining the necessity to limit those in attendance. The chair was a neutral facilitator and in ways is an ideal candidate for such a role. With no allegiance and with an understanding of the complexities of this case, this made certain that the trial was fair and therefore can be considered to have assured its transparency (0.83).

EU

The process was not strong in terms of publicity and information (0.48, 0.48). Having said that, the information on the project is all on the EC website and easy to access if people know to look for it (ESC 2014). In terms of knowing what happens in the future as a result of this hearing, the average citizen will discern very little. As an information gathering and roundtable discussion to try and develop ideas for improving European Manufacturing it is understandable that this may not be of interest to everybody. Again though, recordings or live streaming could have helped to make this a more open process. The participants were clear about why they were there and what they would bring to the hearing meaning that the process was open, contributing to its ability to offer a transparent process (0.83)³². The chair in each of the plenary discussions changed which ensured that the discussion was not led in a particular direction and the topic changed thus safeguarding that the wider agenda or discussion was not being steered by one person (0.83).

6.2.4 Considered judgement

Innes and Booher (2004: 422) suggest that participatory methods, such as hearings, ‘challenge the status quo and ask hard questions about things that are otherwise taken for granted. They seek agreement or at least build shared knowledge and heuristics for collaborative action’. Through the inquiry process, further information is accessible and perspectives are made available to the public and officials. The potential therefore exists for hearings to encompass Smith’s (2009) definition of considered judgement. Within a public hearing a degree of openness and increased communication is possible which includes a variety of actors from lay citizens to government officials, the media to interest groups and many others, which differs from other deliberative processes. The advantages of communicating face-to-face, offers a

³¹ A full report of the findings can be found here:

http://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/env/pp/compliance/CC-40/ece.mp.pp.c.1.2013.3_eng.pdf

³² A copy of the agenda can be found here:

http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/policies/innovation/policy/amt/public-hearings-workshops/index_en.htm

level of interaction which increases the trust and quality of discourse (Bloomfield *et al.* 2001: 503). Rodger (1978: 105) believes that public hearings should be a 'system which embraces the totality of the oppositional process'. Polarised opinions are to be encouraged because they widen perspectives and provide a diversity of outlooks. As discussed in section 3.3.1, debate may not be something that should be automatically shied away from. From this, a different type of communication can occur, which may or may not be adversarial in nature but nonetheless requires an arena to be accommodated and explored.

It is necessary to attempt to measure considered judgment, or the ability of people to use considered judgement. Smith (2009a: 24) believes that arguments or judgements should be based on 'informed and reflective assessment of the matter in hand'. This will assuredly rely heavily on the background information available to the wider public before, during and after the process. The condition (10) Was information made publicly available? will therefore be included. This will help forward some understanding of the quality of input from participants. Yet, Smith warns that considered judgement cannot be judged on this alone. Facts and technical knowledge is 'crucial' but it is not enough to ensure an open and malleable mind to the points of others. Although it cannot be assured within this context that anyone is approaching it with an 'enlarged mentality', as Arendt (1968: 220) would refer to it, this would be a tall order for any deliberative institution. What can be assured is that the participants are being exposed to various groups and perspectives, consequently the condition (4) Was there a diverse range of groups in attendance? is measured too.

The next condition, working in conjunction with condition (4), will be (6) Was everyone allowed to contribute? in order to ascertain the level of 'participation'. This will decide whether everyone has had a chance to contribute to the debate and if they have, was all information open to them. Using the justification measurement from the DQI to guide the next condition, the research seeks to decipher the quality of discussion. Steiner (2012: 183) explains why justifying ones claims is so important in a deliberative interchange; 'If...actors justify their claims in a rational way, they also show respect toward the claims of others. If, on the other hand, the level of justification is low, the level of respect is also low'. In order to evaluate this, the justification measurement is applied to the minutes taken in the meeting, while taking into consideration the actors who took part; the sort of contributions which were encouraged from the participants and the information that was available to these people. It must be acknowledged

that there is a risk in utilising minutes, as the wording is not verbatim, yet the minutes will indicate what the speech act included.

(12) Did participants give justification/ explanation for objections/ points?³³

- | | |
|------|---|
| 1.0 | Yes, the speaker gives a reason Y why X should or should not be done, and a linkage is made why Y will contribute to X, by 100% ³⁴ of the participants. |
| 0.83 | The speaker gives a reason Y why X should or should not be done, and a linkage is made why Y will contribute to X, by over 80% of the participants. |
| 0.67 | The speaker gives a reason Y why X should or should not be done, and a linkage is made why Y will contribute to X, by over 60% of the participants. |
| 0.52 | The speaker gives a reason Y why X should or should not be done, but no linkage is made why Y will contribute to X, by over 40% of the participants. |
| 0.48 | The speaker justifies only with illustrations why X should or should be done, by over 40% of the participants. |
| 0.33 | The speaker only says that X should or should not be done, that it is a wonderful or terrible idea, etc. But no reason is given for why X should or should not be done. |
| 0.17 | The speaker does not present any arguments (asks, for example, merely for additional information). |
| 0 | No |

If a number of participants gave meaningful presentations, it will be regarded as worth measuring. Therefore this measurement will not be included unless 30% of the participants from a variety of groups made measurable speech acts (to determine this the 'variety of groups in attendance' condition can be employed).

³³ This value has been taken directly from Steiner's DQI (2012: 270). In an effort to establish considered judgement, making use of the entire DQI was the most effective tool for this, unfortunately the absence of transcripts meant this was not possible.

³⁴ This measurement may include 20% of people that offered a speech act at one of the lower scores. This will be explained in the cases study, yet it is interesting to consider if these different groups are offering similar justifications to their points. As is usual in hearings, participants are often only heard once or twice so using the percentage of people in attendance rather than speech acts will give a better indication of the variety of people, rather than speeches, witnessed.

Case study values

Table 6.4 Considered judgement

Row	CASES (public hearing)	GRP	CON	INFO	JSTF	Y (Outcome: Considered Judgement)	-Y (Outcome: Non-Considered Judgement)
1	ALPAC	0.83	0.67	0.17	0.67	0.52	0.48
2	FORMARTINE	0.83	0.67	0.67	0.83	0.83	0.17
3	BCCA	0.83	0.67	0.83	0.52	0.67	0.33
4	GLENMORIE	0.83	0.52	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.17
5	HELENSBURGH	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.33
6	UN	0.48	0.83	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.33
7	EU	0.67	0.67	0.48	0.83	0.67	0.33

GRP = 4.GROUPS IN ATTENDANCE

CON = 6.EVERYONE’S CONTRIBUTION WELCOME

INFO = 10.INFORMATION AVAILABLE TO ALL THROUGHOUT PROCESS

JSTF = 12.LEVEL OF JUSTIFICATION

Alpac

In terms of considered judgment, the Alpac hearing obtained a high membership of each of the conditions. There was a diverse group of individuals in attendance, meaning that a great number of perspectives were being explored (0.83) (Richardson *et al.* 1993). This does not guarantee that considered judgment was used or evident during the process but it does indicate that those in attendance were exposed to many ideas beyond their own. Experts, including scientists; local council representatives and members of various communities – indigenous and first generation community members - male, female, young, old and people for and against development were there (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 28). The discussions covered very technical details regarding the impacts on the river and the forest. Some of the members of the Review Board accused Alpac of pertaining an ethnocentric outlook, with limited knowledge of the land that there were trying to develop on and of the communities who lived and worked on the land (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 98). The boreal forest which would be cut away, not just here but in many areas in Canada, had been reported to be useless (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 55-6). Alpac claimed that the population should appreciate that the forest was once again a marketable commodity and being of economic value – they had little understanding of the animals or plants which resided within it, which were of intrinsic worth to the people, and in doing so; ‘devalued the place of the boreal forest in global ecosystems, and its role as a homeland for aboriginal peoples, a habitat for wildlife, and a source of biodiversity’ (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 55). Further affects would be felt by the locals, not only through the pollution of the rivers and the

negative impact on fish stocks, but by the transference of control over the forest and rivers from public to private management (Novek 1993: 344-45).

On the other hand, there was a strong support for the mill to be built. Not just from developers and the government but from many of the local people that felt there was no future for the younger generation in that area. They argued that people had to leave to seek employment and here was an enterprise which would benefit the people and the area;

I think it's time that our native people and other people in the community of Athabasca take advantage of opportunities...we are enthusiastic about the prospect of having work for our people, and we believe that the mill can be brought into this community and the environment can remain safe for us to continue to live here (Citizen 1, cited Richardson et al. 1993, p.38).

Another commented;

I have not had any concrete evidence to show that it's going to be detrimental (Citizen 2 cited Richardson et al. 1993, p.39).

The local press quoted the president of Alpac; *'If you turn this down, I think it would be basically saying the most environmentally-sensitive mill that can ever be built is not allowed'* – the overall impression given would be that the North Territory and specifically Athabasca *'is not serious about its future'* (cited Richardson et al. 1993: 39). A group that called itself 'Friends of the Mill' organised to support what they believed would 'expand the economic base, improve the social and economic opportunities and facilities which were available' (Richardson et al. 1993: 37-38).

In many instances, the local people were highlighting the flaws of the development application and how the cumulative impact would be far higher than predicted by the developers. As there was many different groups in attendance and the level of contribution was high (0.83, 0.67) the capacity for considered judgement was high. There were no checks put in place to ensure people were open to other people's opinions but this is the case in any mini-public. The most that can be expected is that people will listen to one another and internally reflect on the meaning of other's words. As affirmed in the transparency section, this hearing did not do well in terms of being open and honest - the information was not readily available to the local people (0.17). It would seem that the process was continuing unabridged, regardless of public

opposition. Interestingly though, regardless of the low levels of information which were available to those in attendance, the speech acts prove to be high in terms of justification (0.67). The participants had considered the input, supported their claims and done their homework. Using expertise that were available to them through their local knowledge or their native customs, as well as their more eco-centric approach to the land ensured that their contribution to the process was considered and thought-provoking (Richardson *et al.* 1993).

Formartine

Similarly to the Alpac hearing, this hearing welcomed a diverse and rich group of attendees (0.83). The local people, interest groups, community activists and business groups all felt compelled to attend, such was the feeling of support or opposition. Those that did contribute had a reasonable (10 minutes) period of time in which to voice their concerns or their support (0.67) (Minutes from Special Meeting 2007: 2). What can be taken from the very detailed minutes was that the presentations were of a high standard (0.83). The following examples have all been taken from the Minutes of the meeting. A report from the neighbouring community informed the councillors that;

A few felt that a golf resort would be visually less imposing than other forms of development and would be relatively green in comparison, with wildlife thriving better in this environment than in other options. Golf courses were thought to be good for both wild life and rural communities and some felt that it would lead to an improvement of the condition of the links areas.

Like Alpac, the local people brought a rich knowledge of the local area to the hearing which guided the discussion. A Mr Milne highlighted;

Menie was one of only two known locations in the UK to provide a habitat for the jumping red spider and this, together with 36 references to the estate in the Red Book of Entomology's most recent survey, should confirm its special interest and need for protection.

And Mr Banks, another local resident, offered;

In terms of the relevant policies and plans, Mr Banks was well aware of the need for environmental legislation – having worked offshore, including involvement with review of safety regulation and legislation in the wake of the Piper Alpha disaster. Mr Banks felt

that if the intention of legislation was to be protective, it should, and would, be taken seriously.

Environmental experts considered the impact on the SSSI and the dunes:

David Bell (an ecologist and advisor on the Environmental Statement) referred to the environment section of the Environmental Assessment, which was both broad ranging and detailed. There was a commitment to acknowledge the existing interests and to minimise impacts. Whilst the outline Environmental Assessment was not able to look at issues in the detail which would have been liked, ongoing work by the team of scientists were able to progress this, which would be enhanced at the stage of the detailed planning application. It was intended that a great deal of mitigation work would be ongoing, especially to those areas between the holes. New research had been received this season, for example, identifying more rare plants, which would be part of the more detailed response.

Business owners forwarded specific financial examples of why this development would be beneficial for the area;

Aberdeen and north east Scotland, in Mr Skene's opinion, missed out on the bulk of tourists coming to Scotland as they tended to travel to Edinburgh/ Perth /the Highlands/ the West Coast. Mr Skene believed that there was currently nothing of major importance to bring tourists to the north east.

Information was readily available, enabling oppositional and support groups to mobilise and organise themselves effectively (0.67). Less clear was the amount of information following the event. Why the decision was overturned and why Cllr Ford was dismissed is unclear. It is understood that the SG simply did not agree with the council's decision (McCulloch *et al.* 2008; Ford 2011).

BCCA

The process was well attended and contributions were welcomed (0.83, 0.67). Although the participants were informed of what the process was doing and had access to information regarding the various electoral systems (0.83), there is largely nothing to indicate that the contribution of statements was overly justified (0.52). The speakers appeared to have voiced their opinion on an electoral system, and asked questions of the CA participants. However,

although many speakers indicated why they thought one electoral system was better than another and offered reasonable justifications, there were many who did not, as can be illustrated through the comments below. It was highlighted that those that attended the CA felt they were better equipped to deal with the complexities of the system (Ratner 2005: 26) than those attending the public hearings. To highlight this, Ratner (2005: 26) comments that;

In absorbing the various critiques and proposed solutions, CA members improved their understanding of electoral systems in the B.C. context, occasionally experiencing a confidence boost when they discovered that they knew more than the immediate public and thus felt more capable of proposing a recommendation.

This is particularly significant - if the members of public that attend the mini-publics become more knowledgeable than the average person, then it could be said that they are becoming more like experts and, in turn, less representative of those that they are meant to be representing, i.e. the general public. As discussed in chapter 2, Flynn (2009) deems the formal, transformative powers of deliberative institutions as problematic, which may be attributable here. Interestingly, Ratner (2005: 26) tells us;

Most CA members nevertheless made it their business to wade through a significant number of submissions (some boasted they had read them all), sharing their assessments on the Members-Only-Discussion Forum.

The use of words 'boasted' and 'members-only' gives an insight into this somewhat exclusive group. Having selected CA members being part of a deliberative system from which others are excluded, may still create an 'us and them' situation. Which any or all of the hearings in this analysis could be accused of by creating chasms between politicians and lay citizens. One group holds the power of decision-making and one has not. The following, reported by Lang (2007: 45-6) highlights some conflict between the Assembly members and the lay persons during the public hearing phase:

...when it came down to deciding which tradeoffs to make, Assembly members got little help from their audiences, who frequently responded to Assembly members' questions with "that's your job" to decide... What annoyed some Assembly members was the inability of the presenters from these groups to answer detailed questions about the system they were promoting. They thought that this showed a lack of informed deliberation and felt inclined to discount these presentations.

It would seem from this, the CA members took on an almost elitist stance, becoming annoyed with public members who could not articulate themselves as well as the members and were not as informed on the subject. The BCCA hearings therefore lacked the inclusivity and equality that deliberative theorists support. Furthermore, the CA members were acting without a mandate given that they were not elected.

Glenmorie

The Glenmorie hearing seemed to display high membership of three of the four conditions. A real variety of attendees with access to the necessary information indicates that the capacity for considered judgement was high (0.83, 0.83). This public hearing held rigidly to the evidence-giving, quasi-judicial procedure meaning the contribution was not as flexible as it could have been in a more natural or informal setting (0.52). It is possible that associations work better in this type of hearing, indicating that experienced presenters or mobilised strength is more effectual than an individual in this setting (although there were a few individuals speaking for themselves). The justification seems to have been high, according to the minutes (0.83). Some relied on a more anecdotal style of evidence giving, such as two local residents;

The purpose of our participation in this hearing session is to illustrate the value of these locations for recreational and tourism purposes through our experiences of visiting the two viewpoints, and also of travelling through the landscape on foot to reach them. We submit no supporting documents; we do mention tourist guidebooks in a general way, but do not seek to rely on them for the purposes of the hearing session (taken from the written evidence for presentation).

Whereas many of the organised groups were much more demonstrative of their knowledge of the case, and for this reason maybe all the more compelling;

Let there be no doubt about the economic benefit Wild Land including Wild Life. Tourism brings to Scotland. Para 4.2.1-4 and Table 7(11) discusses this and compares it to the economies of the hunting industry para 4.2.5-6(11). The results are revealing. Whilst access by tourists (walkers, mountaineers and wildlife) bring in 100's of millions of pounds, and sustains 1000's of jobs; the hunting industry brings in barely 10 million pounds, and barely a 1000 jobs in the whole of Scotland. The benefit flows into largely private hands. The report also points out that the Red Deer population does a lot of damage to, in particular, the forestry industry. The cost and benefit of all these should

all be weighed up when considering this application (taken from the written evidence for presentation).

The above extract comes from the proposed statement from the group 'Save Our Straths'. They promised to bring no less than three speakers to the hearing. And another group;

ScotWays' purposes include the safeguard of rights of public access, whether by rights of way or statutory access rights under Part 1 of the Land Reform Scotland Act 2003), also to guard the amenity enjoyed by people as they participate in open-air Recreation (Scottish Rights of Way and Access Society).

Many of the groups proposed to bring multiple experts or representatives to speak for them, several groups also strived to show that there were on no way partisan or intolerant of wind-power;

In recent years we have objected to less than 6% of onshore windfarm proposals, approximately the same number as the RSPB, demonstrating that we have adhered to our policy, and that we are not anti-windfarm per se (Mountaineering Council of Scotland 2013).

On the whole, the Glenmorie hearing participants were remarkably well organised and well versed on ways to oppose the development. Those that were in favour were limited to the developers and companies which had been hired by them.

Helensburgh

The local hearing held in Helensburgh was consistent throughout the conditions. There were diverse groups in the audience and experts from differing backgrounds who made up the panel (0.67). Those that made up the panel of experts were from various groups and there was a mixed opinion on wind-power throughout the participants (Helensburgh Advertiser 2014). The information was readily available and a final decision was not required (0.67). Presentations were given from many of the participants, however, the quality of the speech acts was limited to anecdotal (witness observation). Much was also based on basic arguments for and against wind-power in terms of Helensburgh but little was discussed about the wider implications of wind-power. The audience and panel obviously had marked opinions on wind-power and there was no real feeling of open-mindedness or depth of knowledge (witness observation). The panellists spoke knowledgably and interacted well with the public. However, with no minutes in which to apply the DQI to, it is not justifiable to apply any measurement here. For this reason

the membership will be considered by looking at the various groups available which will at least give an insight into the diversity of groups in attendance which was 0.67 – a good level of variety in attendance. More than this, everyone was encouraged to contribute. The Helensburgh hearing has a consistent score of 0.67 in ‘considered judgement’ as well as 0.67 for contribution and groups, for this reason, a 0.67 has been applied as the membership for this missing condition. The membership for the justification condition was based on an average of its membership overall and by basing a reasonable reflection of the other hearings. This would not usually be an acceptable measurement to ‘guess’ or estimate but in keeping with the idea that this thesis is looking at if a public hearing *could* harness a reasonable level of considered judgement not whether it does. If the research was looking at if they *do*, then estimating would not be a reliable way to ascertain this.

UN

As discussed the diversity of participants was not the strongest element of this hearing (0.48). In terms of considered judgment, there is no doubt that all those who attended had a good grasp of environmental law, international law and the specific complexities of this case. The defending lawyer of the UK government was James Maurici QC, he was supported by a team which included representatives from DEFRA. Maurici’s website quotes Chambers and Partners (2015) saying; ‘He has a deep understanding of environmental law and has leapfrogged many long-established leaders’. The spokespeople for the subcommittee were a lawyer and an academic from the University of Edinburgh. This was not designed to be inclusive or widely participatory, again more similar to the Glenmorie hearing, it had more of a judicial element to it. Again, there were no minutes from the meeting so like the Helensburgh hearing, this has to be estimated. Having read extensively on the knowledge of all the participants there is no doubt that these people were informed, well versed and knowledgeable (ESC 2014, email interactions with Dr. Lloyd). This can make some moves to ensure that considered judgement was possible. More than this though, given the high quality of the chair and committee, who were the decision-makers in this instance, it is fair to estimate that the level of considered judgment would be high. As it is an estimate, based on the researcher’s knowledge of the case and, again a rough average of the other conditions, it is deemed problematic to give the top membership score of 0.83 but 0.67 seemed realistic, if not slightly pessimistic.

EU

The variety of people in attendance were experts in their field (0.67). They were specifically at this hearing due to what they could bring to the process. They were free to contribute to the discussion (0.67). The level of information, although not high, in terms of considered judgment is not really applicable. Those that attended were informed in their field of research which meant that their level of justification for their point would be high. For the wider populace, the information was available but not actively pushed into public consumption (0.48). The way this process works is that there is already a very specific agenda in that the purpose of the hearing has already been declared i.e. what the target or focus is of the hearing and the speakers, therefore it is apparent what X (from the justification measurement) is. The reason for Y is to keep Europe competitive; to ensure that modern manufacturing methods and clean technologies are continually supported and to make up for skill deficits and shortages which Europe is facing in terms of its industrial sector. Below are some examples of the points offered;

Massimo Mattucci, the chairman of the European Factories of the Future Research Association (EFFRA), explained how the Factories of the Future public-private partnership ... is promoting job creation, growth and industrial leadership by focusing on four different domains: sustainable manufacturing, ICT-enabled intelligent manufacturing, high-performance manufacturing, and by exploiting new materials through manufacturing.

Adrian Harris, the Director General of Orgalime, the European Engineering Industries Association. 'If we look at the share of engineering in Europe's industrial production we can be delighted, because it looks as if it is becoming progressively more important, but overall manufacturing output is rather flat, he said at the outset. To correct what he described as 'flat output' he suggested measures which the EU could launch to support the market uptake of advanced manufacturing technologies.

He went on to underline the importance of legislative predictability for Europe's industry. 'If rules are changed, investments might be lost, and without predictability you will see less investment', he maintained. "Some pieces of legislation in force could theoretically be galvanising the demand for advanced manufacturing products, for example the Energy Performance in Building Directive and the Energy Efficiency

Directive, but they are not yet playing their full role in this regard as the implementation is not completed yet, e.g. in smart meters'.

Sue Fleet, representing SusChem ETP, the European Technology Platform for Sustainable Chemistry, argued that university-business cooperation has, for too long, been limited to research activities. The partnerships should target educators and involve them in the discussion in the way education is provided.

There is the need to put more emphasis on the dissemination of research and innovation project results, making these attractive for educators and students. This would support the development of innovation and entrepreneurial skills among young people, she said.

(Taken from Minutes)

The sophistication of the justification is evident, which could be due to the fact that it is experts who are delivering the speech acts (0.83). This section has set out and justified all the measurements of the DSEI, which is vital for the qualitative analysis of the thesis. Admittedly there must be some allowance for researcher bias but efforts have been made to provide clear evidence for all the decisions taken. The next section will offer some discussion points and some finding from the above section.

6.3 Findings and discussions

A number of key findings have emerged from this exercise. From the initial section on the democratic norm inclusion, it can be seen that there is no real understanding of *who* is part of the process with no record of gender, age, ethnicity or socio-economic position, which is a real concern for analysing hearings. This can be perceived to be a benefit of the mini-public and the random sampling technique; within the mini-public the demographic is known. Yet, as previously argued, there is an openness to a self-selecting process quite unlike a randomly sampled one. A second finding from the inclusion section - it would seem that there was a high level of contribution from a variety of groups. Thus, no one group can dominate the discussion, ensuring that wider perspectives are heard. Arguably this could more easily be accommodated if organisers made use of social media in informing the public and offering an alternative means of getting involved, although it must be noted from the Alpac hearing that there were still diverse groups in attendance, despite the lack of internet. This was, in many ways, because of the number of hearings they held and the controversial nature of the topic. Macro levels of

discussion, such as discussions between neighbours and opinion pieces in newspapers, arguably played an intrinsic part in getting people involved. Interactions between members of various groups - but also from different levels of governance – including local people, government officials, interest groups and experts all together in one setting is an interesting addition to the public hearings process.

Another element which deviates from some mini-publics is the notice that is given for a hearing. The agenda and procedure is known to all early on, therefore the various groups can prepare for the subject in their own way. Although experts can sometimes take the form of a panel, the information is not fed to the participants in the same way as it is in a mini-public. This may be problematic in terms of people approaching the hearing with a fixed mind-set but this may give in to a more rigorous level of discussion than in a mini-public. Maybe more heated or adversarial, but this is not necessarily a bad thing; it may work to a different advantage. On the other hand, if what will be presented in the hearing has to be pre-submitted, as was the procedure in the Glenmorie case, it limits the spontaneity of discussion and the reflexivity of natural interaction. And yet, in some ways, it ensures that no one dominates the conversation and people are not just reacting to opinions. The Formartine meeting, which encouraged people to submit presentations but still allowed people to speak on the night, is maybe a compromise here. A fixed time slot and a presentation style of speaking is not strictly deliberative but it works to the advantage of the speaker where they are unlikely to be interrupted, meaning that people will be encouraged to listen to one another, which is an essential aspect of deliberation (Dobson 2014) and more specifically considered judgement. Holding more than one hearing in certain instances, most notably the Helensburgh debate, may have ensured that it was better attended. Furthermore, access to the high level hearings is problematic, different methods to make them more accessible need to be put in place. Live streaming is the cheapest and most effective option here.

There were many interesting findings which arose from the discussion on popular control. Specifically in terms of agenda setting, the information sharing (the Helensburgh hearing) or the information gathering (the EU hearing) processes, are particularly useful for this. This will be discussed at greater length in the next chapter but in terms of the policy-making process, hearings could be seen to be effective in setting agendas and highlighting issues which are of intrinsic value to lay citizens. Further to this, one of the key aspects which emerged from the

popular control sub-section is the importance of hearings being brought about by public pressure. The Alpac and the UN were driven by the public, in protest to decisions made by government bodies without appropriate use of public consultations. Demanding to be heard through this method can be highly effective – though, in the Alpac hearing the decision was ultimately overturned by the government. The UN upheld one of the three complaints. It must be noted that this is not a suggestion that the public should be able to overturn every decision made by a government, this would defeat the purpose of having a representative government, but enabling the public to call decision-makers to account ultimately strengthens the representative democratic system. Furthermore, if the public have a say earlier on in the development process, and are able to enter talks with those that have the power to make decisions, this may serve to minimise opposition to policy decisions. In regards to the Glenmorie and Formartine hearings, it is useful to have a hearing as part of the recommended planning process, but in these situations the temptation or likelihood of hearings being tokenistic remains high. It should not just be a box ticking exercise. Being able to vote at the end of a hearing could indicate the strength of public feeling and thus avoid the uncertainty of whether the hearings has actually impacted on the final decision or not. This would be a clear way to enhance accountability of the public hearing process as a whole.

The framework for transparency has highlighted that the hearings held at the top level of governance (EU and UN) were not advertised in the same way. It stands to reason that not many people could attend these due to where they were located but making use of recordings or live streaming would ensure greater levels of transparency. Access to information is paramount for an open process. This should be provided where appropriate, with access to information on the development, including the predicted cumulative impacts. As new information emerges it is important that this is highlighted right away so that there is no divergence in understanding between experts and participants. If the locals, experts and government officials all wish to make a meaningful contribution the dialogue must be open and they must be open themselves. Knowing that the outcome has not been pre-determined will go a long way to decrease tensions or suspicions between the various actors. People who participate do so by sacrificing their own time and energy, which must be taken seriously. Wasting people's time or allowing them tokenistic inputs will only exacerbate the feeling of alienation that citizens feel from the political system and the lack of control they exercise over their own area.

The final section on considered judgement is interesting. The Alpac hearing specifically here was highly troublesome with plans and developments going on as the process was happening. Moreover, the jobs and benefits which had been promised seemed to decrease as the hearing went on. This only served to make the public feel powerless. The chair is an important appointment. A person, or a panel, should be suitably neutral with no obvious affiliation to either side. The chair in the UN case study, as well as the Committee, is a suitable example of a neutral and qualified chair. An alternative, used in the BCCA and EU hearings, is to use different chairs if there is more than one hearing. A concern is that lay citizens become experts once taking part in a mini-public, as was the case in the BCCA example. Does that mean that they are still representative of the wider populace or did it just make them capable of seeing the flaws in the other members of the public's arguments who attended the hearings? The level of pressure on these people and the frustrations with those that weren't selected is tricky to overcome. Yet, offering those that were not selected to take part in an alternative platform, such as a hearing, creates a system where multiple methods of being heard exist.

The effectiveness of the associations and groups in mobilising in opposition to the proposed windfarm in the Glenmorie case study is interesting. If they had not been members of these organised groups, would they have felt as confident to participate in such a formal procedure? Is that why so few individuals forwarded a complaint or showed their support for the project? Similarly in the UN cases study, if the group that brought the complaint before the UN had not been made up of professionals, would they have made such an impact? Would they have even known about the Aarhus Convention in the first place? Would they have been overwhelmed by the undoubtedly huge amount of work and effort their objection required? The UN case study is undoubtedly an interesting example due to its uniqueness, yet it is unclear how these questions could be answered with any certainty.

Further to the above, a number of discussion points have been highlighted throughout this chapter. Specifically from the case studies, it is seen that public hearings can result in a number of outcomes including challenges to governments and big businesses; greater levels of participation and a deeper understanding of complex issues. More specifically, if it can result in policy decisions or amendments (UN and Alpac) it can thereby link collective deliberation with decision-making. This is useful when measuring impact of the outcome of the hearing; if a tangible change has been made to policy or law then the hearing has had a high level impact.

The changes made to the EIA and CIA in the Alpac hearing specifically challenged the idea that the public has little control over the decision-making process. As Novek (1993: 352) tells us; 'the Alpac proposal was substantially modified so as to be less environmentally obtrusive' due to the EIA process being lengthier, more public and more controversial.

Despite this, the provincial government went back on their decision to uphold the board's verdict and instead, supported Alpac's development. The UN hearing, similar to the Alpac hearing, concluded in a recommendation to amend UK policy on the access of information throughout the development process; in contrast to Alpac though, this decision was upheld. As the Committee highlighted, the accessibility of information is fundamental to the participant's ability to not just participate, but to participate effectively. Although these recommendations made by the Committee have in the past been largely upheld, a recommendation is not the same as being able to implement change, the impact is therefore arguably low. The impact could, however, be made greater by giving the Committee more powers.

BCCA hearing's impact is arguable given that the CA members did not recommend that the MMP system should be the replacement electoral system, which was the preferred system of the citizens in the hearings. The CA members decided to recommend the STV system instead, thus giving little indication of having listened to the participants of the hearing. The Glenmorie and Formartine hearings held in Scotland had no measurable impact outcome, and yet their purpose was to make a decision on a proposed project. Therefore the outcome of hearings does not always have to result in measurable policy outcomes, but they can, if used correctly inform and gather information. Resultantly, the outcome of a hearing can be varied and flexible. This will be looked at in more detail in the next chapter.

Not many of the hearings resulted in a vote. This is, in a way, understandable in terms of information gathering (EU or Helensburgh) but in terms of legitimising and highlighting discrepancies, voting might be a vital indicator. If citizens vote unanimously in favour of a project going ahead then the formal decision-makers reject that stance, knowing the strength of resistance to this decision could highlight the imbalance in decision-making powers. If the citizens have no impact in the outcome, it can be questioned why they are there at all. Specifically in terms of the Alpac and Formartine hearings, despite the vote being taken by the panel and the council, the decisions were overturned by the Provincial government in Alberta

and the devolved government in Aberdeen. This is a real concern. Furthermore, the purpose of the Formartine and Alpac hearings are highly questionable. Both governments were embedded within the process and had what could be described as vested interest in the projects. The SG meeting with Trump prior to the development indicates that there were agreements made. The Alberta government had invested (lots) of money into the pulp mill signifying that it was already invested in the outcome. The public hearings here could even be described as placatory or tokenistic, but more worryingly, there are elements of manipulation here in terms of who the government chose to listen to and how they went about getting the result they wanted.

Another interesting aspect which has emerged throughout this chapter is that both Helensburgh and BCCA public hearing could be described as sequential in the procedure they adopted. This arguably results in a stronger process and a more informed populace. More discussions between experts, government officials and the public can help to create tighter bonds and the feeling of empowerment from the public. The hearing in Helensburgh was the first of many consultations on the subject of wind-power. People knew what their input would be and were pleased to have a voice so early on in the development plans (witness observation). This ensured people were not angry, resentful or overly negative. The panel were experts in their field but stayed away from overly technical details and encouraged a more broad conversation on wind-power (witness observation). The BCCA led to a direct impact from the voters, with a referendum. How useful the BCCA actually was has been questioned given that the referendum did not vote for change following the CA, and 50% of people reported to know nothing about the referendum (Lang 2007: 36; Fung and Warren 2010: 54).

There is further discussion to have on the impact of citizens becoming experts in using the CA, which may then separate them from lay citizens. The pressure the CA members felt in coming up with an answer as well as the trepidation to the public's response indicates the responsibility the members felt, which may not be positive thing. The above also highlights the importance of a good chair. The key to creating trust and respect within democratic processes between the two opposing sides, and between the officials and the people, is by the assurance of a qualified experts and the non-biased professionalism of the facilitator. What can be gathered from the issue of the overturned decisions in the Alpac and Formartine hearings is that if the chair has been given the power to make the decision, then this decision should be upheld. How else is trust to be instilled in decision-makers and the democratic system? The neutrality and the

fairness which is apparent from the Compliance Committee in the UN case study is one of the key aspects of this hearing which makes it a strong example of institutionalised democracy. The next chapter will set out the application of fsQCA to this normative theory, thus triangulating these results with empirical evidence. This will support the emergent points from this chapter and illuminate new findings.

Chapter 7: Evaluating the democratic possibilities of public hearings

7.1 Introduction

Using fuzzy set Qualitative Comparative Analysis (fsQCA), this section will analyse the usefulness of the public hearing in playing a role in a deliberative setting by focusing on seven key case studies, which were set out in the fifth chapter. Aforementioned, each hearing has been picked for its own unique insight into the hearing process; and although they vary to a certain extent in purpose and process, they are intended to highlight the potential of hearings to achieve the separate elements of democratic deliberation and the fsQCA outcomes: inclusion, popular control, transparency and considered judgement. Having applied the 'Democratic Standard Enactment Index' (DSEI) to the case studies, this chapter intends to look at the configurations of conditions which lead to the above outcomes (the democratic standards) by applying the fsQCA to the scaled measurements which resulted from section 6.2. This chapter will therefore discuss the key findings which have resulted from carrying out fuzzy set analysis on the case studies and determine which configurations or 'sets' are most likely to reveal the democratic standards. In the first section a fuzzy set analysis will be carried out on the hearings. Throughout this section the conditions, which correspondent to 'independent variables' will be reintroduced and explained in terms of their role in the analysis. For inclusion the necessary elements which must be met are 'publicity'; 'notice'; 'accessibility'; 'groups in attendance'; 'mode of selection' and 'contribution'. Within popular control, the membership value of 'groups in attendance'; 'everyone's contribution welcome'; 'publically driven hearing'; 'vote'; 'chairperson' and that the 'outcome is still to be determined' will be measured. The conditions for transparency will incorporate the 'publicity around the event'; the 'level of information available'; that the 'outcome is still to be determined' and that the 'chair is reputable'. The last outcome, considered judgement will be measured by the membership it displays for 'groups in attendance', 'everyone's contribution welcome'; 'level of information available' and the 'justification offered for opinions and statements'³⁵. In the second half of the chapter, key findings from the analysis as a whole will be explored and further considerations on the case studies will be offered.

³⁵ Please refer to the DSEI model (figure 4.4) for an illustration of the conditions and outcomes which will highlight the overlap where many of the conditions can be attributed to more than one democratic norm. The set membership scale can be found in section 6.2 which offers a coherent explanation of each measurement awarded.

7.2 Truth Table Analysis

The following tables show the causal conditions necessary to outcomes inclusion, popular control, transparency and considered judgement. As Kent (2008: 10) says, interpreting output from fsQCA can be difficult as there is no single result, as would be the case in other types of analysis. The problem is that there may well be several different causal combinations which each have their own level of consistency and a unique level of coverage. Moreover, each set of conditions can change according to the frequency threshold and the level of consistency which has been selected when constructing the truth table. In this instance the consistency threshold has been set at 0.9, although as low as 0.75 and 0.8 are still viewed as having a reasonable level of consistency (Ragin 2008). By setting the consistency threshold at 0.9 it can highlight the outcome which has a higher membership score than any of the conditions. Any one condition may differ according to which other conditions it has been combined with; which is evident given that many of the conditions in each table will be paired with different conditions depending on which outcome is being analysed. For instance, 'chairperson' and 'information' are in more than one table. But within the one analysis each condition can be greatly affected by any grouping. What is particularly difficult with this analysis is that when all or most of the cases possess a causal condition, that condition becomes necessary – regardless of how trivial or limited that condition may be (Kent 2008: 9). Similarly when all the cases evidently display some degree of the outcome (which they all do) this means that all the conditions are sufficient, again, however little that impact may be.

Under Kent's (2008) recommendation, an additional analysis has been conducted while substituting inclusion for non-inclusion; popular control for non-popular control and transparency for non-transparent. Due to the high level of membership for considered judgement, there is little to be achieved by including 'non-considered judgement' as all the configurations have indicated that the conditions that would enable considered judgement were present, meaning that considered judgement is theoretically obtainable. The wording here of these outcomes is purposely not the opposite of the initial outcome. It would have been tempting to use the term 'exclusive' in opposition of inclusion but it is unlikely that hearings actively exclude people, given that it is a public event. For this reason 'non-inclusion' denotes the ease in which people can be left out without actual action being taken. This is the case for popular control - the opposite could be considered elitist or minority control but non-popular control again does not assume that action has been taken to take the power away from the

public. In terms of transparency the new outcome is referred to as non-transparent. More often than not, the issue which needs highlighting is that information or the process is not transparent *enough* to make it a truly open process. Kent (2008: 7) notes that if the conflicting or the reverse outcome is entered then a very different analysis can emerge and with that, a more insightful output which is discussed in the section below.

7.2.1 Analysis of Inclusion

Table 7.1 shows the results of a study into the causal conditions relevant to the inclusion or non-inclusion of seven hearings. Three of the hearings are chosen to represent local, EU level and international level governance. The remaining hearings include two from Scotland and two from Canada. The outcome of interest is the degree of membership that the hearings have displayed to an inclusive process. This is deciphered by the degree of membership in the sets of the following ‘publicity’ (PUB), ‘notice’ (NOT), ‘accessibility’ (ACS), ‘ groups in attendance’ (GRP), ‘selection method’ (SLT) AND ‘all contributions welcome’ (CON).

Table 7.1 Indicative truth table showing fuzzy set membership for inclusion

Row	CASES (public hearing)	PUB	NOT	ACS	GRP	SLT	CON	Y (Outcome: Inclusion)	~Y (Outcome: Non-Inclusion)
1	ALPAC	0.52	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.52	0.67	0.83	0.17
2	FORMARTINE	0.83	0.48	0.67	0.83	0.52	0.67	0.83	0.17
3	BCCA	0.67	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.52	0.67	0.83	0.17
4	GLENMORIE	0.67	0.83	0.67	0.83	0.48	0.52	0.67	0.33
5	HELENSBURGH	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.52	0.67	0.67	0.33
6	UN	0.48	0.83	0.48	0.48	0.17	0.83	0.33	0.67
7	EU	0.48	0.83	0.67	0.67	0.48	0.67	0.67	0.33

The data has then been entered into the fsQCA software. The next table shows the data from table 7.2 after it has been run through the truth table algorithm. Inclusion was selected for the outcome and the sets into the causal conditions. Table 7.2 shows the 2k possible combinations of the 6 causal conditions and each configuration is in a separate row. k is the number of causal conditions included in the model.

Table 7.2 The completed truth table for inclusion

Row	pub	not	acs	grp	slt	con	No.	Y (Outcome: Inclusion)	raw consist.	PRI consist.	Case(s)
1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2
2	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	1,3,5
3	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0.955882	0.904459	4
4	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0.943182	0.814815	7
5	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0.89785	0	6

Table 7.2 shows that there were 5 or more possible logical configurations. A score of ‘1’ demonstrates the full or partial membership of a condition or outcome; 0 reflects the absence of any condition or outcome³⁶. The ‘0’ gives the measurement of consistency which, as explained in section 4.7, measures the degree in which a relation of necessity or sufficiency between a causal condition(s) and an outcome is met within any data set (Legewie 2013: 11). This means that the membership score is higher in the outcome than the causal combination, which is weighted in relevance of each case. The number section (No.) shows how many cases are specific to that causal combination.

To explain further, table 7.2 highlights that there are three hearings demonstrating the same causal combination: Alpac, the BCCA and Helensburgh. All the other configurations are displayed by just one case. The three cases sharing a configuration, along with the Formartine hearing, have displayed the conditions which could lead to the presence of the outcome ‘inclusion’. Glenmorie and the EU hearing have both displayed different configurations which have led to a lower raw consist of 0.96 and 0.94 respectively. Therefore the top 4 configurations contain a combination of conditions which indicate that the process has the potential to be inclusive. The condition CON (contribution) is evident in all cases which may specify that it was necessary for the outcome. However, given that it is present in the hearing which has theoretically not been inclusive means that it is not sufficient. On the other hand, NOT (notice) and SLT (selection) are not necessary for the outcome. Moreover, PUB ‘publicity’ and SLT are not evident in one of the sets, and yet the membership is still above the threshold. The UN hearing has not resulted in the presence of the outcome, and has therefore been allocated a ‘0’. With a raw consist score of 0.898 it is below the consistency score which is below the cut off for the consistency score which, as previously explained, has been set at 0.9, although it should be noted that as low as 0.75 is acceptable (Ragin 2008). Arguably the UN case shows too much inconsistency, but only by a squeeze. The next step to look at is the truth table analysis. Both

³⁶ All output can be found in appendix 3.

the least and most parsimonious solutions have been run for all the tables in order to see if a simplified configuration becomes apparent, or if it is necessary to look a little deeper. Having said that, the small-*n* makes it unlikely that the most parsimonious will yield results of interest. The least parsimonious configuration can be seen in the table below.

Table 7.3 Sufficiency analysis solutions for outcome 'inclusion'

frequency cutoff: 1.000000
consistency cutoff: 0.943182

	raw coverage	unique coverage	consistency
not*acs*grp*~slt*con	0.681159	0.049689	0.956395
pub*acs*grp*slt*con	0.664596	0.033126	1.000000
solution coverage:	0.714286		
solution consistency:	0.985333		

A further explanatory factor, which can be found in table 7.3, is the solution consistency and coverage. As van der Heijden explains (2015: 582), '...a 'consistency score' helps the researcher to understand how well a finding reflects the empirical data, while a 'coverage score' helps the researcher to understand how much of the empirical data are explained by the causal recipes uncovered'. There are three different types of coverage: first the 'solution coverage' which indicates how much is explained by the solution term; the second 'raw coverage' shows how much of the outcome can be explained by a particular configuration, and the third; the 'unique coverage' shows how far, or which share, can be exclusively explained by that particular combination. The coverage therefore helps to determine how much of the outcome can be explained by that configuration (Wagemann and Schneider 2007: 7). Kent (2008: 4) also remarks that often the consistency and coverage may appear to work against each other as it is common for one to be high while the other low and vice versa.

The first column shows that the raw coverage of each configuration is 0.68 for the first and 0.66 for the second. This indicates the extent to which the outcome can be explained by the configuration. If this is a low score then this indicates that the causal combination is less empirically relevant (Legewie 2013: 20). It is usually the case that the higher raw coverage configuration is the main one. The second column 'unique coverage' shows how many of the

cases can be explained by this configuration. At this point the first combination has a unique coverage of 0.04 and the second at 0.03. This is consistent with the results from the first column. With this, the researcher can decipher any unique configurations which do not require any other combinations to offer explanations for the outcome. A low score is not unexpected, usually lower than 0.15 (Legewie 2013: 21). The final column is the consistency score for each configuration. It is 0.96 for the first and 1.0 for the second. This means that the second combination covers more cases than the first, ie the configuration has been demonstrated in one or more cases. The solution consistency is set at 0.96 and the solution coverage at 0.7, in this instance the consistency is above the expected threshold of above 0.9, as is the coverage which is expected to be above 0.5. The coverage is ‘simply the overlap expressed as a proportion of the sum of the membership score in the outcome’ (Ragin 2008: 57). Or in other words, the coverage here is measuring how well the causal expression is explaining the outcome (Kent 2008: 4) and is providing a ‘measure of empirical relevance’ (Legewie 2013: 11).

From the output in table 7.3 it is apparent that the outcome was obtained through two different configurations. The least parsimonious configurations are:

not*acs*grp*~slt*con =Y

and

pub*acs*grp*slt*con =Y

(here * denotes the intersection of sets. If the condition was absent this is indicated by ~).

This indicates that ‘not’ (notice) is not necessary for the outcome to be achieved. The absence of ‘pub’ (publicity) in the first and ‘not’ in the second shows that they are interchangeable. Yet if ‘not’ is present it would seem that the selection process ‘slt’ will have a low membership. Therefore, it is apparent that the absence of ‘not’ is part of the combination in determining the outcome in the first combination which would indicate that it is not necessary for the outcome. Using this logic and determining that 2 other cases achieved the outcome; one where ‘slt’ is absent, and the other without ‘pub’ or ‘slt’. The configuration which features all the conditions, apart from ‘not’, has a solution coverage of 0.66. But the first with the combination of notice, accessibility, groups and contribution has the slightly higher score of 0.68. However, as said ‘not’ cannot be said to hold a strong value in the configuration as Formartine achieved inclusion without it. So it can be concluded that the conditions with the most value in the configuration are accessibility, variety of groups and contribution from all. All the case studies which

achieved the outcome included high membership of three conditions. The UN case study, which is the only one which did not show evidence of inclusiveness, does not display a high enough level of accessibility and contribution but does show a high level of membership for groups. This would indicate the combination of these three is sufficient but not necessary (INUS) to the outcome (Mackie 1965: 246). However, as Ryan and Smith (2012: 107) tell us, for a small-n study of about 6 or 7 cases, as this is, the consistency would have to be really high – they say 1. It is apparent that all the conditions being present will lead to the outcome, as it has for Alpac, BCCA and Helensburgh. Yet the other two cases narrow down the sufficient combinations. Therefore, the combinations of variables that lead to the outcome can be simplified to:

$Acs * grp * con = Y$ (if y is the outcome).

This means that the accessibility to the process, the groups involved in the hearing and the diversity of the contributions are the core conditions in achieving an inclusive process. The UN process had limited accessibility, whether this be due to where it was held or how people had heard about the process. Despite the hearing being held to discuss a very controversial issue effecting Scotland, those that were included was, to some extent, limited. And yet, if the process has been live streamed or informed by a sequential process of hearings held at a lower level, perhaps at national or local level prior to this hearing; it may have overcome this lack of inclusivity. Nevertheless, it must be acknowledged that it was exactly this lack of consultation at local level which led to the hearing in the first place. The three hearings that display all the conditions were by no means flawless but in terms of including the wider population and groups, they did well. Alpac used many hearings in lots of different areas to ensure that those affected were involved. The BCCA was unique in its sequential characteristics. It was fed by a citizens' jury and again was held in more than one location. The final hearing which had high membership for all the conditions was the Helensburgh hearing. This was a local hearing and it is possible that local hearings find it easier to tick the boxes which ensure inclusivity. However, that is not to say that the process is effective or helps shape the democratic policy-making process as it is held at such a low level of governance.

Most notably, the analysis which was run indicates that there is no difference between the least and most parsimonious. The most parsimonious analysis means that the remainders have been included in the analysis (the output for this can be found in the appendices). The solution coverage is still 0.7. If all five conditions are present then this is sufficient to ensure that

inclusion has been obtained. However, the absence or presence of a slt (specific selection process) makes little difference to the outcome of the analysis. Furthermore in the top configuration not (notice) is present and in the second it is absent. Whereas pub (publicity) is absent in the first but present in the second – the two appear to be interchangeable. So it could be changed to just include notice, accessibility, diverse groups and contribution.

A further exploratory way to analyse the findings is to consider which conditions led to the process being non-inclusive. For this, the least parsimonious analysis is likely to produce the more insightful output, as the simplified analysis can sometimes explain very little, specifically in a small~n study such as this. Highlighting where the UN process went wrong, or where mistakes can be avoided in the future, is useful. Considering the outcome as non-inclusive can help determine if these conditions are necessary to the outcome. In this case there is only one configuration that leads to this outcome and it includes the absence of 4 conditions: ~pub*not*~acs*~grp*~slt*con. In the output showing the least parsimonious analysis, publicity, accessibility, groups representation and a selection process were absent which led to a non-inclusive process, which was regardless of whether notice was given and contributions are all welcome. For this the solution coverage is 0.86. The configuration could thus be simplified to not*con=Y, if Y is non-inclusion. This is particularly interesting as it would seem that 'con' had been a significant factor in achieving the outcome but by consulting the table and non-inclusion configuration, 'con' was also present in this hearing. This condition is part of both configurations which may indicate how important it is to get the contribution of all; if conjoined with notice it makes little difference in the inclusiveness of the process. Yet if contribution is connected with a variety of groups and accessibility, the result is an inclusive process as it ensured that people attend the hearing and they are included once there.

7.2.2 Analysis on Popular Control

Table 7.4 shows the degree of membership in the sets of the following 'groups in attendance' (GRP), 'everyone's contribution welcome' (CON), 'publically driven hearing by public' (PUBDRI), 'vote' (VOTE), 'chairperson' (CHR) AND 'outcome still to be determined' (OTCM).

Table 7.4 Indicative truth table showing fuzzy set membership for popular control

Row	CASES (public hearing)	GRP	CON	PUBDRI	VOTE	CHR	OTCM	Y (Outcome: Popular Control)	~Y (Outcome: Non-Popular Control)
1	ALPAC	0.83	0.67	0.83	0.17	0.48	0.33	0.48	0.52
2	FORMARTINE	0.83	0.67	0.33	0.17	0.17	0.83	0.33	0.67
3	BCCA	0.83	0.67	0.48	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.17
4	GLENMORIE	0.83	0.52	0.48	0.17	0.48	0.52	0.52	0.48
5	HELENSBURGH	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.52	0.52	0.83	0.48	0.52
6	UN	0.48	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.33	0.67	0.33
7	EU	0.67	0.67	0.48	0.17	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.17

Here, the most notable observation is that ‘vote’ is absent in 4 of the seven hearings. However, this can be attributed to the point in the decision-making process that the hearing takes place. For instance, if the purpose of the hearing is information gathering or reviewing an already implemented decision, then the absence of a vote is unremarkable. Within the Alpac and the UN hearings the fact that the issue being discussed was fairly assured to go in a certain way³⁷, may mean that OTCM could be a distinguishing factor in the analysis.

Table 7.5 The completed truth table for popular control

Row	grp	con	pubdri	vote	chr	otcm	No.	Y (Outcome: Popular Control)	raw consist.	PRI consist.	Case(s)
1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	6
2	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	7
3	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3
4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.980099	0.885714	5
5	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0.978378	0	1
6	1	1	0	0	0	1	2	0	0.845455	0.105263	2,4

In this table (7.5) only one causal configuration has fallen under the 0.9 consistency threshold with 0.85. This applies to two of the public hearings; Formartine and Glenmorie. This does not indicate a good result for the Scottish public hearing process as these hearings follow very specific, and therefore similar, procedures. Participants in these hearings had a low level of control over the hearing being held; over the outcome and the chair was not suitably neutral or qualified. Crucially though, the Alpac hearing has had an interesting result. While displaying the presence of popular control with a raw consist of 0.98, it does not have high membership for vote, chr or otcm. The PRI consist (Proportional Reduction in Inconsistency), which highlights discrepancies within the data and works as a corrector by penalising major inconsistencies, which can be seen to be the case here. Erkens and Van der Stede (2013) and

³⁷ As stated in the case studies chapter this was because in the UN case, the committee was going to find in favour of the citizen group or the UK government. In the Alpac case the development was going to go ahead or not, there was little manoeuvrability for those involved.

van der Heijden (2015) believe that this is a more accurate score. The only hearing which displayed all the conditions is the Helensburgh hearing in row 4. Again a positive result for a local hearing. Although it may be easier to have a level of popular control at the local level. It has a consistency score of 0.98. The three results that have a consistency score of 1 are the UN hearing, EU and the BCCA. Yet, the UN hearing has a low membership of groups involved and a low level of control over the outcome of the hearing. Although the EU was a transnational process the groups that were involved was still diverse and encompassing both in nationality and areas of knowledge. The process was not driven by the public or voted on afterwards. The BCCA was not publically driven but displayed high membership of the rest of the conditions. Whether the hearings have been driven by the public does not seem to impact on a positive outcome. Nor does the combination of publically driven and no vote impact in one of the causal configurations. Again, the contribution of participants within the hearing is consistent in being present in the cases.

Table 7.6 Sufficiency analysis solutions for outcome 'popular control'

frequency cutoff: 1.000000
consistency cutoff: 0.978378

	raw coverage	unique coverage	consistency
grp*con*~pubdri*chr*otcm	0.570048	0.084541	1.000000
grp*con*vote*chr*otcm	0.521739	0.072464	0.981818
grp*con*pubdri*~vote*~chr*~otcm	0.437198	0.074879	0.978378
~grp*con*pubdri*vote*chr*~otcm	0.371981	0.045894	1.000000
solution coverage:	0.801932		
solution consistency:	0.976471		

Within popular control there are more configurations which result in the outcome than for inclusion. It is clear that a number of combinations are effectual in obtaining popular control according to the least parsimonious analysis. The first configuration with the highest level of consistency (1.0), as well as a unique coverage of 0.08 and a raw coverage of 0.57, is the combination of groups in attendance, contributions, that has not been publically driven, with a neutral qualified chair and a outcome than has not already been decided leads to a hypothetically high level of popular control. This has excluded voting at the end of the process $grp*con*~pubdri*chr*otcm$. The next combination is group, contribution, voting with a neutral chair and an unpredictable outcome: $grp*con*vote*chr*otcm=Y$. As can be seen from

the table above, there are two more configurations of conditions which lead to a positive level of membership for popular control. None of the configurations are obtaining a high score for raw or unique coverage which indicates first that they are not displaying a high level of empirical relevance, ie the configurations are not determining the outcome; and second that there is few cases that can be assigned to the combination of conditions. This was evident in the truth table as it illustrates that two cases have been assigned 0 minimising the data available for the fuzzy set software to consider. Having said that, the consistency scores are high, all above 0.97 and two at 1.0 meaning that there are cases that do display the combination accordingly. In terms of which configuration is most effective it would be $grp*con*\sim pubdri*chr*otcm=Y$ as it has a raw coverage of 0.57. Which can then be simplified to $grp*con*chr*otcm=Y$. The hearing that encompasses this is the EU case study.

In terms of the most parsimonious analysis. It would seem that the chair is the only sufficient condition. The solution coverage is 0.95 which is acceptable but the solution consistency has fallen below 1.0 which can indicate that one or more of the cases do not display the outcome – as seen in the truth table. And yet it is significantly higher than in the least parsimonious analysis where the coverage is 0.8. The solution coverage has remained fairly consistent at 0.99 and 0.85. If the hearing was driven by the public ‘pubdri’ then this has a direct effect on the outcome; but it is neither sufficient nor necessary, with only a 0.82 raw consistency. When the same analysis is run for non-popular control quite a different story emerges. The solution coverage is higher here than in the least parsimonious analysis at 0.88 instead of 0.8. There were only 4 configurations with a consistency over 0.9. The results are different in terms of conditions which could lead to a lack of popular control. Interestingly the unique coverage scores are high in comparison to the popular control analysis. This means that there are interrelated observations, probably from an overlap between configurations.

$grp*con*\sim pubdri*\sim vote*\sim chr*otcm$
 $grp*con*pubdri*\sim vote*\sim chr*\sim otcm$

Thus this can be simplified to:
 $Grp*con=Y$ (if Y is non-popular control)

The results from the fsQCA indicate that the Glenmorie hearing had the lowest ability to create high levels of popular control. It did not obtain high scores of membership for being driven by the public or for including a vote as part of the process, despite the hearing resulting in a

recommendation on a development in the area where the hearing was held and finally, a low score for having a reliably neutral chair. It is interesting that the chair is featuring so prominently in both inclusion and popular control. Yet, for this outcome, it is apparent that for the hearing to avoid non-popular control it is important in part, for it to be publically driven. One of the biggest criticisms of hearings is that they are held too late in the decision-making process, this can show evidence of why an open agenda may be a vital part of ensuring hearings are driven by popular control. Moreover the lack of a vote has also been highlighted as sufficient in reaching non-popular control. This is probably a fairly obvious assumption, but considering how rarely hearings make use of voting this could indicate that hearings are generally non-inclusive. Finally, the outcome of the hearing being established prior to its completion is a part of a non-inclusive process, in this instance the hearing would be merely tokenistic. Alternatively, similarly to ‘inclusion’ it is possible that hearings would need linked with another institution or process which could set the agenda for the hearing democratically in a way that enhances popular control, such as a citizens’ assembly or a poll.

7.2.3 Analysis on Transparency

Table 7.7 shows the degree of membership in the sets of the following; ‘publicity’ (PUB), ‘information available to all throughout the process’ (INFO), ‘outcome still to be determined’ (OTCM) AND ‘chairperson’ (CHR).

Table 7.7 Indicative truth table showing fuzzy set membership for transparency

Row	CASES (public hearing)	PUB	INFO	OTCM	CHR	Y (Outcome: Transparency)	~Y (Outcome: Non-Transparency)
1	ALPAC	0.52	0.17	0.33	0.48	0.33	0.67
2	FORMARTINE	0.83	0.67	0.83	0.17	0.67	0.33
3	BCCA	0.67	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.17
4	GLENMORIE	0.67	0.83	0.52	0.48	0.67	0.33
5	HELENSBURGH	0.67	0.67	0.83	0.52	0.52	0.48
6	UN	0.48	0.67	0.33	0.83	0.52	0.48
7	EU	0.48	0.48	0.83	0.83	0.67	0.33

Here it can be seen that the low scores of the publicity, information available and the outcome has led to a low level of transparency for the Alpac hearing, and the publicity and information for the EU case study is noticeably lower than many of the other conditions membership. The chair for three of the cases was not deemed neutral or qualified; all the hearings are at a

comparable level of governance – for the federal government of Canada and the decentralised power of Scotland. If a chair is not obviously neutral it can impact heavily on the transparency of the hearing and subsequently, the participants trust in that process. At this level (sub-national), hearings are often accused of tokenism or placation; understandably this is the case for the Formartine and Alpac hearing where both government bodies went against public opinion and the conclusions of the hearings and instead aligned themselves with the developers. Having said that, the Formartine hearing has demonstrated high membership levels of pub, info and otcn thus resulting in a positive outcome for transparency. The next table shows the resultant ‘recipes’ for establishing transparency in an event.

Table 7.8 The completed truth table for transparency

Row	pub	info	otcn	chr	No.	Y (Outcome: Transparency)	raw consist.	PRI consist.	Case(s)
1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	7
2	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	6
3	1	1	1	0	2	1	1	1	2,4
4	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	3,5
5	1	0	0	0	1	0	0.876623	0	1

This time two hearings are displaying the same configuration. Table 7.8 shows that the lowest consistency score is Alpac. It is therefore the only hearing which is below the consistency threshold. All the other hearings demonstrated the ability to enact the democratic norms. The Formartine and Glenmorie saw the same mix of conditions which led to the outcome – all but the neutral chair, as stated above. The similarity in conditions again is not surprising as both hearings are from Scotland and held at the same level of governance, and yet what can be taken from the decisions made as a result of these hearings, as well as the public feeling following the process – judging by the press coverage and written documents following them – they were in many ways very different processes. The BCCA and the Helensburgh hearing also shared the presence of the same conditions leading to the outcome transparency. Yet in this instance they both had created a hearing which embodied all the democratic norms necessary for this outcome. Again, as an information session (Helensburgh) and the information gathering (BCCA) transparency should not have been a key issue here as they weren’t focused on a particular development or something that could result in conflict. However, the truth table highlights and reinforces the suggestion that deliberative or participatory decision-making processes held close to communities are most effectual at enacting democratic norms and the

value of utilising public hearings in a deliberative sequence, as in the BCCA example, requires closer attention which will be given here.

Table 7.9 Sufficiency analysis solutions for outcome 'transparency'

frequency cutoff: 1.000000
consistency cutoff: 1.000000

	raw coverage	unique coverage	consistency
pub*info*otcm	0.798100	0.327791	0.957265
~pub*info*~otcm*chr	0.403800	0.045131	1.000000
~pub*~info*otcm*chr	0.479810	0.047506	1.000000
solution coverage:	0.890736		
solution consistency:	0.961538		

Table 7.9 demonstrates that there are 3 possible formations of the conditions which lead to the presence of the outcome. The configuration in the 'least parsimonious' analysis would suggest that the chair has little impact on the level of transparency, which is obtained through:

$$\text{pub*info*otcm} = Y$$

This configuration has the highest raw coverage at 0.798. It also displays the highest unique coverage at 0.3. Yet the consistency is the only set that is not displaying 1.0 membership score but instead 0.96. However, the following configurations shown in table 7.9 would suggest that no one condition has more influence than the others. Both the solution's scores are above 0.7, which means they are displaying the combined consistency of the causal configurations at 0.96 and the proportion of membership in the outcome, which can be explained by membership of the combinations the solution coverage which is 0.89.

The above configuration applies to the cases Formartine and Glenmorie. As discussed, both are Scottish public hearings and similar in process. However, the EU case study has achieved the outcome with only the otc*chr as conditions. Admittedly the raw coverage is 0.48, while the first combination is 0.798. The final configuration is info*chr at 0.41. This indicates that the chr is necessary when pub and info are not present. Yet, the chr is not sufficient on its own. As evident from the UN case study, the transparency and accessibility of information is key, which was the resounding conclusion made by the Compliance Committee. Edinburgh Council, and in turn the UK, should have made the information regarding the project public property as, and when, the new information came into fruition. In order to challenge

representatives or 'trusted' experts, the public should be utilised as another democratic body able to scrutinise decisions. Without the necessary information, this was not possible for the Moray Feu Traffic Subcommittee. The solution coverage is 0.89 and the solution consistency is 0.96 showing that each are displaying a reasonable level. The consistency is well above the 0.9 threshold and the coverage is giving a reasonable measure of empirical relevance to the outcome.

To dig a bit deeper, the most parsimonious analysis reveals further explanatory factors. This is done by including the remainders (of which there is only one) as a 'don't care'. The most parsimonious outcome explains that there is just one condition necessary to the outcome: for one: otcn, and the other: info. This analysis is maybe too simplistic and yet, as seen from table 7.9, these are the conditions which resulted in the outcome, either together or alternately. When info is missing but otcn is present, the outcome is still achieved (EU). Conversely though, when otcn is missing but info present, the outcome nonetheless is achieved (UN). Yet when both are missing, the outcome is not evident above the 0.9 threshold. It would seem that either:

Info+otcn=Y

These conditions are necessary for the outcome. And yet they are not sufficient and therefore must be part of a configuration which includes the presence of conditions chr or pub.

The analysis for non-transparency gives three different formations of conditions which result in the outcome. The absence of a determined outcome as one of the conditions seems to be able to lead to a lack of transparency, alongside limits on information and non-bias chair. Publicity does not seem to make much impact either way. This time the solution coverage is higher when looking at transparency as the outcome and not the opposite at 0.84 and the solution consistency is 0.91. The most useful collaboration of conditions is no publicity, no information but an open outcome and a good chair – this combination leads to non-transparency with a score of 0.656. This makes sense as publicity and information is vital to transparency within democratic processes. Therefore what can be concluded from this analysis is that a determined outcome and information which is accessible leads to a transparent process. It would appear that the level of transparency in all but the Alpac hearing was of a suitable level thus suggesting that public hearings have the potential to enact this democratic standard. The final democratic norm will be looked at next.

7.2.4 Analysis on Considered Judgement

Table 7.10 shows the degree of membership in the sets of the following ‘groups in attendance’ (GRP), ‘everyone’s contribution welcome’ (CON), ‘information available to all throughout the process’ (INFO), AND ‘level of justification’ (JSTF).

Table 7.10 Indicative truth table showing fuzzy set membership for considered judgement

Row	CASES (public hearing)	GRP	CON	INFO	JSTF	Y (Outcome: Considered Judgement)	~Y (Outcome: Non-Considered Judgement)
1	ALPAC	0.83	0.67	0.17	0.67	0.52	0.48
2	FORMARTINE	0.83	0.67	0.67	0.83	0.83	0.17
3	BCCA	0.83	0.67	0.83	0.52	0.67	0.33
4	GLENMORIE	0.83	0.52	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.17
5	HELENSBURGH	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.33
6	UN	0.48	0.83	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.33
7	EU	0.67	0.67	0.48	0.83	0.67	0.33

The membership of the condition ‘grp’ is high for all the hearings apart from in the UN hearing. As discussed, a variety of groups is necessary for inclusion and popular control; for considered judgement this is a fundamental necessity to ensure that the participants in any process contains the ability to consider a variety of viewpoints by those perspectives being represented. Various actors, forwarding a plethora of opinions expands the capacity for considered judgement as actors are encouraged to justify their political stances and explain their positions. In order for this to be legitimate, as many as possible within the process should be able to contribute to the discussion. As the table above shows, the contribution to the discussion from all the groups is high. It must be acknowledged however, that there is little to prove that all these opinions were taken into consideration. In Alpac, Glenmorie and Formartine, the opinions forwarded are designed to guide a decision on whether to go forward with a particular development – in two out of three of the hearings the developments went forward despite sizeable public opposition. The BCCA and the UN, as a sequential democratic innovation and a legislative hearing respectively, are making judgments based on the evidence presented to them, as it comes in. The Helensburgh hearing and the EU are utilised in a different fashion; they are an exercise in information gathering where the others are primarily problem solving.

The information that the attendees are privy to is crucial to how considered judgement can be utilised and focused toward forwarding practical and effective arguments or discussion points. Again, information throughout the processes has been high throughout. This means not only

that attendees are informed throughout the process - about the process and about the development/issue - but this can be added to the varied perspectives and specific knowledge that each actor is bringing to the process. It is evident that all the outcomes resulted in an adequate degree of membership; yet the table below shows some different results.

Table 7.11 The completed truth table for considered judgement

Row	grp	con	info	jstf	No.	Y (Outcome: Considered Judgement)	raw consist.	PRI consist.	Case(s)
1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
2	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	2,3,4,5
3	1	1	0	1	2	1	0.940476	0.722222	1,7

The EC hearing and the Alpac hearing are the cases with the lowest outcome membership, which specifically, in terms of the EU hearing is surprising. The condition with the lowest membership is information which may indicate that for considered judgement to be achieved this is a necessary condition. As the EU hearing was an information gathering event designed to 'problem solve' the issue of Advanced Manufacturing, it would not have been required to circulate information on the issue amongst the participants in the same way that would be vital to the other hearing. Many of the participants would have been attending the process due to their prowess in the field and what they could contribute to the discussion; which may explain why information was readily available to the public and the wider audience, yet it was not advertised or actively distributed more widely. Despite the hearings both achieving high membership of all other conditions, this has been enough to lead to a lower membership of considered judgement, yet still above the set threshold.

When looking at the justification measure, there is evidence to suggest that deliberation did occur. The BCCA hearing received the lowest membership score for this with 0.52. All the other hearings including Glenmorie, Formartine and the EU all received high scores (0.83). If an explanation could be ventured - these high membership scores are arguably due to public hearings being announced early, giving individuals and groups enough time to organise, mobilise and prepare which account for the high justification in the Glenmorie and the EU hearing. And yet, Formartine did not get a strong membership score in terms of the notice given, despite rating high on the justification. Hearings are not like mini-publics where there is often time between the stages of the process to reflect and weigh up information and discussions. Therefore the notice period, where the hearing is announced and individuals are

made aware of the agenda, is the time where participants will ready themselves for the process. This space is important as it may shape the way citizens approach the procedure, thus impact on how able they are to utilise considered judgment. Admittedly on its own the justification measurement gives little indication of ones considered judgement, or more specifically ones capacity for considered judgement, but in conjunction with the other values it is an important reflection period - particularly if the hearing follows a connecting mini-public, as it did in the BCCA example.

Hearings can differ from deliberative institutions here where, in some cases, the participants do not know what they will be discussing until they enter the process. This gives them little time for independent research; which could be detrimental to independent preference transformation. In mini-publics information can be provided through an expert panel and/or written documents, yet, if participants are provided with information solely through the discretion of the organisers - however non-biased and independent that information - there is a danger that organisers are impressing their views upon the participants. Admittedly there is nothing preventing the participants of mini-publics to seek extra information themselves. Again though, this is another way that public hearings diverge from other consultations. Having said that, it must be acknowledged that most mini-publics do leave time for individuals to prepare themselves mentally between the stages of the process. Yet, hearings are one of the only consultation processes which allow individuals to enter the process ready for dialogue³⁸. This is because the agenda is known to all prior to the process, not only known, it may have been set by the public. Knowing the agenda and being given a chance to mentally prepare for such a process, whether that be in opposition or in support; as an individual or as part of a mobilised organisation, can bring a different dimension to the participatory process.

This can, of course, be a detrimental aspect of the hearing process too. People are less likely to enter the process with an open mind. Participants may well be put off by the readiness and the preparation undertaken by others. Terminology and arguments put forward by organised groups may be beyond the comprehension of others that have just 'turned up' to the event with a view to learning or gathering information. Many people may have the same access to resources of time, research skills, money etc. Marginalisation in these cases are far more

³⁸ The Citizens' Assemblies held in British Columbia, Ontario and the Netherlands all had a widely known agenda on electoral reform.

apparent that everyone entering on an even keel. This could in some way explain for the lack of individual participants in the Glenmorie hearing, where most people were represented by a group, such as Save Our Straths; Scottish Rights of Way and Access Society and the Mountaineering Council of Scotland.

What is apparent from the table above (7.11) is the capacity of hearings to host considered judgment. The potential for this is evident – in the diversity of groups which attend; the input of those groups; the information those attendees are privy to, and finally; the speech acts which were analysed. Admittedly the high speech acts could also be a sign that hearings only play host to certain groups of citizens resulting in them being exclusive, or intimidating for lay participants. However, the hearings that have been looked at all showed the flexibility of individuals to mobilise and effect change. Most specifically through associations, as particularly demonstrated by the Glenmorie hearing. The hearing process allows associations to enter the discursive arena in a way that some deliberative institutions, such as citizens’ juries, do not. On the other hand, this can be a negative thing as fewer people will be open to transferring their preferences or taking on board other people’s views. Yet again though, associations do in some ways counter the power of the elite within these institutions. The comradery of communities in the examples of the Formartine and Alpac hearings demonstrate the ability of citizens to challenge unpopular and destructive developments and developers which need to listen to the local people, specifically in terms of their untapped expertise.

Table 7.12 Sufficiency analysis solutions for outcome ‘considered judgement’

frequency cutoff: 1.000000
consistency cutoff: 0.940476

	raw coverage	unique coverage	consistency
grp*con*jstf	0.833333	0.111111	0.964286
con*info*jstf	0.761317	0.039095	1.000000
solution coverage:	0.872428		
solution consistency:	0.965831		

Table 7.12 shows that there are two different formulations.

Grp*con*jstf+con*info*jstf=Y

In the first combination info is not part of the combination and in the second, grp is not required. The first combination leads to a higher level of raw coverage of 0.83. However, the table above shows that the outcome with a raw consistency of 0.94 is lower than the other combinations. It is safe to assume then that the various groups is not a necessary factor of reaching the outcome. It is the UN case study which is demonstrating this combination. The raw coverage is 0.76 and the unique coverage 0.039 which would highlight the necessity of information, although this outcome can still be achieved without 'info' therefore it is not sufficient. It would appear that contribution of many actors and the justification of the opinions offered are the key conditions required for considered judgement to be enacted. Yet, each formulation requires the assistance of either a mixed group (grp) or the freedom of accessibility to information (info), which are an important part of enacting considered judgment effectively. In order to offer a deeper insight into this democratic standard would require a larger sample, including case studies that did not show membership of all the conditions. This would enable this research to consider in more detail and offer more robust evidence into what prevents a hearing from assisting discussion which embodies considered judgement. Furthermore, it is necessary to remember that the justification of opinions has been measured through minutes from hearings rather than transcripts. The validity of the measurement is therefore not as reliable as it could have been – or could be if the procedural requirements of hearings demanded better recordings of the process being undertaken. The next section will draw together and discuss the key findings.

7.3 Key Findings and Recommendations

The fsQCA results have revealed some interesting findings. This section will offer a discussion of these results and offer some early recommendations for future public hearings. In terms of inclusion, the only hearing that was not considered to hold a high level of membership was the UN hearing. It is important to state that despite this, it still held a degree of membership. The process included a diverse group of people who congregated to decide on an important matter. To correct this would merely have required a recording or transcription of sorts. Admittedly this measurement cannot control for internal exclusion; it is not obvious who was there and was, for one reason or another, restricted from attending. The resultant configuration which gained the best outcome included the conditions: easy access to the process; a variety of groups in attendance; and for all participants to make contributions. Ensuring these conditions are present is not necessarily easy but there are areas which can help support this. Enabling people to access the process by ensuring the location is sensible and the time is suitable is a start.

Furthermore, using language which is appropriate for the attendees is important, including avoiding the use of overly technical terminology and accommodating those that are afflicted by hearing/visual problems. The increased accessibility that these aspects afford will also help to get a more diverse group of people to attend. Extending an invitation to people that would not normally attend would help here too. It is, or should be, easy to open the floor to those that wish to contribute. Expecting citizens to submit their testimonies prior to the hearing may discourage contributions from those that did not know enough before the event or those whose thoughts are provoked by the process. It is the chair's responsibility to make sure as many people who wish can speak, and in turn, those that do, do not dominate proceedings.

For popular control the most effective configuration is: a variety of groups; everyone makes a contribution; a neutral/ qualified chair and that the outcome be known to all prior to the event. That the hearing was publically driven or that participants voted did not seem to impact on the potential of the hearings to enact popular control. The condition 'otcm' could be considered the most important aspect for popular control; the participants of any democratic process should know what their input will be or the purpose of their contribution. As this research has shown, hearings can serve a number of very different purposes. They can embody both legislative or quasi-judicial characteristics; they can be held from the local to the supranational governmental level; they can be for information gathering, information giving, problems solving, adjudicating or a collaborative decision-making process; and finally, they can be a place for citizens, experts, associations and governmental representatives to listen, learn, appease, rage or debate at one another. With such a variety of uses and procedures, organisers must endeavour to inform participants of what the purpose of the hearings is, and thus what their impact will be on any outcome. Again, here the chair has been paramount to the outcome popular control. As the fsQCA has highlighted, the neutral chair is vital to the process. The Scottish cases did not have a neutral chairs at they were seen as 'political' and thus they had loyalties, if not to the government or developers, certainly not in favour of the citizens. Despite the outcome of some of the hearing being in the favour of the citizens (arguably) and not for the perceived developers, the chair has to be non-biased with no alliance and most importantly; they need to hold the power to ensure the decision is upheld. Which was not the case in the Formartine case. Some sort of constitutionally engrained power needs to be placed on the chair to ensure the hearing is not just mouth-service; which is why the neutrality and the skill of the chair is paramount. The UN example and the BCCA encapsulate this entirely. Not only were there neutral chairs who were deemed qualified and recognised for the job they performed, but they

also had committees which could verify that this neutrality was unshaken. The committee in this sense gave the participants confidence in the security and the openness of the process.

In the analysis for transparency, the necessary conditions are: information should be readily available and that the outcome known. This is at its most parsimonious. However, at its least parsimonious these conditions are necessary for the outcome and yet they are not sufficient, and therefore must be part of a configuration which includes the presence of a neutral chair or be publically driven. The distribution of the necessary information, not just to those that participate in the process, but more widely is indicative of the far reaching capacity of a hearing. Only then can people make an informed decision as to whether they should attend the process and feel that they know what is happening in their area or on a certain issue which may affect them. Again, knowing how their input will affect the outcome will naturally help to make the process more transparent. Further to this, transparency and information is also key for those who do not want to or are unable to attend the process. In terms of those who are participating, the ability to vote does not seem to make an impact here, as long as the decision-makers take on board what is said in the hearing, ostensibly they should then be qualified to make decisions on behalf of those in attendance at the hearing. Whether the process was publically driven is evidently of more worth here. Being able to call for a process which enables local people to be heard – whether in their own community or at UN level - gives a great level of power and control to citizens, who all too often are not heard by their representatives. Whether or not the community group in Edinburgh would have been as effective in this process if they had not been made up of academics and lawyers is not assured. Therefore the ability to call to attention any matter of local concern is a fundamental right of any citizen living in a democratic society; and if they are not heard, for them to be able to go over the head of a national government or have alternative methods of drawing attention to their concerns is democratic necessity.

Interestingly for considered judgement the configurations of all conditions consistently led to the desired outcome. Yet, this could also be achieved without the necessary information or in a separate configuration without a mix of groups. The level of justification offered from participants and the contribution of all participants are the necessary conditions for the outcome to be achieved but are not sufficient for that outcome. The justification is a difficult measurement to ascertain, using anecdotal evidence in many instances may well qualify as justification, but ensuring that justifying why something should be done and offering one or more reasons why this would be the case, is linked to the strength of a hearing's deliberative

quality. Based on the minutes from the hearings it was clear that the quality of the speech acts were consistently high. Those that spoke had put time and effort into their presentations and spoke at great length with varied levels of references and evidence. It is prudent to highlight that a high level of justification in conjunction with a mixture of groups in attendance assures that these are not just highly qualified and affluent people who are able to defend themselves, but inclusive and representative of wider society. The high speech act evident in this research could persuade politicians and experts that citizens are capable of contributing to the democratic process in a more effective way than just voting every five years.

Further findings and recommendations can be taken from the above discussion. A hearing needs to be held at the relevant time in the decision-making process. Admittedly this is a double-edged sword. If the consultation is done too early, information is not readily available thus transparency is problematic as there is often little information to give. It is both part of the EIA and a determining factor of it. Groups need the required time to ready themselves for the, at present, adversarial nature of the hearing. Decisions would often be disregarded through NIMBYism or a fear of the unknown. However, people would be far less likely to be emotively reactionary if they are consulted in an honest and effective way. The main critical point of a hearing is when it is held and often that is too late for participant to feel they have any real control. The understandable mistrust of developers, cooperation's, governments and experts has created a suspicious and resentful population. More needs to be done to align citizens with politicians and experts; having them work together in processes like this, where citizens' input is valued, is the first step to achieving this.

The most fundamental recommendation that can be taken from these findings is that in public hearings, as in any democratic institution, the outcome of the process needs to be known to all – whether it will end in a decision, a vote, if it is an information gathering or information giving process. In addition it must be relied upon that if the outcome is expected to be a decision, it must be known to all who have the power to make that decision. Overturning a decision, such as it was in the Alpac and Formartine hearings, is counter-productive to any democratic process or relationship between the governed and the governors. The public will not enter the process with an open mind if the type of process is deemed weak; inconclusive or there is a lack of trust. The 'virtuous cycle' cannot be something that is restricted to civic society; people need

to learn to trust decision-makers. The first step to achieving this is for the public to see the democratic process more clearly and to be a part of it.

In addition, recordings must be taken of the public hearing process. This will increase transparency and openness and thus trust. This could include recording the proceeding with a recorder or videoing it, and live streaming them or at least archived for future use. Alternatively transcriptions would be acceptable in a closed session. Minutes are not adequate if hearings hope to keep up with the increasingly effectual democratic innovations in informing deliberative literature. Hearings should be live streamed or televised as a matter of practice. Online TV channels can be effectively utilised here. A detailed description of who attended and who contributed. At present, there is no acknowledgement of any gender, generational or ethnic divide during any of these hearings. In order to highlight, and thus correct the missing demographic from these hearing, it is crucial to determine who is missing; in terms of gender, class, age, ethnicity. However, representation is not useful if all those affected do not contribute. Associations can help in this instance to engage shy or less able participants by representing them if they choose.

Providing an arena for wider macro level discussion which exists in communities, associations, transnationally and intergenerationally can harvest it into a useful and collaborative decision-making process, where real decisions are made. Following the actions of the Glenmorie hearing, encouraging or facilitating citizens to enter a deliberative process as part of an association may help to ensure that they are less vulnerable to coercion or manipulation, and could arguably counter the power of the state. As discussed, knowing the agenda beforehand may ensure that individuals can collate their own information; avoiding the danger of being 'led' by experts or having the agenda set firmly by organisers. This also helps to give individuals time to mobilise into groups if they see this as suitable. This should not however, undermine the power of an individual participant who does not wish to be part of a group. This is undoubtedly difficult to control for.

A final finding is that public hearings have the potential to host deliberation and result in decisions in a unique way, specifically by bringing experts, government officials and citizens together. Throughout this chapter it has been evident that the variety of groups which have attended the hearings has been wide-reaching and diverse. This is incredibly useful in terms of combining local knowledge, with expert understanding and policy planning. There is an

argument to be made that citizens are more likely to accept decisions made when they are part of the deliberation but the same argument could apply to politicians. If they see the formulation of arguments and open themselves up to conflicting perspectives they would open themselves up to other possibilities. The cycle of trust can be taken into the hearing process as the different groups watch and learn from one another.

7.4 Conclusion

This chapter has applied the fsQCA to the normative criteria which indicate the potential of hearings to harness deliberative and democratic standards. Each hearing had a strength at different levels. The UN hearing was not very inclusive but did well in terms of popular control. Perhaps because of the control the citizens had over the agenda and their unlimited access to information. The local hearing did well in most aspects, indicating perhaps that the hearing is most democratic when held at this level. In fact interestingly it is the middle level governance ones which fared the worst. This could be the lack of legitimacy by the chair members or the lack of power they wielded when it came to actually making decisions. The BCCA hearing measured high throughout all democratic norms highlighting the strength of the sequencing technique, this is supported by the strength of the Helensburgh hearing as it too was coupled with other consultation processes. However, there is little evident that these processes directly impacted on policy outcomes and demonstrated little popular control. The Alpac and Formartine hearings held at a similar level of governance showed similar conclusions. Alpac had a low level of considered judgement and Formartine was low in popular control. Both resulted in the decision being overturned highlighting the lack of effect they held over the policy process. The EU level hearing scored the highest in all democratic goods. The organisation was independent of political elites, the outcome resulted in EU wide recommendations which were implemented into national legislation on green manufacturing, and all this was guided by a variety of experts and groups. The next chapter will draw together the findings from this chapter and the last. It will seek to show how the research aims have been achieved and consider how this contributes to wider research on deliberative democracy and how public hearings can accommodate environmental decision-making.

Chapter 8: Public hearings: filling the democratic gaps

8.1 Introduction

This chapter seeks to illustrate how public hearings can help to fill the deliberative democratic gap between liberal institutions and deliberative processes. At the beginning of this research it was posited that the potential of public hearings may draw from their hybrid characteristics – their ability to harness opposing spheres in one arena; the inclusion of different types of actors into deliberation and their ability to be utilised at different points in the democratic process. Although hearings had been largely neglected in the deliberative literature, this research proposes that they could support deliberative democratic institutions to overcome issues which they have yet to counter. Linking liberal institutions with deliberative processes within the hearing process could help overcome the weaknesses of each thus creating a synthesis between deliberative democracy and ecological decision-making. As witnessed through this research, public hearings show the potential to harbour the democratic goods of inclusion, popular control, transparency and considered judgement which are necessary for legitimising democratic processes and to initiate wider participation. Nonetheless, institutional goods are also necessary which, as discussed in section 2.3, are efficiency and transferability (Smith 2009a). It is argued in this chapter that public hearings are able to fulfil Smith's institutional goods, as well as his democratic goods, which is conducive to forwarding a green agenda.

Therefore the first section of this chapter will look at how the institutional goods can be achieved through public hearing's hybrid characteristics. The first institutional good is efficiency. While acknowledging the need to discuss issues in a rational and reflective manner, efficiency highlights the need for linking deliberation with decision-making. The outcome of participant's hard work needs to be measurable in tangible results such as, policy decisions or amendments; control over legislation developments or monetary spending in local areas; or influence over discussions and decisions made at a supranational level. Better control over decisions at different levels of governance can directly impact on how much citizens can control the environmental agenda. Four areas are determined where public hearing's hybrid elements can help bring public deliberation closer in line with decision-making; first, by aligning deliberative processes with liberal institutions; second, considering the opportunities hearings can create by connecting the micro and macro level deliberation; third, by

accommodating weak and strong public spheres and fourth, by bringing together a wider variety of actors to the process.

The second section will consider the institutional good – transferability. This will be done by developing hearing's potential by concentrating on their affiliation with interest groups and associations, which arguably harness their transferability. It is argued here that associations, interest groups and experts can be used by citizens as democratic tools to widen their input into the political arena. Through Fischer's (2009) participatory inquiries, spheres which accept alternative forms of representation can help hearings to transcend tokenistic participation. The second portion of hearing's transferability stems from their ability to span the various level of governance. Public hearings have been shown, in this research, to have the potential to scale up in a way that not all other deliberative institutions can. Their flexible procedure and adaptability is an intrinsic part of this. Through these key features it will be shown how public hearings can challenge the problems facing deliberative processes and thus take a position in forwarding green interests.

8.2 Efficiency and effectiveness: The hybrid credentials of public hearings

Deliberative democracy is widely understood to require liberal institutions to be realised. To initiate effective and efficient policy-making within deliberative democracy, deliberation must be conducted in collaboration with representative and aggregative forms of democracy, which liberal democracy embodies (Rawls 1993; Cohen 1996). As demonstrated, deliberative processes can lend legitimacy and transparency to decisions which are made under liberal democracies, as well as educating the public and encouraging an inclusive process (Warren 2002: 195). Therefore, enabling the strongest aspects of deliberation to thrive while ensuring that the process results in a decision, demands more of the democratic mechanisms.

8.2.1 Aligning deliberative processes and liberal institutions

The key problems facing existing liberal institutions is the lack of transparency and legitimacy. Opening up the decision-making process to the public, exposing the discussions which lead to the implementation of policies and enabling the public to have a stronger role in any decisions made, makes clear steps toward overcoming these two key issues. Public hearings have a crucial role in administrative governance and are institutionalised into most liberal democratic states (Beierle and Cayford 2002; Baber and Bartlett 2005). Beierle and Cayford (2002: 3)

argue that, 'A fundamental challenge for administrative governance is reconciling the need for expertise in managing administrative programs with the transparency and participation demanded by a democratic system' while Abels (2007: 108) notes; hearings are the only participatory model which links 'public administration and decision-making'. Therefore hearings have the potential to facilitate administrative governance in an open and transparent setting by connecting decision-makers to their public, and as previously noted deliberation is more easily absorbed into political institutions if the deliberative ideal is not forcibly upheld (Davidson and Stark 2011: 175).

Public hearings differ from purely deliberative forums in that there is a level of popular control and inclusion created by the very idea of a 'public' hearing. They can ensure that deliberation and, in turn the decision, of an issue is made in closer proximity to the local area. Public hearings can not only facilitate discourse between various actors from different levels but provide an arena where the public are able to demand accountability or justifications from these actors (Richardson *et al.* 1993: 171-2). Thus hearings can incorporate face-to-face interaction which can facilitate problem-solving and discussion. A decision is made on the back of the hearing, often with the panel voting and justifying their positions with the public participants present. They have been seen in Finland to have more impact on policy-making than other participatory processes currently being used (when compared to petitions, surveys, committees and discussions) (Karjalainen 2014: 13). This may be because they are institutionalised in the land-planning legislation in many European countries and their function is to inform policy. Therefore, it can be said that hearings can offer a process that can provide an 'end-point' through some form of aggregation, which may better reflect the popular will as the participants are invested in the issue. From this, it can be seen that public hearings can facilitate a realistic approach to merging deliberation, and many of its benefits, in a liberal system. The next subsections will set this out in more detail by offering practical ways that this can be implemented and how hearings can combine oppositional spheres of decision-making.

8.2.2 *Micro and macro deliberation*

Through the hybrid capacity, one of hearing's core features is the ability to host micro and macro level deliberation within the hearings process. As discussed in section 2.4, Hendriks (2006) believes that micro and macro deliberative strategies must be combined in order to

institutionalise deliberative democracy. Micro level deliberation can facilitate an understanding of feeling that surrounds issues; narrow the field of discussion and offer feedback or recommendations for political actors. They can also offer a clearer representation of a smaller area which will then feed into a wider area using representatives who have participated (Goodin 2005). Applied separately, micro deliberation tends to be exclusive and while macro deliberative democracy is more inclusive, it is often considered to be ineffective at empowering citizens at any level which enables them to affect change (Bächtiger *et al.* 2009: 8). To be properly effectual, inasmuch that the decisions reached or recommendation that result from the deliberative institution are used to advise and guide policy-making, micro and macro deliberation must be linked.

The difference with a hearing is macro level discussions are filtered in in a more direct fashion than, say, parliaments. Like parliaments, in hearings and citizens' juries, the agenda are often set by macro discussions such as the media, public pressure or research. The difference, though, between parliamentary debate and the discussions held in hearings is that rather than the debate being conducted between representatives of the people, in hearings those that have demanded the debate are able to take part. This of course, can be conducted by citizens in a citizens' jury. Yet, citizens or participants rarely set the agenda in a deliberative process – this is usually done by the organisers. What differs here though, from citizen's juries and assemblies is that experts and government bodies deliberate as part of the process, this is not based solely round citizen's interaction. For this reason, public hearings could accommodate a system that encompasses micro level deliberative fora with macro level inclusion, which could create a third level of deliberative democracy called the 'meso' level of deliberation. Offering a third level of deliberation within the deliberative system. Not by replacing mini-publics, which are vital for inclusive and safe places for citizens to learn and discuss, but it provides an alternative space where citizens can contribute to the debate and understand the technological and complex areas which are being discussed.

Meadowcroft (2004: 188) says the meso level involves; 'deliberative interactions at the interface between state and society, where the personnel and structures of the state meet individuals and groups rooted in civil and commercial life'. It is necessary for the meso level to be informed by the macro conversations and narrowed down to benefit from micro deliberation (Evans 2001: 543). Therefore, in context – if the BC deliberative processes is taken

as an example; the Assembly was the micro deliberative process, the agenda had been set by the macro level deliberation (public pressure, the political environment and the media). Yet it was the hearing which brought the macro level discussion (public opinion informed by the media and other informational frameworks) into a micro level process. In turn, the hearing narrowed and informed the agenda for the next stage of the CA. Where hearings are part of a process or a sequence they can be informed by a micro institution and a macro level deliberation thus making them a useful tool. This is where citizens can really call government officials and experts into question without attacking them. Anger or fear would be less likely to overtake if citizens can verbalise concern, and by appropriately facilitating this public opinion, it is more likely to be connected with a decision. The public hearing is a natural point which brings together those that work at parliamentary level and those contributing to the public pressure. In this way it embodies Hendriks' (2006) mixed discursive sphere in a single process. The hybrid capabilities of a hearing can, if properly applied, assist in further democratising the liberal democratic model. Moreover, this three level approach could be an intrinsic part of allowing deliberative democracy to permeate each level of governance and each stage of the decision-making process.

8.2.3 Strong and weak publics

Fraser (1990: 74) sees the necessity in maintaining a link between civil society and the state in order to produce a functional public sphere. 'Weak publics', she explains, are those whose deliberation results in opinion formation but no decisions, and 'strong publics' generate discourse which embodies both opinion formation and decision-making. The risk of separating these two publics, or relying on one over the other, means that there is a move away from 'self-management, inter-public coordination and public accountability' that Fraser (1990: 76) deems necessary for 'a democratic and egalitarian society'. Through public hearings, it could be argued, the strong publics can be held to account by 'their' weak publics – as was seen in the Alpac hearing. They can communicate and manage one another through a hearing which can offer this 'inter-public coordination', meaning the public can not only hold the decision-makers accountable, but inform the decision-making process through their own deliberation. As Fraser (1990) discusses, maintaining the connection between the weak and strong publics can limit the inequalities which result from liberal democratic societies where, in attempting to create a robust public sphere can, if not properly implemented, result in greater divides between social groups. Through deliberation, self-interested standpoints are discouraged and instead the

promotion of common good dominates. Therefore, there is an assumption that within a democratic public sphere, civil society must separate itself from the state.

If indeed environmental issues are focussed on as public goods and thus worthy of attention for the good of all, then it can effectively be discussed through deliberative processes. However, individual and singular events which are still environmentally focussed but whose impact is only felt by individuals or groups – such as the events highlighted in section 3.2.1 – do not fit the deliberative context so comfortably. It is possible that the ‘moralising’ aspects of deliberation can only serve to quieten individual perspectives and push extreme or minority views to the periphery. This is not how environmental effects are felt. Allowing people to enter the process who are affected, who make use of anecdotal evidence and whose lives and communities are closely linked with the outcome of a deliberative process cannot in all instances be left up to a randomly sampled populace. Therefore avoiding this separation of the public and the decision-makers is not conducive to a productive and legitimate decision-making process. By challenging the status quo, it can be argued, that decision-making is diversified and encourages a plethora of opinions, those that may be key to forwarding the green agenda. What must be addressed is the participation of various actors, working together, to make decisions.

8.2.4 The interaction between all stakeholders within deliberative discussions

Within this research it has been highlighted that a mix of actors interacting in a different, yet no less important way than other democratic innovations, deserves attention. It has been argued that the engagement of a range of stakeholders throughout the hearing process is a unique and powerful tool. Housing all the necessary actors in one arena can conclude in tangible results as it can link deliberation with decision-making. As discussed in section 3.2, the problem with many deliberative processes, such as mini-publics, is that the impact on a decision is often not assured. The emphasis which is placed on citizen deliberation rather than an interaction between the various levels of stakeholders and policy-makers is problematic for a number of reasons, least of which is that there is no democratic mandate to which the process can draw claim. In turn, this argument also applies to implementing policies which are environmentally aligned. Not only do participants have no legitimacy but in many instances, they have no specific expertise which can clearly map out a realistic path for tackling environmental issues.

Therefore, the inclusion of all key stakeholders, and the various affected voices, is what makes public hearings unique and valuable, but more than that, it is an imperative feature of guiding environmental policy-making.

Deliberation which leads to decisions must include all stakeholders, which includes experts and policy-makers. Where experts are often there to provide information or evidence, they are frequently left out of the deliberation (Fischer 2003: 210). Within a public hearing a multitude of actors engage with one another, this includes representatives from interest groups, the media, government officials, council members, lay citizens and experts of a particular sort, depending on the issue at hand. Bringing all these actors into discussion together combines differing perspectives and may result in different, but nonetheless, legitimate outcomes. Fischer (1999: 299) says that this is an important component of the participatory process; 'Experiences of participatory inquiry have emerged from such practical problems: the future of such activities depends in many ways on a more systematic development of cooperative relationships among citizens and experts more generally'. Aforementioned, experts of science, environmentalism and academia often set the agenda for policy-making processes, first by doing the research required on these complex issues and second by shaping public opinion, which can be done through the media (Moore 2011: 3). Knowledge of policy, law, finance and the political infrastructure is also expertise required for decision-making. Government officials, policy development officers and council members are likely to know what is practical in terms of implementing policies, therefore they can contribute to a realistic conversation.

That is not to say that citizens are not a vital aspect of decision-making, if a legitimate and democratic system is to be pursued. Hearing can bring the public face-to-face with decision-makers where they can cross over from a position of 'lay citizen' to a knowledgeable and worthy source of information on the issue (Fischer 1999: 299). Furthermore, citizens can also see experts as laypeople with similar aspirations to themselves in terms of 'political goals and social judgements' (Fischer 1999: 296). This encourages; 'the cross-fertilisation of ideas across different kinds of actors, connecting broader public discourse to the conversations and decisions of the political elite' (Hendriks 2006: 501), creating a different level of interaction and inclusiveness where the formal actors meet the more informal lay citizens. Further than that though, this could be a step forward in nurturing a new, re-imagined partnership between communities and experts. In order to dispel the negativity which exists between ordinary

citizens and those unelected that guide decision-making is to create a position of 'counter-expert' where communities themselves can consult and discuss with experts on issues which affect them. Fischer (1999: 298-9) reports that instances where this has occurred are not infrequent. Where communities and individuals have local knowledge and the time and energy to pursue their cause, there is a place for experts to help them. It is vital that lay citizens are not 'talked down to' or 'talked at', as Fischer (1999: 299) says;

Rather than providing technical answers designed to resolve or close off political discussion, the task of the participatory expert is to assist citizens in their efforts to examine their own interests and to make their own decisions.

The expert therefore takes on a role of facilitating the citizen 'learning and empowerment' process (Fischer 1999: 299) as opposed to just a purveyor of information. The experts would help shape the citizens own research rather than driving it, as was discussed in section 3.3, through a participatory inquiry.

Yet, instead of the arena which Fischer (2009) suggests, the consensus conference, it is believed within this research that a public hearing is the correct setting for this. Especially a quasi-judicial hearing, like the Glenmorie or UN hearings, which gives citizens time to present their finding and scrutinise the policy-makers and experts who are working for the government or developers. Here the experts they work with as part of the participatory inquiry would be counter-experts. Seeking guidance from experts should not be only something policy-makers can do. In order to effectively mobilise communities, not just in opposition to a development, drawing citizens into a discussion where they are considered key players will create a different discussion. One in which all parties – experts, policy-makers and citizens – are conducting themselves on an even playing field. Maintaining a system where policies and solutions are left to the experts is excluding stakeholders of the environment. In order to forward the environmental agenda, it is crucial that every person feels the responsibility of that. Insights on agriculture, land use and local ecosystems can be a form of expertise themselves and as stated, should not be dismissed.

Admittedly, there can be no guarantees that any public consultation will lead to greener public policy or that participant's ideas on the common good will align. Having said that it is worth considering what has been highlighted by this analysis in terms of tackling matters of environmental impact. It is indicated from the case study analysis that in the small sample of

hearings that have been looked at in this research that the public were overwhelmingly in support of green decisions. The informants for the UN cases study were protesting the rise in pollution in their local area; the protestors in the Formartine were objecting to the development of a golf course which would impact on the SSSI; the EC participants were discussing how to excite innovation in the field of environmental manufacturing; and the Alpac hearing was driven by locals who were against the destruction of their forests and the decimation of their river and local ecosystem. Conversely though, it can be argued that the UN informants were merely looking out for their own health and the inconvenience they were faced with by the bungled tram development; the Formartine participants cared more about preserving their community, their land and freedoms than the actual environmental impacts of the development; in the EC hearing it is arguable whether environmental manufacturing and modernisation is really in the environment's best interest; and finally, the people of Alberta could have felt compelled to speak, not through concern for the biosphere which had been carefully honed for years but due to the changes in the landscape and wildlife, and the impact it would have on the people living there. It cannot be said with any assurance which is the case, people are motivated by different desires. All that can be said with some certainty, whatever the reason, the participants of the majority of cases in this research acted with environmental sympathy.

Crucially though, the public cannot tackle environmental challenges alone. It must be acknowledged that citizens are restricted by the time available to them and the knowledge they have. Which is one of the reasons why politicians or policy-makers also need to be part of this process, as argued in section 3.3.1. The efficiency or effectiveness of any process must take into consideration any measurable policy outputs. Therefore government officials should be part of these conversations and should be contributing to them, as they are vital for implementing legislation. Separating civil society and the state, as previously said, is not conducive to legitimate decision-making. When shaping policy, the role of experts, citizens and policy-makers is paramount. Thus, combining micro and macro level deliberation creates a meso level which can be accommodated within a public hearing offering an innovative and flexible setting for environmental discussion. Furthermore combining the strong and weak publics creates an area for accountability and partnership in policy-making and offers a different outlet for those that are affected by environmental issues, which is likely to be a minority (*see* Simcock 2014). Finally, hearings provide assistance in offering a practical way to discuss issues by including a variety of actors who are all vital to the decision-making

process. The various levels of decision-makers need to learn from one another, converse and be made more accountable to one another. Those that make decisions, those that advise decision-making and those that are impacted upon by the decisions made. A mix of actors is vital for breaking down and problem solving in such a complex topic as environmentalism. Consequently the opportunity for all considered parties to speak in one process lends a distinctive attribute to the hearing. The next section will consider how public hearings can accommodate the institutionalisation of deliberative democracy through their transferability. This will include looking at how public hearings can work at the various levels of governance.

8.3 The transferability of hearings: institutionalising public hearing

As the title of this thesis suggests, the institutionalisation of democracy is key to the deliberative democratic movement. Instilling it within the political paradigm is intrinsic to its value and worth. It could be suggested that public hearings can play a role in actualising this aim. Despite the fact that the literature has moved on to consider deliberative systems and sequences, there is still work to be done in envisioning its institutionalisation. If indeed deliberative democracy is the best model to forward environmental issues, as argued here, it cannot do any harm to widen the discussion beyond the existing political narrative, including reflecting on where the democratic literature has come from. With this in mind, deliberative democracy's institutionalisation is fundamental to its success. This section will discuss the transferability of public hearings. First by envisioning what can be achieved by inviting interest groups into them, and second by examining their institutionalisation at different levels of governance. It will be considered how this will actualise green decision-making.

8.3.1 Green decision-making: transcending tokenistic participation

Innes and Booher (2004: 422) believe that such participatory processes should incorporate citizens, organised interests, academics, profit and non-profit making organisations, and planners and public administrations. Interest groups and secondary associations can provide expert advice and knowledge while remaining politically neutral – independent from external persuasion (Elstub 2007: 8). Elstub (2008) believes that associational democracy and deliberative democracy can be productively aligned. It has been seen from this research that public hearings can embody associations and group interests, as well as individuals. With the public increasingly losing faith in politicians and political institutions, interest groups and non-

governmental organisations (NGOs) could offer an alternative form of representation within the deliberative process. Woods (2007: 39) highlights the importance of structuring participatory processes to ensure that they are at their most effective. By utilising representation through large interest groups, issues can be forwarded from a wide-reaching group, rather than people representing countries; geographical groups or commercial interests that may not really represent their own interests. Hendriks (2011: 11) believes that interest groups can serve a number of functions. Through their participation within citizen based processes, they can ensure that the deliberators are all 'accurately informed'. They can provide relevant information which enriches the process by bringing to light a variety of perspectives ensuring that officials are questioned in all areas of interest (Hendriks 2011: 11). This means that issues are discussed by international groups. Global interest groups that straddle worldwide interests, such as Oxfam, Amnesty International and/or Greenpeace can report on diverse issues and can make checks on global governance by reporting and analysing on outcomes and policies (Woods 2007: 36).

Interest groups can guarantee a level of legitimacy to the deliberation process and its outcome. It means that no one policy input can dominate proceedings thus opening the process up for criticism, diminishing the strength of the outcome (Hendriks 2011: 11). Furthermore, interest advocates can ensure that decision-makers not only react, but *act* on citizen's recommendations. Interest groups can forward 'principles and values', core interests and individual's concerns to the forefront of policy-making (Woods 2007: 39). These groups are well placed to keep an eye on policy processes to ensure that the public are taken seriously (Hendriks 2011: 12). Finally, interest groups can attract the attention of a wider audience such as; their members, politicians and the media (Hendriks 2011: 12). Interest groups in turn can benefit from a continued interaction with lay citizens. As opinions and issues are continuously fluctuating interest groups need to continue to be aware of new information to avoid becoming static and losing touch with citizens. Hearings can provide this service. This participation is designed to make these groups more effective by making information more readily available and easier to understand (Woods 2007: 39). Within a hearing the interest groups can achieve this level of communication with lay public (Hendriks 2011: 11). Communication creates greater levels of transparency which leads to governments and policy-makers being held accountable thus legitimising their decision-making powers. Furthermore, as Brown (2014: 57) explains,

Though lay citizens must trust their experts, their trust need not be blind. When technical uncertainty or public controversy raises justifiable doubts about expert claims, lay citizens and their representatives need effective opportunities to hold experts publicly accountable.

In order to connect the central government to the people, and overcome these societal changes, secondary associations can play a part. These can help to reduce the scale of decisions and thus overcome many social obstacles. By decentralising decisions to associations and applying the principle of ‘subsidiarity’, issues of scale and the necessity for specialist information can be done by ‘quasi-public functions’ which can either take the place of, or support, the state (Elstub 2007: 5). Subsidiarity is the idea that ‘decisions are taken as closely as possible to the citizen’ (Elstub 2007: 5) in order to include individuals that are affected by policies and decisions in a setting where all are counted as equal. It could be argued that the association’s role is to support the state, not replace it. Hearings could play a part in realising this normative idea as they can accommodate secondary associations and organisations in their deliberative setting. Public hearings could offer an alternative democratic situation that is confined to a smaller number of representative individuals.

Aforementioned, the role of associations within the hearing is worthy of further study. The UN, EU and Glenmorie case studies, though held at different levels, all made use of group interests. Utilising and focusing the power of group politics was effectual in these cases. Representatives spoke on behalf of their members conveying a wide variety of interests. For the UN hearing, the group that brought the case to the Compliance Committee pooled their resources – time, knowledge, expertise – to forward a convincing resistance. It may have been harder to initiate without the forming and support of a group. The EU invited experts from across the European region to come and share information on green manufacturing. Making use of the experts was productive in reaching the best outcomes. And experts from a range of countries meant that a myriad of ideas were forwarded combining research, development and different backgrounds. In the case of the Glenmorie hearing this may have been a contributing factor in the success of the opposition. There is an argument to say that this may encourage more people to attend, where they have the support of a network or others to speak on behalf of them. Although what was witnessed through the Glenmorie hearing was very few individuals coming forward. Therefore, an inherent flaw is that associations could instead make people feel that their individual input does not hold the same impact.

Having said that, making use of associations, expert representatives and interest groups cannot be expected to be the panacea for the problems faced in the existing system. Fischer (2000: 113) states, that, 'Although interest groups represent citizens, especially "public interest groups", they are themselves hierarchical organisations frequently quite removed from the citizens for whom they speak'. Fischer (2000: 113) continues and highlights that these groups can gradually evolve into professionals themselves, using the technical language, understanding the complex nature of policy-making and even working as consultants to governments or industry. Also they tend to water down their policies and take on more conservative strategies in an effort to push through their interests in the political sphere. Though it must be considered that any individual or group is unable to stop themselves from adapting to this form of participation. As discussed in section 3.2.2, Flynn (2009) raises concerns about participating citizens transforming into engaged and active members thus ceasing to represent wider society and instead starting to think more in line with experts. It would seem that no group can resist changing throughout the process. There is a risk therefore, of groups or individuals becoming 'professionalised' and in order to maintain legitimacy and a necessary distance from the professional actors they should instead rage and campaign from out with the political process. It is suspected within this research, that while thinking and connecting differently the more citizens are involved, the greater the diversity represented and different interests forwarded. Again though, that is not to say that only representatives are useful in public hearings, there is the obvious and aforementioned risk of intimidating individuals who chose to represent themselves regardless of the limitations to their resources. The point here is instead, that this is another tool which public hearings offer. Specifically when held at a higher level of governance, interest groups can play an effective role in representing a greater number. The next section considers how public hearings can permeate all levels of governance, again demonstrating their hybrid characteristics and their ability to institutionalise participation and some aspects of deliberative democratic norms at a variety political levels. .

8.3.2 Initiating the discussion at all levels of governance

As discussed in chapter 1 and 2, academics have attempted to discover how deliberative democracy can be implemented at all levels of decision-making – local, national and international. However, no single deliberative method can be incorporated effectively throughout all levels. This is because only certain institutional mechanisms will be compatible with democratic goods, and be able to adapt according to the complexities that arise at

particular stages of the decision-making process, and at the varied levels of governance. Elstub (2014b: 400) explains;

The features of complexity...that determine the transferability of institutions to enact a deliberative interpretation of democratic principles vary across these levels of governance. With respect to the transnational and global levels of governance, language becomes a factor, pluralism is increased further, and the logistical problems of scale are intensified. As a result, inclusion becomes harder to achieve in non-territorially bound units as it is less likely that citizens will see each other as equals in determining collective decisions.

However, as this research has shown, hearings can be held at any level – local, regional, federal and national; as well as transnationally and globally. And, as this section will show, research has shown that not only can hearings adjust to the different levels but that they can be effective. This is important as it means that hearings could play a role in overcoming issues of scale which deliberative processes have struggled with. Public hearings have been shown to be effectively institutionalised at various levels of governance throughout this research, which they are not alone in doing – parliaments and mini-publics have also been seen to overcome issues of scale. Yet, a very different process is enacted at various levels through a public hearing.

Through the Aarhus Convention, the UN acts as an impartial adjudicator on issues and events which have impacted on citizens and ensures that dissatisfied citizens have a voice, and that local and national level governments are held accountable to the people. Further to this, the EU hearing was held on environmental manufacturing, bringing together representatives from a multitude of nations to collaborate on initiatives designed to improve green technology to make Europe more competitive. The recommendations which resulted from the hearings will be implemented in businesses within these nations as well as internationally. Representatives from the European Commission and Parliament and individuals from institutions of research, engineering and academics alongside representatives from groups like EFRA and ASPIRE all came together to discuss how Europe could move forward on this issue. The analysis carried out in chapter 7 indicates that the hearings at both EU and international level demonstrated the ability to enact democratic norms while being held at a global and transnational level. Having said that, EU and UN level hearings can, and should be, streamed online which means the process would be more open, transparent and accessible in terms of communicating with a

wider and larger audience. Thus accommodating the inclusion of a wider populace and ensuring that the process is transparent.

Three hearings which were held at local level but closely watched by federal level governance (devolved in Scotland), included the Alpac, Formartine and the Glenmorie hearings. These were perhaps the most rigid processes, in terms of procedure followed, which were looked at. Specifically the Formartine and the Alpac hearings, as already discussed, were hugely problematic in terms of the outcome of the hearing. Although they both showed the ability to produce the right conditions in three out of the four democratic goods (Formartine did not show the necessary attributes for popular control and the Alpac did not have the right conditions for transparency) both decisions which had been made by the panels as a result of the hearings were overturned. This means that even if the process had been able to achieve any, or all of the democratic principles, it would not have mattered as the result of the hearing was not adhered to. The time and effort of the participants in these processes was neither rewarded nor valued.

The Glenmorie hearing recommendation was upheld however, which indicates that this is not a consistent pattern. To reiterate though, this could indicate that hearings held at a level which exists between two levels of governance – the local and the regional – are not considered to be serious consultations which offer influence to the public over their futures. If these hearings, and the people that are acting as chair hold no power, there is little point in holding the hearing in the first place. These will have an adverse effect on participatory processes and will ensure that individuals will not attend and if they do, they will be defensive and resentful. The BCCA hearings were also held at this level. There were a number of key differences with these hearings though, the first being is that they were organised and run by CA members and not politicians. Second, the purpose of the process was known to all as an information gathering and sharing session rather than being held as part of the necessary procedural practice for planning approval. And third, the resultant output of the hearing did not require anyone to make a final decision based on what they had heard – until a series of deliberative citizens' juries had taken place. The participants knew that they would be heard but knew the final recommendation would be made by the CA members. As the research is seeking to decipher whether the hearing process can be an effective democratic tool in an integrated deliberative sequence or system, not looking at individual cases for anecdotal evidence, it is safe to ignore the democratic failings of the Formartine and Alpac hearings following the conclusion of the

process, however it is important to acknowledge this in the discussion. Having said that, a key recommendation which would result here from the case study analysis is that whomever has the power to make the decision, that power should remain with them regardless of whether the regional government or developers support it. If that is not the case the regional government should hold the hearing themselves.

The final hearing was held at the local level. Again, like the BCCA hearing, it was used to hear from people and share information. The Helensburgh hearing received high scores for most of the conditions for all four democratic norms. In terms of embodying the capacity to enact democratic principles it appeared to tick all the boxes. Having said that, how effective the hearing was is unclear. There was no tangible output from this process. It may well have inspired or informed a multitude of participants on the benefits or perils of wind-power. Yet, with no report, recommendation or decision the outcome is unclear. Again, recording the process could mean that the impact of this hearing could have been more widely spread. The discussions or concerns from this hearing could have been used to guide the next participatory process or even just written up and posted online for the local people and the wider community to read.

Here, public hearings were shown to harness the potential to enact some, or all, of the democratic norms to varying degrees. This is a key finding and should not be dismissed due to the faults of the individual hearing. The mixed method approach has demonstrated what these hearings are theoretically capable of as well as highlighting the individual weaknesses of each, illustrating where improvements can be made. Beyond this research though, hearings have been used as part of the Economic Commission for Europe assisting discussions on overcoming transboundary environmental impacts and within the Great Lakes-regime between the USA and Canada (Klinke 2009). They are also used as part of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) as a scientific body for the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change. Furthermore, decisions made within hearings often transcend the level they are held at. For instance, a public hearing held at local level can impact on governance at national level (see Richardson *et al.* 1993; Ford 2011 *for examples*). Moreover, hearings which are held on environmental or economic issues, undoubtedly impact at the level they are held and all the levels below too. Policy initiatives or EIA's held at EU level impact on national governments and local councils. In terms of communicating with a wider and larger audience and ensuring

transparency is upheld EU level and UN hearings are often streamed online. This accommodates the inclusion of a wider populace. It must be acknowledged that the level of considered judgment between the various levels of stakeholders will most likely be decidedly lessened. Yet, in an effort to apply that to a wider and broader contextualised level of governance; the 'ideal' method may be unsuitable for that level. This research has highlighted the potential of public hearing to enact democratic goods, and institutional goods required for legitimized decision-making. Through this, it can be determined that public hearing can feasibly play a role, maybe even a significant one, in accommodating the institutionalisation of democracy.

8.4 Conclusion

The importance, and certainly the benefit, of combining liberal institutions with deliberative processes is the opportunity to overcome the weak aspects of each democratic model. Deliberation needs to become more efficient and tangibly more effectual – resulting in measurable outcomes. Liberal democracy requires greater levels of legitimacy and to accommodate a reconnection between citizens and their governments, where experts could feasibly play a more balanced role. By merging the somewhat opposing spheres which exist within any democratic society – the civil society with public officers, the micro level decision-making with the discourses that exists in the macro level, the weak and strong publics – the gap between elites and the people can be bridged, offering a pluralistic dispersal of control over the democratic process. Throughout this chapter, it has been argued that public hearings embody hybrid characteristics, which accommodate the creation of a middle ground connecting micro and macro level deliberation. The meso level of deliberation connects the discussions and opinions of wider society, whose voice and opinions rarely have any impact beyond the macro level, with actual decision-making ensuring that citizens have an element of influence over the outcomes. Furthermore, blending the weak and strong publics permits a confrontation of sorts which provides an arena for weak publics to hold the strong publics to account. Providing an arena which can better utilise the experts, associations and other deliberative institutions, in a deliberative sequence, can arguably offer a diversified public sphere which enables the public to develop and employ an assortment of democratic tools. It would appear that public hearings can play a strong role here. This does not mean to say that public hearings are better or more useful than other deliberative institutions but instead that they can *also* contribute to a deliberative democratic system alongside mini-publics. Further to this, public

hearings embody the ability to transcend the local levels of governance and thus their ability is presently underestimated. If deliberative democracy is to be properly institutionalised, public hearings can play a part in this. Finally, there is evidence here to suggest that they may be able to harness the democratic and institutional norms which could arguably place the environment and environmental concerns on the political agenda.

Chapter 9: Conclusion

9.1 Introduction

This research has sought to carry out a robust analysis on the use of public hearings in institutionalising deliberative democracy. In order to do this, they would need to demonstrate the ability to enact some or all of the democratic norms. Deliberative democracy has been linked with promoting the environmental cause due to its focus on pursuing the common purpose and coupling rational discussion with collective decision-making. The educative benefits of diversified interaction promises to expose individuals to perspectives and opinions which challenge their understanding of complex issues. Making use of case studies, a fsQCA was applied to ascertain the extent the democratic norms could be realised. The DePER framework provided a flexible theoretical framework which was required to choose suitable case studies and to guide the collection of information. From this, the DSEI was designed and utilised which has grounded the theoretical concepts driving the research. Providing a quantifiable framework by which to evaluate the case studies was necessary to offer a full analysis. Within the conclusion the most important findings which have emerged from this research will be reiterated, including the findings from the DSEI and the fsQCA. The next section will set out some recommendations in order to establish how hearings could reach their potential. Finally, the chapter will look at where further research is required, beyond this study.

9.2 Key findings from the DSEI

The research has sought to highlight the strengths and weaknesses of hearings in terms of the decision-making process, in order to clarify where hearings' lack the ability to host the democratic goods thus signifying a different democratic process could better fill this position. It was clear when applying the DSEI that a number of flaws could be attributed to the public hearing process. It has been discussed that the simplicity of the decision-making process set out by Saward (2003), and adapted by Elstub (2014b) for his DePER framework, is problematic. However, it does work as a loose structure in which to assess where hearings are best placed. The following draws from the main findings from chapter 6, section 6.3, and will highlight where hearings could be of most use or where they would be of least, and in turn, where they could be used in conjunction with other deliberative institutions.

9.2.1 Effecting change through agenda setting

It has been consistently argued throughout this research that the ability to set the agenda is a unique and valuable element of the public hearing. Yet, the agenda cannot just be set by those that shout the loudest or those that are in a position to enact these protestations. A concern is that the people from Alberta were heard because there was many of them, and in the case of the UN hearing, the complainants were articulate, knowledgeable and well equipped in terms of money and time to pursue this undoubtedly painstaking line of inquiry. The three information gathering/sharing hearings – Helensburgh, BCCA and EC – all helped to narrow the agenda, or set the agenda for the next phase of the deliberative sequence. However, the agenda had still been set prior to the hearing. For agenda setting, it could be argued, that a wider process is required to set the agenda, for instance, a poll or a citizens' assembly.

Consequently, it is acknowledged here that deliberative institutions, such as citizens' assemblies, are a good way to narrow an agenda. This can bring a varied and representative group of people together to discuss issues which matter to them, or what they value. From this it can be ascertained what the public wish to discuss and this information can help to set the agenda for a hearing. An alternative way to set the agenda is through a petitions systems, for instance, the Public Petitions System in the Scottish Parliament. Although this too is a tool, much like the UN hearing, which is represented by a more limited demographic, those that are predominantly white, middle class and middle aged males (PPC Report 2006). Often, people do not know the various avenues open to them as an actor in the democratic system, which reduces their political clout considerably. How to educate individuals about the UN process, how to widen the demographic which feel able to utilise this to their, and their communities, advantage and how to make this a more effective tool are questions that are beyond this research. Online resources and concentrating on these issues within political studies in schools and colleges may educate a new generation about these tools but how to reach the variety of disenfranchised groups and individuals on a large scale is deeply challenging.

9.2.2 Who's taking part in the debate?

Most of the hearings were held as a mechanism to inform a decision or to gather information. The analysis found that all the hearings had the potential to create the right conditions for the democratic principles – including considered judgement. The level of discussion was high,

considered and well supported with evidence. However, as previously discussed, there is little indication of who is taking part, and therefore little indication of who is part of the discussion. This means, specifically if the hearing is being held at local level, that the process may be dominated by a vocal minority and frequented by the same groups of people. Certain groups in society may avoid the public hearing process due to the impression that it is just for the outspoken; for those who feel strongly about the subject or those who have a stance on the subject. This may limit the perspectives that are engaged within the conversation and therefore, have a negative impact on the diversity of opinions which are represented. Opinion change is not guaranteed throughout a hearing process, and there is no evidence of this having occurred due to the lack of research done about hearings in a deliberative context, yet it is not likely to occur if there are only participants who have entered the process with a fixed mind set. As argued though, this could be rectified to some degree if the hearing was held earlier in the decision-making process and the participants had a stronger impact on the outcome of the process.

Knowing more about the people that attend the public hearing process is key to ascertaining if the self-selection process is an effective method of recruitment. In this respect, it may be preferable to be more considered in the sampling technique – specifically in the case of cross sampling if it is felt to be necessary, especially in diverse communities. Yet, it is worth reiterating that a self-selecting process may be of use in certain situations. When a controversial development or topic has captured the attention of many, handpicking a random sample of individuals may not be the best option. In terms of a variety of actors contributing in a deliberative and considered discussion, a public hearing will probably not provide the most effective arena for this; a citizens' jury would be more suitable. However, there is an argument for having a wider more debate style interaction to accommodate hard questions and concerns which are put to organisers, experts and decision-makers from a wide audience. The transparency which is exercised by a willing and invested audience participating and interacting with those that hold the capacity to make decisions and advise further policy development cannot be underestimated. Being able to witness the decision-making process is imperative to increasing trust between government officials and citizens. So too, by live streaming, this would expose the process to a much wider populace. Therefore it could be said that the public hearing process facilitates a different type of debate from a mini-public. The quality of deliberation may be higher in a citizens' jury which is specifically designed to create

an open and engaging discussion, taking in all opinions, whereas the public hearing process offers a number of key differences which make it a process well worth pursuing.

Informing the chair of their views prior to the meeting, as was the case of the Glenmorie and Formartine, can be useful as it gives people time to articulate their views without the pressure of thinking on the spot. Although this could result in a lack of spontaneity as people may be less likely to be flexible or open to other arguments having already declared their stance. Set times can help to control the discussion and limits the ability to interrupt or intervene; although the presentational style can be intimidating for lay citizens. Coming prepared, almost with a script in certain instances – such as the Glenmorie case – gives people space to think why they hold these opinions, to offer supporting evidence to their points and to articulate their points in a more convincing fashion. Given that one of the key stances of deliberative democracy is to acknowledge the pervasive force of a good argument, the quality of the argument should not be diminished by the way it is forwarded - whether it be more formal and in a presentational manner or a roundtable discussion. A good argument is either persuasive or it is not, therefore a good argument forwarded within a hearing should have the same impact in transforming opinions and preferences. Yet, similar to other deliberative institutions, the chair is key for an open, transparent and controlled discussion. If the debate is heated as people get frustrated or passionate, the chair must be able to direct this in the correct way. A chair that has a vested interest or allegiances beyond those affected cannot be effective or a legitimate decision-maker.

Although the level of debate seemed to be of a high calibre within the UN hearing, there is an uncertainty of the UN being such a success if it was not for the members who brought the complaint to the Compliance Committee. The ability of these members to articulate themselves clearly while facing what must have been an intimidating team of lawyers hired by the UK, can be attributed to some degree to their socio-economic position – predominantly white, middle class, British born males. The justifications offered within the speech acts were undoubtedly superior in the higher governance hearings – the UN and the EC. Arguably this is because these people are not lay citizens but experts in their field working to problem solve, learn from one another or adjudicate in a specific issue. The other hearing that the level of justification was high were in the Glenmorie case, which similar to the EC hearing had associations and interest groups representing and speaking on behalf of others.

9.2.3 Effectual decision-making

None of the hearings accommodated the right of citizens to make the decision within that hearing. If they persuaded or influenced the decision-makers in any way this remains unclear through any tangible form of evidence. Certainly the participant's points were noted in the reports (Glenmorrie and Formartine, UN, EC) but the impact of those arguments made in the public hearings is unsure. Therefore, a process may well be inclusive but if the issue holds little political salience then there will be a low level of popular control; as Smith (2009a: 23) comments, 'Participation is either ignored by political authorities or is used to confirm decisions made elsewhere'. This is a significant failing of public hearing, as discussed in section 2.5.2, one which prevents them from becoming a more effectual tool in the democratic process. This does not mean that a final decision has to be made within a hearing for it to be an effective process but an understanding of what the outcome will be is vital. It is key to trust and understanding that participants are aware of who has the power to make the decision, if a decision is indeed to be made, and this is known to all prior to the hearing. The Glenmorrie hearing has been used as a process to gather information and is designed to result in an audible output – the report and recommendation written for the Scottish Government – and this concluded in a decision on the issue, made by the Scottish Government. Although this is the most recent hearing and therefore gives some indication of the process the hearings take. However, the right to ignore a recommendation, or indeed overturn a decision made by a local council still resides with the Scottish Government.

The Alpac and Formartine hearings showed that many members of the public were angered, disappointed and felt powerless following the decisions being overturned by the Provincial and the devolved government in Alberta and Aberdeen respectively. This could be described as a Burkean response to local councillors from the representative government. If a hearing is part of a planning process, and is a necessary proponent of planning law, this should not lessen its impact by the hearing becoming a box ticking exercise – the hearing should be effective whenever and for whatever purpose it is applied. Yet, as previously mentioned, the impact of the participants on the outcome of the hearing is rarely known. It is therefore suggested from this research, that voting within the hearing may highlight discrepancies in opinion or at least to draw attention to the feeling within the hearing. Had this method been utilised in the Alpac and the Formartine hearings, the ease in which the government dismissed the decisions of the panel may have been diminished. This is just a useful and simple tool to lend a degree of

accountability to a decision which has been made off the back of the hearing. If a hearing, such as the Formartine does have economic ramifications for local and national governance, clearer guidance on where the role of the panel or chair power's stop and start need to be expressly relayed to those that have a stake in the outcome of the hearing. Having said that, if decisions were not the express outcome of some of the hearings, recommendations were. Alpac, the UN and the EC hearings all made clear and explicit recommendations for policy initiatives or future practices highlighting that the outcome can result in tangible decisions.

9.2.4 Implementing change

None of the hearings in this research contributed to the implementation stage of the decision-making process. Smith (2009a) concedes that few participatory processes involve citizens at the implementation process but points out that for a democratic innovation to be effective, it may indeed mean that citizens will have to share power with other actors. This would seem to be a stage that hearings could be helpful, given its ability to combine the expertise of various stakeholders. Having said that, it would seem that in order to implement a policy or decision that a smaller more reflective and deliberative process could be of more use. The hearing though could feed information into this through the debate stage. If various actors interact at different stages of the decision process, but also within alternative democratic mechanisms, this could result in the discussion and thus the outcome being richer. The relations between governments and citizens, interest groups and the media could then forge. Using the BCCA as an example, the hearing and the CA gave the citizens more time to reflect on their thoughts, to interact with the organisers. Yet, had the experts and government officials been part of the CA, this could have resulted in a different outcome. As discussed, the discomfort that some of the citizens felt in announcing their recommendation for the referendum may have been diminished if their ideas and discussions had been supported by experts and policy-makers; the relationship with the new government could have been strengthened as the citizens and governors worked together like peers rather than separately. And finally, the electoral system which the public decided to vote for in the referendum may have been the one that the CA suggested - which was not the case. There is no evidence to validate this claim, but an interesting summation worthy of some thought. Finally, what have the findings indicated for hearings as a review procedure?

9.2.5 Reviewing the decision

The review process enables policy-makers and the people time to reflect on the decision that has been made and determine whether this has been the right decision and if not, should amendments be made. It could be argued that the UN and the Alpac demonstrated a significant level of popular control from the public body in setting the agenda for a review hearing, designed to consider decisions which had already been made. Within these hearings, evidence was put forward from opposing parties in order to discredit each other's claims resulting in a rather effective judicial procedure. A third party was brought into make a judgement based on the evidence and the discussion. For this, access to the necessary information was vital to the process. All participants, and the wider communities needed to know how they were being effected. Feasibility studies and EIAs are paramount in the early stages of decision-making to ensure that the review section can reflect on whether the claims were abided by and that the participants have been treated justly. Along with the debate stage, it is possible that this is another effective role that public hearings can fulfil. What can be said with some confidence, is in theory, public hearings could be an effective institution within a deliberative sequence or an integrated deliberative system – yet some adjustments must be made.

9.3 Key findings from the fsQCA

Chapter 7 carried out the fsQCA and there were a number of interesting findings. Each democratic norm will be set out and the configurations which indicated achieving the highest membership of that norm will be discussed.

9.3.1 Creating an inclusive public hearing

To enact inclusion within a public hearing process there were a number of configurations which would accommodate this. This required easy access to the process; a variety of groups in attendance and all participants making a contribution. The hearings held at the higher level of governance, the UN, was the least inclusive despite impacting at a local and national level. Yet as seen in sections 6.2.1 and 7.2.1, this could have been corrected by making use of recordings or live streaming. Local hearings were capable of embodying the most inclusive process. It is important to acknowledge that hearings will not be as inclusive as other mini-publics as they do not offer incentives where many other democratic innovations do. Incentives are important to compensate people for taking the time to participate and to cover expense which may incur as a result of taking part such as child care, transportation, and wage replacement. This may be

a weakness of the public hearing process but that is not a reason to cast them aside. Public hearings tend to be less time intensive as some mini-publics, the BCCA for instance was held over many days which were spread over 8 months. This is why accessibility in terms of when a hearing is held is so important to the inclusivity of the process. Many of the hearings showed that they were accessible, having more than one in various locations is a good idea. Providing transport for those who wish to attend is another idea. Inclusion in terms of voice is important. It has to be clear that no one should dominate the proceedings but in order to enable everyone to 'testify' in this process the pre-application and timed response may be the most practical way to do this. A chair to facilitate a reasonably inclusive conversation is paramount.

9.3.2 Creating a public hearing which embodies popular control

The analysis highlighted that the hearing held at the higher level – UN and EU – and the local level – Helensburgh - demonstrated the greatest capacity to enact the norms required for popular control. The BCCA hearing was also strong in this section, perhaps due to it being part of a wider deliberative and participatory process. The analysis highlighted the important aspects necessary to setting the right conditions for popular control, or how it would be reasonable to measure this. First, was the variety of groups within the process; second, these groups making a reasonable contribution; third, a neutral chair guiding the discussion and finally, what could be considered significant – people knowing what the purpose of the hearing was and in turn how the output of the hearing would be used.

The variety of groups within the process was a key condition in creating the potential to enact the principle of popular control. It has therefore been discussed at length that there are a variety of actors which enter this process. However, popular control may be easier to obtain if citizens are sharing an arena with policy-makers; they will be well placed to 'push back' against policies they do not agree with and well versed on issues that will affect them. An interesting development which requires further consideration from the findings of the case studies and the analysis though, is that not only a range of groups were in attendance but also, hearings can accommodate groups and associations as participants. Therefore, there is the capacity of citizens to enter this process under different circumstances. They can enter as an individual or as part of a group, or be spoken on behalf of as a member of association. In terms of challenging the liberal democratic model, the Glenmorie, EC and UN hearings demonstrated that groups can exist within the hearing process, and this within hearings which have the potential to enact

the democratic norms, meaning that hearing could be a fairly effective process for associations. This could provide potential for engaging greater numbers of people into the public hearing process and also the contribution those individuals or groups can make within the process. Again, a trustworthy and neutral chair is vital for facilitating these types of conversations.

Finally, and somewhat importantly – people should know what their input will be prior to going in to a participatory process. Is this hearing going to be used to guide a committee to a decision on a specific project, like the Scottish and Canadian examples? Alternatively it could be used to gather public opinion on a particular topic like the Helensburgh hearing. It could also be used as a brainstorming meeting to alter a policy or course of action, like the EU hearing. Or is it giving a voice to an otherwise silenced population, like in the UN hearing or the Alpac hearing. If people know they can impact the outcome of the hearing, the way they approach the hearing could be different. This could be in terms of how much preparation they do or whether they enter as an individual or group. Different people may be encouraged to attend different hearings, based on their control over the situation. Some who do not want control over decisions may be interested to attend information giving and gathering hearings but not interested in a process like the UN hearing. Further to this, knowing how much power is held by the task force or committee who is running the meeting, will reassure the public that they are witnessing a democratic process, not that the decision will be changed at a later date. Only by having confidence and assurance in the process can the public be expected to get involved, and for those that did not attend, to trust the outcome of the hearing.

9.3.3 Creating a transparent public hearing

For transparency the configuration required for the outcome to be realised was that the information should be readily available and outcome known to all – the presence of a neutral and qualified chair or for the hearing to have been driven by the public are key elements too. What is key is that in order to make valid and well informed environmental decisions, information about the project or the policy and the environmental implications of that decisions are imperative for those attending and contributing to the process. This was the resounding conclusion of the UN case study. In a more abstract way it was also a key revelation from the Alpac hearing as the public became empowered by their own knowledge and blurred the line between being the public and being the expert. Information was necessary so that the

participants could offer a robust argument in favour or against the subject being discussed. Access to EIAs and project impact is critical to enabling people to engage in a meaningful conversation. Similarly, decision-makers and organisers should appreciate that they require information from the public on what they know and what they feel about projects that affect them. A two way conversation between these groups is vital for transparency. Furthermore, helping those that did not attend to understand what happened in the process is vital for wider transparency. Better recordings and documenting of what occurred and how that led to the outcome could also help for this. A proper review process is key here.

9.3.4 Public hearings and considered judgement

The analysis in 7.2.4 highlights that there were evidence of the key conditions which would or could enact the correct criteria for the process to demonstrate considered judgement. The configuration required was the justifications of who was in attendance, but also important were the information available and a diverse mix of people in attendance. The justification is the only measurement of deliberation which can be taken from this framework but it is interesting how the other factors prop this up. The group or associational dimension to the Glenmorie hearing is significant in how effective this could be. This, it could be argued, was the same in the EU hearings as individuals went and represented groups (in most cases companies) that were capable of voicing the views and concerns of a wider number of people. It is worth highlighting that associational democracy can be a fundamental risk here in that those that aren't represented by a group may well feel that they have less resources and expertise in pushing forward their agenda and indeed those with the most, and loudest members, may well steer the conversation. Yet, interest groups are competent in countering the slick government officials or the officious experts with overly complicated explanations. Undoubtedly there are other conditions which would impact the democratic norms and it is not possible to undertake research that incorporates all aspects within this research, but the framework works as a kicking off point.

9.4 Recommendations for UK public hearings

It has been argued that public hearings are being undervalued, underestimated and underused in the UK. They are currently being utilised more effectively in Finland, Sweden and in some parts of Canada, and much can be learned from the way these countries implement and utilise

them. A number of changes should be made to the way they are approached in the UK if they are to meaningfully contribute to the institutionalisation of deliberative democracy. This research highlights that there is measurable worth to hearings so that they must be utilised effectively. Whether they are used to help narrow the agenda, set out a clear debate of opposing sides which will set out the competing discourses or give lay citizens a platform for their opinions or to call decision-makers to account, they have been shown in this research to have the potential to bring together a diversity of actors into an open and flexible process. Deliberative democrats should embrace the oppositional nature of the hearings instead of shying away from it. People invariably disagree in politics, it does not have to be a negative thing. Pushing people toward consensus may be more dangerous to environmental decision-making than accepting the adversarial nature of people's opinions. Hearings held at local level and high governance are more effectual and it is argued here that the judicial nature of them can be utilised more effectively.

The first recommendation is that it is not acceptable for hearing to be merely tokenistic or used as a way to placate the public. Greater care and effort must be put in to avoid tokenistic gestures. The hearing can be a useful tool, if it is properly utilised. Fischer (1999: 298) says; 'Beyond radical political rhetoric, collective citizen participation is not something that just happens. It has to be organized, facilitated, and even nurtured. Without such commitment and concern, it is better to abandon the idea'. Making use of other deliberative institutions and linking the hearing with democratic institutions, like parliament, can ensure that what happens in the hearing is effectual in creating respect between the various political actors and enacting legislation which reflects wider public opinion.

The second recommendation is that better use should be made of interest groups and experts. Neutral groups like the Compliance Committee, pressure groups or small community groups, can excite a wider participatory process. Depending on which groups are involved can determine which level of governance that hearing can effectively work at. Therefore, establishing clearer practices for these groups within public hearings could help people ascertain how they may use them to infiltrate the democratic process at different levels of governance. Furthermore, experts, fulfilling the role of advisee in a participatory inquiry could embolden the public in tackling issues which affect them. Specifically in environmental matters, experts can provide insights into the wider research which exists and help citizens to

understand the complex terminology. They can also ensure that realistic solutions are being forwarded which are more in line and more persuadable to policy-makers. As Fischer (1999: 299) tells us; 'Experiences of participatory inquiry have emerged from such practical problems: the future of such activities depends in many ways on a more systematic development of cooperative relationships among citizens and experts more generally'.

Third, public hearings should be more effectively linked with other institutions. The Helensburgh hearing and the BCCA showed that hearings can play a role in linking macro discussions with micro level deliberation. Having the ability to set the agenda and enter the process without being selected gives the hearings a unique insight into public opinion. Connecting the discussion or decisions which result from a hearing into other deliberative institutions, like mini-publics or parliaments, provides a stepping stone between the micro and macro deliberation by offering a meso level process.

Fourth, they must be modernised to keep up with 21st century demands and ensure they are not rendered obsolete by the internet. First, the publicity that surrounds hearings must be improved. This may mean making more use of the media and social media. Extra care must be taken to reach those that are often excluded from the process. Publicity must include making all information which is relevant to the process readily available to the wider populace and actively updating participants if anything changes. Bherer *et al.* (2014) believe that this could be done through information programmes and meetings held prior to the hearing. This could help to eradicate the lack of trust which surrounds hearing and the accusations of tokenism which they currently face.

In addition, the public hearing process should make more use of online tools. This can be done in a number of ways. Creating online forums for those that do not want to, or cannot attend. This virtual space can be fed directly into the hearing (for instance through twitter). Making use of live streaming on all hearings would maximise transparency and include a far wider audience. This may even encourage more people to attend once they have witnessed the process, and are more familiar with proceedings. Live streaming makes the process more accessible to those that may face challenges to attend. Furthermore, every hearing should be recorded and transcribed. This would make a better move to guaranteeing transparency within

that process than the minutes which currently constitute worthy documentation. The records should be made readily available online as soon as possible.

The fifth recommendation is that the review stage of the process must be improved. This could be done merely by keeping communication open. After a number of weeks have passed, organisers should take into account all those opinions of people who could not attend or have expressed interest through online pathways and ensure these opinions are taken into account. At present there are aspects of UK public hearings which are not open and transparent, with information being held from the public or the actual decision process being held with no public in situ. These are aspects that can, and should, be easily overcome.

Finally, and arguably most importantly, it is imperative that the facilitators/chair are fair and effective (Baker *et al.* 2005: 498). A fair and trustworthy facilitator that can properly adjudicate the hearings will further increase trust in the process. Ensuring that the process is facilitated by a neutral and non-bias person, or persons, is crucial to the internal inclusivity in terms of allowing everyone to have a say and all concerns voiced. Specifically when various groups and interests are being represented, a good chair is effective in ensuring the process runs smoothly and that the process is transparent throughout. More notably though, it should be the role of the chair to ensure that the appropriate information is received by all who wish to contribute, and indeed more widely. Within developments or planning applications new information can emerge throughout the proceedings and by affording the chair responsibility for this, attributes a level of accountability for ensuring that information is readily available and every participant is on an even playing field in terms of information of the development.

9.5 Next steps

The complexity of this research has demanded a sophisticated methodology and rigorous exploration into the possibilities of hearings. It was necessary to establish what hearings were presently doing, in order to decipher what they could potentially do, given the right conditions. Using a mixed methods approach, this research has managed to garner a two pronged investigation into the uses of public hearings and where they can best be utilised. By formulating and applying this innovative methodology for evaluating intuitional design these problematic democratic gaps, highlighted in chapter 2 and 3, can perhaps be avoided in future practices. The mixed method approach of analysing the practical attributes of public hearings

have concluded in some interesting findings. The case study analysis, guided by the DSEI, highlighted the differences between the cases. It was imperative to look at where some hearings did better, and others were not as effective, in terms of providing a practical arena for the democratic goods. The variety of hearings considered in this research is key to discovering how flexible hearings can be and what sort of role they could play. Conversely, the fsQCA has demonstrated which democratic goods can be achieved by the different aspects of each; where the different types of hearing's strengths lie. Hearings appear to be most effective when they are concentrated at one stage – be that local, national or transnational and not pulled between two levels. What is clear though, is that public hearings could be an effective institution within deliberative democracy.

The case studies here indicate that they are capable, and proficient, at hosting discussions and movements which are sympathetic to the environment. Further to this, welcoming a mix of actors – including citizens, experts and politicians – indicates that they hold the capacity to enact decision and policy-making. Therefore they could accommodate the transition between discussions on environmental issues to tangible policies. Having said that though, much has been established in this research on a theoretical level. Hearing *could* enact the democratic norms. They *show the potential* to connect deliberation with decision-making. *It would seem* that they welcome groups who are environmentally minded which results in greener practices. The ability to create a meso level of deliberation *is a possibility*. And finally, the interaction of all key actors *could feasibly* result in better and more legitimate decisions. Yet, a wider and more rigorous study is required which makes use of a greater number of case studies. Preferably where transcripts are available and the DQI can properly be applied. In addition, an ethnographic study into public hearings holds the possibility to yield some very interesting result in how the various groups interact; how the chairs conduct themselves and the process; who is there in terms of gender, intergenerational groups and minority groups and also how closely the outcome of the hearing reflects the discussion which was held within it. Although the research here provides important insights into the public hearing process and therefore contributes to the deliberative democratic research, there is further exploration yet to be done.

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³⁹ Due to the 12 week post hearing rule that applies to the public inquiry documents, many of the hyperlinks in this bibliography for reports and summaries, including minutes, are no longer available from council or government web-pages. The author has a copy of all documentation listed here and is happy to supply it if required.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Coding Categories for the Discourse Quality Index (DQI)

Nature of speech act

1. Interruption: speaker interrupts another speaker with a few utterances of not more than a few seconds.
2. Regular speech act: all other speeches, including briefly interrupted speech acts.

Participation

Code in minutes and seconds the length of the speech act.

Participation (constraints)

1. The speaker indicates verbally or by body language that he or she is constrained by the behaviour of other participants (interruptions, private conversations, body language such as making faces, yawning, etc.).
2. The speaker can speak in an unconstrained way.

Respect (foul language)

1. The speaker uses foul language to attack other participants on a personal level. Include also mild foul language, not only statements such as “you are a liar” but also statements such as “you seem a little confused”. Code the names of the participants attacked in this way and give the exact quotation of the foul language.
2. The speaker uses foul language to attack the arguments of other participants but abstains from personal attacks. Here again include also mild foul language, not only statements such as “this argument is stupid” but also statements such as “this argument is a little weak”. Code the names of the participants whose arguments are attacked in this way and give the exact quotation of the foul language.
3. No foul language.

Respect (respectful language)

1. The speaker uses respectful language toward other participants and/or their arguments. Include also moderately respectful language, not only statements such as “your argument is truly brilliant” but also statements such as “your argument is not bad”. Code the names of these other participants and give the exact quotations of the respectful language.
2. No respectful language used.

Respect (listening)

1. The speaker ignores arguments and questions addressed to him or her by other participants. Code the names of these other participants.

2. The speaker does not ignore arguments and questions addressed to him or her by other participants but distorts these arguments and questions. Code the names of these other participants.
3. The speaker does not ignore arguments and questions addressed to him or her by other participants and engages these arguments and questions in a correct and undistorted way. Code the names of these other participants.
4. As yet no arguments and questions addressed to speaker.

Level of justification of arguments

1. The speaker does not present any arguments (asks, for example, merely for additional information).
2. The speaker only says that X should or should not be done, that it is a wonderful or terrible idea, etc. But no reason is given for why X should or should not be done.
3. The speaker justifies only with illustrations why X should or should be done.
4. The speaker gives a reason Y why X should or should not be done. But no linkage is made why Y will contribute to X.
5. The speaker gives a reason Y why X should or should not be done, and a linkage is made why Y will contribute to X.
6. The speaker gives at least two reasons why X should be done and for at least two reasons a linkage is made with X.

Content of justification of arguments (own group)

1. The speaker refers to benefits and costs for own group. Give exact quotation of how the group is referred to. Also give exact quotation if a postulated improvement of one's own group is justified by reference to its past discrimination in the larger society.
2. The speaker does not refer to benefits and costs for own group.

Content of justification of arguments (other groups)

1. The speaker refers to benefits and costs for other groups represented in the experiment. Give exact quotations of how these groups are referred to.
2. The speaker does not refer to benefits and costs for other groups represented in the experiment.

Content of justification of arguments (common good)

1. The speaker refers to benefits and costs for all groups represented in the experiment. Give exact quotations of how the groups are referred to.
2. The speaker does not refer to benefits and costs for all groups represented in the experiment.

Content of justification of arguments (abstract principles)

1. The speaker refers to abstract principles, for example social justice, quality of life, peace. Give exact quotations of how these principles are formulated.
2. The speaker does not refer to any abstract principles.

Force of better argument

1. The speaker indicates a change of position. Gives as reason for change arguments heard during the experiment.
2. The speaker indicates a change of position. Does not refer to arguments heard during the experiment.
3. The speaker does not indicate a change of position. Does acknowledge the value of other positions heard during the experiment.
4. The speaker does not indicate a change of position. Does not acknowledge the value of other positions heard during the experiment.

Stories

1. no story
2. story unrelated to argument
3. story related to argument, sole justification
4. story related to argument, reinforces rational justification.

(Steiner 2012)

Appendix 2: List of Attendees at EU Public Hearing

Annex1: List of participants to the Public Hearing of March 19 First Name	Family Name	Country	Organisation
Marco	ABATE	Belgium	European Commission
Charlotte	ANDERSDOTTER	Belgium	European Commission
Annamalai	ARUNJUNAI	Netherlands	TNO
Lanfranco	BENEDETTI	Belgium	SEA Europe
Michael John	BENNETT	Belgium	European Commission
Francesco Giuseppe	BETTIOL	Italy	TENARIS
Fanny	BROKAMP	Germany	Senator für Wirtschaft, Arbeit und Häfen des Landes Bremen
Rikardo	BUENO	Spain	TECNALIA
Gordon	BUHAGIAR	Belgium	European Commission
Gelu	CALACEAN	Belgium	European Commission
José Carlos	CALDEIRA	Portugal	PRODUTECH / INESC PORTO
Pietro	CALOPRISCO	Belgium	EPIA
Jesus	CARBAJOSA	Spain	International Center for Numerical Methods in Engineering (C
Gilles	CASANOVA	France	STMICROELECTRONICS
Peter	CHURCHILL	Belgium	European Commission
June	COOLS	Belgium	EC
Koen	COPPENHOLLE	Belgium	CEMBUREAU
Ronald	DE BRUIN	Belgium	European Commission
Timoteo	DE LA FUENTE	Belgium	European Commission
	GARCIA		
Olivier	DEBANDE	Belgium	European Investment Bank
Chris	DECUBBER	Belgium	EFFRA
Lorenzo	Zito	Belgium	Finmeccanica

Appendix 3: Analysis Output for fuzzy set QCA

INCLUSION TRUTH TABLE ANALYSIS

(LEAST PARSIMONIOUS, this means that the remainders have been excluded from the analysis)

TRUTH TABLE ANALYSIS

File: C:/Users/Ruth/Documents/PhD empirical work inc case studies/Truth Table Analysis/1 inclusion/inclusion truth table csv.csv

Model: inclusion = f(pub, not, acs, grp, slt, con)

Rows: 5

Algorithm: Quine-McCluskey

True: 1

0 Matrix: 0

--- TRUTH TABLE SOLUTION ---

frequency cutoff: 1.000000

consistency cutoff: 0.943182

Assumptions:

	raw	unique	
	coverage	coverage	consistency

not*acs*grp*~slt*con	0.681159	0.049689	0.956395
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pub*acs*grp*slt*con	0.664596	0.033126	1.000000
---------------------	----------	----------	----------

solution coverage: 0.714286

solution consistency: 0.958333

INCLUSION TRUTH TABLE ANALYSIS

(MOST PARSIMINIOUS, this means that the remainders have been included from the analysis).

TRUTH TABLE ANALYSIS

File: C:/Users/Ruth/Documents/PhD empirical work inc case studies/Truth Table Analysis/1 inclusion/inclusion truth table csv.csv

Model: inclusion = f(pub, not, acs, grp, slt, con)

Rows: 5

Algorithm: Quine-McCluskey

True: 1

0 Matrix: 0

Don't Care: -

--- TRUTH TABLE SOLUTION ---

frequency cutoff: 1.000000

consistency cutoff: 0.943182

Assumptions:

	raw	unique	
	coverage	coverage	consistency

not*acs*grp*~slt*con 0.681159 0.049689 0.956395

pub*acs*grp*slt*con 0.664596 0.033126 1.000000

solution coverage: 0.714286

solution consistency: 0.958333

NON-INCLUSION TRUTH TABLE ANALYSIS

TRUTH TABLE ANALYSIS

File: C:/Users/Ruth/Documents/PhD empirical work inc case studies/Truth Table Analysis/1 inclusion/inclusion truth table csv.csv

Model: non-inclusion = f(pub, not, acs, grp, slt, con)

Rows: 5

Algorithm: Quine-McCluskey

True: 1

0 Matrix: 0

--- TRUTH TABLE SOLUTION ---

frequency cutoff: 1.000000
consistency cutoff: 1.000000

Assumptions:

	raw	unique	
	coverage	coverage	consistency

~pub*not*~acs*~grp*~slt*con 0.857143 0.857143 1.000000

solution coverage: 0.857143

solution consistency: 1.000000

POPULAR CONTROL TRUTH TABLE ANALYSIS

(LEAST PARSIMINIOUS)

TRUTH TABLE ANALYSIS

File: C:/Users/Ruth/Documents/PhD empirical work inc case studies/Truth Table Analysis/2 pop control/popular control truth table csv.csv

Model: popular control = f(grp, con, pubdri, vote, chr, otcn)

Rows: 6

Algorithm: Quine-McCluskey

True: 1

0 Matrix: 0

--- TRUTH TABLE SOLUTION ---

frequency cutoff: 1.000000

consistency cutoff: 0.978378

Assumptions:

	raw	unique	
	coverage	coverage	consistency

grp*con*~pubdri*chr*otcn 0.570048 0.084541 1.000000

grp*con*vote*chr*otcn 0.521739 0.072464 0.981818

grp*con*pubdri*~vote*~chr*~otcm 0.437198 0.074879 0.978378

~grp*con*pubdri*vote*chr*~otcm 0.371981 0.045894 1.000000

solution coverage: 0.801932

solution consistency: 0.976471

(MOST PARSIMINIOUS)

TRUTH TABLE ANALYSIS

File: C:/Users/Ruth/Documents/PhD empirical work inc case studies/Truth Table Analysis/2 pop control/popular control truth table csv.csv

Model: popular control = f(grp, con, pubdri, vote, chr, otcM)

Rows: 6

Algorithm: Quine-McCluskey

True: 1

0 Matrix: 0

Don't Care: Remainder

--- TRUTH TABLE SOLUTION ---

frequency cutoff: 1.000000

consistency cutoff: 0.978378

Assumptions:

raw unique

coverage coverage consistency

chr 0.951691 0.169082 0.951691

~otcm 0.557971 -0.000000 0.924000

pubdri 0.821256 0.038647 0.829268

solution coverage: 0.990338

solution consistency: 0.854167

NON-POPULAR CONTROL TRUTH TABLE ANALYSIS

TRUTH TABLE ANALYSIS

File: C:/Users/Ruth/Documents/PhD empirical work inc case studies/Truth Table Analysis/2 pop control/popular control truth table csv.csv

Model: no popular cont = f(grp, con, pubdri, vote, chr, otcn)

Rows: 6

Algorithm: Quine-McCluskey

True: 1

0 Matrix: 0

--- TRUTH TABLE SOLUTION ---

frequency cutoff: 1.000000

consistency cutoff: 0.981818

Assumptions:

	raw	unique	
	coverage	coverage	consistency

grp*con*~pubdri*~vote*~chr*otcn 0.755245 0.230769 0.981818

grp*con*pubdri*~vote*~chr*~otcn 0.646853 0.122378 1.000000

solution coverage: 0.877622

solution consistency: 0.984314

TRANSPARENCY

TRANSPARENCY TRUTH TABLE ANALYSIS

(LEAST PARSIMONIOUS)

TRUTH TABLE ANALYSIS

File: C:/Users/Ruth/Documents/PhD empirical work inc case studies/Truth Table Analysis/3 transparency/transparency truth table csv.csv

Model: transparency = f(pub, info, otcn, chr)

Rows: 5

Algorithm: Quine-McCluskey

True: 1

0 Matrix: 0

--- TRUTH TABLE SOLUTION ---

frequency cutoff: 1.000000

consistency cutoff: 1.000000

Assumptions:

	raw	unique	
	coverage	coverage	consistency
	-----	-----	-----

pub*info*otcm	0.798100	0.327791	0.957265
~pub*info*~otcm*chr	0.403800	0.045131	1.000000
~pub*~info*otcm*chr	0.479810	0.047506	1.000000

solution coverage: 0.890736
solution consistency: 0.961538

MOST PARSIMONIOUS

TRUTH TABLE ANALYSIS

File: C:/Users/Ruth/Documents/PhD empirical work inc case studies/Truth Table Analysis/3 transparency/transparency truth table csv.csv

Model: transparency = f(pub, info, otc, chr)

Rows: 5

Algorithm: Quine-McCluskey

True: 1

0 Matrix: 0

Don't Care: Remainder

--- TRUTH TABLE SOLUTION ---

frequency cutoff: 1.000000

consistency cutoff: 1.000000

Assumptions:

	raw	unique	
	coverage	coverage	consistency
	-----	-----	-----

info 0.916865 0.080760 0.893519

otcm 0.919240 0.083135 0.860000

solution coverage: 1.000000

solution consistency: 0.817476

NON-TRANSPARENT TRUTH TABLE ANALYSIS

TRUTH TABLE ANALYSIS

File: C:/Users/Ruth/Documents/PhD empirical work inc case studies/Truth Table Analysis/3
transparency/transparency truth table csv.csv

Model: no transparency = f(pub, info, otc, chr)

Rows: 5

Algorithm: Quine-McCluskey

True: 1

0 Matrix: 0

--- TRUTH TABLE SOLUTION ---

frequency cutoff: 1.000000

consistency cutoff: 0.905941

Assumptions:

	raw	unique	
	coverage	coverage	consistency

pub*~info*~otcm*~chr 0.551971 0.068100 1.000000

~pub*info*~otcm*chr 0.594982 0.111111 0.976471

~pub*~info*otcm*chr 0.655914 0.114695 0.905941

solution coverage: 0.835125

solution consistency: 0.910156

CONSIDERED JUDGEMENT

TRUTH TABLE ANALYSIS LEAST PARSIMINIOUS

Algorithm: Quine-McCluskey

True: 10

--- TRUTH TABLE SOLUTION ---

frequency cutoff: 1.000000

consistency cutoff: 0.940476

Assumptions:

	raw	unique	
	coverage	coverage	consistency

grp*con*jstf	0.833333	0.111111	0.964286
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con*info*jstf	0.761317	0.039095	1.000000
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solution coverage: 0.872428

solution consistency: 0.965831

NON-CONSIDERED JUDGEMENT

Not possible due to all configurations leading to outcome.

